

REFERENTIAL AND LEXICAL COHESION IN YORUBA

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I hereby certify that this thesis has not been submitted for a higher degree to any other university or institution.

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SUMMARY

This is a study of two aspects of cohesion in the Yoruba language using Systemic Functional Theory (SFT). These are 'referential' and 'lexical' cohesion. The contributions of Halliday and Hasan (1976, 1985) provide a comprehensive description of this linguistic concept in the English language. SFT is, indeed, synonymous with Halliday; but Hasan has contributed significantly, and in particular, to the theory of cohesion.

This study is, therefore, an application of the linguistic theory to Yoruba because cohesion is, presumably, present in all languages although their patterns may differ.

In chapter one, a description of Yoruba is given from its historical, educational and cultural perspectives. The past and present developments of the linguistic theory and some of its criticisms are examined.

The second chapter examines three aspects of the grammar of the language; nominal, verbal and adverbial groups provide a foundation for the description of chapters three and four.

The third and fourth chapters examine referential and lexical cohesion; and the fifth chapter draws the whole together by an analysis of cohesive harmony. The implications of the study are discussed briefly in the sixth and concluding chapter.

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CHAPTER ONE

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

1.1 - Introduction

This is a study of two aspects of cohesion in the Yoruba language using Systemic Functional Theory (henceforth SFT). These aspects are 'referential' and 'lexical' cohesion. The description will be based on Halliday and Hasan's (1976, 1985) work on cohesion in English which provides the most comprehensive description to date.

The structures in a language are the resources which provide its speakers the means for conveying messages (Hasan 1984a; Fawcett 1984a). The resources which are internal to the clause or clause complex are mostly dependent on grammatical structure. Cohesion, from the perspective of SFT, extends beyond the internal relationships which exist among the various divisions that comprise the structure of the clause; it makes explicit the external relationships that exist between one clause and another independent of grammatical structure. The study of cohesion is explicable in the way Halliday and Hasan examine, among others, 'reference' and 'lexis' in English.

The study of cohesion is the study of the non-structural aspects of a language system. It concerns the organisation of how what is said is realised in spoken and written forms. In a similar way, then, to structure, what is said or written is not just set up randomly. There is an ordered

relation, that is, between the form of what is said and what is understood by it.

Cohesion points, therefore, to the processes at work in the system of the language whereby the speaker's or writer's messages are linked together with one another across clauses in a given text. Being independent of grammatical structure, it provides another view of language, and the total meaning of a text depends mostly on properties of both structure and cohesion. In the study, I shall look at inter-clausal connections in a corpus of texts from a number of genres in Yoruba. In this chapter, I shall give a brief and general survey of two basic aspects of the thesis. The first aspect is about the development of the study of the Yoruba language, past and present; its phonetics, phonology, morphology and grammar. The second aspect concerns the linguistic theory that is being applied to the study of the language. This may be further divided into two parts. The first concerns its development and features. The second relates the way it describes the concept of cohesion; some of the observations that have been made by other scholars regarding the concept and its applications.

1.2 - The Yoruba Language

1.2.0 - Linguistic Classification and Historical Background

Of all the pioneering investigations into the languages of Africa, Greenberg's contributions are not only detailed, but also outstanding in the clear way he classifies African

languages into various groups. Greenberg (1963:153), echoed by Adetugbo (1973:178), Ruhlen (1975:59), Shaw (1978:93-95) - classifies African languages into four major families: Niger-Kordofanian, Nilo-Saharan, Afro-Asiatic and Khosan. The Niger-Kordofanian group includes 'Niger-Congo' which was a different group in earlier classifications. He further subdivides Niger-Kordofanian into the following two sub-groups: Niger-Congo - West Atlantic, Mande, Voltaic, Kwa, Benue-Congo and Adamawa-Eastern;¹ (numbers of this kind refer to notes at the end of the chapter) Kordofanian - Koalib, Tegali, Talodi, Tuntum and Katla (Pulleyblank 1987a:961).

The Kwa sub-sub-group includes, among others: Kru, Baule, Twi, Ga, Ewe, Fon, Yoruba, Edo, Igbo, Ijaw, Idoma, Nupe, and Efik.² Of its geographical spread, Greenberg indicates that the languages in this family are spoken throughout much of the southern half of Africa from Senegal in West Africa to Kenya in East Africa.

Bascom's (1969:1) comments on Yoruba and the Yoruba people are interesting because of the way he places them in a contextual framework within and outside Africa. He went to Nigeria initially as a doctoral research scholar, later as a Fulbright scholar and, for decades after, worked as a government civil servant. His field work began among the Yoruba people at Ile-Ife in 1937. He travelled extensively in Nigeria and Africa. He reports:

"The Yoruba of West Africa are one of the largest ethnic groups south of the Sahara, and in several ways one of the most interesting and important peoples of Africa. In economics, government, and in particular in art and religion, they rank with those other West African groups which represent the highest level of cultural achievement in sub-saharan Africa. Within Nigeria, the Yoruba are one of the three largest and the most important ethnic groups. The Hausa, the Igbo, and the Yoruba together constitute more than half of Africa's most populous nation, and they dominate its Northern, Eastern, and Western Regions respectively. For more than a century, the Yoruba were the dominant group among Nigeria's educated elite, and they provide school teachers and other white-collar workers both in Nigeria and in neighbouring territories."

When Bascom wrote the above, the population of the Yoruba in the then Western Nigeria (excluding Midwest) was about twelve million people (Udo 1978: 209; Katzner 1975: 292; Ologunde 1982: 277). Recent estimates indicate that it is about twenty million. In modern Nigeria, following the creation of twenty-one states,³ Yorubas are found predominantly in Oyo, Ondo, Ogun and Lagos States. Most of the other Yorubas are found in Ilorin, Kabba, Igbomina, and Ekiti Local Government Areas of Kwara State. The Itsekiri of Warri Local Government Area in Bendel State are also a Yoruba speaking group. The degrees of divergence or dialectal variation among the various groups of its speakers are mainly spatial. A major contributory factor to this variation among the speakers of the language is believed to be that Yorubas initially migrated from somewhere in the Middle East or lower Egypt to Ile-Ife from where they moved to their present homes in a series of migrations between the seventh and eleventh centuries A. D. (Adetugbo (op. cit. p. 182)).

The Yoruba language has, by sheer historical accident, extended beyond the confines of Nigeria. Significant numbers

of Yorubas are found in nearly all the major market towns of West Africa (Bascom op. cit. p. 2) - Togo, Dahomey (now Benin), and Sierra Leone. Even beyond the continent of Africa, Yorubas or their descendants are found in Cuba, Brazil (Bascom op. cit. p. 2; Adetugbo op. cit. pp. 196-197) and the United States of America (Pulleyblank 1987b:972).

Astride the Togo-Benin boundary, the Yoruba people are called Manigri; in Benin, Idasha (meaning an enclave), and in the heart of Benin; Anago. In Sierra Leone, Yoruba descendants are known as Aku, in Cuba, Lucumi and in Brazil, the Nagos. The Cuban name, Lucumi, Bascom suggests, comes from a Yoruba greeting, olùkùmi, meaning 'my friend'. He points out that the Sierra Leone name also originates from the many Yoruba greetings which begin with the root word ekú. Ekú, now spelt èekú in the modern orthography, is still commonly used by the Oyo and Ilorin speakers of the language in Nigeria as a form of greeting.

Bascom observed, concerning the Yorubas in foreign lands:

"...their descendants still preserve Yoruba traditions including some which many Yoruba in Nigeria have forgotten... the contribution which Yoruba slaves and their descendants have made to the culture of the Caribbean and South America, in particular of Cuba and Brazil... nearly all of the slaves brought to the Americas came from West Africa, between Senegal and Angola, and no African group has had greater influence on new World culture than Yoruba" (op. cit. pp. 1 and 2).

The above quotation shows how vigorous the Yoruba culture is and obviously its language. For precision, I would refer to these various dialects of the language as 'Yoruba in diaspora' because of their dispersion, hence my use of the

plural term 'Yorubas' in some parts of this chapter. These dialects of the Yoruba language in dispersion are of interest to many scholars for a number of reasons. Firstly, they vividly portray the importance of the Yoruba people and their language in those parts of the world into which they dispersed. Secondly, they are historically relevant as a reminder of the four centuries of the Trans-Atlantic slave trade when numerous Yorubas were carried as slaves to the 'New World.' Although dialects of the language are still used in Benin and Togo, they have ceased to be spoken in Cuba and Brazil. In the latter countries, they have become ritualised in religious festivals. Adetugbo's comment regarding the Yoruba dialect of Cuba affirms this:

"Lukumi is now a cult language in Cuba, peculiar to the adherents of the San Tiera group and is preserved for worship. This form of Yoruba, and we must insist it is Yoruba, has been subjected to much Spanish 'stress' system and retains, by our computation, less than 50 per cent of basic core cognates (47 per cent to be exact) with Oyo Yoruba." (1973:196-197)

In other places where the language is no longer spoken, like Sierra Leone and the United States of America, it has influenced the languages that replaced it, for example, Krio in Sierra Leone and the dialects of Black English in some areas of the United States. Pulleyblank reports that 'Yoruba has also undergone revivals such as that exhibited in Oyotunji⁴ village of the United States of America' (op. cit. p. 972). Even though considerable effort is being made to investigate various aspects of the language in Nigeria, virtually nothing has been done to investigate its dispersion. These dialects in diaspora therefore are ripe

fields of linguistic investigation. This study concerns, however, some aspects of the Yoruba language in Nigeria.

1.2.1 - Historical Survey of the Study of Yoruba

The study of the Yoruba language in Nigeria can be traced back to the introduction of formal education in Nigeria. Abiri (1981:iv) places the beginning of its study at 1842 probably because it was the year that the missionaries arrived in the country. Awoniyi (1981:71) claims that a study of Yoruba first appeared in print in 1819, perhaps, in Sierra Leone. In 1854 and 1875, conferences were held in Lagos on its orthography (Bamgbose 1965:5; Ologunde 1983:280). A notable African, Bishop Ajayi Crowther⁵ was a participant at the Lagos conferences⁶; he appears to have been the first Yoruba language scholar. As early as 1849, he published the first publication on Yoruba - First Primer (Ologunde op. cit. p. 82). In 1852⁷ he published his second work on the language - Grammar and Vocabulary of Yoruba (Bamgbose 1967:1; Salami 1982:120). Other scholars within and outside the country have since made significant contributions to the study of the grammar of the language. Among other areas of the development of the language are the publication of a newspaper Iwe Irohin⁸ by Henry Townsend in 1867 and a Yoruba Dictionary a few years later. These publications still exist today along with several new ones.

Early conferences held on the standardisation of the orthography of Yoruba, (and several other African languages), were motivated by European non-native speakers. These

Europeans were missionaries, anthropologists, historians, administrators and linguists who needed a working knowledge of the Yoruba language. The development of the language became the responsibility of Nigerians after the country attained independence in 1960. Nigerians began then, according to Bamgbose (1986:29-30), to pay

"increasing attention to the linguistic bases of education. The question of whether a child's education should begin in a familiar language, that is, his mother tongue, or in a foreign language (that is, English) has to be answered."

In 1966, the Yoruba Orthography Committee (Y. O. C.) was established by the indigenous government of Western Nigeria (Ologunde op. cit. p.282). Today, despite the use of English as the country's official language, the Yoruba language is used in some state parliaments, mass media, schools and universities; and many linguistic scholars in Nigeria and abroad are attracted on a continuing basis to its study. I shall briefly describe three basic levels of the study of the language in the following sections.

1.2.2 - Phonetics and Phonology

The language has seven 'pure' (oral) vowels - /a, e, ɛ, i, o, ɔ, u/. In their written forms /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ are represented as [e] and [o] respectively. There are four nasalised vowels which are formed morphophonemically by the addition of the nasal particle n to each of the oral vowels except /o/ and /e/. These are /ĩ/, /ẽ/, /õ/ and /ũ/. [õ] and [ã] are regarded as allophones of single phoneme /õ/ as in, for example, iyán /iyõ/ (pounded yam) and opón /ɔkpõ/

/(trough). Examples of the four nasalised vowels are ihín /ihĩ / (here), iyen /iyÊ /, (that), iyùn /iyũ / (coral) and opón /ɔkpɔ̃ /.

Long vowels and diphthongs are treated as clusters of two short monophthongal vowels. The following examples occur in negative prefixes. Examples are /ai/ as in àilágbára (strengthlessness) and àiláanú (wickedness). Others without negative prefixes and which may have different tones are oògùn (medicine) and àánú (mercy).

There are eighteen consonant sounds /p, b, t, d, j, k, g, kp, gb, f, s, ʃ, h, m, r, l, w, y/ in the language. Consonant clusters do not occur within words, but can occur across word boundaries, and the realisation of a consonant phoneme is affected by an adjacent consonant across a word boundary. Such processes result from coarticulation to place or manner of articulation. In regard to the phonemes, the four basic places of articulation for the Yoruba 'stops' are: bilabial /b/, /p/, alveolar /t, d/, palatal /j/, and velar /k, g, gb, kp/. The language has two 'stops' that are doubly articulated with simultaneous labial and velar closure - /kp/ and /gb/. These labial-velar 'stops' are orthographically represented as p and gb respectively. There are four fricatives in the language - /f, s, ʃ, h/, all of which are voiceless; the palato-alveolar fricative is represented by the dotted consonant ɕ / ʃ/. Others are the sonorants /m, l, r, y, w/ which may be further divided into nasal /m/, lateral /l/, tap /r/ and glide /y, w/.

Oral Vowels	Nasalised Vowels
a, e, ɛ, i, o, ɔ, u	ĩ, ã, ẽ, õ

	Stop	Fricative	Nasal	Lateral	Tap	Glide
Bilabial	p b		m			
Labio-dental		f				
Alveolar	t d	s		l	r	
Palato-alveolar		ʃ				
Palatal		j				y
Velar	k g					w
Labio-velar	kp gb					
Glottal		h				

Table 1.2.2 - Segmental Phonemes of Yoruba

(Pulleyblank 1987b: 973)

Pulleyblank does not include the syllabic nasal /n/ in the above table because of the various ways it functions in a word. If the following phoneme is a vowel, as in n ò lo / ñ ò l ã / ('I didn't go'), it is pronounced as a velar. If it is followed by a consonant, it is 'homorganic' ^{with?} to the following phoneme - mbo / ñ mb ã / ('is coming) or ńká / ñ kà / ('is reading'). Lastly, it is confusing, potentially, to classify it as either a vowel or a consonant when it occurs medially in words. The sound /n/ functions, for example, in a complementary distribution with /l/. The former functions before nasalised vowels and the latter before oral vowels. These are examples - ní òla ~ l'òla ('by tomorrow') and ní aya ~ l'áya ('have wife'). The nasal consonants, generally, are very complicated in their phonological status and their orthographical representation.

There are three basic tones⁹ which are marked on vowels. (La Velle 1974:169-170; Gandour 1978:47-49). These are high, represented by the acute accent (/); low, represented by the grave accent (\); and middle or mid, which is usually left unmarked, except in certain circumstances which involve a syllabic nasal and the macron (-) may then be used.

The functional importance of the tones is a crucial factor in the use of the language. Up to five words may be spelt alike but the different meanings are realised by the use of the tone marks. For example: iqbà (time), iqba (two hundred), iqbá (garden egg), iqbà (a climbing rope), and iqbá (calabash).¹⁰

In continuous speech, the operation of the tones becomes quite complicated when sequences of words become modified or contracted. Vowel deletion, affecting sequences of adjacent vowels, commonly occurs in connected speech. The tone of the deleted vowel may pass to the undeleted vowel in the sequence. In the following, for example:

(1) mo kí òbí
I greet parent
'I greet the parent(s)'

and

(2) mo bí omo
I bear child
'I have a child/children'

the vowel /i/ forming a part of each of the verbs kí (greet) and bí (bear) may be deleted in both instances, and the following contracted forms are formed:

(3) mo kó'bí
I greet parent
'I greet the parent(s)'

and

x (4) mo bó'mo ?? b(ma)?
I bear child
'I have a child/children'

In (1) where no vowel deletion has taken place, the final high tone on òbí (parent(s)) is realised as a rising tone because of the preceding low tone on /ò/. In (3) where vowel deletion has taken place, a rising tone is realised on the final vowel but the low tone on /ò/ is replaced by a high tone. In (2) where it is the terminal high tone vowel that undergoes deletion, the deleted mid-tone adjacent vowel is realised as rising tone in (4) in recognition of the deleted high tone. There are therefore some restrictions on the distribution of tones in connected speech. Abiri (op. cit. p. 28), Bamgbose (1967:16), and Ogunbowale (op. cit. p. 21) agree that the tone marks are not only an essential part of the written language.¹¹

1.2.3 - Morphology and Grammar

1.2.3.0 - Morphology

In the Yoruba language, the formation of words is not by inflexional processes. Word formation mainly involves two processes: prefixation and reduplication. In this section, I will briefly describe prefixation processes, homonyms, different spelling, reduplication and ideophones.

There are two ways by which a prefixation process may occur: by vowel prefixes, and by syllable prefixes. Some nouns¹², for example, are derived by prefixing certain vowels to verbs. Examples of verbs to which these vowels could be prefixed are de (to hunt), ké (to cry), and lé (to increase). These verbs may be prefixed with /o-, i-, and e- / to form the following nouns - ode (hunter), iké (cry), and élé (increase). Prefixes of the 'actor' or 'agentive' group formed by deriving nominal forms from verbs include /a-, ò-/ and olù-. Examples of these are: apàniyàn (killer/murderer), òsisé (workman/worker), and olùfé (a loved one/lover). Prefixes for the 'possessor' group are oní- and alá-.
Examples are oniléogoro (one who owns a skyscraper), and aláso (cloth-owner/seller). Prefixation¹³ may involve the prefixing of one or more syllables. Examples are àbá- (to meet) and adá-. These join with pàdé (to meet) and dálóró (to cause someone harm) to become àbápàdé (an unexpected meeting with someone particularly on the pathway), and adánilóró (someone who causes harm or great misfortune to another person). Two prefixes are 'infinitival': àti- and ài. The former suggests or introduces a 'process', or 'being about to do something' and, the latter suggests or introduces a negative meaning to a word. The combination of these two prefixes is significant in the language. Examples are: àtisùn (to sleep/sleeping), and àimò (ignorance or to be ignorant).

Homonyms (a group of words that are written and pronounced in the same way but have different meanings) - occur in the

language. These words may appear ambiguous, but the listener or the reader disambiguates them through their context. Ni is a typical example in the following clauses:

(5) ó wà ní'lé
3sg is PREP. house
's/he is in the house'
or

(6) Mo ní owó
I VB. money
'I have money'
or

(7) Ade ní kí o wá
Ade VB. that you come
'Ade said that you should come'

Bi in

(8) iyàwó mi bí omo mérin
wife my VB. child four
'my wife gave birth to four children'

or

(9) Mo bi Ojo bí ó ba ri baba mi
I ask Ojo COND. he PRE. VB. see father my
'I asked Ojo if he saw my father'

Finally, afárá in

(10) okò náà kojá lóri afárá
vehicle d-d pass PREP. bridge
'the vehicle passed on the bridge'

or

(11) Baba mi pa eèpó igi afárá
father my kill cover tree afara
'my father removed the back of afara tree'

Ní (not as in [6-8 above]) may be used in such a manner that it becomes semantically empty (often written as SEW [semantically empty words] see Pulleyblank 1987b: 983) such that it becomes difficult to translate in the written form.

For example:

- (12) Kunle fún Ojo ní iwé kan
Kunle give Ojo (SEW) book one
'Kunle gave Ojo a book'

It seems odd to describe a word as semantically empty because the speakers of the language use it in the context of other words to convey meaning. In a similar way, Awobuluyi (1978) describes a group of 'symmetrical verbs' - bí (as in ínu bí mí [I was angry]), bà (as in èru bà mí [I was afraid] and se (as in ó n se wèrè [He is mad] which their literal meanings are uncertain (p. 61). He also regards a class of 'introducers' as 'untranslatable.' Examples are àgbààgba (the elders?), and òwòòwò (different groups?) (p. 91). The distinction in English between 'content' and 'function' words in English may be a relevant explanation of this linguistic phenomenon otherwise the difficulty may be a part of the problems of translation from one culture to another.

Before going into other features of words in the language, it is necessary to remark on the different forms of spelling currently available in the language and which clearly feature in some of the texts that will ^{be} used in this thesis. Despite many conferences held by scholars of the language to standardise its orthography, there still exist different ways of writing and pronouncing the same word. These differences are not dialectal. For example:

nà may also be written as náà (the)
sà as sáà (just/ordinarily)
ènià as èniyàn (person(s))
aiyé as ayé (earth)
dédé as déédé (correct/all right)

<u>dáda</u>	as	<u>dáadáa</u>	(good)
<u>àláfíà</u>	as	<u>àláfíà</u>	(peaceful)
<u>ògùn</u>	as	<u>òògùn</u>	(medicine)
<u>iròhin</u>	as	<u>iròyin</u>	(news)
<u>ikehin</u>	as	<u>ikeyin</u>	(last/last one)

The first column of the above list of words contains the old orthographical way of writing and pronunciation and the right column, new forms. Although both are still used in writing and in speech, the new forms reflect the most common pronunciation of these words.

One of the most interesting word formation processes in Yoruba is the several types of reduplication, some involving partial reduplication, and some involving complete reduplication. The process of partial reduplication often involves the affixation or the addition of any elements from a mere particle to a syllable or more. In complete reduplication, however, the entire word is duplicated one or more times. One of the main functions of complete reduplication is to introduce to an utterance an emphatic meaning or to express some kind of intensification.

There are two kinds of partial reduplication: the first type involves the derivation of a kind of related syllable which has a similar sound and meaning to the initial consonant of the verb. This may be called a kind of alliterative reduplication. Examples of this type are: from lo (go) - lilo; and from so (say/speak) - siso (saying/speaking). The second type of partial reduplication also involves some kind of affixation. A formant or particle is affixed between two reduplicated nouns with some vowel deletion normally taking

place. Examples are: enikéni (whoever/any person), where eni (person) is reduplicated with the particle ki in between; ijókijó (whatever dancing/indecent dancing), and again having the particle ki in between it. A final example showing a different type of particle is omokómo (any child/an untrained child) formed from omo (child) with kó as particle in between it.

Complete reduplication, on the other hand, mostly involves the total repetition of the word in focus with some occasional vowel change in the process but without any kind of affixation. Examples are: diè (little) to dièdiè (very little/little-by-little); púpò (much/many) to púpòpúpò (very much/quite-a-lot at a time), and méta (three) to métaméta (three-by-three)/in threes). Examples of complete reduplication involving some type of vowel change, particularly relating to some time or a particular period of time are osùosù (month-by-month/every month) which is actually pronounced as osoosù; and odúnodún (year-by-year/year after year/every year), again which is pronounced odoodún.

Another group of words some of which may be reduplicated are ideophones. Ideophones, apparently, are very difficult to define or at least are often open to re-classification (Rowlands 1970:289; Welmers 1973:461; Pulleyblank 1987b:981). Rowlands recognises them as 'particularly expressive words marked off from the rest of the vocabulary by similar special phono-semantic characteristics to which it has been found convenient to give the name ideophones.' Welmers describes

an ideophone as 'a vivid representation of an idea in sound. A word often onomatopoeic, which describes a predicate, qualificative or adverb in respect of manner, colour, smell, action, state or intensity.' The difficulty, perhaps, lies in the way the various definitions cannot account for the manner in which the sound pattern of a word conveys its meaning. What seems generally obvious to speakers of the language, often by intuition, is that the expressive (i. e. phonetic) possibilities correlate in many instances with semantic information.

What is crucial to my definition of ideophones as given above is the way some information is associated with their total phonological realisation. Pulleyblank (op. cit. p. 981) observes that 'a low tone correlates with largeness or lightness, and a mid tone indicates an average value.' He gives these examples to illustrate this phenomenon - rògòdò (of a big round object), rogodo (of an average round object) and rógódó (of a small round object). Another set of examples is - rùgùdù (large heavier object), rugudu (medium heavy object) and rúgúdí (small slightly heavy object). This characteristic of the ideophone would appear to mean that the quality of its vowel turns out to be semantically significant. /o/, according to Pulleyblank may generally be said to indicate 'roundness' as in rógbódó (any round or spherical object), and /u/ 'weight' as in rúgúdí (a solidly built and apparently heavy object). He explains, however, that in some ideophones there may not be any obvious source of interpretation semantically, whereas others may be related

semantically and phonologically to a source morpheme, as kéré (small) is related to kéékéékéé (very small/in small bits). According to Rowlands (op. cit. p. 294) words 'with the tone pattern high-mid-low-mid generally have a pejorative meaning of untidy, disordered, stupid, and unpleasant.' The examples he gives are 'réderède', 'jágabajágbá', 'kántankántan' and 'wúruwúru'. Some other reduplications have an intensifying effect - for example: fíofío (lofty) is used to describe objects of immense height, and wéréwéré (quickly) for very urgent matters. Bamgbose (Rowlands op. cit. p. 289) includes ideophones in the 'open class of adverbs' which 'expound the adjunct in clause structure.' Rowlands (1970:290-294) describes them as functioning in initial, medial and final (i.e. adjuncts) word positions in utterances. Some examples:

- (13) fèrègèdè ni àyà omo náà (initial)
 broad VB. chest child d-d
 'the boy's chest is very broad'
- (14) Bisi ná owó diè sí ilé yen (medial)
 Bisi spend money little PREP. house that
 'Bisi spent a little money on that house'
- (15) nwon lo kiákíá (final)
 they go quickly
 'they went quickly'

When ideophones occur in the final word position of an utterance, particularly when they are duplicated as in (15) above, they are often pronounced in a far more expressive way than the preceding words. The pronunciation often ascribed to them is louder, carefully articulated and with increased duration. As in (14) above, not all ideophones form reduplications although diè (little) may be reduplicated to form diédiè (little-by-little).

1.2.3.1 - Grammar

A typical Yoruba sentence or clause may be classified typologically as SVO (Subject-Verb-Object) (Odunuga 1982:266; Pulleyblank 1987b:983)). This basic word-order of the language is highly configurational. A configurational language is one in which word-order is not entirely free within the clause but in which the organisation of words into the constituents forms an ordered pattern or string (Hudson 1984:81). The interpretation of the string depends upon the order inherent in the system, and vice-versa. That it is highly configurational means it lacks inflections for grammatical relations.

Although the terms 'sentence,' 'phrase,' and 'word' are regarded by some scholars of the language (Ogunbowale 1978; Awobuluyi 1978; Abiri 1981) as units in the hierarchical constituents of the language, I will refer to the units as clause complex, 'clause', 'group', and 'lexical items' because these terms are commonly used in SFT (Halliday 1985a:38^{ff}) and also appeal to very much the same evidence. A sentence, in this regard, will usually be made up of one or more clauses or clause complexes. A clause will usually have one or more groups, namely nominal, verbal, and adverbial. A group will usually consist of one or more lexical items which are made up of morphemes. Each of these units, then, becomes a 'rank' for the grammar of the language. Its patterns of word-order, pronominal, verb, tense, aspect and yes-no question particles will be described briefly in this section.

1.2.3.2 - Word Order in the Clause

In the following:

- (16) Ojo gun igi
Ojo climb tree
'Ojo climbed the tree'

In a traditional description of the language, Ojo (a noun) is the subject; gun (climb) the verb and igi (tree) the object. The head of the group occurs, generally, in the initial position in the clause, while the adjective occurs post-nominally. For example, in

- (17) Omo kékeré ni
child small VB.
'he is a small child'

kékeré (small) postmodifies omo (child). The possessives, determiners, and demonstratives all occur, generally, after the head noun they modify. Examples are:

- (18) ilé baba ni (possessive)
house father VB.
'it's the father's house'
- (19) ajá náà gbó (definite-determiner)
dog d-d bark
'the dog barked'
- (20) aja yi gbo (demonstrative)
dog DEM. bark
'this dog barked'

Similarly, a relative clause generally occurs post-nominally as in (21) below:

- (21) òun ni ó kọ ilé [tí ó jó lánà]
s/he FOC. s/he build house that it burn yesterday
's/he it was who built the house that burnt yesterday'

where 'ti ó jó lánà' is a relative clause in a focus construction. A focus construction is realised by fronting a constituent which is marked by the morpheme ni in order to establish, thematise or emphasise a particular point or argument.

1.2.3.3 - Pronominal

Since pronominals serve to indicate rather than to name things within the same clause, they present a kind of structural reference, that is reference as a unifying rather than cohesive relation. (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 6-7; Ridler 1933: 1468). A few examples are as follows:

(22) Dele so pé ó wá
Dele say that 3sg. come
'Dele said that s/he came'

The 'third person singular' pronoun ó (s/he) refers to someone other than Dele in (22) above. In (23), however;

(23) Dele so pé òun wá
Dele say that 3sg. come
'Dele said that s/he came'

the 'third person singular' pronoun òun (s/he) obviously refers to Dele. The different interpretations given to (22) and (23) are based on the different pronominal items alone. In some cases, as in (24) below where the two types of pronominals are present some kind of ambiguity may be introduced in embedded clauses:

(24) Dele so pé òun ni ó wá
Dele say that s/he FOC. s/he come
'Dele said that it was s/he who came'

Not only do we have the two types of the 'third person singular' pronouns in (22) and (23) used in (24), they may or may not refer to Dele. They either jointly refer to Dele or to someone else. Neither of them may refer to a different person.

The third person plural pronominal nwon (they) is also significant. For example in (25) below:

- (25) Nwón so pé Dele ati iyàwó rẹ wá
they say that Dele and wife POSS. come
'they said that Dele and his wife came'

nwón (they), grammatically, refers to at least two people who are not identifiable in the clause. Its referent is however retrievable in another sentence or known to speakers in the discourse.

1.2.3.4 - Verbs

One of the most fascinating features of verbs in the language is serial verb pattern; two or more verbs forming a consecutive string in clauses. In

- (26) Kunle sáré wá
Kunle run come
'Kunle ran this way'

sáré (run) and wá (come) are verbs. They share the same subject, Kunle as in 'Kunle sáré' (Kunle runs) and 'Kunle wá' (Kunle comes). wá (come) also indicates the direction of the action towards the location of the speaker. In

- (27) Kunle rí owó ná
Kunle see money spend
'Kunle's got money to spend'

the verbs rí (see/get) and ná (spend) both have a single object, owó (money), occurring between them. In

- (28) Kunle kò lè jí owó náà rará
Kunle NEG. PRE. VB. steal money d-d at all
'Kunle cannot possibly steal the money at all'

There are two pre-verbal items between the subject and the verb. The first is the negator kò and the second the modal lè (expressing possibility). Both stress the impossibility of Kunle stealing the money. Rará (at all) post-modifies the verb to emphasise this notion. Although there are many adverbs and adverbials that post-modify the verbs in the language, there are only a few preverbal adverbs as in (29) below:

- (29) Kunle kò dédé jí owó náà
Kunle NEG. PRE. VB. steal money d-d
'Kunle did not just steal the money'

1.2.3.5 - Tense and Aspect

Tense and aspect ^{markers?} being preverbs in Yoruba, are signalled by certain particles that occur mainly between the subject and the verb. In the case of the past tense, the users of the language may know, through context that the meaning of a clause, is past, otherwise a lexical item is needed to indicate its tense. This is because verbs in the language do not inflect for either tense or aspect. In

- (30) Nike sáré
Nike run
'Nike run/ran'

the verb sare (run) may stand for either present or past.

But in

- (31) Nike sáré láná
Nike run yesterday
'Nike ran yesterday'

the lexical item láná indicates its 'pastness'.

or in

- (32) Nike wa ní'bí nísisiyi
Nike is here now
'Nike is here at present/at the moment'

the lexical item nísisiyi indicates its 'now-ness or present-ness.'

The progressive is marked by a particle:

- (33) Nike n sáré
Nike PROG. run
'Nike is running'

The progressive particle, n, in the modern orthography, is often separated from the verb. In the old, the n is affixed to the verb sáré (run) which then becomes nsáré (running). Particles are also used to mark aspect in the language. For example in:

- (34) baba ti lo
father PERF. go
'father has gone'

ti signals the perfective aspect marker. Also in

- (35) baba á lo
father FUT. go
'father will go'

á signals the future tense marker.

For yes-no questions, a particle can be added either at the beginning or at the end of the sentence. The following example:

- (36) Njé/Sé baba lo?
PART. father go
'did father go?'

shows that either of the question particles Njé or sé may be used. In the alternative, either bí/ná may be inserted but at the end of the sentence.

- (37) Baba lo bí?
baba go PART.
'did father go?'

- (38) o ti lo ná?
you PERF. go PART.
'have you gone?' (i.e. to where I sent you)

More importantly, the stress also shifts position to the end of the question specifically on the particles: bí and ná.

1.2.4 - The Current State of the Language

1.2.4.1 - A Dialect Continuum

The Yoruba language, perhaps like most languages in Nigeria and in Africa, is a dialect continuum. However, one dialect is often referred to as Standard Yoruba (henceforth, S.Y.). In recent years, the term S.Y. has been used to refer to the form of the language often called Modern Yoruba (M.Y.). Linguistically, the Yoruba language is the totality or aggregate of all its dialects. It also holds true linguistically that all forms of any language are equally deserving of due respect and attention. For my purpose, nevertheless, I will concentrate on S.Y. in this description. S.Y. may be considered the most important Yoruba dialect for two main reasons. Firstly, it seems to be the only model which is completely mutually intelligible to all speakers of the language. There are features of some of the dialects (I myself speak four dialects) that present intelligibility problems for speakers of other dialects of the language. Secondly, it is more socially defined, whereas the other dialects are delimited geographically. Attempts are made, therefore, by speakers of S.Y. to acquire the highest level of competence, particularly in formal situations. This interest by speakers of the language in such a babel of multilingualism as Nigeria (^{about?} over 400 languages (not dialects) are spoken - Obanya (1979:268)) is encouraging considering the extensive use of the English language which is the country's official language. As a result of the role of

English as the public language, the role of the Nigerian languages in administration and public affairs has been limited. Even so, the State and the Federal governments have recognised the importance of reaching the masses through the local languages.

1.2.4.2 - Lexical Borrowings

The pervasive influence of the English language contributes to the linguistic phenomena known as code-mixing and code-switching. In code-mixing, speakers of both English and Yoruba mix the vocabularies of both languages, particularly in informal situations, whilst in code-switching the speaker of both languages switches from one code (either of the two languages) to another. These bilingual phenomena cannot but feature in any extended corpus of text. Yoruba therefore has, as a result of the linguistic interaction through education, politics, science and technology, borrowed, and will continue to borrow, words from English. The language has in the same manner borrowed from other languages, such as Arabic, the world-wide language of Islam; Hausa, the language of the largest number of users in the country, and a few other languages with which it has come in contact (Adebisi 1982: 118).

A few examples of the borrowings from English and other languages are provided below:

English to Yoruba

doctor (a medical practitioner)	-	dókità
bread (food)	-	bùrédi
amen (as in christian liturgy)	-	àmin
lace (textile)	-	léèsi

Hausa to Yoruba

aya (a title - a document)	-	àáyà
lafia (good health/peaceful)	-	àlàáfia
labari (news - mass media)	-	làbarè
arewa (north - geographical)	-	àríwá

A few Others

French (contact with France)	-	faransé
Creole (contact with Sierra Leone)	-	kiriyó
Spanish (contact with Spain)	-	páàdi
Portuguese (contact with Portugal)	-	potokí

Table 1.2.4.2 - Lexical Borrowings into Yoruba

Most lexical borrowings, particularly from English, occur so frequently in the day-to-day use of the language that none but the language specialists are aware of these being words of languages other than Yoruba. Some of the foreign words become assimilated, initially only partially, and, later, after a long period, fully into the Yoruba vocabulary. In various ways, these words also adapt themselves partially or wholly to the existing phonological system.

1.2.4.3 - Descriptions/Analyses of Yoruba

Bamgbose's (1986:1) remark about the 'different models of description, and differences in perception' of the language is very appropriate here:

"Students of Yoruba at practically all levels complain about the difficulty of the language component of their courses. They compare it with literature and wonder why there is a wide divergence of views of analysis and sometimes on data. 'Why can't grammarians agree on anything?' they ask helplessly. ...different definitions for the same class of words, different classifications for the same set of words, and different analysis for identical structures. For examples, some define the class of nouns to include adverbs, others exclude them. What some call 'predicative adjectives' are merely 'verbs' to others, and what some analyse as 'nominalised sentences' are seen by others as 'relative clauses'."

Differences of approach, or different theoretical underpinnings, are a contributory factor to the wide divergence of analysis which, in turn, leads to varied definitions and classifications. In spite of divergences, Afolayan (1982:xxiv) remarks:

"The first necessity, therefore, for the grammarian, particularly of a language such as Yoruba whose academic description is just coming of age, is to recognise that his is not the ONLY CORRECT (sic.) grammar of Yoruba. Such a grammar is not ever likely to be produced."¹⁴

There is no difficulty in understanding Afolayan's view as expressed above that no single approach to the study of a language will be its only correct version, yet the most relevant way to give coherence to any linguistic analysis is to give it some theoretical underpinning. Commenting on the major and minor analyses of Yoruba in academic publications, Adeniran remarks:

"...Their merits lie in different aspects of their works. For example, Bamgbose's grammar is known to be based on the well-known linguistic theory called the Scale and Category Grammar (SCG) (sic.). Thus in terms of this theory it is explanatorily adequate. One is not so sure of the theoretical bases of the other grammars but as teaching grammars, they are sufficiently adequate. There are still other linguistic theories which, if systematically applied, may explicate the structure of the language as well as, or better than SCG." (1978:83)

More important is the apparent urgent need to evolve, in the midst of several un-theoretical (Bamgbose is one exception) descriptions of the language, a more precise, and theoretically coherent, meaningful and functional description. More so that Halliday et. al. (1964) agree that cohesion is a property of all languages:

"all languages display certain features which can be regarded as cohesive; such features are of different types and belong to different levels, but all contribute to the internal binding of the text." (pp. 247-248)

This study aims at a systematic analysis of two aspects of cohesion; 'referential' and 'lexical' from the theoretical viewpoint of Systemic Functional Theory (SFT) as enunciated by Halliday. SFT is a more advanced and a far more explicit linguistic theory than SCG but is based on it. The theory's explication of meaning, and the paradigm set up to realise it, coupled with its emphasis on both the linguistic and situational contexts make it remarkably explicit and attractive. Following Adeniran's comment above, it seems that the application of this linguistic theory to the investigation of some aspects of the language will be a worthwhile effort.

1.3 - Systemic Functional Theory (SFT)

There have been many names used to refer to this linguistic theory, for example Systemic Linguistics (SL), Systemic Theory (ST), Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG), or Systemic Functional Theory (SFT). The terms 'theory', 'grammar' and 'linguistics' are at times substitutable one for another. It

seems that the use of any of these labels has something to do with the emphasis¹⁵ that the user of the model wants to make, or the direction in which to take the particular analysis.

My choice of the name Systemic Functional Theory (SFT) does not indicate any significant difference from any of the others. The two key words 'systemic' and 'functional' form part of the term in order to differentiate it from the other 'functional' schools of linguistic theory.

1.3.1 - The Origin and the Development of SFT

The SFT's view of language to which Halliday has given its present shape, owes its origin, in part, to the influence of the British linguist, John Rupert Firth. Other influences can be traced to the European Functional tradition of the Prague School, the anthropologist Bronislaw Malinowski, Louis Hjelmslev, Benjamin Whorf, and Ferdinand de Saussure (Halliday 1985a:xxvi-xxvii, 1977a:34, 1973:23-24; Berry 1975:22-23; Langendoen 1968:67; Butler 1985a:1-3; Morley 1985:v-vi; Henderson 1987:57-68; and Hasan 1987:208). Firth's ideas were not fully developed before he died in 1960; Halliday has put them into a coherent form, and has opened up new directions in their application.

Firth believed that a language was not, as Ferdinand de Saussure claimed, merely a 'system' but rather 'a system of systems'. An aspect of Firth's polysystemic hypothesis is related to the notion of meaning as 'function in context'. He, however, in large measure, owed his idea of context to

the influence of Malinowski. Malinowski's 'Context of Situation' (COS) refers to the context in which the users of any language or participants in discourse find themselves. It is a universe of discourse concerning what they say, and what is going on when they say what they say.¹⁶ These contexts, for Firth, are always culturally determined (Lyons 1968:289). Therefore from the perspective of meaning as 'function in context,' there are different contexts in which an item can function.

Influenced by the notion of interrelated categories inherent in discourse and its content, Halliday developed a linguistic theory called 'Scale and Category Grammar' (SCG) in 1961. This provided a framework for the analysis and description of any stretch of written or spoken language which had actually occurred. There are three basic grammatical categories in the framework - 'unit,' 'element,' and 'class' (Butler 1985b:14-15) The 'unit' is a category which corresponds to a segment about which statements may be made. There are five of such units - sentence, clause, group, word and character. 'Elements' are set up to occupy places in the structure of particular units, and there are classes of 'free' and 'subordinate' clauses.

During the late 1960's, the functional nature of language increasingly influenced Halliday's work, and a multifunctional dimension (corresponding to Firth's polysystemic principle [Butler 1985b:14]) was added and became central to the theory. Contemporary SFT thus is seen as a linguistic theory having 'meaning' in the widest sense

as the real goal of linguistic investigation.

1.3.2 - The Current Features of the Theory

The view of language as a system is central to the theory because 'meaning' in language is a well-ordered phenomenon; hence the all-importance of the term 'systemic' in SFT. Halliday says of 'system':

"A system is a set of options with an entry condition: that is to say, a set of things of which one must be chosen, together with a statement of the conditions under which the choice is available." (1976:3)

The theory is, therefore, a theory of meaning as choice. Language users, albeit unconsciously, choose to say what they say out of several options available to them in the language they use as conditioned by relevant extralinguistic parameters. These linguistic choices can be interpreted as a system of meanings, and these meanings are realised in the wordings of the language. The idea of choice in language entails paradigmatic relations (the linguistic choice as one from a set of possibilities) and its realisation - the syntagmatic (the linguistic chain or 'structure') relations. Structure, in SFT, is an output device, the device is used to express the choices already opted for in the language.

As users of a language make choices in the language, they produce texts. These texts are produced in context. According to Halliday, the concept of text relates to the 'instances of linguistic interaction in which people engage: whatever is said or written, in an operational context, as

distinct from citational context like the words listed in a dictionary' (Halliday 1978:108-109). A text therefore is a unit of language in use; a semantic unit (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 1-2).¹⁷

A text occurs in a 'Context of Situation' (COS). According to Halliday, the components of COS are Field, Tenor, and Mode¹⁸, and these assist in focussing attention on the particular speech situation by making explicit the particular characteristics of the text (Halliday et. al. (1964: 90-94); Halliday 1978: 62-64, 1977a: 200-207; Hasan 1978: 230; Maley 1985a: 160-161; Martin 1985: 250). Martin states, for emphasis, that the concepts of Field, Tenor and Mode are not components of speech by themselves but that they help to PREDICT (sic.) text through code. The are components of Context of Situation.

Field refers to the on-going activity and the particular purpose that language is serving within the context of the activity; what is 'going on' has some meaning in the social system; and these meanings have a well-ordered configuration. Field is particularly relevant to making predictions about longer stretches of text, or about the most typical kinds of processes that will occur. Tenor refers to the interaction among participants (status and role relationships). These role relationships are situation-specific. More importantly, these concern aspects of the exchange of meanings among the interlocutors. Mode covers the channel of communications. This is the symbolic organisation with particular reference to the form of the text concerning its channel or medium.

The two modes commonly referred to are the spoken and the written modes.

Text and register are basically related. The configuration of situational and linguistic features of a text realise its register. That is, the semiotic features of the situation in which the text is functioning, and the relevant corresponding patterns of the semantic system, both predict the type of text. What is said at a particular time is determined by the social activity in which one is engaged because a situation is influenced by the semiotic environment (Halliday 1978:35; O'Toole 1988; 1989:5-6). The semantic system is encoded in the 'systemics of language - the ordered sets of options that constitute the linguistic system'. The notion of register in SFT provides one dimension of describing or rather differentiating various texts. The above description of register by Halliday is relevant for my purpose because its application to different texts will be sufficient to identify and characterise them.¹⁹

My reference to texts and text-situations evokes the notion of culture because any language in use manifests its culture, at least situationally. It was this idea of the interrelatedness of language and culture which underscores Malinowski's concept of culture. Through the linguistic code, the users of a language demonstrate the principle of semiotic organisation governing the choice of meaning in culture. It is tacit knowledge that one of the ways to understand a culture is through the understanding of the key role that language plays in the society as the main vehicle

for the transmission of a people's culture from one generation to another (Halliday 1977a:25, 1978:2; Halliday and Hasan 1976:23,26; Hasan 1984:104; Nasr 1980:112-113; Langendoen 1968:7).²⁰ The cultural implications of 'what people mean by what they say' in a specific cultural milieu, however, may be incorporated into the discussions of the contextual configurational meanings of an utterance or a text.

Another very important component of the theory is its explication of functional categories. This sets it clearly apart from other theories of language. These functional components which are regarded as semantic are referred to as 'metafunctions' (Halliday 1985a:xiii-xvi, 1977a:26, 1977b:178, 1978:45-46,112,118; Halliday and Hasan 1976:26-27; Berry 1977:116-112). They are the 'ideational', 'interpersonal', and 'textual'. All languages in use, according to the theory, have in their 'wordings' and 'grammar' meanings interpretable in terms of these three strands of metafunctions. 'Wordings' and 'grammar,' the units of vocabulary and grammar are, both referred to as 'lexicogrammar' (Halliday 1978:21,39; 1985a:xiv). Each element in a language can therefore be gainfully explained when reference is made to what function it plays in the linguistic system because the lexicogrammar as a behavioural potential realises the metafunction.²¹ All languages, in this regard, are organised in terms of what the speaker of any language 'can mean, can say, and can do' as he or she interacts with others in the society (Halliday 1978:39-40).

The ideational metafunction deals with the construction of experience through language; through it, a speaker expresses his experience of the external world and his own world of consciousness. This component is divided into experiential and logical (Halliday 1977b:177-179; Halliday and Hasan 1976:26). The experiential deals more directly with the representation of experience. The logical expresses the abstract logical relations which deal indirectly with experience. The logical subgroup is normally expressed through the recursive patterns of a language. In other words, it shows 'paratactic' or 'hypotactic' (the way groups and phrases form complexes as clauses) relations such as co-ordination, apposition, and so on. These, according to SFT, constitute the logic of the natural language.

The interpersonal metafunction concerns the participants in discourse thereby presenting language as doing something by, and to, the people. It deals with role relationships among the participants in a universe of discourse. It 'represents the speaker in his role as intruder', while the ideational 'represents the speaker in his role as observer' (Halliday and Hasan 1976:26-27). Each speaker directly or indirectly adopts and assigns roles, and the interpersonal thereby expresses the role relationships of the participants in a linguistic situation.

The textual component complements the ideational and the interpersonal by creating what is commonly referred to as relevance; relevance to the environment, both situational and cultural²². Through the textual metafunction, language

is imbued with the potential not just to create text, but to relate itself both to the context of situation and to the preceding and the succeeding text. Cohesion is a typical example of this textual phenomenon because it does not require any specific categorisation of the contextual configurations. By its text-forming potential, it makes provision for texture (see below, section 1.4). It then becomes an important component to both ideational and interpersonal 'meanings' because through it they become actualised.²³

The grammatical systems or categories of Transitivity, Mood and Modality, and Theme correspond respectively to the three main metafunctional categories. Transitivity is the grammar of processes. Halliday defines Transitivity as follows:

"'Transitivity' is the name of this range of meaning potential - the encoding of our experience of processes. To put it in another way, transitivity is the ideational component in the meaning of the clause... Transitivity is the grammar of processes - and the participants in these processes, and the attendant circumstances." (1976:21, 30)

Halliday's concept of transitivity is different from the traditional notion of the verb in English. It neither focuses specifically on the verb as a grammatical category, nor make^s a direct distinction between transitive and intransitive verbs. Its explication involves the entire clause - that is, its entire 'content' and structure. In its characterisation, transitivity is concerned with the relations between the processes and the participants in the clause and such relationships are functional (Halliday 1985a: 39, 101-102; Butler 1985b: 164-165).

The systems of Mood and Modality correspond to the interpersonal metafunction. Both concern the participants' expression of such nuances as attitudes, propositions, possibilities, probabilities and familiarity. Theme corresponds to textual metafunction. It relates to meanings in messages as relevant in the communication process - that is, to the organisation of the clause as message. The three different components - Context of Situation, Metafunctions and the Grammatical Systems may be viewed side-by-side as shown in the table below:

<u>Context of Situation</u>	<u>Metafunctions</u>	<u>Grammatical Systems</u>
Field	Ideational	Transitivity, Tense etc.
Tenor	Interpersonal	Mood/Modality etc.
Mode	Textual	Theme, Deixis, Cohesion, etc.

Table 1.3.2

Correspondence in COS, Metafunctions and its Grammar

Of the three categories of metafunction, cohesion belongs to textual metafunction (Halliday and Hasan 1976:29; 1985:82). Unlike other textual categories, for example Theme and Information, cohesion is regarded as non-structural. Cohesion, as a concept, forms a part of the system of a language. Although it forms a semantic relation in discourse, it is expressed partly through the grammar and partly through the vocabulary.

The notion of a language as a system in SFT however is, incomplete without the notion of its 'formal construct' - the System Network (SN) (Halliday 1985a:xxvi, 1978:40, 1976:101; Berry 1975:188; Fawcett et.al 1984b:135-177). Being the

formal representation of the linguistic theory, the construction of a system network shows a set of features of the language from which the paradigmatic options can be drawn (Joia and Stenton 1980:4). Halliday specifically describes the SN as the main theoretical component of the 'Systemic Grammar' (1985a:x). Martin (1987:17) argues that it forms 'the creative and generalising heart of the grammar' (Turner 1987:70; Fawcett 1987:162).

Fawcett's (1984b:147) work on SN is perhaps the most explicit. He observes that SN is a tool that can be used for modelling relationships between meanings in language. Butler (1985b:44) identifies two major kinds of systems in the SN: simultaneity and dependence. Systems are simultaneous if choices must be made independently of the systems concerned; and dependence occurs where terms in different systems are hierarchically ordered. Apart from evolving a paradigmatic²⁴ but not always symmetrical patterning of language, the organisation of systems into networks becomes possible as the concept of delicacy (a scale of depth of differentiation in grammatical analysis) is extended from structural to systemic relations. Paired symbols are, therefore, organised from left to right to the more delicate. Networks may be drawn at all levels of linguistic description (Butler 1988:93). The grammatical network, for example, looks towards the semantics for its own structural output, while the semantic network focuses on the speech situation and the grammar. This interaction occurs because grammar and semantics are interwoven in this linguistic theory.

The SN is an illustration of possibilities of ordering, and constitutes a set of hypotheses about what is and what is not possible in the language being described. It gives a concise account of the structural descriptions and analyses. In this way, it looks like its summary, or the summary of any of its parts. Most importantly, perhaps, it provides a pattern which is peculiar to the language to which it is applied.

1.4 - Cohesion

Prior to what is often regarded by many linguists as the most comprehensive work on cohesion to date (Halliday and Hasan 1976), a few attempts were made to describe the phenomenon of cohesion (e.g. Darbyshire 1971; Grimes 1975). In the year that Halliday and Hasan's Cohesion in English (1976) was published, Gutwinski's Cohesion in Literary Texts also appeared in print. Although the approaches may be different, the main thrust of all the descriptions is that cohesion is a device utilised by users of a language for the maintenance of the continuity of certain aspects of messages in texts. It seems obvious, even as some claim, that these other attempts to describe cohesion have benefitted tremendously from Halliday's earlier publications particularly those on transitivity, textual functions, theme and rheme, lexicogrammar, and the structure of connected discourse (Darbyshire 1971:123; Grimes 1975:272; Gutwinski 1976:21). Grimes (op. cit. p. 272-273), for example, observes that all of these scholars directly or indirectly adopt their terminologies from Halliday's works. Halliday and Hasan's notable contribution to the study of cohesion is often mentioned by scholars (Fowler 1977:64; Richard et. al. 1985:45-46; Bingham 1986:51; Pappas 1985:177; Joia and Stenton 1980:110-112; Grimes 1975:272-273; Gumperz et. al. 1984:5)²⁵. Fowler (op.cit.) remarks about the consistency of Halliday, among modern grammarians, in maintaining 'a continuous interest in the features of linkage between co-occurring sentences studied under the study of 'cohesion.'²⁶

Darbyshire's description of cohesion is from the perspective of 'style', while Grimes's is from 'discourse'. Each of their descriptions forms a very minor part of the entire work. Gutwinski's major contribution is limited to 'literary texts'. Halliday and Hasan's work is, generally, applicable to different genres. In order to avoid the confusion that may arise from a mixture of terminologies, I will adhere strictly to Halliday and Hasan's description. Besides, no other description is as thorough and integrated as theirs. Moreover, Halliday and Hasan (1985:70-95) have recently built into the concept of cohesion the analysis of 'Cohesive Harmony;' an illuminating method of realising aggregates of cohesive relations in texts.

Concerning its definition, Halliday and Hasan (1976) comment:

"The concept of cohesion is set up to account for relations in discourse... Cohesion refers to the range of possibilities that exist for linking something with what has gone before. Since the linking is achieved through relations in MEANING (sic.)... what is in question is the set of meaning relations which function in this way: the semantic resources which are drawn on for the purposes of creating text. Cohesion is defined as the set of possibilities that exist in the language for making texts hang together: the potential that the speaker or writer has at his disposal" (pp. 10, 18).

From the above definition(s), some issues are clearly set out. The concept of cohesion is a semantic one. It refers to relations of meanings which exist in a text. Being relational means that the interpretation of some element in the text depends on that of another element. This concept of relations, furthermore, leads to the concept of presupposition - the presupposing element and the

presupposed; consequently the concept of tie - that links both parts together. According to Halliday and Hasan a relation of cohesion cannot be effectively decoded except by recourse to the elements of presupposing and the presupposed (1976: 5, 13, 14, 17, 294, and 303; 1985: 73; Widdowson 1979: 67-70 and Gumperz et. al. 1984: 5).

Five types of cohesion are identified in English: reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction, and lexical (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 13, 29, 303; Halliday 1977b: 180, 1985b: 287-289; Hasan 1984b: 185). Further distinctions are made: reference, substitution and ellipsis are classified as grammatical, while lexical is, as the label indicates lexical. In between the two groups is conjunction cohesion. The grammatical group is so described because it is realised by the 'closed system' of the language. Lexical belongs to the 'open system' - the items of the vocabulary. Conjunction differs from both of these in that it is cohesive not by continuity of form or reference but by semantic connection. That is, some relation is established between the meanings of two continuous passages of text, such that the interpretation of the second is dependent on the relation in which it stands to the first.

What establishes the phenomenon of cohesion inter-clausally is the cohesive tie.²⁷ The tie links one item from one clause to another. In an extended text, a series of ties then form a chain or chains depending on how the messages are organised. Hasan's emphasis on two-ness and texture is significant. A tie cannot exist without two members (Hasan

1984a:7; Halliday and Hasan 1985:73). In, for example, a non-text or a minimal text, cohesive ties can have no function. For a text to have cohesive ties, there must be texture - the display of some semantic relations which can be referred to as cohesive. Texture differentiates a text from non-text. When a cohesive tie points back to an item in a text, it is referred to as anaphora. But when it points forward, it is referred to as cataphora. The interpretation of a cohesive device is endophoric when it is found within text and exophoric when it lies outside text, that is, in the context of situation. In this linguistic theory, only the endophoric reference is cohesive. This, perhaps, explains why anaphora is often described as 'implicit', 'unmarked', and 'Given'. Cataphora is described as 'explicit', 'marked', and 'New'. (Halliday and Hasan 1976:19, Halliday 1968:231; Grimes 1975:288-289). But the concept of 'phoric' direction is a process one, involving one item pointing to another.

It is not that exophora has nothing to do with cohesion. It does 'have potential relevance to statements of meaning about texts of language events' (Gregory 1967:177-178). More frequently, it is impossible to interpret a piece of language in whatever form or genre without some information regarding its situation of use.²⁸ Endophoric relation, first of all, is evident in texts, and may not be open to subjective interpretations as may be given to exophoric relation. Secondly, the Contextual Configuration (CC) of Field, Tenor and Mode, as earlier referred to, is sufficient to indicate not only the COS but the register of a text. Cohesion and

the experiential and the logical. Other systemicists, for example, Fawcett, recognise as many as eight. Butler also observes that systemicists draw different networks for the same area of grammar because there is no agreed set of criteria and possibly because the criteria for setting up system networks are not free of any prior functional bias (see also Butler 1985b: 83-88; Hudson 1976: 100^{ff}). He also suggests that work needs to be done to justify convincingly the correlation between the semantic choices within the grammar and the situation type categories of field, tenor and mode because work done on it so far appears to justify these categories merely as a set of semantic choices.

SFT, like any theory, ought to be seen at any stage of development as capable of being improved upon because language itself is dynamic. As a result, there ought to be re-groupings and re-subcategorisations. A foundation seems to be laid because each of the components of the categories of 'function' and 'situation' is able to stand on its own as well as form an integrated whole with the remaining components.

In his review article titled 'Systemic grammar,' Hudson (1986: 791-815) makes very critical observations about SFT. He acknowledges, nevertheless, the tremendous impact that it has made in comparison with other linguistic theories as he suggests in the following comment:

"That a lot of linguists are attracted by Halliday's general philosophy, especially with the rather dry-as-dust and daunting wares offered by the alternative theories. Halliday is interested in the relations between language and

people, and many people with similar interests find his work stimulating. Another reason is that Halliday offers a comprehensive analysis of English grammar which is relatively easy to apply to texts - something which no other school has to offer."³⁰

The above quotation supports SFT in comparison to other linguistic theories. It shows SFT's recognition that language can only be meaningfully described by considering its users. Finally, it stresses the importance of textual analysis, as the analysis of reference and lexis is meaningfully shown in this study, by investigating naturally occurring texts in the Yoruba language.

Most relevant to this work, however, is his somewhat passing remark on the place of cohesion in SFT:

"The identification of SG with Hallidayan linguistics has a disadvantage, however, which is that SG then comes to include any area of linguistic work in which Halliday has engaged, whether or not it has anything specifically to do with the theory of language structure called SG. I have in mind here the work on cohesion (Halliday and Hasan 1976) and much of the work on social structure and language and on language in education." (p. 792)

I regard this comment as a passing remark for two main reasons. Firstly, Hudson states in the same paper that the work forms part of SFT. Secondly, and surprisingly, he does not see the need to answer, even if briefly, the question that he poses to his readers - "how much of the work is 'really' part of SG."

Conceding to Hudson the fact that many people³¹ working within the framework of SFT may regard all works by Halliday as being motivated by it, yet I regard Cohesion in English

(Halliday and Hasan 1976) as an enduring part of SFT. Being a significant part of SFT, on the one hand, the concept of cohesion has again been examined in Halliday (1985a) and Halliday and Hasan (1985). In the former, it is up-dated in a fairly long chapter (chapter nine). In the latter, it is expanded in the concept of Cohesive Harmony (section 1.4 above). The concept of cohesion, on the other hand, has significantly established SFT's concept of the relation between semantics and discourse by investigating the use of language above the clause. Discourse, as Hudson notes in the first quotation above, is concerned with the textual organisation of the clause. Through textual analysis SFT seems to capture more vividly than the other linguistic theories the analysis of discourse. It thus provides a better representation of the way people use language to mean in different contexts.

Further on cohesion, Brown and Yule's (1983) criticism of text and cohesion in Halliday and Hasan (1976) should be noted. They referred to a distinction of meaning relation which according to them 'many students adopting Halliday and Hasan's approach have failed to draw, and which Halliday and Hasan themselves are somewhat ambivalent about' (p.195).³² Although both of these scholars declare that Halliday and Hasan (1976) is by far the most comprehensive standard text on the subject of cohesion, they question its position on the explicit realisation of the cohesive relation which exists between the items in a text. They suggest that a distinction need be drawn between the meaning relations which hold

between items in a text and its explicit expressions. It is their view that formal cohesion will neither guarantee an identification of a text nor guarantee textual cohesion. They, nevertheless, concede that Halliday and Hasan are not really concerned to produce a description which accounts for how texts are understood, but rather are concerned to examine the linguistic resources available to the speaker/writer to mark cohesive relations. To them (Brown and Yule) such an examination, and their (Halliday and Hasan's) justifications, are 'rich, interesting and insightful' (p. 204).

A closer look at Brown and Yule's consideration is, nevertheless, insightful. They use Halliday and Hasan's (1976) Example (1.1.) on page 2:

"Wash and core six cooking apples.
Put them into a fireproof dish." (underlining mine)

They question the validity of Halliday and Hasan's view that the item 'them' in the second sentence really refers to the six cooking apples in the first sentence as anaphoric reference. To them, the six cooking apples in the second sentence have undergone a change of state, and that in the first sentence they were the original apples 'washed and uncored.' Their view therefore is that in any adequate mode of discourse description must accommodate the various connections which exist in texts.

It is my opinion, however, that 'them' implicitly can neither be interpreted, nor explained semantically any more than it has the features 'specific, plural, solid and plus animate.'

Its explicit meaning therefore can be interpreted, particularly within the text, only in relation to something with which it shares a class of co-referentiality. That is, its semantic interpretation is not available except by relating it to something else in the sentence or in the text. This correlate, unlike Brown and Yule's, means that 'them' is only identical with six cooking apples. It may be true that while the complete interpretation available to this item can only be retrieved through the features of its specific state, neither the listener nor the reader will normally, and consciously show an awareness of these specificities as enumerated by Brown and Yule. The fact, therefore, that the apples are peeled does not mean that they have lost their status as referent. It seems to me, nevertheless, that the use of 'them' is linguistically mediated - since this state of affairs has obviously been mediated. That is, they are peeled apples.

Also the explication by SFT context, register and coherence is relevant to this argument. Texts make meaning in context. The users of the language would know through context, even if intuitively, that 'them' shares the same register as six cooking apples in the text. It is this tacit understanding that makes the text coherent. Agreeably, a description of the state of affairs may be necessary, but not an emphasis on a change of identity.

1.6 - Language and Culture

The context of a text or an utterance is embedded in the context of culture because the systemic options occurring in the structural patterns of a language provide a very elaborate set of resources for meaning (Hasan 1984a; Fawcett 1984a). This means that the relation between language and culture is a relation between overlapping semiotic systems - the linguistic and the cultural. A speaker of a language selects, therefore, between the semantic options of his language in the light of his knowledge of his culture.

The Yoruba language semiotic environment is a well-regulated one in which a speaker has to consider complex social activities, social groups, roles and behaviour patterns in any linguistic interaction (Lamb 1984:88-98). Social activities are perhaps the most obvious characteristics in which people engage. Governance, farming, are examples of social activities. People in any society belong to different social groups. Examples are the rich and the poor, the educated and the uneducated. Social roles and behaviour patterns in any culture are multilayered. Examples are the social role of a father in a family or a religious priest.

Most important is that a typical Yoruba language speaker or writer is expected to make the necessary distinctions in his or her choice of language concerning these cultural determinants. An example is the referring expressions or terms of address which take into account the status, age etc. of the addressee in the community. Brown and Gilman's (1972)

classic work shows that in the languages of several European countries, the consistent use of a pronoun style by a speaker reveals his or her class, status and political views. It is symbolic of what they (Brown and Gilman) refer to as 'the power semantics' whereby the relationship between two persons of unequal statuses demands that the superior uses 'T' ('tu' in French) for his or her subordinate while he receives 'V' ('vous' also in French). Between equals, nevertheless, pronominal address is reciprocal or symmetrical.

One distinction in the pronominal system of many languages (e.g. Korean, Japanese and Javanese), following Brown and Gilman, is described by Levinson (1983:90) as 'a referent honorific system' whereby the speaker may encode respect (i.e. politeness) in the address form to the addressee. In such usages, the morphology of the languages may affect the 'honorific concord' and this may be explained by reference to the context of culture (Levinson op. cit. p. 92).

1.7 - Applications and Conclusion

How applicable³³ then is SFT, which is based on the analysis of the English language, to the study of other languages? Firstly all languages, according to Halliday and Hasan (1976:247-248), 'display certain features which can be regarded as cohesive.' Secondly, the theory has been, and is being used to, describe some aspects of Chinese, ^{Hindi} Indi, Malay, Indonesian, Arabic and Weri languages.³⁴ Thirdly, SFT has universal aspects such as the metafunctions and the fundamental categories which derive from them such as

Transitivity, Mood and Theme. The concepts of reference and lexis which are my focus in this study may be regarded as 'universal' because no language could function effectively without their use. Furthermore, not only has Halliday and Hasan's Cohesion in English become a classic text on this topic, but their latest seminal contribution regarding the concept of 'Cohesive Harmony' (Halliday and Hasan 1985; Hasan 1984) extends significantly the apparently shadowy relationship between cohesion and coherence. My task, therefore, is to apply the relevant analytical categories of the theory to my data on Yoruba and to determine how far they describe and explain referential and lexical cohesion.

Notes

1. The first three of this group lie mostly to the West of Nigeria, but in Borgu, the Busa language belongs to the Mande group, and Bariba to the Gur. Greenberg's Benue-Congo family includes (see Shaw op. cit. p. 94) Kambari, Dakakari, Jaba, Birom, Jukun, Ibiobio, Efik, Andoni and Bantoid - which itself includes Tiv, Mambila and the Bantu languages of Africa. The Adamawa-Eastern family includes Chamba Vere, Mumuye, and languages stretching eastwards through Cameroon and the Central African Republic. There is one representative of the West Atlantic family in Nigeria, which is Fulani. The Afro-asiatic group in Nigeria, the group in which Greenberg places ancient Egypt, Berber, Semitic, and Cushitic includes the Chadic languages. Finally, Chadic includes Hausa, Angas, Kotoko, Margi, Tera, Mandaran, and Mubi.
2. To this group Shaw (op. cit. p. 93) adds Igbirra and Igala.
3. Nigeria, initially, had three regions: North, West, and East. In 1963, the Midwest was created out of the Western Region. In 1966, 12 States were created; by 1976, the States numbered 19. Two more were created in 1987 excluding the Federal Capital.
4. Oyotunji appears to be a very significant name. The town and people of Oyo in Nigeria play very significant roles in the history, language, and religious life of Yoruba people. Oyo State in Nigeria contains the largest population of Yoruba speakers. There is also a belief among non-linguists that the Oyo dialect of Yoruba is the most 'original' (i. e. archaic) of all its dialects.
5. This remarkable Yoruba man was born about 1809 and was sold into slavery at the age of twelve. On his return to Sierra Leone, he was educated and baptised as Samuel Crowther, the origin of this name not being clear although his Yoruba name Ajayi is often used as well. In 1842 he went to the CMS (Church Missionary Society) London and took Orders, the first African to do so. He returned to the Yorubas as a missionary, and in 1844 made the first biblical translation into Yoruba. He was made Bishop of the Niger territory in 1864, and continued in this office until his death in Lagos in 1891.
6. The manuscript report of the conference proceedings can be found among Crowther's papers at the Church Missionary Society Archives in London.
7. Bamgbose (1986: 64) erroneously refers to the date as 1843.
8. Some of the texts to be analysed in this work are taken from newspapers.

9. For a definition of tone, see Ogunbowale (op. cit. p.20).
10. Igba is given three meanings which suggests that unless in the content and the context of the sentence, a word could mean more than one word. Other examples are: dá (to break) as in Mo dá igi náà (I break/ broke the wood), and da (to stop) as in òwú náà dá èjè náà dúró (the cotton stopped the bleeding); fé (blow) as in mo fé iná náà I blew at the fire), and fé as in Alabi fé Iyabo (Alabi married Iyabo). These examples, however, form a very small proportion of the words in the language compared to the ones made clear just by the tone marks. x Surely not the same word?
11. In the Yoruba language, the importance of tone is emphasised (Adetugbo 1973:200; Bamgbose 1986:33).
12. Words are formed in the language mostly by the process of derivation. Nouns and verbs are essentially invariant; that is, nouns are neither declined for case nor inflected for number, and verbs do not change for person, number or gender. Instead, words are formed by prefixation and reduplication.
13. Pulleyblank (op. cit. p. 982) discusses certain inflectional processes observed in the Yoruba pronominal system. Examples given are mo rí i (I saw him/her/it); je é (eat it) and fà á (pull it) noting, in particular, that these i (him/her/it), e (it) and a illustrate the fact that the form of the third person singular pronoun object is dependent on the verb that it follows. That is, the quality of the vowel of the verb will influence the quality of the pronoun. Furthermore, the tone of the object pronoun depends on the tone of the verb: if the verb is mid or low, then the pronoun is high; if the verb is high, then the pronoun is mid. He concludes that these three examples are not exhaustive. For example, additional forms are required in possessive noun phrases. They are representative of the morphological changes in both segmental make-up and the tones that characterise the various syntactically determined pronominal forms.
14. Again, according to Afolayan, it is doubtful if any full or complete analysis of any language can ever be achieved. This appears impossible, in my view, given the dynamic nature of a natural language, and for the fact that most if not all the analysts who are native speakers of the language enter its use through their various dialects. I, for example, speak four dialects of the language: Ijesa, Ilorin, Igbomina, and Yagba. In the process, the sociological entry behaviour potential differs from one to another. This fact may partly account for what Bamgbose meant regarding different perceptions of the analysts.
15. Quick et. al. (p.10) note that the term 'grammar' constantly moves away and subsequently returns to the catholicity that it had in the Greek tradition more than x

two thousand years ago, covering the whole field of language structure.'

16. All these processes whereby participants say what they say and the contexts in which they say what they say seem to make language real (see Peter L. Berger and Thomas Luckmann's The Social Construction of Reality, A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge, Penguin Books, 1966).
17. In Hallidayan appraisal, the level above lexicogrammar is viewed more as text and less as discourse in contrast to how some other textlinguists (e.g. Dijk 1977:11-12; Grimes 1975:17) appear to look at text. Halliday (1978:2) believes that 'language does not consist of sentences, it consists of texts or discourse - the exchange of meanings in interpersonal contexts of one kind or another.'
18. It is necessary to point out that style was used in place of Tenor in Halliday et.al. (1964).
19. Ellis (1966:83) sees register as a division of idiolect-registers of the performer (I prefer a user of language). Martin (1985) argues that because registers vary from text to text, the variation can be accounted for in each text by the use of schematic structure. It seems that he views register as a semiotic system. But Lemke (1985:279) views register from a 'protean point of view and suggests five interpretations: (1) the paradigmatic system of discourse, (2) a source of systematic typology of texts, (3) a typology of situational contexts, (4) as a resource for language in a speech community, and (5) as the semiotic of genre.
20. In regard to culture, see also Crick (1976:43).
21. In retrospect to Malinowski (Malinowski 1923, in Halliday 1973:23-24) concerning the functional nature of language, Halliday writes: "It was in the language of young children that Malinowski saw most clearly the functional origins of the language systems...The social functions which language is serving in the life of the child determine both the options which he creates for himself and their realizations in structure...The adult language bears the marks of its humble origin in systems like these. But it differs in fundamental ways; and perhaps the most fundamental because this is what makes it necessary to develop a linguistic form...Every adult linguistic act, with a few broadly specifiable exceptions, is serving more than one function at once."
22. For the interaction of language and culture see Halliday (1977). There is a clearly enunciated interplay of the semantic system and the social system.
23. Berry (1977:119-121) classifies the experiential and the logical metafunctions as main rather than as subgroups.

24. Butler (1985a:217) observes that it is the late version of SFT, not the SCG which considers paradigmatic relations 'as formalized in system network.'
25. On another note, however, Widdowson (1979:67), and Ferrara (1985:141) use Labov/Sacks models on Cohesion respectively.
26. Fowler further makes reference to other influential body of linguists who have also demonstrated notable interest in 'unity' of a text from a different perspective: Jakobsonian analyses; Sinclair and himself (1977:64).
27. Larson (1984:390) refers to cohesive ties as 'spans'.
28. It is perhaps because of the above three major aspects of the theory that some argue that it aims to achieve too much. It seems to me a dynamic approach given the pervasive influence of language on man and his society.
29. See Benjamin N. Colby's 'psychological relationship' in Coherence in language and culture p.454^{ff}.
30. Acknowledging also that the treatment by SFT of categories is superior to what is found in other current theories, he considers the categories of feature and function the most positive characteristics of the theory. He, however, remarks that Halliday has made significant contributions at all levels of linguistics except morphology.
31. He also observes that various other linguists have developed Halliday's ideas in their own direction such that they often finish with rather different theories which could be included under the label of the theory only at the cost of enormous confusion.
32. Fowler (1977:64, 72-74), on the other hand, refers to Hasan (1968) in which she identifies some 'indispensable syntactic ties' between sentences that ensure that discourse is coherent in the ordinary sense of the word.
33. Halliday (1987) in his plenary paper (which I recorded) presented at the 14th International Systemic Workshop in Sydney on "Systemic linguistics: directions for development," makes an attempt to respond briefly to some of the criticisms and misinterpretations often placed on the theory. He feels that apart from the lack of time to answer his critics, it is impossible to explain step-by-step each of the steps taken in any analysis. He concedes, however, that there is need for more discussion of some fundamental concepts, categories and notions.
34. He also reported at the Workshop (see note 33) that much of his works have and are being translated to Italian, Spanish, and Portuguese languages.

CHAPTER TWO

STRUCTURAL GROUPS

2.0. - Introduction

In order to explain cohesion in both reference and lexis, that is referential and lexical cohesion, a prior description of the main grammatical groups of a language becomes necessary. This is because the cohesive relations build on existing structures in the language. The cohesive ties between clauses, for example, are to be found within the various groups which constitute the clause. Also reference, in the specific sense that Halliday and Hasan use it in relation to referential cohesion is almost exclusively a property of the nominal group. Halliday and Hasan comment:

"Grammatically, all reference items except the demonstrative adverbs, and some comparative adverbs, function in the nominal group (noun phrase). It will be necessary therefore to give a brief account of the structure of the nominal group, in order to explain the grammar of reference in more explicit terms" (1976: 37-39).

It is necessary, then, for this study to provide a description of the structural groups in Yoruba.

Yoruba language, as indicated in the preceding chapter (1.2.3.1) has, generally, the structural typology of Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) (Odunuga 1982:266). Halliday (1985a:159) divides the English clause into nominal, verbal and adverbial groups. In grammatical terms, languages with SVO typologies usually have the structural functions of Subject, Predicate, Complement, and Adjunct (SPCA). The V-element of the SVO

typology corresponds generally to the verbal group or the Predicate of SPCA. The nominal group may occur in both S- and O- elements of the SVO and in systemic terms the S, C, A elements of the SPCA.

In SFT, the three functional components of 'meaning'- ideational, interpersonal and textual may be realised in the grammar of the clause. They are also relevant for the interpretation of the group structure because their realisation occurs 'throughout the grammar of a language' (Halliday 1985a:158). The difference is that while each component may be fully realised in the clause, it is partially realised in the group. Rather than analyse the structure of the group simultaneously from the three strands of 'meaning,' one interpretation at a time will be sufficient because the group has fewer structural constituents than the clause. In the process, the ideational component will be split into two: experiential and the logical. This demonstrates the notion that apart from organising meaning as experience, language is also organised as expressing 'certain very general logical relations' (Halliday 1985a:159).

What is a group? This is clearly explained by considering the difference between a phrase and a group: a phrase 'is a reduced form of the clause, whereas a group is an enlarged strain of word' (Halliday 1985a:xxi). By this is meant that a phrase has more of the clause-potential; and a group that of the word-potential. Although the combination of words in both the phrase and the group is organised in a particular logical relation, the phrase has the potential to admit any

variant of the grammatical unit whereas the element in the group occurs 'in certain sequence; and the sequence is largely fixed' (Halliday 1985a:176, 187). The group must have a 'head' - the noun or pronoun in the nominal, the verb in the verbal and the adverb in the adverbial. These base units form 'heads' in the group structure and the other elements pre- or post-modify (or qualify) them, whereas it may be difficult to ascertain the 'head' of a phrase. Both phrase and group function in the intermediate position between the rank of a word and a clause (Halliday 1985a:159).

Huddleston's (1988:140-155) criticism of Halliday's (1985a) idea of rank, group/phrase is hereby pertinent. He wonders why in Halliday (1985) the major category of adverbial group replaces adjectival group as found in his earlier descriptive work, yet he describes a small class of prepositions as a prepositional group. In his discussion of Halliday's 'rank grammar for English,' Huddleston observes that some aspects of his analysis lack 'total accountability.' He points out, for example, that allowance is made for 'downward rankshift' (which Halliday refers to as 'embedding') but none is made for 'upward rankshift' (e.g. a word functioning directly in the structure of a clause) which enables a sentence to be 'analysable exhaustively into an integral number of clauses, groups, words, and morpheme.'

Huddleston also observes that Halliday uses the term group in two senses. First, it is contrasted with phrase as described above. He relates this contrastive idea to that of Halliday's analysis of the relation between a preposition and

its complement (both complements being nominal groups) in clause structure whereby the preposition functions as a 'minor Predicator' on the interpersonal dimension and as 'a minor process' on the ideational dimension. Second, group subsumes phrase; and in this sense it equates rank. Being that it is the prepositional phrase only that is recognised in the theory, phrase cannot be a rank because sentences cannot be analysed exhaustively into phrases, hence it is thus assigned to group rank. Huddleston asserts, however, that assigning the prepositional phrase to a group rank is 'quite anomalous' even though the idea behind it is to satisfy the total accountability requirement such that a clause like 'the train/ had arrived/ on time' had to be analysed neatly into three groups. When a complement is also included such a group must have a group functioning within it thus involving rankshifting in order to satisfy total accountability.

Huddleston's argument concerning the 'downward rankshift' (which he claims Halliday accounts for) and 'upward rankshift' (which he claims Halliday does not account for) seems to me to be explicable in the way the notion of paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations is explained in the theory. It is noteworthy also that Huddleston acknowledges that ^aprepositional phrase does not need to involve rankshift (Huddleston, op. cit. p.154). The criteria for categorising prepositional group and phrase as they occur in the theory may not be very explicit, the category of adverbial group is seen to cover and distinguish the analyses of both

prepositional group and phrase at a level of delicacy.

Although the category of sentence is referred to as clause complex in SFT, the hierarchy of its constituents (i.e. clause, group, word, and morpheme) is regarded as a rank for the grammar of English (Matthiessen 1989:864). It seems to me also that Halliday's analyses show the boundaries between the constituents. A general observation of Huddleston's criticism on the issue of rank/group-phrase is that he seems to emphasise single words (i.e. prepositions) rather than group. Halliday's interpretation of grammar is clause-based rather than word-based (Matthiessen 1989:863). A word functions more meaningfully within the total meaning potential of other words in the group.

In this chapter, I will briefly investigate the structures of the nominal, verbal and adverbial groups in Yoruba. Short texts and relevant clauses will be used to illustrate them.

2.1.0 - The Nominal Group (NG)

The following two descriptions of the NG will be briefly examined. The first is by Halliday and relates specifically to the English language; the second is by Bamgbose and relates specifically to the Yoruba language.¹

(1)

"Nominal groups are nouns plus their determiners and any other modifiers; while in nominalisations some element other than a noun, a verb perhaps or a whole clause has nominal status assigned to it" (Halliday 1977a:7).

(2)

"A word or a group of words which can stand as the subject of a clause is a nominal group. Such a word may be a noun, a pronoun, or a pronominal; and the group of words consists of a noun and its qualifier or qualifiers." (Bamgbose 1967: 8)

The first definition makes a clear distinction between nominal groups and nominalisations. Nominal groups are nouns 'modified' by other elements whereas nominalisations² are words other than nouns which play the role of nouns. The second definition by Bamgbose which describes the nominal group in Yoruba consists of a noun which may serve as the subject of a clause and its qualifiers. Qualifiers, in this instance, may be adjectives and determiners. Like Bamgbose (1967: 8, 11-17), other Yoruba scholars (Awobuluyi 1978: 38-44; Abiri 1981: 37-39), describe the ^{nominal} elements which comprise the nominal group in the language as qualifiers. In SFT, the group structure is analysed mainly from the perspectives of its experiential and logical meanings.

The basic question to be answered concerning the nominal group in this study is: what kind of items comprise the nominal group in the Yoruba language? My analysis will be discussed in relation to Halliday's analysis of the English language wherever necessary.

Meanwhile, I shall briefly look at the patterns of the nominal group already described by some Yoruba scholars. The general patterns of NG set up by Bamgbose (1967: 16) and Awobuluyi (1978: 42) are very similar but certainly differ significantly in certain respects.

Bamgbose's pattern:

1	2	3	4	5
Head Noun or Pronoun	Adjective	Numeral	Clause	Demonstrative

He gives this example to illustrate the pattern;

(1)

àwon iwé kékèké mèrèrin ti mo kó wá yen
 those book small all four that I carry come that
 'those four small books that I brought'

The clause may be structured according to this pattern:

1	2	3	4	5
Head Noun or Pronoun	Adjective	Numeral	Clause	Demonstrative
awon iwe	kekeke	mererin	ti mo ko wa	yen

'those four small books that I brought'

Figure 2.1.1 Bamgbose's Pattern of Nominal Group

Awobuluyi's pattern:

1	2	3	4	5	6
Head Noun or Pronoun	Appositive Qualifier	Adjective	Numeral	Relative Clause	Topical Qualifier

He gives the following example to illustrate the pattern;

(2)

okò ayókélé dúdú méta tí mo rà ni wón bàjé
 vehicle slow-moving black three that I buy FOC. they damage
 'the three black cars that I bought were what they damaged'

Clause number (2) may be structured according to Awobuluyi's pattern:

1	2	3	4	5	6
Head Noun or Pronoun	Apositive Qualifier	Adjective	Numeral	Relative Clause	Topical Qualifier
oko	ayokele	dudu	meta	ti mo ra	ni won baje

'the three black cars that I bought were what they damaged'

Figure 2.1.2 - Awobuluyi's Pattern of Nominal Group

Examples (1) and (2) are obviously non-symmetrical patterns: (1) is a nominal group and (2) is a clause.³ The Head Noun in (1) is preceded by awon (those), a demonstrative word. Number (1) also does not have what Awobuluyi describes as 'apositive qualifier' and 'topical qualifier' in number (2). I will, at the end of the following analysis arrive at a pattern of the nominal group in Yoruba described in SFT terms. I will make reference to the above two patterns whenever it is appropriate.

2.1.1 - Experiential Structure of Nominal Group in English

As already explained in the first chapter, the experiential metafunction concerns the encoding of experience. The encoding of experience, however, can only be carried out through the interpretation of certain elements within the entire syntagm. In Halliday's consideration of the nominal group, its elements are explained in different types of structural organisation from the Thing to the Deixes. The Head Noun or Pronoun is labelled Thing. The Thing is the main semantic component of the NG; that is, the element Thing in a NG is realised by a proper noun, a common noun or

personal pronoun. As a functional label in SFT, it stands for the same element often described as Headword. Proper names refer to persons, institutions and places. Common nouns refer to a common class of referents, hence they are often accompanied by some elements which express their specificity or particularity. This is because the NG has to do both with the way we name and describe something. These characteristics are vital both to the person doing the naming, or describing, and to the participant to whom these messages are being conveyed.

The 'Adjective' is labelled 'Epithet' in SFT. Epithets describe the quality of Thing. This description may be an 'objective property' of the Thing or a 'subjective attitude' of the speaker towards the Thing. The Epithet describing the objective property of the Thing is 'potentially defining' hence it is experiential in function. A special element of the Epithet is the Classifier. A Classifier indicates a subclass of the Thing being described. It does not compare, however, with the other Epithets or Thing in degrees or in intensity. The Numeral is given a very close label, Numerative; the Numerative element indicates some numerical feature of the group. Numeratives may specify an exact number by the use of cardinal (i.e. one), or an inexact number (i.e. many/several), they may be ordinals (i.e. first). The Deictic element in English identifies a specific subset of the Thing in three ways. First, it identifies a kind of proximity to the speaker (e.g. this) demonstratively. Second, the speaker may identify possession

by making reference to 'Person' (e.g. my). Third, it indicates that the Thing is identifiable somewhere where it is recoverable (i.e. the). The Qualifier may consist of 'Process'⁴ (a 'Process' may express the process itself, participants in the process and circumstances associated with it [Halliday 1985a:101]) or a 'Range' (an element or a circumstance which specifies the scope of the process [Halliday 1985a:134, Butler 1985b:166]).

The following two figures illustrate, generally, the experiential structure of the nominal group in English (Halliday 1985a:159;170). The first group, that is number (3), contains trains as Thing which is preceded by various other items which occur in certain sequence. The second group, that is number (4), also has trains as Thing but is followed by two other items.

(4) Those two splendid old electric trains.

Structurally:

those	two	splendid	old	electric	trains
Deictic	Numerative	Epithet.1	Epithet.2	Classifier	Thing

Figure 2.1.3 - Experiential Structure of the Nominal Group in English from Deictic to Thing (Halliday 1985a:159)

Deictic and the other functional elements may be abbreviated as follows (Deictic = Deic.; Numerative = Num.; Epithet = Epi/Epit.; Classifier = Classi.; 'Process' = Pro.; and 'Range'

(5) Those two splendid old trains with pantographs

Structurally:

those	two	splendid	old	electric	trains	with	pantographs
Deic.	Num.	Epit. 1	Epit. 2	Classi.	Thing	Qualifier	
						'Pro'	'Range'
							Thing

Figure 2.1.4. -Experiential Structure of the Nominal Group in English from Deictic to Qualifier (Halliday 1985a: 170)

2.1.1.1 - Experiential Structure of the NG in Yoruba

Bamgbose and Awobuluyi's (section 2.1.0 above) patterns of the nominal group may be briefly considered. Both of these scholars use class labels for the elements comprising the nominal group to show their sequence as qualifiers. I will describe these elements in their functional terms because the experiential component of SFT describes language as the expression of patterns of experience. It concerns the functional view of language that attempts to explain the organisation and patterning of language from the perspectives of the functions it is meant to serve.

As remarked above (section 2.1.0), Bamgbose's example is a nominal group but Awobuluyi's is not; it is a clause. Bamgbose's example will be analysed first and the nominal part of Awobuluyi's example will then be analysed.

(6)

awon	iwe	kekeke	mererin	ti	mo	ko	wa	yen
those	book	small	all-four	that I carry come that				
Deic.	Thing	Epithet	Num.	Qualifier				
				'Range'	'Process'			
				Thing		Deic.		

'those four small books that I brought'

Figure 2.1.5. - Experiential Structure of Bamgbose's Nominal Group Pattern

Relevant comments on the above NG will be discussed along with that of Awobuluyi which now follows:

(7)

oko	ayokele	dudu	meta	ti	mo	ra
vehicle	slow-moving	black	three	that	I	buy
Thing	Epithet.1	Epit.2	Numerative	Qualifier		
				'Range'	'Process'	
				Thing		

'The three black cars that I bought'

Figure 2.1.6. - Experiential Structure of Awobuluyi's Nominal Group Pattern

Bamgbose and Awobuluyi's patterns above already drawn attention to some differences between English and Yoruba nominal groups. In English, typically, the elements from the Deictics to the Classifier precede the Thing (e.g. Figures 2.1.3 and 2.1.4 above). The Thing is then followed by a

Qualifier which in English is either a phrase or a clause (Halliday 1985a:166; [e.g. Figure 2.1.4]). In Yoruba, typically, the Deictic may precede the Thing or follow it - awon (those) and yen (that) in Figure 2.1.5. Other Qualifiers follow the Thing; these may be single elements or an embedded clause - numbers (5) and (6) above (Figures 2.1.5 and 2.1.6).

In order to effectively establish the nominal group pattern in Yoruba, more examples will be considered. The following examples will be organised from the minimal to maximal groups. The attainment of maximal group is possible in principle but not in practice because the structure may become unusable except for special purposes.

(8) 'mo' (I) in Mo gbo lana
 I hear yesterday
 'I heard yesterday'

'I' and

(9) nwon (they) in Nwon tete lo
 they quickly go
 'they went quickly'

'they'

Figure 2.1.7: 1-Element NG

(10) Inu mi (my stomach) in

inu mi ko dun rara
stomach my NEG. sweet at all
'I am not happy at all'

Inu	mi
stomach	my
Thing	Deic.

'my stomach' and

(11) iwe yi (this book) in

iwe yi dara pupo
book this good many/much
'this book is very good'

iwe	yi
book	this
Thing	Deic.

'this book'

Figure 2.1.8: 2-Element NGs

(12) Olorun alaanu alagbara (God merciful powerful) in

Olorun alaanu alagbara yio toju omo naa
God merciful powerful will look child d-d
'the merciful and powerful God will take care of the child'

Olorun	alaanu	alagbara
God	merciful	powerful
Thing	Epithet (1)	Epithet (2)

'God the merciful, the powerful'

Although there are two groups of NG's in (12) above, that is, Olorun alaanu alagbara (God merciful and powerful) and omo

naa (the child), it is the former that is hereby pertinent.

(13) awon koko oro (those important statements) in

Eni ba mú awon koko oro wá
 who PRE. VB. bring those important word come
 'whoever brought those important statements'

awon	kókó	òrò
those	important	word
Deic.	Epithet	Thing

*E. before Th?
cf. p. 72*

'those important statements'

Figure 2.1.9: 3-Elements NGs

(14) irohin buburu kan bayi
 news bad one this that
 'this one bad news'

irohin	buburu	kan	bayi
news	bad	one	this
Thing	Epithet	Num.	Deic.

'this bad news'

and

(15) oga awon olopa patapata
 chief those police over-all
 'the chief police boss'

oga	awon	olopaa	patapata
chief	those	police	overall
Thing	Deic.	Epithet (1)	Epithet (2)

'the chief police boss'

Figure 2.1.10: 4-Element NGs

(16) Ogbeni Oloni oluko agba naa
 Mr Oloni teacher senior d-d
 'Mr. Oloni the senoir teacher'

ogbeni	Oloni	oluko	agba	naa
Mr.	Oloni	teacher	senior	d-d
Epithet	Thing	Classifier	Epithet	Deictics

'Mr. Oloni the senior teacher'

Mr. Oloni has two Classifiers, each on both sides - ogbeni (Mr.), a class of people, men, and oluko (teacher), a type of profession.

(17) oga olopa patapata orile-ede yi
 chief police overall country this
 'the chief police boss in this country'

oga	olopa	patapata	orile-ede	yi
chief	police	overall	country	this
Thing	Epithet(1)	Epithet (2)	Epithet (3)	Deictic

'the chief police boss in this country'

Figure 2.1.11; 5-Element NGs

18) Wo ile oloke giga fiofio daradara kan
 look house storey high lofty beautiful one
 'look at one beautiful high multi-storey house'

ile	oloke	giga	fiofio	daradara	kan
house	storey	high	lofty	beautiful	one
Thing	Epi. (1)	Epi. (2)	Epi. (3)	Epi. (4)	Num.

'one beautiful high multi-storey house'

Is it both classifier & epithet?

Oloke (storey) is a Classifier - a group of buildings.

For the second 6-Element NG, the following clause will be considered. It is the first sentence and paragraph of a newspaper item⁶, but its NG consists of only the first two lines.

(19)

Gbajumo atamoto eni odun-meedogbon kan,
 socialite vehicle-dealer person year twenty-five one
 'one socialite, vehicle-dealer, twenty-five years old'

Olalekan Adaraloye ti n gbe ona Ife atijo, Ibadan
 Olalekan Adaraloye PERF. PROG. live path Ife old Ibadan
 'Olalekan Adaraloye who lives on the old Ife road, Ibadan'

fojuba ile ejo kekere kan ni Iyaganku, Ibadan
 set-eye-on house court small one PREP. Iyaganku Ibadan
 'appeared in a local court at Iyaganku, Ibadan'

laipe yii lori esun ole jija
 recent this PREP. allege thief SEW
 recently on an alleged theft'

This NG is analysed as follows:

1	2	3	4
Gbajumo	atamoto	[eni odun meedogbon]	kan
socialite	vehicle-dealer	person year	twenty-five one
Epith. (1)	Epithet (2)	Phrase Qualifier	
		Epi. (1) Epi. (2)	Numerative

Thing?
77

cf. number phrase Qualifier eg. (15) p. 74 (16) p. 74 (17) p. 75 (18) p. 75

5	6
O. Adaraloye [ti n gbe ona Ife atijo Ibadan]	
O Adaraloye	PERF. PROG. live path Ife old Ibadan
Thing	Clause Qualifier
	Epi. (1) Epi. (2) Epi. (3) Thing

Apposition?

'socialite, vehicle-dealer, twenty-three year old, Olalekan Adaraloye who lives on the old Ife road, Ibadan'

Figure 2.1.12: 6-Element NGs

The 6-Element NG is the maximal group for the purpose of this analysis because it is deemed sufficient to illustrate an extended NG; it may be extended, in practice, in special situations.

Figure 2.1.7 shows that NG may consist of one item - Thing. Mo (I) is personal pronoun; nwon (they) is pronominal. In Figure 2.1.8, NG consists of two items - Thing plus other elements which may vary depending on usage. The first in this Figure (2.1.2) consists, for example, of Thing + Deictics (Possessive Determiner); and secondly, Thing + Deictics (Demonstrative Determiner). Figure 2.1.9 (12) consists, on the other hand, of Thing + Epithet₁ and Epithet₂; whereas 2.1.9 (13) consists of Deictics (Demonstrative) + Epithet + Thing.

It is apparent from the above Figures 2.1.7 - 2.1.9 that qualifying elements may occur on either side of Thing. The direction in which the elements go may be regressive (associating with the left of Thing) or progressive (associating with the right of Thing). Awon (Figure 2.1.9 [13]) generally appears to be a 'polymorphic' (Awobuluyi 1977:22-23) qualifying element. Bamgbose (1967:11) classifies it as 'a plural pronominal'; Awobuluyi (1978:11-12) refers to it as 'human noun' and Ogunbowale (1970:66) signals its demonstrative potential. In Figure 2.1.9 (13), awon (those), functions as a demonstrative. It seems to direct the reader to look for 'those' important statements in the book. Another possible reason for its being a demonstrative is because the NG may still be qualified by the definite determiner (d-d).

(20) àwon kókó òrò nàá
 Dem. important word d-d
 'those important statements'

The addition of the d-d makes clearly definite a particular group of statements to which the writer refers.

Figure 2.1.10 (14) consists of Thing + Epithet + Numerative + Deictic. But the NG (15) in the same Figure has the pattern Thing + Deictic + Epithet₁ + Epithet₂. Figure 2.1.11 (16) has an Epithet prequalifying Thing and two others postqualifying it before a compound Numerative whereas (17) has three Epithets consecutively postqualifying Thing before the Deictic. cf. p. 71

The 6-Element group in Figure 2.1.12 (18) displays the longest type of NG in this analysis. It depicts to what extent the Thing may have several Qualifiers attached to it but it does not exhaust all the possibilities. The first NG of Figure 2.1.12 is slightly different from the second. The first has all the qualifiers postqualifying the Thing - a position that is the most common in the language. Also all these elements are organised singly without a phrase or a clause. The second item, on the other hand, has a series of qualifiers prequalifying the Thing after which there is a clause. Among the prequalifiers is a phrase - 'eni odun meedogbon' (person twenty-five years old). Both the phrase and the nominal aspect of the clause - 'ona Ife atijo Ibadan' (old Ife road Ibadan) are analysed as embedded nominal groups. ??

Further comments will be made on the second NG in Figure 2.1.12. All the examples analysed above are taken from both spoken and written texts. The second NG in figure 2.1.12. is

taken from a newspaper text⁷ and is different from the earlier patterns. As in this clause, Awobuluyi (1978:94) points out that 'the introducer ti marks sentences that are used as relative clause qualifier.' Similarly, Bamgbose (1967:16) observes that the clause can be part of the Qualifiers of a Thing when it has more than one qualifier. Even though both these scholars give examples to illustrate their points of view, they do not state under which conditions these clauses are built into the NG other than that they provide additional information useful for either the identification or the classification of the Thing. The examples that they give to illustrate patterns of NG occur as shown above (Figures 2.1.5. and 2.1.6.) occur right of the position of Thing.

I shall give, however, a possible interpretation of the organisation of NGs in this way in this Yoruba newspaper. Firstly, it seems to be a stylistic feature of newspaper reporting to give as much detailed information as possible before mentioning the name of the person or thing. This kind of information may be organised in series of Epithets which occur before the Thing in NG. Beyond style, nevertheless, a meaningful interpretation of this pattern of NG in newspaper reporting may be found in the Yoruba people's cultural practice. This aspect of Brown and Gilman's (1960:272) assertion is hereby relevant:

"...interpretations of style must be statements about communities of speakers, statements of national character, social structure, or group ideology."

Paradigms of 'social identification' (Hudson 1987: 581) which concern, in particular, 'achieved status' (Alo 1989: 171-172) in the Nigerian sociolinguistic milieu include, among others, chieftaincy titles (hereditary or acquired), educational attainment, political position, age, kind of profession or career, communal responsibility and wealth.⁸ All of these influence the choice of description used by a journalist using the Yoruba language as a medium of expression for a person of higher status in the community. In this particular NG (i.e. the second clause of Figure 2.1.12), the two prequalifying Epithets - gbajumo (socialite), stamoto (vehicle-dealer) and the phrase eni odun meedogbon (twenty-five year old person) are all important social markers. They seem to mean that the person is well-known to the community through his social responsibility and activity. As a vehicle-dealer at the age of twenty-five he is obviously rich. These achievements are very significant among the Yoruba people. Rather than the speaker using the pronoun of respect for the addressee because of his higher status, a journalist writing in Yoruba may use a series of Epithets to attain the same goal.

The Qualifier element oloke (storey) in the first clause of Figure 2.1.12 needs further study. Although Awobuluyi (1978: 38-40) classifies such items as belonging to the group of Genitival Qualifiers⁹, it seems more appropriate to describe them as Classifiers using Halliday's terminology. Oloke, as Epithet, in terms of its meaning, expresses a sub-class or a sub-group of items. In this case, it indicates a

building that is tall among other buildings. By forming a distinct sub-class or sub-group among the other buildings, it conjures a different structure in the reader's mind from just being big or small. Ogbeni (Mr) in Figure 2.1.11. is also a Classifier. Oloni belongs to a class of 'males' rather than 'females'. The line between Epithet and Classifier may not be very distinct. One apparently good criterion for identifying Classifiers in English as well as Yoruba is that they are closer to the Thing whenever they introduce its sub-class. Another criterion is that the sub-class into which the Thing is sub-divided can no longer be divided. From the above two examples, a building is either built in storey form or as a bungalow; a person is either male or female.

Another type of Classifier is a class of gender in Yoruba.

For example:

- (21) /ako/ ajá kékeré dúdú dáadáa méta wònyí
 male dog small black beautiful three these
 'these three beautiful small black male dogs'

Expressed Experientially:

/ako/	ajá	kékeré	dúdú	dáadáa	méta	wònyí
Classifier	Thing	Epith. (1)	Epith. (2)	Epith. (3)	Num.	Deic.

or

- (22) /abo/ ibépe náà
 female pawpaw d-d
 'The female pawpaw'

Expressed Experientially;

/abo/	ibépe	náà
Classifier	Thing	Deictic

Figure 2.1.13: - Gender Classifiers

Although Bamgbose (1967: 2), Ogunbodede (1970: 38), and Abiri (1985: 37) deny any basis to the claim that there is grammatical gender distinction in Yoruba, it may be suggested that grammatical gender is expressed lexically to show the distinction between the sexes in humans, animals and plants.

This group of Classifiers, like all Classifiers, function to narrow down the conceptual range or meanings of the Thing they modify.

More importantly, these experiential elements show variation in use. The Epithet subset, for example, consists of adjectives that function to show the objective properties of the Thing. A few of these are: dúú (black), kúkurú (short), àgbà (old). The other subset includes dára (good/beautiful), búburú (bad/evil), l'ágbára (powerful). ??

ni 'have'
agbà
strength

These latter examples express the speaker's subjective attitude, and are far less objective descriptions of the Thing if compared, for example, to the former subset in which a consensus might be reached regarding the expressed quality of the Thing. Both of these subsets are experiential in function, but the latter subset also simultaneously expresses some interpersonal function. A discussion of this aspect of the Epithets will be discussed in the next section.

Following the description above of the NG in the language, a more comprehensive and general pattern than the ones set up by Bamgbose and Awobuluyi may be given. This pattern, generally, should be able to account for all expressions of the NG in the language. All the qualifying elements are

optional except the Thing.

(Epithet) + (Classifier)¹⁰ + (Deictic) + (Numerative) + Thing
-----Prequalifiers-----Head
(Classifier)+(Epithet) + (Numerative) + (Clause) + (Deictic)
-----Postqualifiers-----

Figure 2.1.14 - An Extended Nominal Group in Yoruba

It is obvious that not all of these elements of the NG could occur together at once; the following are some of the constraints on the extended pattern:

(i) Two Deictics only qualify Thing on either side: àwon (those) can only be a prequalifier and náà (the) a postqualifier.

(ii) Clauses occur only postqualification.

(iii) Except if other elements of the group occur in compound forms, only the Epithets may occur in several numbers in principle.

(iv) Functioning basically as an Epithet, only one Classifier occurs in a NG to identify the class of thing.

These constraints will be discussed further in the following section 2.1.2.

2.1.2 - Interpersonal

In the above discussion of the Epithet in the experiential metafunction, mention has already been made of the subset that simultaneously expresses both the experiential and the interpersonal meanings. A brief discussion on this may here be necessary to clarify the distinction. In the following example:

(23) Eja dindin pupa didun pupo

fish	fried	red	delicious	many
Thing	Epithet	Epithet	Epithet	Epithet
Exp.	Exp.	Exp.	Int.	Int.

Figure 2.1.15; - Simultaneous Analysis of Experiential and Interpersonal meanings

These elements are mutually exclusive categories. Dindin (fried) classifies the type of fish - it is neither cooked nor boiled; it is fried. Pupa (red) indicates the nature of the oil used in cooking; this is experiential. Next in the structure is dídùn (delicious) which has to do with taste. This is attitudinal since how or what people feel about or think of a particular taste differs. Púpò (many) describes the quantity (i.e. numerous) which can change at any moment. It is, perhaps, clearly seen that these elements have progressively less identifying potential as we move away from what the Epithets are to the Deictics. The frying identity, for example, seems a more permanent characteristic than its colour, sweetness and quantity, in that order. The fish may lose its sweetness sooner than expected, and the quantity may easily increase or decrease.

The Deictics, that is, the demonstratives and the determiners, also express interpersonal meanings either by reference to some entity in the proximity or by giving a definite signal for the identification of the specific referent (Halliday 1985a: 160-162, 291-294). The demonstrative words, yi (this) - (Figure 2.1.8.) awon (those)

- (Figures 2.1.9 and 2.1.10), bayi¹¹ (this) - (Figure 2.1.10), yen (that) and kan (some, certain) (Figure 2.1.12. [19]) and wonyi (these) - (Figure 2.1.13) either direct the listener's attention to some location, or specify the entity being referred to.

Beyond the two opposite ends of the 'this-ness' and the 'there-ness', that is, yen (that) of the demonstratives,¹² is the location of an entity in the immediate environment. These Deictics express proximity (nearness) (for example, eyi [this]) and non-proximity (farness) (for example, iyen [that]) among interlocutors. Eyi (this) may mean 'near me' or 'near both of us'. Iyen (that) may mean 'farther from me' but 'near to you.' The language possesses a third distinctive item of 'not far from either of us' which is different from the medial position. The word that is used to express such a phenomenon is ààrin (middle). This third sense is therefore expressed by nitòsì, meaning 'not too far from either or both of us' but actually 'near both of us.'

2.1.3. Logical

The idea of logic in SFT does not, by any means, exactly fit the description of conventional or formal logic. Its use relates to the logical-semantic relations as encoded in the structure of the language, and it complements the experiential view of the nominal group. Even though the logical relation is more explicit in the clause, it is also evident in the subcategorisation of the nominal group as its elements shift either to the left or right of Thing in a

linear order. Rather than describe these logical elements as qualifiers (i.e. Experiential analysis above), modifiers (i.e. pre- and post-modifications) are used. Unlike the experiential structure in which the different categories are emphasised, the logical structure emphasises the similarities which run through the modifying elements that precede or follow the Thing. It is also the logical analysis that shows the iterative property of the modifying relation. Perhaps one of the characteristics of the nominal group, and one which may clearly depict its different sequential or orderly arrangement,¹³ but at the same time emphasise the similarities, is iteration or recursion.¹⁴ I shall examine the recursive property in one of the items already examined above in Figure 2.1.13. - ajá kékeré dúdú dárádára méta wònyí - and shall see how each element gives a new information about the Thing:

- (24) ajá
'dog'
- (25) ajá kékeré
dog small
'small dog'
- (26) ajá kékeré dúdú
dog small black
'small black dog'
- (27) ajá kékeré dúdú dárádára
dog small black beautiful
'beautiful small black dog'
- (28) ajá kékeré dúdú dárádára méta
dog small black beautiful three
'three beautiful small black dogs'
- (29) ajá kékeré dúdú dárádára méta wònyí
dog small black beautiful three these
'these three beautiful small black dogs'

The corresponding questions that can realise the above reiterative structures may be set up by using any of Ki ni (what), Bawo (how), Elo (number) and Nibo (where) appropriately:

- For (24) ki ni ohun naa ? (what is the object?)
- (25) ki ni iwon ohun naa? (what is its size?)
- (26) ki ni awo ohun naa? (what is its colour?)
- (27) Bawo ni o se ri? (how does it look?)
- (28) Elo ni ohun naa? (how many are they?)
- (29) Nibo ni ohun naa wa? (where are they?)

Graphically, the structural pattern for these questions is like this:

- (24) Thing
- (25) Thing + Epithet
- (26) Thing + Epithet₁ + Epithet₂
- (27) Thing + Epithet₁ + Epithet₂ + Epithet₃
- (28) Thing + Epithet₁ + Epithet₂ + Epithet₃ + Numeral
- (29) Thing + Epithet₁ + Epithet₂ + Epit.₃ + Num. + Deictic

With aja as Head, we can represent (or subcategorise) its logical-semantic relations as in Figure 2.1.16. below, using the following approximated letters of the Greek alphabet: alpha (α) beta (β), gamma (γ), delta (δ), epsilon (ϵ) and zeta (Σ), etc. All those elements modifying Thing in this particular NG are associated to its right.

aja	kekere	dudu	daradara	meta	wonyi
Head	Postmodifiers				
α	β	γ	δ	ϵ	Σ

'These three beautiful small black dogs'

Figure 2.1.16 - Elements to the Right of Thing

But in Figure 2.1.17. below, all the modifying elements are associated to the left of the Thing:

Gbajumo atamoto eni odun meedogbon kan Olalekan

socialite	veh. -dealer	person	year	twenty-five	one	Olalekan
Premodifiers						Head
∩	Σ	ε	δ	ϣ	β	α

'Socialite, vehicle-dealer, twenty-three year-old Olalekan'

Figure 2.1.17. - Elements to the Left of Thing

Within the logical structure, there may be 'sub-modification' - that is, a kind of sub-division or 'internal bracketing'.

Figure 2.1.18, for example, is a six-element NG with a modifying clause containing its own NG. This clause may be analysed as follows showing its sub-modifying elements:

1	2	3	4	5
ile	oloke	fiofio	daradara	kan
house	storey	lofty	beautiful	one
Head	Postmodifiers			
α	β			Ω

'One beautiful high multi-storey house'

6				
Iti	mo	sese	ko	yenl
PERF	I	PREV.	VB.	ADV. build that
Postmodifier		cont.		
Clause				
δ				
'Process'	'Range'			
	Head	'Process': Material		
	α	β	ϣ	

'that I just built'

Figure 2.1.18 - Submodification

A nominal group ought to have a Head but not always a Thing (Halliday 1985a:173). Although Halliday (op. cit. p.173) also states that 'Epithets and Classifiers do not normally function as Head in English, the Thing is realised in them as substitutes.' It seems that in Yoruba, particularly in elliptical constructions, it is only the definite determiner naa (the) that cannot function as Head. All of the other elements including Classifiers may function as Head. The meanings of these elliptical Heads in SFT are retrievable both in the co-text and in the context of situation. For example, oloke (storey) which is a Classifier will be Head in the NG - as in (30) (ii) below if the question in (30) (i) is asked:

(30) (i) - ile wo ni?
house which is
'which of the houses?'

One of the choices open to the addressee is to give a one-word answer, oloke (storey) as in (ii) below:

(ii) oloke

storey
Head
α

'storey'

Here the head ile is presupposed?

Other examples are:

(31) (i) wonyi (ii) meta wonyi (iii) kekere naa

these
Dem.
Head
α

'these'

three	these
Num.	Dem.
Head	Mod.
α	β

'these three'

small	d-d
Epithet	Det.
Head	Mod.
α	β

'the small/little'

Figure 2.1.19

Demonstrative, Numerative, Epithet as Head in NG

Apart from occurring in elliptical constructions, any of (i) - (iii) above can be exclamatory. In other words, they are meaningful in relation to other segments retrievable in that universe of discourse.

2.1.4 System Network

The following two system networks attempt to describe the nominal group in the language. They capture graphically all the above descriptions of the group.

The following abbreviations are used:

Pers. = Personal, Subj. = Subjective, Obj. = Objective
 Pron. = Pronoun, Inter. = Interrogative, Num. = Numerative
 Sg. = Singular Pl. = Plural

* (1) =

mo (I)	o (you)	o (s/he/it)
a (we)	e (you)	nwon (they)

* (2) =

mi (me)	e (you)	i (s/he/it)
wa (we)	yin (you)	won (them)

Figure 2.1.20. Nominal Group (1) : PRINCIPAL SYSTEMS

Examples of

Prequalifying Deictics

awon (those)
ogbeni (Mr.)
omidan (Miss)
iyaafin (Madam)

Moveable Deictics

gbogbo (all)
opolopo (many)
opo (many)
kan (one)

Postqualifying Deictics

gan an (specifically)
paapaa (especially)
naa (the), soso (single)
pere (only), nikan (alone)
iyen (that), eyi (this)
wonyi (these), ni (that)
bayi (this), kaka (sheer)
wa (ours), mi (my)

open set

Figure 2.1.21.: Nominal Group (2) -Deictics

The two system networks above attempt to describe the nominal group succinctly. These are adapted from Halliday 1976. They are open-ended from the left to the right. Figure 2.1.20 - 'Nominal Group (1): Principal System' attempts to describe the nominal group as a whole. So its entry

condition is the entire nominal group. It describes the Thing which may be either nominal or non-nominal. The nominal may consist of nouns -animate or abstract (Yemi [a name] or ogbón (wisdom) at its head. Otherwise it may be pronouns which may be either personal or possessive. If personal, it may be either subjective or objective. If possessive, it may be either singular or plural. The non-nominal is a nominalisation formed from verbs. Epithet may be either a Classifier or a non-Classifier. Numerative may be numbering or qualitative. The Qualifier consists of phrase and clause. Both examples of a phrase are given below because they not very many in my data:

(31) (i) Dele, [eni odun meedogbon] di olowo
 Dele, person year twenty-five become owner of money
 'Dele, who is twenty-five years old becomes rich'

(ii) [Eni odun meedogbon], Dele di olowo
 person year twenty-five Dele become owner of money
 'Dele, who is twenty-five years old becomes rich'

Appositive
 (15)

'Eni odun meedogbon' in both examples function on both sides of Thing -Dele. The Deictics are fully described in the Figure 2.1.21.

The Deictics may be divided into two major groups - demonstrative and determiner. Being a group system network, the Deictics reflect the choice made either of the two by the speaker to reflect its basic function. The demonstrative may be selective to show marked and non-marked choices. Marked demonstrative, by its function, directs a listener or reader's attention to the Thing. Others which do not particularly show selective choices may generally direct the

listener's or reader's attention to the Thing in terms of proximity. When such a demonstrative does not show proximity, it functions to identify the Thing more specifically as a focus element. For example:

(33) Ade [ni] eni ti a n soro si
Ade that person that we PROG. speak PREP.
'That person we are talking to is Ade.'

Determiners, apart from limiting the meaning of the Thing they qualify, may or may not restrict further its number and specificity. When restricted, the particular element may be further differentiated either as singular or plural. In non-restricted form, what is emphasised, essentially, is the limited (i.e. negative) value of the determiner regarding the Thing.

(34) Meta [perel] ni mo mu
three only that I take
'I took only/just three'

As the network is built up to the right in delicacy, a large number of selections are simultaneously ordered. In the group structure, the delicacy is less complex than the clause structure. Realisations in lexical forms are shown in brackets as the last step in the 'most delicate grammar' (Halliday 1977b:223), or as one of the possible options in the representation of the systems in each unit of the rank scale.

2.1.5 - A General Summary of the Nominal Group in Yoruba

(i) Thing

In the nominal group, the Thing is the Head which may be qualified experientially by a complex organisation of elements. In the logical relations, these elements modify the Head. The Thing may be more than one in embedded clauses as in Figure 2.1.12 above.

Essentially, the qualifying elements are organised progressively to the right of Thing. In some newspaper texts, however, some clauses, introductory ones in particular, are organised retrogressively to the left of Thing (Figure 2.1.12). In the language, except the determiner naa (the), all the other elements of the NG may function as Head.

*relative
in 7-59*

(ii) Deictics

Deictics in the language may be divided into two - demonstrative and determiner. The demonstratives have three expressions 'near me' (eyi-[this]), 'near you' (iyen-[that]) and 'near either or both of us' (nitosi [near]). The last one as in the following example:

- (35) [Nitosi] ile mi ni soobu naa wa
near house POSS. VB. shop d-d exist
'The shop is situated near (to) my house'

*an adjacent 100
of 100
nitosi ile mi
SPA*

As a result of the Thing being modifier on both sides, some Deictics may occur typically ⁱⁿ on either positions with the exception of awon (those) and naa (the). Awon (those) occurs

in a pre-qualifying position to the Thing and naa (the) in a post-qualifying position. It is possible to have, for example, the following:

(36) Awon oluko nse ise kitakita
 those teacher PROG.do work hurriedly
 'Those teachers are working hurriedly'

But it is not possible to have

(37)*Oluko [awon] nse ise kitakita
 teacher those PROG.do work hurriedly
 'teacher those are working hurriedly'

The same situation relates to naa (the); it cannot pre-qualify the Thing although its literal translation will be meaningful in English.

(38) *[naa] oluko nse ise kitakita
 the teacher PROG.do work hurriedly
 'the teacher is/was working hurriedly'

Unlike the Epithet which may have, in principle, an infinite number the Deictic is functionally limited to two in a nominal group although these may occur on either side of the Thing.

(39) Oluko [yen] [náà] buru
 teacher that d-d wicked
 'that particular teacher is wicked'

Not if all the items in 1-92 are deictics !!
o.g. éyèni
niáà
D

Both yen (that) and náà (same/particular) are Deictics.

(iii) Epithet

The Epithet shows some quality of the Thing. Some of these may express the objective characteristic of the Thing and the speaker's attitudes towards it. In principle, there is no limit to the number of Epithets that may be used to qualify

the Thing but in practice it is limited.

What is particularly interesting is the general pattern of the organisation of Epithets. Figures 2.1.12 (1) and (2), 2.1.15 and 2.1.16 may be used as illustrations. It is important to show the difference between the group of Epithets which prequalify the Thing and those which postqualify it. For the prequalifier Epithet the following example from the newspaper¹⁶ will supplement two containing in Figure 2.1.12.

(40)

Arakunrin mekaniki kan ladugbo Adekunle Ibadan Olubayo Alao
male mechanic one PREP. area Adekunle Ibadan Olubayo Alao
'a man, a mechanic who lives at Adekunle Ibadan Olubayo, Alao'

Both nominal groups in (19) and (40) are examples of prequalifying Epithets from the newspaper. The Epithet part of them show the following pattern:

sex/Classifier	(arakunrin [male person])	- 40
social role	(gbajumo [socialite])	- 19
profession	(atamoto [vehicle-dealer])	- 19
	(mekaniki [mechanic])	- 40

and a series of other qualifiers (Deictics, phrase) before the Thing (i.e. names). The pattern shown by the postqualifying Epithets is different from that of the prequalifying considering Figures 2.1.12 (i), 2.1.15 and 2.1.16. It is as follows:

Height/Classifier	(oloke [storey])	- 18
	(dindin [fried])	- 23
size	(kekere [small])	- Figure 2.1.16
colour	(pupa [red])	- 23
	(dudu [black])	- Figure 2.1.16
aesthetics	(didun [delicious])	- 23
	(daradara [beautiful])	- Figure 2.1.16

The Classifier, as part of the Epithet, shows a particular subgroup of the Thing. Oloke (storey) and dindin (fried) as subgroups of building and fish respectively. In the postqualifying pattern it is the objective Epithets that are nearer to the Thing while the attitudinal ones are further from it.

(iv) Numerative

This element shows some numerical feature of the nominal group. It is either expressed as an exact numbering or some quantity. The numbering may take the ordinal or the cardinal patterns. It may be singular or plural. One important feature of its numbering pattern is the duplication of numbers (e.g. ogooqun [twenty-twenty, or in the twenties], ogboogbon [thirty-thirty or in the thirties]).

2.2.1.0 - The Verbal Group (VG)

Of all the Yoruba grammatical components, the verbs and the verbal group have received the most descriptive attention. The verb, presumably, is often regarded as central to the structure of any sentence because it is crucial to its lexical meaning - that is, its meaning as a process.

2.2.1.1 - Previous Analyses of Verbs in Yoruba

Verbs in the Yoruba language, from the time of Crowther in the middle of the 19th century, were described as transitive, intransitive, or both (i.e. neutral) because the grammarians who first described them adopted a universalistic approach and modelled their analyses on the Indo-European languages, particularly the English language (Awobuluyi 1982:226). The next group of grammarians described them as simple, compound and complex verbs, or that they are either strong or weak, by considering the tone system and their various characteristics. This group, in reaction to their predecessors, adopted a particularistic approach to its study by refusing to see any similarity between the language and any other natural languages.

Bamgbose (1967:18^{ff}) classifies the verbs in Yoruba into three main types: preverbs, free verbs, and post-verbs. Preverbs are further divided into four: verbal particles, restricted preverbs, unrestricted preverbs and negators. The verbal particle is n (or m before b) as in his example nlo below:

(1) nwon [n] lo (they are going)

Restricted preverbs generally exclude one another and the verbal particle. Some of his examples are iba (would have), ba (happen) as in

(2) awa [iba] le mo (we would have been able to know)

Unrestricted Preverbs do not exclude one another nor the verbal particle. Some examples are tie (even), saa (just), fi (with). Tie (even) as in (3) below:

(3) omo yen [tie] si wa lode (that child is still outside)

Three negators are identified - ko/o, ki, and ma. Ma as in (4) below:

(4) [Ma] wa (don't come)

Awobuluyi (1982:233 & 244), in a different way considering the types of sentences in which they operate, classifies verbs into nine main categories: adjectivisable, serial construction, splitting, complex, causative, indirect statement, locative, particle-selecting, and reduplicating-nominal-selecting.

Adjectivisable verbs, according to him, may be turned into adjectives often without any modification. Examples are dudu (black) and pe. Dudu (black) as in the following example:

(5) Oko Ade [dudu] (Ade's car is black)

This category may be based on the fact that the statement has no verb and dudu appears to be a substitute.

Serial construction verbs contain at least two verbs - gbe (carry/take) and ta (sell) as in his example below:

(6) Ade gbe e [ta] (Ade sold it out)

Splitting verbs are certain idiomatic phrases which when used with objects split into two. For example baje (to damage) or reje (to cheat). For example:

(7) Ade [ba (agogo naa) je] (Ade damaged the clock/wristwatch)

Whereas if the object agogo (clock) is not used the verb will remain unsplit as in (8) below):

(8) Agogo naa [baje] (the clock got damaged)

Complex verbs refer to relatively fixed combination of verbs and objects. Examples are ranti (to remember) and subu (to fall). Ranti (to remember), for example, is a combination of ran and ti; the latter of which may be associated with ear (ear). For example:

(9) Mo [ranti] owo naa (I remember the money)

Causative verbs are used in situations in which an agent implies some action on the part of another agent. Examples are gbo (to hear) mo (to know). For example:

(10) Mo [gbo] pe Ade ko ile si Eko (I heard that Ade built a house [houses] in Lagos)

Locative verbs require the preposition si (to, at)¹⁸ when location (not motion) is indicated. Examples are ku (to die), duro (to stand up). For example:

(11) Ade ku [sil ibe (Ade died there)

Particle-Selecting verbs, in most cases, optionally occur with the particle ni as in

(12) Ade ya mi [ni] sisi (Ade lent me six pence)

Reduplicating-Nominal-Selecting verbs always occur in sentences containing nominalisations whose initial reduplicative consonants have been optionally dropped. Examples are ko (to learn), and mo (to know) as in

(13) Ade [ko] oko wiwa (Ade learned to drive)

where wiwa (driving) is a nominalised form of wa (drive).

Even though Bamgbose still recognises transitive, intransitive, and neutral verbs, Awobuluyi does not see any need for such a classification. He criticises the issue of transitive and intransitive as 'factually questionable and of comparatively limited practical value.' The tonal classification, he feels, 'belongs more properly in phonology, the level of description at which the spoken form of the language is considered' (1982:233).

There are other divergent views. A class of verbs which Bamgbose calls preverbs (i.e. restricted and unrestricted [saa - just/even; baa - would have/even if]) is termed preverbal adverbs by Awobuluyi (1978:68-69). This same class of verbs is called auxiliary elements by Oke (1982:248), and as formants¹⁷ by Odunuga (1982:269). Odunuga argues that it is wrong to refer to this class of verbs as auxiliaries because they have their own lexical meaning, and can be used

independently. Formants, on the other hand, can only be 'endowed with their grammatical role' (op. cit. p. 269). It is even wrong, according to him, to analyse formants as part of the verbal group since they function only to show tense and aspect in the language.

Tense, nevertheless, is analysed as part of the complex internal organisation of the Yoruba verbal group. Tense in Yoruba, according to Bamgbose, has two major types: simple and perfective (1967: 26-30). The simple tense are subdivided into two - five are positive while four are negative. An example of the positive is the future tense which may be illustrated with a (will) as in (14) below:

(14) Baba a bere (father will ask)

An example of the negative also in the future tense may be illustrated with ko nii (won't) as in

(15) Baba ko nii soro (father won't talk)

The perfective tense is equally divided as the simple tense. Perfective tenses consist, however, of the simple tenses plus the perfective marker - ti (have). An example of the perfective positive tense is

(16) Baba a ti bere (father will have asked)

An example of the perfective negative tense is:

(17) Nwon o tii nii lo (they won't have gone yet)

Awobuluyi recognises the future and the non-future

(1982: 241). Of future, Welmers (1973: 353) argues for two future constructions, both of which are used by many speakers of the language but without any semantic distinction. Awobuluyi argues that the tense is basic because every Yoruba sentence carries an indication of it but that many sentences occur without any indication of aspect. Odunuga, on the other hand, expresses the idea that aspect, the completion or non-completion of an action, is perhaps more important than the actual time.

It is in the midst of the above claims and counter-claims that an application of the SFT to the analysis of the VG seems to stand a better chance of providing a far more systematic, terminologically less cumbersome approach than hitherto. Firstly, Awobuluyi's criteria of classifying verbs as items which predicate a sentence between its subject and object as well as by considering the major basic sentence do not clearly account for the basis of classifying dudu (black) (as in clause 5 above) as a verb even though he asserts that they can be turned into adjectives and by giving prominence to them considering the type of construction in which they occur. Some of Awobuluyi's examples are overlapping. Mo (to know), for example, occurs both in Indirect Statement and Reduplicated-Nominal-Selecting verbs without any explanation.¹⁸ Bamgbose's description of the verbal group as free, preverbs and postverbs based on their organisation in the clause does not seem to take adequate account of both their semantic and grammatical implications. Both these descriptions may be improved by describing them in their

experiential and logical relations.

I shall, first of all, attempt a classification of the verbs in the verbal group in SFT's terms and shall then examine some clauses in Yoruba to see how the VG is organised. Its general organisation in the clauses will then be discussed according to its experiential and logical patterns.

2.2.1.2 - The Concept of Transitivity in SFT

SFT views transitivity, a component of the ideational metafunction, as a property of clauses; it is used to specify the different types of processes in clauses. Since a full description of transitivity is complex, it would do injustice to the concepts to condense them thereby creating the risk of oversimplification. Detailed accounts of its description are found in Halliday 1976:159-173, and 1985a:101-157. In what follows, I shall present a definition of each critical term.¹⁹

Evoking the concept of Transitivity, Halliday identifies three main and three minor types of processes in the English clause (Halliday 1976:161). The main ones are material, mental, and relational (Halliday 1985a:102-128). The minor ones are behavioural, verbal and existential (Halliday 1985a:128-144).²⁰ Briefly explained, material processes concern 'doing', by expressing the idea that one thing 'does' something to oneself or to another person or thing. Essentially, such a process would have an obligatory participant as Actor while the goal may or may not be

present. When the process does not express 'doing' it expresses 'happening' or 'bringing about.'²¹ Examples are clauses containing 'catch,' 'fall,' and 'resign.' Mental processes are different from material process. They express feeling, thinking and seeing, thereby involving, potentially, both a Senser (always a human being in normal usage) and the Phenomenon sensed. What is sensed, thought or perceived is not restricted in English, for example, to any particular semantic or grammatical category. It may be either a 'thing' or 'a fact.' Like material process, however, mental process affects the participants who usually, for example, 'believe,' 'realise,' and 'see.' Relational processes are those of being. That is, the clauses in which they function express the meaning that something is. This expression functions in two modes: 'attributive' and 'identifying.' The attributive mode, which is realised in English in most cases as a nominal group, contains an attribute which is assigned to a 'Carrier.' In the identifying mode, an item expresses a meaning which helps to define the identity of another. This item either specifies its form or function. In most cases, the two elements in focus are the same but are seen from different perspectives. Verbs of relation are 'be,' 'become,' and 'define.'

As for the minor ones, behavioural processes involve physiological and psychological behavioural patterns like breathing, sighing, dreaming, weeping, smiling, and coughing. Grammatically in English, behavioural processes may be grouped to function in an intermediate position

between material and mental processes. Like the Senser in the mental process, the Behaver is typically a conscious being. Like the Actor in the material process, the Process functions more like that of 'doing.' Examples which may function in clauses are 'smile,' 'laugh,' and 'cry.' Verbal²² process involves 'saying' thereby attracting a human 'sayer', again in normal usages. Even then, 'saying,' is interpreted in a broad sense to cover any kind of symbolic exchange of meaning which does not involve a human sayer such as notices, different kinds of signals, sign, wristwatches and clocks. So, unlike mental processes, verbal processes do not, of necessity, involve a conscious participant. Two participants (human or non-human) function regularly in a verbal process. The one to whom the Sayer addresses is referred to as the Receiver and the verbalisation as Verbiage. Examples are 'praise,' 'insult,' and 'flatter.' The last minor process is existential which involves the notion that somebody exists or something happens. In English, existential clauses typically contain the verb 'be' or some other verb expressing 'existence' and is followed by a nominal group functioning as Existent. the Existent may be a Phenomenon or an Event. Most frequently, the existential clause contains a circumstantial element. Examples are 'was,' 'exist,' and 'arise.'

2.2.1.3 - Description of Processes in Yoruba

In the same manner as the terms pertaining to the concept of transitivity in English have been briefly defined (section

2.2.1.2), so will its application to the description of the verbs in Yoruba. One interesting aspect of this approach to the description is that the concept of transitivity itself in this linguistic theory is an extension of the concept of the transitive and the intransitive. As earlier pointed out (section 2.2.1.1), the VG in the language has been investigated mainly from the transitive and intransitive perspectives. One reason accountable for this seemingly attractive approach is that the language has, generally, the structural typological classification of the SVO. This brief description, therefore, attracts two of the three aspects into which processes are grouped: the process and the participants.²³ According to Halliday, grammatically, the participants 'are the elements that typically relate directly to the verb' (1985a:131). Main verbs, obviously, have meanings by themselves because they function, generally, either as 'doings' or 'happenings' (Halliday 1985a:100^{ff}, Halliday and Hasan 1976:33). That is, these main verbs 'are perfectly intelligible on their own' (Halliday 1977b:188) although the participants 'inherently associated' with them are needed for coherent interpretations.

Although Halliday describes these categories of processes as they function in the English language, it seems to me that they have bases in all human societies. There may be borderline cases, and perhaps other categories which are yet to be described, all human beings have to use language to 'do,' 'think,' 'relate,' 'bahave,' 'say,' and 'be.'

2.2.1.3.1 - Material Process

For a brief discussion of this type of process the following text 2.2.1 will be examined:

Text 2.2.1 ²⁴

1. Nigbati nwon ba [mu] omobirin de enu ona
when they PRE. VB. bring girl PREP. mouth door
'when they have brought a girl (i.e. a bride) to the door'
2. ile oko rè, nwon yio [san] ésè fun u
house groom her they PRE. VB. wash leg PREP. her
'of her bridegroom, they will wash her feet'
3. ninu omi yi, nwon yio [da] oti die si i
PREP. water this they PRE. VB. pour wine little PREP. it
'in this water to which some wine has been added'
4. nwon yio si [fi] egba mejilelogun ²⁵ sinu omi na
they PRE. VB. have put 20,000 twenty-two PREP. water d-d
'they would have put nine naira ²⁶ into the water'
5. bi oko iyawo kò ba [ni] ju egba mokaṅla lo
if groom bride NEG. PRE. VB. have more 20,000 eleven more
'if the bridegroom doesn't have more than five naira fifty'
6. o le [fi] sibe
he PRE. VB. put there
'he can put it there'

In the text, mu (bring) -(1), san (wash) -(2), da (pour) - (3), fi (put) - (4) and (6) all have subjects as first participants; ni (have) belongs to a different group. Indeed all of these processes except fi (put) -(6) share the same pronominal nwon (they) as subject. Fi (put) -(6) has the third person pronominal o (he) referring to oko iyawo (husband/bridegroom) in clause 5 as its participant. These material processes require human participants. The complements to which the 'acts of doing' refer in the two clauses are, however, different: In clause (1), for example, the object of the complement still remains 'plus human,'

while that of (2) is a thing - a part of the human body. The process fi (put) in clause (6) has no second participant but a locative element. The grammatical function of these processes in relation to their participants may be examined. I may probe the meaning of the material process mu (bring) in clause (1) by asking the question: ki ni nwon se si omobirin naa? ('what did they do to the girl/bride?') This question looks at the meaning of the process from the viewpoint of the first participant. From the perspective of the second participant a similar probe question may be asked: ki ni o sele si omobirin naa? ('what happened to the girl/bride?'). The second question is not applicable to clause (6) because it does not have a second participant. These processes are therefore systemic options through which some kinds of realities are expressed by considering, in particular, in relation to the grammatical subjects and objects (the latter may not be present). That is, the function of each participant can therefore be interpreted or distinguished by its 'doing' or 'done to.' Following Halliday's description of English, I shall refer to this group of verbs as Material Process because they express the notion that some entity 'does' something, in most cases, to another entity.

2.2.1.3.2 - Mental Process

The verbs expressing material process relate mostly to concrete participants because they involve 'doing' and 'happening.' Verbs expressing mental process, on the other hand, relate to abstract meanings of feeling, thinking and perceiving. In the following clauses:

(18) A [gbagbo] pe orisa yi ni agbara
we believe that divinity this has power
'we believe that this divinity is powerful'

(19) Mo [ro] pe Adetokunbo wa si ipade naa
I think that Adetokunbo come PREP. meeting d-d
'I think that Adetokunbo came to the meeting'

the first participants of the processes gbagbo (believe) - (18) and ro (think) -(19) possess 'consciousness' or have the feature 'plus human.' In grammatical terms, these participants may be referred to as first person plural (a [we] and first person singular (mo [I]) pronouns respectively. The abstract properties of thought, perception, or some kind of consciousness generally require at least one human participant or animate subject. It is the human being who possesses the attribute of 'sensing'; and what is commonly 'sensed' are facts. Facts are abstract things which may be sensed, felt, or thought of but nothing can be done to them physically. In special registers however, like poetry or all forms of metaphor, non-human (animate or inanimate) objects are made to possess human characteristics. When they function this way, they are made to exhibit human characteristics.

The other participant in a clause of mental process (whenever there is a second participant) is not restricted to any particular semantic or grammatical category. Orisa (divinity) in clause (18) above, for example, is an abstraction which further strengthens the abstractness in the clause containing mental process whereas Adetokunbo who is the second participant in (19) has the feature 'plus human.' In a clause of mental process, the first participant is

described as the 'Senser' because it possesses consciousness and the attribute of feeling, thinking and seeing. What is 'sensed' that is felt, thought or seen is described as the Phenomenon. Following Halliday's description of English, I shall refer to this group of verbs as Mental Process.

2.2.1.3.3 - Relational Process

In semantic terms, the verbs of relational process express 'the state of being' of someone or thing. The main focus of the meaning of these verbs is that something is. That, of course, is one way of expressing relationship or the characteristic of some entity in the language.

In the following clauses:

(20) Oloye MKO Abiola [je] Bashorun Ibadan
chief MKO Abiola become Bashorun Ibadan
'Chief MKO Abiola became Bashorun, Ibadan'

(21) Sonponna [ni] eni ti o [ni] aiye
smallpox [god] is person that who has earth
'the smallpox god is the owner of the earth'

In English, this process is divided into two modes - the attribute and the identifying. These, to a large extent, are applicable to Yoruba. In attributive mode, a particular attribute is ascribed to some entity either as a quality or as a circumstance in relation to time, place, and possession.

Je (become) in clause (20) above may be described as an attribute type of relational verb. 'Bashorun' is one of the major chieftaincy titles awarded to highly distinguished sons of Ibadan (the largest city in West Africa). That attribute

is ascribed to Chief MKO Abiola which means that Abiola is recognised as the chieftaincy title-holder. As a result of 'becoming' the holder of the title, he is expected to carry out the duties associated with that office. In the structural analysis of such a relational process, these two phenomenon are described as ATTRIBUTE (attribute) and CARRIER (the entity carrying the attribute).

The first ni (is) in clause (21) above is an example of identifying relational verb. Sonponna belongs to the pantheon of the divinities in the Yoruba religious culture and is in some sense associated with smallpox. Sonponna is identified by the use of ni (is). The second ni (has) unlike the first indicates 'possession.' The word ni, in particular, as indicated in the first chapter functions in several contexts in the grammar of the language. In this clause, the relationship between 'Sonponna' and 'earth' is that of 'ownership' and 'possession.' The structural function the becomes IDENTIFIED and IDENTIFIER.

Two main grammatical differences between the attributive and the identifying relational process may be given. Firstly, the relational property of these processes may be expressed thus: a defines the identity of b where a and b are two distinct entities [IDENTIFIER], or where a and b are the same entity [ATTRIBUTIVE]. Secondly, and an interesting characteristic of some of the relational process - the participants in the identifying relation are reversible [below is the reverse form of clause (21) above].

- (22) Eni ti o ni aiye ni Sonponna
 person that he has earth is Sonponna
 'Sonponna is the owner of the earth'

The attributive clause in (20), on the other hand, is irreversible because it is, though grammatical, meaningless.

- (23) *Bashorun Ibadan [je] Oloye MKO Abiola
 Bashorun Ibadan become chief MKO Abiola
 *'Bashorun, Ibadan becomes chief MKO Abiola'

Bashorun (the chieftaincy title) cannot 'become' chief Abiola. The plausible explanation for this irreversibility in the above structure (23) is that relational process je is merely identifying the role taking up by Chief MKO Abiola rather than actually defining. But ni (is) is identifying Sonponna in relation to 'his possession of the earth.' Following Halliday's description of English, I shall refer to this group of verbs as Relational Process.

2.2.1.3.4 - Existential Process

The verbs functioning as process in this category depict that something 'exists,' 'happens' or 'causes.' These verbs are therefore closely related to relational process because the verb ni may also function in this group. The following clauses are examples:

- (24) Aafin Olubadan [wa] l'oja
 palace Olubadan is PREP. market
 'Olubadan's palace is at the market'

- (25) Orisa yi [ni] o nda arun si aiye
 divinity this is he PROG. spread disease PREP. earth
 'this divinity spreads diseases into the earth'

Unlike in English where 'there' as in 'there is/was x' has no representational function but is used to serve the need for a subject in the clause, an existential clause in the Yoruba language has a nominal group containing a participant [Existent] (Halliday 1985a:130) followed by the existential verb and a circumstantial element. In clause (24) above, wa means 'exist' and is spatial. It refers to a particular place located at the market place - the palace. In the language, wa (exist) is commonly used as the historic past in story-telling - 'ni igbakan/ni igba laelae, ilu kan [wa]...' (once upon a time, there [was] a town...).

Ni (is) in clause (25) means 'cause' or 'causes.' It functions in the clause to depict the Orisa (divinity) as bringing, or the cause of diseases on earth. Following Halliday's description of English, I shall refer to this group of verbs as Existential Processes.

2.2.1.3.5 - Verbal Process

Verbs functioning in this process involve some acts of 'saying' or pronouncement whereby 'saying' is interpreted in a broad sense to cover a range of phenomena concerning symbolic exchange of meaning. The verbs functioning in a verbal process function in intermediate positions between material and mental processes. Like material process they concern 'doing;' unlike mental process they do not directly concern any phenomena but the expression of facts which shows some acts of 'doing'. Like mental process which may be associated with a concrete act from one participant to

another (human or non-human) a process of 'saying' involves a human participant or Sayer except when interpreted in a rather broad sense to include the 'meanings' conveyed by notices on boards, watches and clocks (for time) - Halliday 1985a:129). At that instance, no conscious participant will be required. The Sayer refers to anything that produces some signal. The following examples will be used to illustrate this further:

(26) Oluko wa [so] fun wa pe o soro pupo
 teacher our tell PREP. us that it difficult very
 'our teacher told us that it is very difficult'

(27) Odaran naa [tesiwaju] ninu oro re
 accused d-d continue PREP. word his
 'the accused continued his statement'

In clause (26), oluko (teacher) is the Sayer and so is the verbal element or Process. Wa (us), supposedly referring to pupils/students are the Receiver of the message functionally referred to as the Verbiage.

Tesiwaju (continues) in clause (27) is a process. It may occur as a material process in other clauses to suggest motion - referring to someone continuing to walk. In either case, this process does not change in spelling and pronunciation. In grammatical terms, the two may be differentiated by the kind of participants functioning in predication. Also as a process of motion, it attracts participants such as irin (walk), aajo (journey), irinkerindo (all-round trip). For example in clause (28) below:

(28) O [tesiwaju] irin re
 s/he continues walking his/her
 's/he continued his/her walk'

As an element of verbalisation, it attracts participants such as oro (word/statement) [as in clause 27 above], ejo (report), aroye (complaints). The context of clause (27) is indicative of this grammatical interpretation because the clause is taken from the newspaper report of a court case. It functions to describe a scene in court when a speaker (in this instance the accused) has to stop talking for a while and 'continues' to talk again.

Regarding the category of verbal process in English, Hudson (1987: 496-497) comments:

'The name is perhaps less than ideal as it is intended to cover "any kind of symbolic exchange of meaning"... Perhaps "communication" would have been a more helpful name, to make it clear that at least some of the processes in question are not "verbal" except by metaphor.'

Hudson suggests 'communication' for the category of verbal process because its participant roles are associated with the functional categories of 'Sayer,' 'Target,' and 'Verbiage' which he regards as special cases of 'Range.' The term 'communication,' according to him, has the characteristics of these functional 'range' categories. It may be true that the term 'verbal process' is less than ideal for the description of such a wide range of verbal process, yet Hudson's choice of 'communication' as an alternative appears rather a far broader and inappropriate term than 'verbal' because it is already being used for a range of linguistic and non-linguistic phenomena.

2.2.1.3.6 - Behavioural Process

Verbs functioning in English as behavioural process concern physiological and ego-centric behaviour like breathing, coughing and so on. Grammatically, they operate between material and mental processes. These 'behaviours' are more like 'doing,' and the Behaver is typically a conscious being whether human or non-human. Some of these 'behaviours' differ though from human and non-human Behavers. For example, a human being may laugh but one is not so sure whether goats laugh or giggle. The following clauses may be used to illustrate this further:

(29) Orisa ti a [mberu] ni ile Yoruba ni Sonponna
divinity that we PROG.fear PREP.land Yoruba is smallpox
'The divinity we fear in Yoruba land is Sonponna'

(30) Ma [mi] si mi l'enu mo
NEG. breathe PREP. me PREP.mouth anymore
'dont breathe into my mouth anymore'

Mberu (fearing), in clause (29) above expresses a psychological behaviour. Sonponna is one of the divinities that is much feared in Yoruba land. While the act of fear is not always visibly manifested (that is, it is mostly mental) the behavioural state of the Behaver (one who in this instance believes in the power of the divinity) always demonstrates this inward psychological state such that it is externally realised.

Mi (breathe) as a verb of behavioural process in clause (30) above expresses, on the other hand, a physiological behaviour. Functioning in an imperative clause it is, supposedly, used by a human being to address another person

to stop the behavioural act, although other living but non-human things also 'breathe.'

Although both clauses (29) and (30) possess two participants; hence they share some of the characteristics of material process, it is not uncommon to find numerous examples which are grammatically indistinguishable from intransitive material process. Some examples are as follows:

(31) O rerin
s/he laugh
's/he laughed'

(32) O wu'ko lemolemo
s/he cough successively
's/he coughed successively'

The classification above appears to show that only one main process functions between the participants in the language. A verbal group may consist of more than one process. This is often referred to as Serial Verb Constructions (SVCs) (Baker 1989: 513; Pulleyblank 1987b: 988). Such clauses are numerous in the language. This is a major aspect whereby Yoruba and other Kwa languages of West Africa (as set out in Chapter One) differ from, say, the English language. SVCs are, however, prevalent in the Caribbean Creoles (Baker 1989: 513), New Guinean languages (Foley and Olson 1985), East Asian languages such as Thai and some Central American languages (Craig and Hale 1988).

Each of the following clauses (33) and (34)

(33) N o jeki Olanlokun [ri] oro [sol si mi rara
I NEG. allow Olanlokun see word speak PREP. me at all
'I did not allow Olanlokun to rebuke me at all'

(34) Gbogbo aso naa ni Olusola [ko] [lo]
all clothes d-d is Olusola carry go
'Olusola carried all the clothes away'

contains two serial processes. Clause (33) contains ri ([see] mental process) and so ([speak] verbal process). Clause (34) contains ko ([carry] material process) and lo ([go] material process). The SVCs exhibit a number of interesting grammatical properties. This serial process may occur with [clause 33] or without [clause 34] any word or phrase between them, and definitely without any intervening conjunction or subordinator. There is usually one tense/aspect specification for the whole group of verbs; they would also share a single [34] or double participants [33].

This means that in (33) ri (see) and so (speak) both function with Olanlokun as their participant. In a similar way, ko (carry) and lo (go) both function with Olusola as participant. In (33) both processes possess different grammatical meanings (i.e. mental and verbal), while ko (carry) and lo (go) have, generally, the same grammatical meanings (i.e. material). In addition to these meanings, lo (go) indicates the 'direction' in which the meaning of the first process - ko (carry) functions or took place.

2.2.1.4 - Auxiliary Verbs (AV)

Having classified the processes in the language according to their meaning and function, the other constituents of the group need to be considered since the structure of the verbal group is the expansion of the verb (Halliday 1985a:175).

This means that there are other elements which may occupy the position between the subject and the verb in some grammatical structures.

In this analysis, those elements which function along with the verbs will be described neither as formant (Odunuga 1982:267-274) nor preverbs (Bamgbose 1967:18) because these descriptions tend to lay undue emphasis merely on their grammatical relevance. I will prefer to refer to them as optional Auxiliaries (Halliday 1985a:175; Butt et al. 1989:44; Adewole 1989:1; Oke 1982:248)²⁷ because even though these are often present in the VG they occur optionally. Furthermore, even though they have their own lexical meaning, they are organised to provide support for the main verbal element in the clause. Odunuga (1982:268) states that these elements which occur between the subject and the verb express tense, aspect and tense-aspect. The term preverbs as Bamgbose refers to it is, however, preferred in order to emphasise the fact that these elements which constitute the verbal group, other than the main verbs, particularly those elements commonly referred to as the auxiliaries, do have their lexical meanings (Odunuga op. cit. p. 269). This position can be demonstrated when we consider that most of these preverbs could be used independently as main verbs in certain clauses. In this position, one important grammatical element in this position that Odunuga clearly omits is the negation element. Verbal group negation in Yoruba, according to Oke, (1982:247) is effected through the operation of certain negator elements in the verbal group.

SFT's analysis of the optional auxiliary in English emphasise the Finite in experiential structure; tense and aspect are emphasised in the logical structure (Halliday 1985a:176, 1976:136^{ff}). Tense is further divided into primary and secondary. The concepts of finiteness, primary and secondary tenses, modality and any attitudinal meaning in the auxiliary verbs express interpersonal meaning.

As illuminating as the above concepts may be in this analysis, it is doubtful if the concept of finiteness is appropriate to the description of auxiliary verbs in Yoruba. If in English, finiteness is shown in an auxiliary item to show relationship which occurs between the participant (i.e. Person) in terms of number and tense or modality, there is no clear-cut auxiliary item which performs exactly the same function in Yoruba. This is because word order in Yoruba is configurational rather than inflectional.²⁸ This means, in particular, that morphological case marking is absent in the language (Pulleyblank 1987b:982). It may be difficult also to divide the tenses into primary and secondary as Halliday does for English because the grammatical elements which occur between the subject and the verb in the language express tense, aspect and tense-aspect (Odunuga 1982:268).

The textual meaning which is inherent in the ordering of the elements will then be emphasised. Moreover, these elements will be labelled in terms of their grammatical features (e.g. tense, polarity etc.) because they fully represent their meaning (Halliday 1985a:176).

Before considering the auxiliary verbs in Yoruba, the pattern set up by Bamgbose (1966:74) may be summarised briefly (Adewole 1989:12-14).

I	II	III	IV
Negators	yoo (will)	gbodo (must)	All the others

Figure 2.2.1 - Pattern of Auxiliary Verbs in Yoruba

Column IV (all the others) above is nearest to the lexical verb or process. Adewole's (1989:13) criticises Bamgbose because he did not discuss the variants comprising I and II of the above pattern in his 1966 publication (pp. 69-73). Apart from Bamgbose's observation that the auxiliary verb ma (not) in column I cannot co-occur with yoo (will) in column II, the negators kò (not) and ki (not) also cannot occur in column I whenever yoo (will) functions in column II.

In the following paragraphs, I shall examine the auxiliaries in Yoruba and, in particular, the order of their constituents. I shall begin however with a lexical verb as in (35) below:

(35) mo [rí okò ayókélé re
 I see/saw vehicle pleasurable your
 'I see/saw your car'

it is difficult to know or say definitely the actual time the verb rí (see/saw) refers to; that is, the past or present. In the language, the present verb is not overtly marked or inflected, except by the addition of certain words - (e.g. nísisiyí (now) or lówólówó (at the moment of speech/now).

But if we have

- (36) mo rí okò ayókélé re [lànà]
I see/saw vehicle pleasurable your yesterday
'I saw your car yesterday'

there is an indication, by the addition of the lexical word lànà (yesterday), that the action is past. On the other hand, if we have

- (37) mo [ti] rí okò ayókélé re
I PERF. seen vehicle pleasurable your
'I have seen your car'

the auxiliary verb ti expresses an action in the past, or completed without the lexical word lànà. Ti (occurring before rí) expresses the perfective aspect 'up to present time'. The AV yíò (will/shall) indicates a future action.

Other AVs that can be used for the future expression in the language are: á, máa, as in

- (38) Adebisi [á] lo sí oko
Adebisi FUT. go PREP. farm
'Adebisi will go to the farm' or

- (39) Adebisi [máa] lo sí oko
Adebisi FUT. go PREP. farm
'Adebisi will go to the farm'

- (40) Adebisi [á máa] lo sí ilé iwé
Adebisi FUT. HAB. go PREP. house book
'Adebisi will be going to the School'

- (41) Adebisi [yíò máa] lo sí ilé iwé
Adebisi FUT. HAB. go PREP. house book
'Adebisi will be going to the school'

The above AVs (40 and 41) which express futurity occur in free variation because when they occur in any structure the second (usually máa [will]) will change to Habitual auxiliary.

Nri introduces another dimension to the AVs. The verbal particle n (its other variant is m, both nasalised) shows an action taking place at the moment of speech or a generalised action in time. Generalised actions are common with some behavioural processes (e.g. habitual activities) such as jeun (eating), or wè (bathing) etc. These particles n/m and the auxiliaries á/máa indicate continuous (incomplete) actions.

In certain contexts, these auxiliaries may join together in the same clause to express altogether different meanings. It is the combinations of these auxiliaries which Odunuga (1982:268-273) describes as tense-aspectal forms of the language. He suggests that these AVs either form 'a double or a triple component formation.' For example:

(42) èmi [yíò ti] rí okò ayókélé re
 I FUT. PERF. see vehicle pleasurable your
 'I would have seen your car'

(43) èmi [ti n] rí okò ayókélé re
 I PERF. PROG. see vehicle pleasurable your
 'I have been seeing your car'

Examples (42) and (43) above possess the double-component formation. As for (42), another variant of yíò ti (FUT.+PERF.) is á ti with exactly the same meaning. In both clauses tense-aspect forms are expressed; (42) is past perfective and (43) progressive perfective.

But

(44) èmi [yíò ti máa] rí okò ayókélé re
 I FUT. PERF. HAB. see vehicle pleasurable your
 'I would have been seeing your car'

shows the triple-component formation. In it there are the expressions of past, perfective and habitual tense-aspect forms.

The expression of possibility or certainty (i.e. modality) in the above paragraphs leads to the description of what Awobuluyi (1978:68-70) defines as the 'preverbal adverbs' - adverbs which occur before the verbs. He describes the adverbs that occur after the verbs as 'postverbal adverbs.' He then proceeds by identifying five major preverbal adverbs: negators, the past and future markers, modality and those that function as modification. This grouping is rather too gross and apparently unsystematic. Negation and modality, for example, express two different kinds of meanings, and it is very doubtful if negators can be described as adverbs in the language. I shall, first of all, describe these verbs which indicate modality as 'auxiliary adverbs' and then describe negation:

condition - ibá, bá as in

- (45) bí o /bá/ gbé oṣí náà wá
if you AUX. ADV. bring wine d-d come
'should you bring the wine'

potentiality - lè, to as in

- (46) ó /lè/ di èniyàn nlá
3Sg. AUX. ADV. become person big
'he may become an important person'

obligation - gbódò, nílatí as in

- (47) ó [gbódò] sáré
3sg. AUX. ADV. run
'he must run'

Of the 'auxiliary adverbs' I shall separate a group to be referred to as 'auxiliary adverbials,' using the criterion

that these auxiliaries can either modify a verb or function as verbs themselves in elliptical clauses (e.g. conversational contexts). This group, for example, consists of the following:

- (48) mo [tètè/yára] lo === [mo tètè] (elliptical form)
 I quickly go
 'I quickly went'
- (49) ó [gbódò] so === [ó gbódò] (elliptical form)
 3sg. must speak
 'he must say' (i.e. something)
- (50) jòwó [rora] lo === [jowo rora] (elliptical form)
 please carefully go
 'please go carefully'

As observed, one important but often neglected part of the AVs in the language is negation, particularly with regard to the different shades of meaning which are expressible in the grammatical structures in which some aspects of the negation function. Kò, a type of negation, occurs before all verbal elements except the existential process wà (be, exist) and the material process ní (have), except in special or euphemistic constructions like

- (51) oba náà [kò] wà
 king d-d NEG. exist
 'the king has passed away'

The negation kò may also precede all auxiliary elements except bá, á, yóò, má, and ní. But in questions like

- (52) [Kò] a tán bí?
 NEG. it finish INT.
 'isn't it finished?'

it functions in the interrogative. It does not however function in the imperative clauses as it does in the

interrogative. For example,

- (53) ***[Kò]** wá ní' bí
NEG. come here
* 'not come here'

rather, a similar construction for the imperative would be

- (54) **[Wá** ní' bí)
come PREP. here
'come here!'

Negative?

Kò has two other forms: **kì**, and **kó**. **Kì** occurs only before **yóò bá**, and **n**, but **kò** follows the subject or **béè** (so) in clauses:

- (55) omo náà **[kì** bá] sáré
child d-d NEG. (AUX. VB.) run
'the child should not have run'
- (56) omo náà **[kò** n] pariwo (e.g. in the classroom)
child d-d NEG. PROG. noise
'the child does not make a noise'
- (57) òun kó lo je oúnje náà
3sg. NEG (SEW) eat food d-d
'he was not the one who ate the food'

kò occurs only in formal contexts. It is very different from kó/kí which are common.

It, that is **kò**, is often realised as /i/, or even as /o/:

- (58) a **[i]** jáde lí òru
we NEG. go out PREP. night
'we don't go out at night'
- (59) a **[ò]** wá nígbàná
we NEG. come then
'we did not come then'

ki? < - kó / kí / kí

In some instances, both **kò** and **kí** may occur in sequence in a sentence:

- (60) **[kò]** **kí** bébè
NEG. NEG. plead
's/he does not plead'
- (61) òun **[kó]** ní
3sg NEG. FOC.
'he is not' (i.e. the one)

kó kó kó

The other negator in the verbal group is má which occurs mainly in the imperative. When it does occur in non-imperative clauses, it is often preceded by another auxiliary- bá (e.g. an auxiliary adverb) - to form a double negative.

- (62) [má] rérin (imperative)
 NEG. smile
 'do not smile'

The co-occurring negators, interestingly, express different shades of meanings. For example:

- (63) [kò] [kì] sáré rará
 NEG. NEG. run at all
 's/he does not run at all'

- (64) kò bá má sáré rará
 NEG. even NEG. run at all
 's/he may not run at all'

In (63), although we have two negatives in sequence, kò and kì, the clause does not by any means have a double negative meaning. Even in (64), where the negatives are not in sequence, there is no double negative effect in the meaning they convey in the sentence. That is, they do not have meanings any different from (65) with just one negator:

- (65) [kì] sáré rará
 NEG. run at all
 's/he does not run at all'

Any change in the structural organisation, however, will only result in ungrammatical or functionless structures:

- (66) *[kì] [kò] sare rara
 NEG NEG run at all
 'not not run at all'

- (67) *[ko] sare [ki] rara
 NEG run NEG at all
 'not run not at all'

But if we have

- (68) [kò] sàré
 NEG. run
 'he didn't run'

then the meaning of the clause is changed from a habitual action to a single event that took place on a particular occasion. It seems that a plausible interpretation tenable in (63) and (64) above is that ki and má function as grammatical emphasisers - emphasising the negative meaning already introduced by the negator (the first negating meaning).

There are however some clauses in the language in which two negatives will result in double negative meanings. Such clauses will normally have, between the two negatives, the auxiliary adverbials:

- (70) [kò mòómò má] san owó náà
 NEG. AUX. ADV. NEG. pay money d-d
 's/he did not deliberately refuse to pay the money'

- (71) [kò gbódò má] san owó náà
 NEG. AUX. ADV. NEG. pay money d-d
 's/he must not fail to pay the money'

If the first negator is deleted in (70) and (71), the former will be grammatical (for example in an elliptical conversational discourse) although the meaning will be different (a kind of intentionality is introduced rather than negativity); whereas the latter sentence will become ungrammatical. The apparent distinguishable factor may be in the functional role of the two auxiliaries. Mòómò has, supposedly, an 'indirect tenor' and gbódò a 'direct tenor'.

This interpersonal implication of the uses of mòómò and gbódò means that the former is less 'salient' than the latter which is an imperative word. In other words, this feature of directness or otherwise is clearly understood when it is realised that the lexical meaning of mòómò usually functions to mean 'unintentionality.' But the imperativeness or obligatoriness of gbódò explains its directness.

If the two clauses (70) and (71) are without the adverbial auxiliaries mòómò (deliberately) and gbódò (must) respectively, and the first negating elements kò (NEG.) and kò (NEG.) they are left with the same structural elements and consequently the same meaning. Both clauses then become imperative statements:

(72) [má san] owó náà
NEG. pay money d-d
'don't pay the money'

2.2.1.5 - Experiential Structure

Consequent upon the above description of the verbal and the auxiliary elements in the language, the following analysis presents some of the experiential structures which range from one word to a long string of the verbal group to illustrate both the classes of the verbs and the auxiliaries as discussed above.

The following SPT terms are introduced:

Event is the verbal content or equivalent of the Thing that expresses a process which may be event, action, act of consciousness or relation (Halliday 1985a:176).

Marked is an information unit that is new or unpredictable in a clause.

Unmarked is an information unit which is already known or predictable in a clause (Halliday 1985a:275).

(73) ri

see/saw
Event: Mental
Tense / Aspect: Marked

'see'

Figure 2.2.2 - Main Verbal Group: Mental

(74) je

eat/ate
Event: Material
Tense/Aspect : Marked

'eat'

Figure 2.2.3 - Main Verbal Group: Material

The tense and aspect of numbers (73) and (74) are unpredictable.

(75) n ri

-ing	see
Auxiliary	Event
Tense/Prog.	Unmarked

'seeing'

Figure 2.2.4 - Progressive Auxiliary

(76)

ti		ri
have		seen
Auxiliary		Event
Tense	Aspect	
Past	Perf.	

Past → ← perfect ?

'have seen'

Figure 2.2.5 - Perfective Auxiliary

The tense and aspect of (75) and (76) are predictable.

(77)

/yìò / máa / je	
will	eat
Aux. (1) Aux. (2)	Event
Future	

'will eat'

Figure 2.2.6 - Future Auxiliary

(78)

máa n je	
be(-ing) being	eat
Aux. (1) Aux. (2)	Event
Aspects	
Habitual Prog.	

'always eating'

Figure 2.2.7 - Habitual and Progressive Auxiliary

(79) ti n je

have (being)		eat
Aux. (1) Aux. (2)		
Tense	Aspect	
Past: Perf.	Progressive	

'have been eating'

Figure 2.2.8 - Past and Progressive Auxiliary

(80) yiò ti rí

will have		see(en)
Aux. (1) Aux. (2)		
Tense	Aspect	
Future	Perf.	

'will have seen'

Figure 2.2.9 - Future + Past

(81) yiò máa je

will be (-ing)		eat (-ing)
Aux. (1) Aux. (2)		
Tense	Aspect	
Future	Habitual	

'will always eat/will be eating'

Figure 2.2.10 - Future + Habitual

(82) ti máa n je

have	be (-ing)	being	eat
Aux. (1)	Aux. (2)	Aux. (3)	
Tense	Aspect		Event
Past	Habitual	Prog.	

'have always been eaten'

Figure 2.2.11 - Past + Hab. + Prog.

(83) kò mòómò sokún

not	deliberately	weep
Aux. (1)	Aux. (2)	Event
Polarity	Adverbial	
Negation	Modality	

'not deliberately weep'

Figure 2.2.12 - Negation + Modality

(84) kò ki mòómò sokún

not	not	deliberately	weep
Aux. (1)	Aux. (2)	Aux. (3)	Event
Polarities		Adverbial	
Negators		Modality	
Neg.	Emph.	Modality	

'not (emph.) deliberately weep'

Figure 2.2.13 - Negation + Emphasis + Modality

(50)

kò		sáà		má		diídi		sé	
not		even		not		intentionally		do	
Aux. (1)		Aux. (2)		Aux. (3)		Aux. (4)		Event	
Pol.		Adv. (1)		Pol.		Adv. (2)			
Neg.		Mod. (1)		Emph.		Mod. (2)			

'not (emph.) even done deliberately'

Figure 2.2.14. Negation + Modality (1&2) + Emph.

(86)

kò		sáà		má		tètè		diídi		nikan		sé	
not		even		not		quickly		intentionally		alone		do	
Aux. (1)		Aux. (2)		Aux. (3)		Aux. (4)		Aux. (5)		Aux. (6)		Events	
Pol. 1		Adv. 1		Pol. 2		Adv. 2		Adv. 3		Adv. 4			
Neg.		Mod. 1		Emp.		Mod. 2		Mod. 3		Mod. 4			

'not even not (emph.) quickly done alone intentionally'

Figure 2.2.15 - Negation + Modality (1-4) + Emph.

2.2.1.6 - Logical Structure

Although the elements of the verbal group are mainly grammatical (that is, the auxiliaries have limited options past/present/future/progressive/habitual/positive/negative), they doubtless, have grammatical meanings, particularly the main 'events,' which, as I have observed, form the core of the lexical meaning of the clause. As the experiential structure has shown the grammatical wordings in the group, so it indirectly shows some logical ordering or orderliness of the wordings (Awobuluyi 1978:70). That is, the particular way the elements - the auxiliaries and the main verbs -

occur, in the process of actualization, is ordered to reflect either certain meaning or style. Part of this relation as is observable in the auxiliaries is what Odunuga (op.cit. p.270) referred to as the tense-aspectual forms of the language. In other words, the tense and the aspect, in some respects, are interwoven in the verbal group. Although parallel to the logical structure of the NG, the VG's logical structure displays separate tense choices (Halliday 1985:177-184). The elements are thus marked to show these choices, and the analysis from the first auxiliary to the Event. The following figures depict the logical structure of the Yoruba verbal group:

(87)

		je
		eat
Past/Present:		Event
		α

'eat'

Figure 2.2.16 - Past/Present

(88)

		ti	je
have			eat
Past			Event
α			β

'have eaten'

Figure 2.2.17 - Past

(89)

	ti	n	jeun
	have	(-ing)	eat
	Past	Prog.	Event
	α	β	$\dot{y}$

'have been eating'

Figure 2.2.18 - Present in Past in Present

The above (87) may refer to the present or past tense. In (88), ti depicts the past tense. Ti n in (89) denotes an action that began some time in the past and still continues at the moment of speech. In aspectual terms, the actions are completed in (88) but progressive in (89). The auxiliary carrying alpha notation (i.e. [89]) functions as Head because it is indicative of the first tense-aspectual relations in a structure with at least two auxiliaries. The subsequent modifying elements' indication of tense and aspect begins to reduce until the final event is reached in a particular structure. In the following figures this characteristic is further illustrated:

(90)

	yíò	rí
	will	see
	Future	Event
	α	β

'will see'

Figure 2.2.19 - Future

(91)

	yíò	ti	rí
will	have	see	
Future	Past	Event	
α	β	γ	

'will have seen'

Figure 2.2.20 - Future + Past

(92)

	yíò	ti	máa	rí
will	have	being	see	
Future	Past	Habitual	Event	
ú	β	γ	δ	

'will have been seeing'

Figure 2.2.21 - Future in Past in Present

In the above, (90) refers completely to the future. In (91), the future is inherent in the past, and in (92), the future is inherent in the present (or habitual). In the three instances, the future is the most important or the tense that features most although the past and the present (habitual) further modify the main events.

The analysis above suggests that in the verbal group in Yoruba, theoretically, the combinatory possibilities of the auxiliaries are vast. In practice, however, they are limited particularly when they become progressively less and less meaningful. The analysis also demonstrates that the following patterns could be identified: (93)

- | | | |
|----|--------------------------|---|
| 0 | je | 'eat' |
| 1. | yìò-je | 'will eat' |
| 2. | ti-je | 'has eaten' |
| 3. | yìò-ti-je | 'must have eaten' |
| 4. | yìò-ti-máa-je | 'must have being eaten' |
| 5. | kì-yìò-ti-máa-je | 'must not have being eaten' |
| 6. | kì-yìò-ti-dèdè-máa-je | 'must not have being eaten intentionally' |
| 7. | kò-kì-yìò-ti-dèdè-máa-je | 'must not (not) have being eaten intentionally' |

Figure 2.2.22 - The Patterns of the Auxiliaries

The following table shows the Tense-Aspectal forms of the auxiliaries:

Aspect	Tense	
	Present	Future
	Present/Past	
	+(-) Negative	+(-) Negative
Neutral Progressive/ Habitual	V n + V máa n + V a máa + V	yìò/máa + V a/yìò má + V
Perfective/ Beginning Perfective/ End	ti n + V ti/a/ ti máa + V	a/yìò/o ti máa + V yìò/a/o/ ti + V

Table 2.2.6 - Tense-Aspectal Forms

2.2.1.7 - System Network

Figure 2.2.23 - Verbal Group (1): Principal Systems

Following Halliday's description of English, the principal systems of the verbal group above captures, succinctly the processes in the language. It seems to me that these processes will be inherent in most if not all languages although these may be expressed in different forms. The entry condition for the network is 'Process.' The systemic choice is open to the user of the language from either 'major' or 'minor' processes depending on the linguistic goal. If major, a further choice in the delicacy is any of the three - 'material,' 'mental,' and 'relational.' If minor, it is any of 'behavioural,' 'verbal,' and 'existential.'

As in the network above, material process, semantically, may be divided into 'concrete' and 'abstract' types although, at times, the division becomes blurred. Considering, for example, the clause omode kunrin naa lo si ile ('the boy went home'), the process verb lo (go) is 'concrete.' On the other hand, tu (scatter/disband) in alaga tu igbimo naa ka ('The chairman disbanded the council') may be regarded as an abstract material process because the action is not supported by a physical action. The conscious 'senser' in the mental process 'feels,' 'thinks,' and 'perceives,' generally, 'things' and 'facts.' In the clause, a gbagbo pe orisa yi ni aqbara (we believe that this divinity is powerful) the meaning of the mental process gbagbo (believe) is inherent in orisa (divinity) - a 'thing.' In mo ro pe Olanlokun sare ni (I thought that Olanlokun ran) on the other hand, the meaning of the mental process 'ro' (think) in the clause does not refer to Olanlokun. Rather, it refers to the fact that 'Olanlokun's running' instead of say, 'walking.' Factual meaning evoked by mental process in English is often signalled by 'the fact that' but by 'pe' (that) in Yoruba. Attributive and identifying types of relational process typically assigns a certain quality (negative or positive) to and defines the identity of an entity respectively. In the expression arabirin naa je oniqberaga (the woman is proud), for example, the verb of relation je (is) assigns the attribute of pride to the woman. But in arabirin naa ni eni ti a sope o qberaga (the woman is the one that we said is proud) the verb of relation ni (is) identifies who the proud woman is.

Physiological and psychological types of behavioural process are mostly involuntary behaviour which may be induced internally or externally to the Behaver. Most physiological behavioural process form part of the internal organic function of the 'Behaver' and psychological process is a reaction to an external stimulus. In agbe naa beru ejo (the farmer fears a snake), for example, the behavioural verb beru (fear) is psychological. Snake is external to but causes fear for the 'Behaver.' In agbe naa nhanrun (the farmer is snoring), nhanrun (snoring) as a kind of breathing is a physiological behaviour. Depending on usage, however, nmi (breathing) though a physiological process, may be brought into being by the fact that the farmer runs away from, say, a snake. Without the adverbial gulegule (rapidly) nmi (breathing) will serve merely as an internal organic function. A verbal process may be divided into 'proposition' and 'proposal.' Seeming alike, both may be differentiated from each other on semantic grounds by the way they function in clauses. So (say) in o so pe Dipo wa ni ile (s/he said that Dipo is in the house) is a 'propositional' verbal process. Seleri (promise) in o seleri pe oun yio wa (s/he promised to come) is a type of 'proposal' verbal process. Existential process functions in clauses to mean that something 'exists/is' or 'happens/causes': In ounje wa lori ina (food is on the stove), wa (exist/is) is an existential process. In the maxim - imototo ni oogun ilera (cleanliness leads to good health) ni (cause) is an existential process which 'brings about/causes or serves' as the basis for good health.

Figure 2.2.24 - Verb Group (2): Subsidiary Systems

The subsidiary systems of the verbal group above are divided into four - tense, aspect, polarity, and modality. The systemic option in the choice of tense is mainly past and future. If past, it is either present-in-past or past-in-past or past-in-past. For the former, it functions in a clause such that it may be classified either as present or past. In Adelanfe je onunje re (Adelanfe eats/ate his food), je (eat) may function in presentness or pastness. For the latter, ti je (Perf.+ eat) indicates in, for example, Adelanfe ti je onunje e (Adelanfe has eaten his food) a clear past. The future tense may also be grouped into two - present-in-future and future-in-future. Ti maa je (has been eating) in Adelanfe a ti maa je onunje re (Adelanfe has been being eaten his food) illustrates present-in-present. Yio maa je (will be being eaten) expresses future-in-future in

Adelanfe yio maa je ounje re (Adelanfe will have been eaten his food).

The combined tense-aspectual nature of the language as earlier indicated (Odunuga 1982:268) shows some aspectual influence on the above description of tense. Basically, aspect in the language may be divided into progressive and perfective. The progressive marker is n or m and the perfective marker is ti. N in o n lo (s/he is going) indicates the progressive meaning in the clause, ti in o ti lo (s/he has gone) indicates the perfective meaning.

Polarity in Yoruba, unlike tense and aspect, is a distinct grammatical category. Based on the systemic option of either positive or negative, verbal group negation in Yoruba is effected by the addition of certain negator elements to the positive verbal group. Wa (come) in olubewo naa [wa] si ile eko wa (the inspector came to our school) is a material process with positive meaning. With the addition of ko (NEG.) to the clause, its meaning potential changes. Thus, olubewo naa [kò] wa si ile eko wa (the inspector did not come to our school) has a negative meaning. It is possible, however, to have more than one negative in a clause which may or may not follow each other in a sequence. Kò ki (NEG., NEG.) in oluko yen kò ki n binu (that teacher does not get angry), for example, shows two negatives occurring in sequence and yet maintaining a negative meaning. For modality, conditional and obligatory meanings are expressed. The auxiliary verb ba (should) in ti olubewo yen [ba] wa si ile eko yin jowo ki i fun mi (should that inspector come to

your school, please express my regards to him) expresses conditional meaning. In olubewo yen [qbodo] wa si ile eko yin l'oni (that inspector must come to your school today), on the other hand, the auxiliary verb qbodo (must) expresses obligatory meaning.

2.2.1.8 - Conclusion

The analysis attempts a description of the verbs in Yoruba in a far more concise and less cumbersome way than earlier attempts. The categories of material, mental, verbal, relational, existential and behavioural processes give a concise classification of the verbs in the language in terms of their meanings in relation to their participants. The auxiliaries have also been examined in terms of their tenses and aspects. Unlike the nominal group, the elements of the verbal group are purely grammatical - past/future, progressive/perfective, positive/negative, conditional and obligatory which represent closed options in the linguistic system. The complementary nature of auxiliary verbs in the language does not allow for a categorisation of certain auxiliary options which may support the above classifications of the processes. Within auxiliary verbs themselves, however, the following ^{co-?} occurrence restrictions are observable:

(i) à (FUT.) and yíò (FUT.) cannot occur together in clauses (examples 40 and 41).

(ii) Ki (NEG. -a variant of kò) occurs only before yíò (FUT.), bá (AUX. VB.) and n (PROG.) - (examples 55 and 56).

- (iii) kò (NEG.) cannot precede à (FUT.) and yíò (FUT.) except in interrogatives (example 52).
- (iv) When they both occur in clauses, kò and kì (NEG. variants) must occur in an ordered sequence without a word between them - kò first and kì second (examples 66 and 67).
- (v) When double negative meanings are expressed by two negatives in a clause, a preverb adverbial must occur between them (examples 70 and 71).

Finally, the system networks have provided a graphic representation of both the processes and the auxiliary verbs which comprise the verbal group.

2.3.0 - The Adverbial Group (AG)

The Adverbial Group (AG) in SFT's description of English has an adverb as Head. This Head may or may not be modified by any other element belonging to the group. Modification may occur before or after the Head. In some cases, however, modification may occur as embedded elements in the form of either phrases or clauses. This type of embedding is similar to that of the nominal group and, apart from these, all other embedding in English occurs as a form of nominalisation (Halliday 1985a:187). Comparison is the only type of postmodification in English and most importantly, the AG may be represented as a logical structure.

The mobility of the adverbial group in the Yoruba language seems to make it difficult to describe. In order to define what I mean by the adverbial group in the language, I shall begin by examining the following definitions of an adverb. Here is Abiri's (1982:39) definition:

1982? Not in B22/197-198

"An adverb is a word which occurs immediately after an adjective or a verb (with the object and its qualifier, if any) in a sentence, and performs the function of modifying the meaning of that adjective or verb. It modifies the meaning of a verb by indicating the time, place, manner or extent of its action, while it modifies the meaning of an adjective by saying something about the extent of its quality."

Similar to Abiri's definition, Ogunbowale (1970:81) states that 'normally an adverb stands after the verb, adjective, or adverb it modifies.' It may be added that this is so except when they act as auxiliary adverbs (section 2.3.1) Further on adverbs, Ogunbowale (op.cit. p.80) writes:

"The adverb expresses some circumstances that attend an action or state or points out some characteristic features of an action or quality."

From the above definitions, the positions in which adverbs occurs in a clause and their functions become crucial to this analysis. But before proceeding with these important aspects of the adverbs, I shall attempt to distinguish between an adverb and an adverbial, and consequently an adverbial group.

In the Yoruba language, the distinction between an adverb and an adverbial is not easy to draw because neither the number of words, that is the length, nor the complexity of the clause, serves as the criterion to distinguish an adverb from an adverbial.

Awobuluyi's (1978:67) distinguishes the two in this way:

"The real or crucial difference between adverbs and adverbials is that the former cannot be moved from their normal place of occurrence in sentences, whereas the latter can."

He gives the following two examples to support the above observation:

(1) Ojo lo rí
Ojo PAST ever²⁹
'Ojo went before'

and

(2) Ojo lo kiákíá
Ojo PAST quickly
'Ojo went quickly'

Rí (before) in (1) cannot occupy any other position in the clause but kiákíá (quickly) in (2) may change position to clause-initial:

(3) kiákíá ni Ojo lo
quickly FOC. Ojo PAST
'Ojo went quickly'

The criterion concerning the mobility potential that the adverbial possesses to move position within the clause, however, remains the distinctive factor between it and the adverb.

The AG in Yoruba, in a similar way to both the nominal and the verbal groups, may consist of just one word or a group of words. When it is a word, it may be either an adverb or an adverbial. When more than a word, it may consist of an introducer (INTR.), a noun or a nominalisation with or without the modifiers.

In this section, I shall investigate the positions and the functions of the adverbial group in the language.³⁰ The positions of occurrence of adverbs and the adverbials in the clause indicate the extent to which the latter are mobile in the structure of the clause. Again Awobuluyi argues:

"The manner in which these adverbs occur together or exclude one another is difficult to describe, especially owing to a great deal of indeterminateness or variation in the way they are used by different speakers and in different dialects" (1982: 241)."

It seems difficult to agree with Awobuluyi that this characteristic of the adverbs and/or the adverbials amounts to indeterminateness. In an earlier publication (see the above quotation -Awobuluyi 1978:67), he makes a distinction which he calls 'the real or crucial difference' to distinguish between the adverb and the adverbial - their

positions of occurrence. It is observable, however, that the variations and peculiarities of the adverbs and the adverbials in the language are indeed very complex.³¹

The modifying role of the adverbs and the adverbials to the verbs and adjectives contributes to the heterogeneous positions they occupy in the clause. As a result of their consistency in modifying the verbs, two major positions can be identified; those that occur before the verbs (the 'auxiliary adverbs' - section 2.2.1.4 on verbal group), and those that occur after the verbs or their objects (the 'post-verbal adverbs'). These modifiers are to verbs what nominal modifiers are to nouns because very few verbs occur in the language unaccompanied by at least one modifier.

The positions of the adverbs and the adverbials influence their functional roles in the structures in which they occur. These adverbs and the adverbials are often functionally interpreted using Traditional Grammar in terms of the categories of place, manner, time, degree and so on. In the process, their modifying roles restrict the meanings of the verbs or adjectives they modify. It seems more useful, at least for the purpose of this study, to investigate adverbs and adverbials mainly according to their positions of occurrence and function, and the types of 'head,' 'action,' or 'process' they modify.

In the following analysis, I shall examine the adverbs and the adverbials which occupy positions before (between subject and verb), mid (between two verbs) and after the verbs. Then

I shall examine the clauses and their various modifications including what Awobuluyi (1978:68) calls sentential adverbs; the special occurrences by which certain adverbs and adverbials function as utterances or comments on the entire sentence.

2.3.1 - Auxiliary Adverbs

The position taken in this thesis, and as stressed in the section on the verbal group, is that the grammatical elements which occupy the position between the subject and the verb consist of the auxiliary verbs and adverbs. The former belongs to the VG, and the latter to the AG.

In clauses (4) and (5) below:

(4) nwon [sa] pe e, o ji
they awhile call him he wake
'they called him for a while, he woke up'

(5) igbati o se Esan-mbo [tun] lo
when it happen Esan-mbo again go
'after some time, Esan-mbo went again'

Sa (awhile) and tun (again) are examples of the auxiliary adverb. Generally, sa could mean any of anyway, for no purpose and for fun. It functions, nevertheless, in the clause above specifically to show the continuity of the verbal act of calling - pe.³² Tun (again), which is very commonly used in the language means again. Sharing some similarity in meaning with sa³³ (awhile), tun (again) in the context in which it is used, functions to mean the repetition of an action - in this case the act of going. This means in SPT terms that it premodifies the material process go. It is

most probable that all auxiliary adverbs in the language are simple words consisting of two syllables.

Awobuluyi (1978:74) states that the auxiliary adverbials in the language are introduced by three prepositions: ti³⁴ (from), bá (for, in company with, on behalf of) and fi (with, by means of). According to him, adverbials containing ti 'are used to indicate the point in space or time from which things and events begin'. Those containing bá 'are used to signify accompaniment or the beneficiaries usually of other people's actions.' Those containing fi 'signify manner, or the means by which an action is accomplished.' His examples are given:

(6) ó [ti] Eko dé ni àná
he INTR. Lagos arrive (SEW) yesterday
'he got back from Lagos yesterday'

(7) ó [bá] mi ra bàtà bò³⁵
he INTR. me buy shoe come
'he bought a pair of shoes for me (from somewhere)'

(8) ó [fi] ayo gbà á
he INTR. joy accept it
'he received it gladly'

Rather than tí in (6), bá in (7) and fi in (9) functioning as prepositions as Awobuluyi describes them, it seems to me that they function as 'introducers' of some events. Tí in (6) indicates the event which begins in 'Lagos' and ends 'yesterday' (ana). Bá signifies the accompaniment of 'shoes' with 'buyer,' and fi signifies the 'manner' in which 'something' is 'received.'

Aside from the above auxiliary adverbs, Awobuluyi (1978:69) points out that one adverb may function either as a nominal

qualifier or as a preverbal (auxiliary is used in this study) adverb. The word is nikan (alone) as in

- (9) Ojo [nikan] ni o jeun
Ojo alone (SEW) he eat
'Ojo was the only one who ate'

nikan functions as a modifier of Ojo.

But in

- (10) Ojo ni ó [nikan] jeun
Ojo FOC. he alone eat
'Ojo ate alone'

*note for you to read
in FOC. marker. See p 113.
114 (Ex. 25)*

nikan functions as an auxiliary adverb.³⁶ It seems that given example (8) above, and following Awobuluyi's criterion on the difference between an adverb and an adverbial, there is no preverbal adverbial in the language. Such a potential adverbial would most probably be nominalised in the process.

2.3.2 -Mid-Position Adverbials

The mid-position criterion, as the description simply suggests, means that such adverbs or adverbials must function between two verbs or one verb and a prepositional element. There are apparently no mid-position adverbs in the language as they function in the clause in close proximity to the verb or the adjective that they modify. Single word adverbials occupy, however, mid-position in clauses (in section 2.3.1., the difference between adverbs and adverbials is distinguished). In grammatical terms, these single word adverbials relate in meaning to both verbs that they simultaneously modify; they have the potential to move from mid-position to clause-initial and final positions in the

clause. In the clause below:

- (11) Alabapade se [gá-ntá gá-ntá] dide
Alabapade act stagger stagger stand
'Alabapade stood up staggeringly'

the mid-position adverbial ganta-ganta (stagger) functions between two verbs, se (act) and dide (stand). Other examples are not uncommon in the language:

- (12) Gbogbo nwón nrin [sísè-ntèlé] lo sí ilé won
all they PROG. walk. step-by-step go PREP. house their
'all of them are walking step-by-step to their house'
- (13) ó ni [pátápátá] ni nwón gé igi náà
3sg. say completely is they cut tree d-d
'he said that they cut the tree completely'

where sísè-ntèlé and pátápátá are also mid-position adverbials functioning between nrin (walk) - lo (go) and ni (say) - ni (is) respectively. As adverbials they may shift position from mid to clause-initial or clause-final. At the clause-initial position the adverbials become emphatic/thematised.³⁷ This emphasis is signalled by the focus word ni. For examples:

- (14) [sísè-ntèlé] ni gbogbo won nrin lo sí ilé won
step-by-step FOC. all them PROG. walk go PREP. house their
'It is step-by-step they are all walking to their house'

and

- (15) [pátápátá] ni ò ni nwon gé igi náà
completely FOC. he say they cut tree d-d
'It is completely that he said they cut the tree'

They occur in the final positions as follows:

- (16) Gbogbo nwon nrin lo sí ile ní [sísè-ntèlé]
all they PROG. walk go PREP. house PREP. step-by-step
'all of them are going to the house step-by-step'

and

- (17) ó ni nwón gé igi náà [pátápátá]
 he say they cut tree d-d completely
 'he said the tree was cut completely'

The characteristic of the adverbials which enables them to shift positions in the clause, as already remarked, is the criterion that can be used to differentiate them from adverbs.

2.3.3 - Post-verbal Adverbs and Adverbials

The post-verbal adverbs and adverbials occur after the processes that they modify or after the participant of such process. The following examples are post-verbal adverbs:

- (18) o le ri imu [dada]³⁸
 s/he AUX. see nose very well
 's/he can see the nose very well'

- (19) Alaisan yi, ko le duro [ju] [bee] lo [mo]
 patient this NEG. AUX. stand more so than any longer
 'this patient cannot stand for longer than that anymore'

Dada (very well) in (18) above post modifies the second participant imu (nose). Ju (more) in (19) is an adverb of comparison. It post modifies the material process duro (stand). More interestingly, it forms a part of a group of three consecutive adverbs ju (more), bee (so) and mo (any longer). Bee³⁹ means so (or if translated in more than one word - bi iru eyi (like this)). It is used, more or less, as an affirmative word to heighten the comparative word ju (more).⁴⁰ Mo (no longer or any longer) functions to mean the heightened comparison of the past (when the patient was able to stand very well) and the present (when s/he does not seem to stand as well as before).

The post-verbal adverbials are used to signify various semantic categories of time, location, manner, circumstance, and several others. They are mostly introduced by ni (in, at, to, on), si (in, at, to), fún (for, on behalf of) and pèlú (with).⁴¹ Awobuluyi observes that the adverbials introduced by the preposition ni form the majority in the language. In some contexts, he argues, it is either possible or obligatory to drop the preposition ni in some clauses. Examples of post-adverbials are as follows:

- (20) oro yi ta si Alabapade leti gere
 word this penetrate PREP. Alabapade PREP. ear straightaway
 'this call penetrated into Alabapade's ear straightaway'
- (21) Alabapade dide gau
 Alabapade stand suddenly
 'Alabapade stood up suddenly'

Both gere (straightaway)⁴² and gau (suddenly) are adverbial elements most especially because they could shift from their FP (Final Position) to IP (Initial Position) if thematised. Both adverbial elements also function to express the manner of how 'the call' ([20] above) to revive Alabapade going straight into his ears -gere (straightaway) and how Alabapade 'stands up' (21) - gau (suddenly).

The preposition ni which may function (to introduce) immediately before the occurrence of the adverbial elements in (20) and (21) above has been dropped, perhaps, obligatorily (Awobuluyi 1978:76).⁴³ If the adverbial elements are thematised (through focusing), the preposition ni functions prominently as in (24) and (25) below:

- (22) [Gere] ni oro yi ta si Alabapade leti
 straightway FOC. word this enter PREP. Alabapade PREP. ear
 'this call penetrated straightaway into Alabapade's ear'
- (23) [Gau] ni Alabapade dide
 suddenly FOC. Alabapade stand
 'Alabapade stood up suddenly'

The occurrence of the focusing element ni as in (22) and (23) above does not change substantially their meaning potential although the focussed items are more explicitly or emphatically presented.

Both gere (straightaway) - (20) and gau (suddenly) - (21) may function in any of the three positions in a clause - IP (Initial Position), MP (Mid Position) and FP (Final Position). Both FP and IP for gere (straightaway) and gau (suddenly) are demonstrated already in (20), (21) and (23) above respectively. In the following clauses their MP is demonstrated.

- (24) oro yi ta [gere] si Alabapade leti
 word this penetrate straightway PREP Alabapade PREP. ear
 'this call penetrated straightaway into Alabapade's ear'
- (25) Alabapade se [gau] dide
 Alabapade act suddenly stand
 'Alabapade stood up suddenly'

All adverbial words may function in all the three positions in the clause except when constrained either by the number of words or by the occurrence of two adverbials.

Loto (truly), for example, may function in both IP and FP but not in MP as in the following clauses:

- (26) [loto], Alabapade ni — (IP)
 truly Alabapade is
 'truly, it is/was Alabapade'

(27) Alabapade ni [loto] — (FP)
Alabapade FOC. truly
'It is/was truly Alabapade'

(28) *Alabapade [loto] ni — (MP)
'Alabapade truly is'

When two adverbial elements occur as in (29) below, neither can occupy the mid position in the clause; that is, functioning between two verbs or one verb and a preposition.

(29) [loto], Alabapade dide [gau]
truly Alabapade stand suddenly
'truly Alabapade stood up suddenly'

The most interesting interpretation of these elements lies perhaps in their semantic relevance in their positions of occurrence. Gau (suddenly) possesses the semantic typology of the expression of manner. But loto (truly) does not seem to fit into the somewhat open semantic typologies often associated with adverbs and adverbials. Neither does it permit any of such groupings as verb, adjective or complement modifier. It seems obvious then that loto (truly) and, to a certain extent, gau (suddenly)⁴⁴ as modifiers function specifically to emphasise particular meanings whenever they occupy clause-initial positions. But both modifiers do not present the sentences as events or situations as most of the other modifiers would normally do. When they occur in the clause-initial positions, they appear thematic - giving salient meaning to the main parts of the clauses. In that position Loto (truly), however, is somewhat different from gau (suddenly) as it functions as a comment, that is, as an 'utterance' of affirmation of a known fact or behaviour, while gau (suddenly) functions as an 'utterance' of

observation of a person's (in this context, Alabapade) bodily movement. As a factual statement of behaviour, loto (truly) has these paradigms:

laisianiani	(without doubt)
ni otito	(in truth)
lotito	(indeed) ⁴⁵

2.3.4 - Introducers

The following multi-word adverbial groups in the language, unlike iu (more), bee (so), mo (than) are, apparently, easier to identify because they are signalled or 'introduced' by certain words that function in such a way that either the listeners or the readers are led to expect more facts or details in the succeeding sentence or sentences. These expectations may be elaborations on known facts or even completely different facts from the previous ones. Most important is that the introducers may be grouped into various types and meaning.

Examples of these are: /bi, pe, ki, ti, igbati, gegebi, ibi, nigbati, nitorina, nitori, iba, lati, etc./⁴⁶ As remarked, in this section these words signal adverbials and their meanings. Some of these words are classified below:

condition	=	bi, iba
time	=	bi, ki, nigbati, igbati, titi
comparison	=	bi, gegebi
manner	=	pe, ki, gegebi
reason	=	ti, ki, nitorinaa
place	=	nibiti, lati
cause	=	nitorinaa

Table 2.3.4 - Adverbial introducers

Whenever there is an introducer there must be either an adverb or an adverbial Head in the group. In (30) and (31) below:

(30) a ma nao /pe (firifiri) ni oju nri imu/
we AUX. PROG. say that barely is eye PROG. see nose
'we usually say that barely does the eye see the nose'

(31) eniyan ti o se farati /bi oke ni Pa Akinola/
person that one can rely like mount is Pa Akinola
'a person reliable as a mountain is pa Akinola'

Firifiri (barely), an ideophonic⁴⁷ adverbial, immediately follows the introducer pe as the Head of the group in (24) above to begin the proverbial statement which describes the indistinct manner with which the eyes see the nose. In the same manner, bi in (25) introduces the adverbial group with oke (mountain) as Head.

2.3.5 - Interrogative Adverbs

Some parts of the characteristics of the adverbs or adverbials in the IP are more explicitly stated in what Awobuluyi (op. cit. 84) describes as the interrogative adverbs. They are so important that they cannot be left out in the consideration of this discussion. Awobuluyi (1978: 78-80) includes in his classification of 'sententials' not just this class of interrogative adverbs, but also the class of adverbs which occur at the end of clauses. Awobuluyi (op. cit. above):

"Sententials consist of adverbs and adverbials which modify sentences. Some sententials occur only at the beginning of sentences, others only at the end of sentences, and still others at either the beginning or the end of sentences."

His classifications include the interrogative adverbs which either occur at the beginning or at the end of sentences. The most important function of these modifiers of sentences is to create the background against which meanings of the sentences are interpreted.

Interrogative IP adverbs form two groups:

1. - those that are used for asking questions;

Njé⁴⁸, sé, níbo, (or láti ibo or ibo)

Nígbawo (láti ígbawo, títi de ígbawo, ígbawo)

Examples are:

(32) [Sé/Njé] omo náà wá?
INT. child d-d come
'does the child come?'

(33) [Níbo/ibo/láti ibo] ni ó ti wá?
INT. (SEW) 3sg. PERF. come
'where did he come from?'

(34) [Nígbàwo] ni ó dè?
INT. (SEW) 3sg. arrive
'when did he arrive?'

(35) [Láti ígbàwo] ni ó ti dè?
INT. (SEW) 3sg. PERF. arrive
'since when did he arrive?'

(36) [Báwo] ni ó se wo ilé
INT. (SEW) 3sg. (SEW) enter house
'how did he enter the house?'

2. - those ones that are used rhetorically or, in certain writings, stylistically.

àsé⁴⁹ àní (meaning 'in other words', as already shown)

This could be shown as follows:

(37) [Asé] ohun tí ó wí ni yen? (rhetorically)
INT. what PERF. 3sg. say (SEW) that
'so that is what he said!'

(38) [Asé] béè kó ló rí? (rhetorically)
INT. so/like NEG. it is
'so it was not like that/so?'

- (39) [Aní] bée kó lò wí! (emphatically or stylistically)
 EMPH. so NEG. he say
 'I mean/am saying that he did not say so!'
- (40) [Aní] kò wí bée! (emphatically/stylistically)
 EMPH. NEG. 50 say so
 'I mean/am saying that he did not say so!'

Aní, as used above, does not superficially turn the clauses to questions. Inherently, however, it could be interpreted as saying that 'don't you hear me properly (with emphasis on properly) saying that 'he did not say so?' or, 'I am very sorry, I did not mean to say what I have said - he did not say so - do you understand now?'

The FP interrogative adverbs also form two groups:

1. - as in bi in

- (41) ó se isé náà [bi]?
 he does work d-d INT.
 'did he do the work?'

2. - those that, again, may be used rhetorically or stylistically as in the following:

o (its use as a particle),
se (meaning 'as indicated'),
ke (used to mean or show contempt)

Examples are:

- (42) mo ti se é [o]
 I PERF. do it RHE.
 'I have done it'
- (43) kò so bée [sé]
 NEG. 51 say so RHE.
 'he didn't say so, alright/ok!'
- (44) Iwo [ke]
 You! RHE. (DEROG.)
 'You! (of all people)'

Singler (1988:123) describes this o in (44) above as 'the sentence-final particle' which is found in Niger-Congo languages along the West African coast from Sierra Leone to Nigeria.⁵² Using the structure Mo ri i o (I see him)⁵³ he cites Bamgbose who identifies o as 'segment which the average Yoruba speaker appends to his utterance to reinforce his message' (see also Badejo 1986: 8).

Bamgbose's and Badejo's descriptions reinforce Awobuluyi's (1978:79) observation that the particle o occurs mostly in greetings, to reinforce greetings. For example:

(45) E⁵⁴ káàbò [o]
 You (sg./pl.) welcome PART./EMPH.
 'you are welcome'

(46) ó dabo [o]
 it bye PART./EMPH.
 'bye/so long'

I would like to suggest that this sentence-final particle o presupposes an interrogative function in all its uses. For example, in mo ri i o (I see him) or mo ti se o (I have done it) the speaker apparently uses o rhetorically in the FP to mean 'do you now understand?' The same function applies to se and ke as identified above. That is, in ko so bee se (he did not say so), se together with other words in the clause functions to mean 'would you believe me that he never said so?' Similarly in iwo ke (you also/you of all people!), ke together with the nominal word iwo (you) means 'do you want me to believe what you are doing/have done to me?'

Is this also true of (45) & (46) above?

From the discussions on the interrogative adverbs it is apparent that they function also, in most cases, to show the

semantic typologies of what, where, when and how.

2.3.6 - Logical Structure

In the adverbial group there do not appear to be several modifying elements comparable to both the nominal and the verbal groups. There are, however, words which may stand as introducers and which must have either an adverb or an adverbial as Head in the Yoruba language. What might account for this characteristic is perhaps the tendency of the adverbials to shift position easily in a structure. It is difficult therefore to be categorical about the patterning of the adverbial elements in a structure although some types of logical patterning could be accounted for as shown in the next paragraph.

This is a type of serialisation consisting of a series of adverbs; for example, ju be lo mo (section 2.3.3. above). In the pattern, an adverb of comparison is followed successively by two manner adverbs showing Comparison-Manner-Manner (CMM) patterning. Its logical structure may be represented as in Figure 2.3.5. below:

(47)

	ju	be	lo	mo
	more	so	than	anymore
	Head	Modifier		
	α	β		γ

'more than that anymore'

Figure 2.3.6 (1) - Serial Adverbs

*lo be mo mo
adverb? See pp. 152
+ lo be mo
is explained.*

Among the interrogatives discussed the rhetorical/emphatic/stylistic adverbs display some interesting logical structures: In (38) above, for example;

(48) [Ase bee] kó ló rí?
 so so/like NEG. it is
 'so it is not like that?'

àsé (so) and béè (so) follow each other in an immediate sequence. The same pattern is observable in (39), again as re-copied below:

(49) [àní béè] kó ló wí
 mean so NEG. he say
 'I mean/am saying that he did not say so'

where ani (mean) and bee (so) follow each other in the clause.

The three clauses show the following logical relations:

(50) ase bee ko lo ri

so	like	NEG.	it	is
Head	Postmodifier -----			
α	β			

'so it is not like that'

(51) ani bee ko lo wi

mean	like	NEG.	he	say
Head	Postmodifier -----			
α	β			

'mean (e.g. 'I') he did not say so"

Clause (52) below does not show, however, an immediate

sequence of ani (mean) and bee (so). It contains, therefore, a submodifier.

(52) ani ko wi bee

mean	NEG.	say	so
Head	Postmodifier_____		
α			β
Submodifier			
	$\beta\beta$		

'mean he did not say so'

Figure 2.3.6. (2) - Interrogative Adverbs

An examination of a text consisting of series of clauses might show some general patterning of the adverbs and the adverbials in the language. Such patternings as Comparison-Manner or Time-Place-Manner may be predominant (this is beyond the scope of this work) in certain texts and may be used to predict their type. In journalese texts in Yoruba, for example, the news reporter may follow a sequence in the way messages are presented. S/he may introduce the topic first, followed by the event and the people involved before describing the time the event took place, the place, and finally, the manner of the occurrence of the event.

The adverbial group may show some type of embedding as analysed in the following short text: The symbol // indicates clause boundaries.

Text 2.3.6⁵⁵

1. a ma nso [pe] firifiri ni
 we usually PROG. say that barely is
 'we usually say that barely can'

2. oju nri imú
eye PROG. see nose
'the eye see the nose'
3. sugbon [bi] ojú ba fi ara balè
but if eye AUX. make body patient
'but if the eye can be patient'
4. o le rí imú [dada]
it may see nose very well
'it may come to see the nose very well'

// a ma nso pe // firifiri ni oju nri imu//
//bi oju ba fi ara bale // o le ri imu dada//

(53) [...pe firifiri] ni oju nri imu

that	barely	is	eye	see(-ing)	nose
Introducer	Head	Post-modifier_____			
β	α				
SubHead		Sub-modifier _____			
$\beta\beta$	-----	$\beta\beta$			

'that barely can the eye see the nose'

Figure 2.3.6. (3) -

Adverbial Group with Embedded Post-modifier

(54)
[bi] oju ba fi ara bale o le ri imu [dada]

if	eye	AUX.	make	body	patient	it	may	see	nose	well
INT.	----- Pre-modifier									Head
$\tilde{y}$	β									α
Sub-Head	Sub-modifier									
	$\beta\beta$									

'if the eye can be patient it may come to see the nose very well'

Figure 2.3.6 (4) -

Adverbial Group with Embedded Pre-modifier

A general pattern may be suggested for the adverbial group in the language as follows:

(INTR.) + (AUX. ADV.) + ADV. + (SERIAL ADV.) + (ADV. CLAUSE)

All of the elements are optional except the adverb or the adverbial element. By this pattern all elements which may occur in the group are accounted for: the introducer (INTR.), the auxiliary adverb (AUX. ADV.), the adverb, serial adverbials and the adverbial which forms the core element of the group.

2.3.7 - Systems Network

Figure 2.3.7 - Adverbial Group: (1) Position

The above system network sets out the positions of the adverbs and the adverbial items in Yoruba. The three

positions are Initial, Mid, and Final. The IP takes either the option of focusing or non-focusing. Its use as a focusing device is hereby divided into two: First, when a new meaning is introduced through the use of the auxiliary adverb (section 2.3.1.) Second, when it functions to thematise the item as in (55) below:

(55) [kiakial ni o de
quickly FOC. s/he arrive
's/he arrived quickly'

Non-focusing takes a series of options. It may or may not be interrogative. When used as an interrogative, it is used also as the first item in the clause -

(56) [Nje] nwon de?
INT. they arrive
'Did (have) they arrive (d)?'

When used as non-interrogative, it may be rhetorical -

(57) [Ase e] nwon de
RHE. they arrive
'You mean (that is) they arrived!'

When non-rhetorical, it may or may not be emphatic. When emphatic, it functions as in (58) below

(58) O o nwon de
EMPH. they arrive
'Yes, (I heard/know) they arrived'

When non-emphatic, then, it may take, for example, the following option -

(59) werewere ni e de
quick quick is you arrive
'you [must] arrive quickly'

The Mid position locates the adverb or adverbial item between

two processes or between a process and a preposition. The item gau (suddenly) is located between two processes in (60)

(60) mo fo [gau] dide
 I fly suddenly stand
 'I flew up suddenly'

whereas (61) is located between a process and a preposition -

(61) mo [be] lojiji [si] ile
 I jump suddenly PREP. house
 'I suddenly jumped into the house'

The introducer is located after the process followed by a noun or nominalisation as shown below (from Text 2.3.6):

(62) a maa nso [pe] firifiri ni oju nri imu
 we usually PROG. say that barely is eye PROG see nose
 'we usually say that the eye can barely see the nose'

where pe (that) is the introducer of the adverbial group.

The AG typology system is as follows:

Figure 2.3.7. - Adverbial Group (2): Typologies

Traditional grammar emphasises more the core items forming each of the above typological classification of the adverbials. Hence, these are classified as adverbial clauses of time, place, manner, degree and cause. Their classification according to their modifying role in logical structure (section 2.3.6 above) is perhaps more useful because it examines the adverbials in a clearer functional perspective within the other elements of the particular clause in which they function.

The above system network (2) shows more their meaning potential particularly by opening up their possible options. Consider (63) below:

(63) Se bi mo ri o [lana]?
INT. COND. I see you yesterday
'Didn't I see you yesterday?'

Laibe (soon) may function in the same position as lana (yesterday) yet with a different meaning. The former is non-specific but the latter is specific. The typology of 'place' has the option of being 'directional.' If directional, it may be neutral as in (64) below:

(64) Fi iwe owo re si [ibikibi] ninu iyara
put book hand your PREP. anywhere PREP. room
'put the book in your hand anywhere in the room'

In (64) above, ninu iyara (PREP. room) indicates the direction to the person given the responsibility to take the book there but ibikibi (anywhere) is 'neutral' in meaning concerning where the book may be put in the room. Niwaju (in front), on the other hand, is 'non-neutral' in (65) below:

(65) Duro de wa [niwaju]
wait PREP.us in front
'wait for us in front (e.g. of the house)

Ni Okemesi (PREP.Okemesi) in (66) below

(66) Ni Okemesi

[Ni Okemesi] ni a n gbe
PREP.Okemesi is we PROG.live
'we live at Okemesi'

is an adverbial phrase meaning a 'place.'

The way the adverbial elements of 'manner' function in clauses may be either partial or non-partial in meaning. In (67) below, it is partial but non-partial in (68).

(67) Jowo ge igi yen [diedie]
please cut tree that little-by-little
'please cut that tree little-by-little'

(78) Jowo ge igi yen [patapata]
please cut tree that completely
'please cut that tree completely'

Adverbial elements of 'degree' function to enable the users of the language to compare things. Two main options are open to users. These are expressed in (69) and (70) respectively:

(69) Dipo ga [ju] Olu
Dipo tall more Olu
'Dipo is taller than Olu'

(70) Dipo ni o ga [julo] ninu gbogbo wa
Dipo FOC. he tall most PREP. all us
'Dipo is the tallest of us'

The causal meaning in a clause is introduced by an adverbial element. Examples are bi (if) and nitori (because) in the following clauses:

(71) [Bi] o ba wa, awa yio wa ni'be
if he AUX. come we AUX. exist there
'if he comes, we will be there'

(72) okunrin naa ko wa [nitoril] iya re ku
man d-d NEG. come because mother his died
'the man did not come because his mother died'

2.3.8 - Conclusion

The criteria of position and function have been used to examine the Adverbial Group in Yoruba. Although the positional criterion has helped to identify adverbs and the adverbials in the language, because of the mobility of these items, a general ordering pattern is given. In terms of function, the adverbs and the adverbials modify words and utterances in order to give different shades of meaning to the particular words and utterances in those contexts of use.

This entire chapter, it must be stressed, is a very brief description of the nominal, verbal, and the adverbial groups in Yoruba.

Notes

1. There is no definition of the nominal group in Halliday 1985 (An Introduction to Functional Grammar) which provides an up-to-date account of this group structure.
2. Nominalisation is not considered relevant to this general description of the nominal group in the study.
3. I must hereby contextualise Awobuluyi's example. He uses it to discuss a series of qualifiers which a noun may have; this includes, essentially, the nominal group and, of course, the clause.
4. This 'Process' expresses the attendant circumstances.
5. 'Range' may also be defined as a set of fairly discrete functional components each with its own meaning potential.
6. The title of the news item is Atamoto N Je'jo Ole (a vehicle-seller who is answering to a charge of theft) in Iroyin Yoruba, Number 8,086 of Wednesday 25 - Tuesday March 3, 1987.
7. There are several examples of NG structured in this way on the pages of the newspaper.
8. One main factor which may support this practice is the prevalence of oral tradition in the literature of the Yoruba people in particular and Africa in general.
9. He (Awobuluyi) claims that such qualifiers express a wide range of concepts such as 'ownership' - owo Dada (Dada's money), 'origin' - omo Oyo (a child from Oyo), 'purpose/use' - obe eran (knife used to cut meat).
10. The bracketed words indicate optional elements.
11. The final sound of the demonstrative bayi must have changed in the string of utterance to bayi i.
12. See Lyons' (1979:93) characterisation of the nominals and pro-nominals in English. His idea of grouping the nominals and pro-nominals as entity-referring expressions, and the locatives and pro-locatives as place-referring expressions is illuminating.
13. Logical relation contributes to the understanding of meaning in language in terms of its being an ordered phenomenon as expressed in chapter one.
14. It seems that Halliday's (1985a:172) view of Multivariate and Univariate structures is different from his earlier view (1977b:177). The publication of 1985a is a further development of the ideas of 1977b.

15. 'How' may be translated also as 'Elo' or 'Melo.' It is translated as 'Bawo' in How does it look? (Bawo ni o se ri?) - Number 26.
16. Culled from Iroyin Yoruba No 8, 086 Wednesday February 25 - Tuesday March 3, 1987, on page 3, Column 2.
17. Odunuga defines formants in Yoruba as 'words that deprived of lexical meanings and used as elements of forms of other words with full lexical meaning.' In the grammatical literature of Yoruba, these formants are often referred to as auxiliary verbs. He feels that 'the latter cannot be correct since auxiliary verbs have their own lexical meaning and could be used independently.
18. Awobuluyi further remarks, without any explanation, that this situation is surprising.
19. In transitivity, meanings of the core elements in the verbal group are referred to as processes. My description of the verbs in the verbal group as processes appeals to the same evidence.
20. Apart from these ones, Halliday also identifies two other participant functions in the English clause which are also specific to each type of process. These are the Beneficiary and the Range (Halliday 1985a:132-137). Range is defined in note (5) above. The Beneficiary is the one to whom the process concerns.
21. 'Doing' or 'doing to' is referred to as the 'Dispositive type' and 'bringing about' is the 'creative type' (Halliday 1985a:104).
22. Hudson (1987:496-497) suggests 'communication' in place of 'verbal' because "the name is perhaps less than ideal as it is intended to cover 'any kind of symbolic exchange of meaning'." He shows this extensive usage of the process by illustrating the Sayer 'I', 'watch' and 'notice' using clauses. This point and these same examples have, however, been clearly made in Halliday (1985a:129-130).
23. The third aspect is the circumstances associated with the process (Halliday 1976:159, 1985a:101^{ff}).
24. Text 2.2.1. is taken from Asa Ibile Yoruba page 4. It is a description of an aspect of the traditional Yoruba wedding ceremony. It concerns the act of bringing the bride into the bridegroom's house.
25. The money, again, is expressed in cowries. This form of monetary system was used before the advent of Europeans to Nigeria.
26. Naira is the country's currency.

27. Odunuga (1982:269) rejects outright the fact that the term auxiliaries is useful because auxiliary verbs have their own lexical meaning.
28. Adewole (1989:1) also does not include the Infinitive [+INF.] in the analysis of the Yoruba auxiliary verbs using the Generalised Phrase Structure Grammar (GPSG) as his theoretical framework.
29. Awobuluyi's interpretation of clauses 1-3 is different; he interprets Ojo lo ri as 'Ojo went there before.' The difference is the addition of 'there' which appears also in 2 and 3. The interpretation I give to them appears more meaningful than Awobuluyi's, given that the clauses are isolated examples, and his interpretation does not have any contextual clue(s) upon which to base the addition of 'there.'
30. Another useful criterion for the classification which I shall not examine here is that of the formation of the adverbs and the adverbials. Adverbs are formed, for example, from adjectives, verbs and nouns. (see Ogunbowale 1970:80-87).
31. Bishop Vidal (Ogunbowale op. cit. p.80) also expresses the view that 'that peculiarity must certainly increase the expressiveness of the language' - that is, Yoruba. He writes: 'Thus, for example, in sentences where we should employ the word very, let the subject of which we are speaking be what it might, Yoruba would express the same meaning with far more definiteness and precision by a separate adverb in each case, no two of which could be used convertibly.' He asserts that 'in order to speak Yoruba correctly, it is necessary to know not only the verb or adjective which expresses what one wants to say, but also the peculiar and appropriate adverbs which denote the degree or quality attached to it since every verb or adjective has its own peculiar adverb to express this characteristic or circumstance.'
32. From the book (Adiitu Olodumare by D. O. Fagunwa) where the clause was taken, Alabapade, the person being called, was unconscious and there was an urgent need to revive him. The method used was to call his name many times.
33. Sa in the modern orthography would be written as saa without any difference either in its grammatical function or its meaning potential.
34. Ti (from) in this usage is different in meaning from ti which has the perfective meaning although both are pronounced and written in the same way.
35. Bo (come) indicates, though inexplicitly, that the subject (o) bought a pair of shoes for the speaker 'from somewhere' (on a trip/journey).

36. He (Awobuluyi) observes further that Ojo nikan ieun is ambiguous in the written form.
37. Abiri (op. cit. p. 39) notes that some adverbs function as nouns in the emphatic construction with the verb ni.
38. I have always retained the old orthography representation wherever it occurs in texts otherwise dada (well) would have been written as either daadaa or daradara, both of which function exactly the same way and mean the same thing.
39. It is translated as thus in A Dictionary of the Yoruba Language page 55.
40. Its superlative is formed by the addition of 'lo' - julo (more than).
41. See Awobuluyi (1978:76)
42. In the modern orthography, would be written as geere.
43. Awobuluyi (1978:76-77) gives several examples of clauses in which the use of preposition ni is either optional or obligatory.
44. Gau (suddenly) by itself seems ideophonic, its sound vividly represents its idea or meaning. However, if reduplicated as gaugau (suddenly suddenly) it becomes emphasised in the clause.
45. ni otito, li otito, l'otito, and ooto, ooto all have the same meaning.
46. see Awobuluyi (1978:101)
47. Ideophones have been discussed briefly in the introductory chapter. Rowlands (1970) observes that Bamgbose's A Grammar of Yoruba includes ideophones in the 'open class of adverbs' which expound the adjunct in the clause structure.
48. These interrogative verbs Nje, se, and bi - are untranslatable according to Awobuluyi (1978:79). I agree substantially with the difficulties in translating these and similar words. There is, however, an inherent so-meaning understanding in these words which re-inforces their interrogative function. This so-meaning interpretation, in several contexts, may further be equated with, for example, as discussed/as already understood' between interlocutors or in written discourse as these could normally be retrieved in the preceding clauses of the text.
49. see note 48 above.

50. Very often the negative word ko, as used here, consists of an inherent subject.
51. see note 50 above.
52. John Victor Singler explores, further than hitherto known, o's geographical range and its function in a specific pidginised aspect of Liberian English.
53. He (Singler) quoted the sentence from a paper written by Ore Yusuf regarding its use specifically in the Yoruba language. The translation of the pronoun him could as well be her/it in the usage.
54. E (you) may be used both as singular or plural in the language depending on the context. It could be used for one person to show respect, and to many people.
55. Text 2.3.6 is taken from Asa Ibile Yoruba, page v.

CHAPTER THREE

REFERENTIAL COHESION

3.0. - Introduction

As indicated in the first chapter, the concept of cohesion accounts for the possibilities inherent in language for making parts of texts 'hang together.' A clause or a sequence of clauses may constitute a text. When a text is more than a clause, each clause has internal structure as well as some particular meaning relations with other clauses. Structure is a grammatical relation which makes parts of a clause or a sentence 'cohere' together, but cohesion explains the external relationships which relate these clauses with one another. Cohesion is not bounded, as a clause is by structure. Being a textual phenomenon, it is not dependent on grammatical structure (Halliday 1985a:287). This 'hanging' or 'linkage,' may occur therefore 'both within the clause and beyond it, without regard to the nature of whatever intervenes' (Halliday 1985a:288). One way in which these possibilities are established in language is through reference and referential cohesion. The referent with which a referential item coheres is, though not exclusively, a property of the nominal group as described in chapter two.

3.1.0 - A General Notion of Reference

The notion of reference in linguistics is manifold.¹ Its central notion points, however, to the capacity of a word to

name or refer (Palmer 1976: 17-24; Lyons 1979: 91).² Reference is certainly a characteristic of all languages as human beings cannot get along without understanding what reference is and using it. Every language must have, therefore, certain items in its system which signal reference. Halliday and Hasan (1976: 32; and Halliday 1985a: 290) suggest that, historically, as language evolved, the reference to 'the thing you see in front of you' evolved earlier than 'the thing I have just mentioned.' This suggestion refers, perhaps, to the distinction between deixis and anaphora which are both referential. In the process, therefore, reference evolved, as it were, because language users needed and still need to direct attention to the other persons, objects and phenomena in their immediate or non-immediate environment.

In the philosophy of language and in linguistic semantics, 'reference' is often contrasted with 'sense' to depict two different but related aspects of meaning. The following definition by Palmer is apt:

"Reference deals with the relation between the linguistic elements, words, sentences, etc., and the non-linguistic world of experience. Sense relates to the complex system of relationships that hold between the linguistic elements themselves (mostly the words); it is concerned only with intralinguistic relations" (1976: 29; see also Lyons 1977a: 174 for 'reference' and page 197 for 'sense').

Reference, then, is an important element of semantics and it is concerned with the relationship between what is both internal and external to language. Internally, it deals with linguistic structure. SPT's ideational metafunction

elucidates the way language is connected to the world through the representation of patterns of experience by reference to participants in clauses and texts ('participants' and 'processes' have been fully discussed in sections on nominal and verbal groups in chapter two). Halliday's use of reference as a cohesive device refers to the way in which participants and processes so introduced are patterned through text.

3.1.1 - The Notion of Reference in SFT

In SFT, the notion of reference is used in a specific sense. Referential items are the items in a language which refer to something else for their interpretation. Reference in texts, Halliday and Hasan argue, sets up a semantic relationship with something in another part of the text which makes a provision for its interpretation to be identical or in contrast with the referent. As 'a participant or circumstantial element' (Halliday 1985a:288) that occurs in one part of the utterance or text, it can be taken as a reference point for something that follows as re-occurring or as a basis for some kind of comparison in an earlier part of the text. It is, therefore, 'primarily a text-forming' phenomenon (Halliday and Hasan 1976:52; Halliday 1977a:189). It contributes a great deal, apart from structure, to the overall comprehensibility and internal cohesion of a text by establishing its texture. The item through certain semantic relation with the referent(s) becomes meaningful because its recoverable meaning does not occur independently.

Potentially reference therefore has a cohesive property in texts, and its text-forming relation is remarkable in two ways. Firstly, through its use, speakers can employ language to speak about things, events and circumstances even if they are not present in the utterance situation, and make other people either speak or act in response. Secondly, it provides the basis for the analysts to speak meaningfully of a referential function of language. Halliday and Hasan succinctly put its textual relevance; that is, reference being a particular kind of cohesion, thus:

"What characterizes this particular type of cohesion, that which we are calling REFERENCE, is the specific nature of the information that is signalled for retrieval. In the case of reference the information to be retrieved is the referential meaning, the identity of the particular thing or class of things that is being referred to; and the cohesion lies in the continuity of reference, whereby the same thing enters into the discourse a second time (1976:31)."

What acts as the pivot for linkage between two messages is a referential tie. Referential ties which occur in various forms in the text maintain 'textual continuity' by creating a relationship in the text of identity of reference referred to as 'co-referentiality' (Halliday and Hasan 1985:73). The relation of co-referentiality is realised or established by the lexico-grammatical devices of reference or what is referred to as 'the implicit encoding device' (Halliday and Hasan 1985:75) or 'grammatical cohesive device' (Hasan 1984b:190). This means that the referent, and the referential item which points to it both share the same property and occur in the same textual environment. They may occur within the clause, and in most cases, inter-clausally in complex sentences (Halliday and Hasan 1976:7-9, 55-56).

Co-referentiality, then, forms the basis of referential cohesion. The messages which emerge from the linkages of the 'term of a tie' are message components. Hence referential cohesive devices form a part of the componential rather than organic devices (Hasan 1984b:187). Meaning relations occurring in clauses and texts, componentially, are established through the cohesive devices of reference, lexical, substitution and ellipsis. Organic devices which are referred to as conjunctives, on the other hand, link whole messages rather than their components (Halliday and Hasan 1985:81). The established componential relations, characteristically, may be patterned in cohesive chains because they are organised sequentially across the text.

3.1.2 - Exophoric and Endophoric Reference

Referential cohesion is signalled in or outside the text by its 'phoric' property - phoric directions. These are two - exophoric or endophoric. Exophora or exophoric reference equates with situational reference, and endophora or endophoric reference equates with reference within the text. Although both types of reference point elsewhere for their interpretation, by situational reference is meant that for an exophoric item reference must be made to the context of situation. Endophoric reference, on the other hand, points to the immediate environment of the text where its referential meaning can be retrieved. Herein lies an explanation for classifying cohesion as belonging to the textual component of the semantic system in SFT terms.

As far as referential cohesion is concerned, only the endophoric reference is cohesive (Halliday and Hasan 1976:37; Halliday 1985a:76). Although exophoric reference contributes to text creation by linking its meaning potential to the context of situation, it fails to contribute substantially to the integration of its content-meaning in the immediate context of situation. The analyst's attention is taken outside the text being analysed. An opaque link between the text and the context is often created in two ways. Firstly, it is often difficult to lay hands on the specific exophoric referent of the relevant context to the text. Secondly, exophora opens the text to manifold interpretations. Exophora, significantly, 'does not necessarily prevent the formation of cohesive ties; and to this extent it does not militate against texture' (Halliday and Hasan 1985:88). An example of such exophoric reference is given below:

Léta tí \o\ fi tú igbimò naa ka
 letter that he use scatter council d-d about
 'the letter for disbanding of the council'

ni a gbo pe gomina funra re
 PREP. we hear that governor PREP. him
 'was, as we heard, signed by the governor himself'

fowósi ki \wón\ to ha fun awon omo igbimò
 sign before they? AUX. distribute PREP. those child council
 'before being distributed to those members of the council'

Text 3.1.1 - Interpreting an Exophoric Item

A brief context of the above text is relevant. It is a newspaper report of a disagreement among members of a traditional council. A letter disbanding the council was signed by the State governor, and copies were distributed to members. There are two personal referential items in the

text. The first one, o, in line one coheres cataphorically with gomina (governor) in the second line. The second one won (they?) in line 3, which refers to the office assistant(s) who distributed the letter, is exophoric because it has no referent in the text. Even though it is exophoric, it is understood because of the situation.

Endophora is further subdivided into two: anaphora and cataphora - in their phoric terms, anaphoric and cataphoric relations. Anaphoric reference points not 'outwards' to the environment of the text, but specifically 'backwards' to the preceding text (Halliday 1985a:291; Halliday and Hasan 1985:76). Functionally and cohesively a listener or a reader has to look elsewhere, that is, back to the referent from what has either been heard or read before. In this process, an anaphoric item forms a link between the two sections of the text. It depicts that the two parts of the texts have some relation - the desired semantic relation.

If the source of the interpretation of the tie follows the linguistic referent, then it is cataphoric. In many languages one may assume generally that the use of anaphoric reference may be greater than that of cataphoric reference. One plausible explanation is that it is explicit to refer to what is gone before. These aspects of discourse are normally a thing, an event or a circumstance. It is difficult to achieve cataphoric reference in a similar way if nothing has been said to which an element would refer. Whenever cohesion is attained, whether anaphoric or cataphoric, the implicit referential item is bound by meaning relation with the

wording of the referent (i.e. the cohesive relation between gomina [governor] and o [he] in Text 3.1.1 above).

3.1.3 - Personal Reference

Of the three kinds of lexico-grammatical elements which form referential devices in texts, the first are the personal pronouns which function within the nominal group to identify function or roles by reference to the speech situation. These roles are those of speaker and addressee. The system of personal reference provides the means of making reference to persons and objects in the speech situation. This is done when it functions either as participant along with the relevant process, or as possessor of certain entities. The first and second person forms are not inherently cohesive because their referents merely define the speech roles of speaker and addressee rather than make reference to text in which they function. In English, these are: 'I', 'you', and 'we.' As a result, they are interpreted exophorically by making reference to the particular speech situation (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 43-52, 48; Ingram 1978: 213-221). The only exception to this pattern occurs in the written language where anaphoric reference may either be realised in quoted speech (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 48-49), or in narrative dialogue (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 50). When it occurs in quoted speech, it is referred to as 'indirect' anaphora (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 49-50). In these instances, the analyst is able to identify the speaker in the text, thereby making the reference endophoric. Certain occurrences of

first and second person grammatical items which are exophoric may, however, provide texture through repetition (Halliday and Hasan 1985: 79).

The third person reference system, on the other hand, does not typically concern itself with the defining of roles as far as the speech situation is concerned. Rather, it defines referential function by the use of the category of person - human and non-human pronominals and possessive determiners as located in its nominal group by forming cohesive devices with what obtains back or forward of the text. It is the third person therefore that is inherently cohesive in texts. When these cohesive devices are repeated, they form a systematic pattern of the particular text. It is indicated by the use of 'he', 'she', 'they', 'it' etc. in English.

The following are examples in Yoruba:

(1) /Ojo/ na omodé kùnrin náà. O lo egba
 Ojo beat child male d-d he uses cane
 'Ojo beat the boy' 'He used a cane'

(2) /Ojo àti bàbá/ rẹ̀ sùn. Nwón sùn di ojó keji
 Ojo and father his sleep they sleep PREP. day two
 'Ojo and his father slept' 'They slept till the second day'

In (1) above, o (he) is the third person singular pronominal. It is co-referential anaphorically with Ojo. This interpretation is implicit in the two clauses even though they are structurally independent of each other. They contain, however, certain particular features of meaning which link them together. That is, referential cohesion is achieved because an element in a clause is only meaningful by

making reference to some other element in a different clause. Ojo then, is the referent and o (he) the referential or the pronominal item. In this case, o (he) is co-referential anaphorically with Ojo, and constitutes an important coding device. In a similar way, nwón (they) in (2), a third person plural pronominal, is co-referential anaphorically with both Ojo and bàbá (father) - a compound nominal group. The following tables show the basic Person Systems in the language.

Number	1st	2nd	3rd
Singular	mo/emi (I)	o/iwo (you)	ó/oun (s/he/it)
Plural	a/awa (we)	eyin/e (you)	awon*/nwón (they)

Table 3.1.3 (1) - Basic Person System in Yoruba

Person	Subject		Object	
	Singular	Plural	Singular	Plural
1st	mo/emi (I)	a/awa (we)	mi (me)	wa (we)
2nd	o/iwo (you)	eyin/e (you)	e/o (you) re (yours)	nyin/yin (you)
3rd	ó/oun (she- /he, it)	nwón (they)	i/u/o/e/e (him her/it) u/i/o/e/e/re (his/hers/its)	won (them)

Table 3.1.3 (2) - Basic Subject-Object System in Yoruba

Some explanations are necessary concerning some of the items on the above Table 3.1.3 (1) and (2). The variants which occur may be graphological (i.e. nyin [you] and yin [you] Table 3.1.3 (2)), phonological and morphological (i.e. i and

g (both it) in ò sí i 's/he/it opens it' and ò gbé e 's/he carries it') in texts.

Awon (they?) (starred in Table 3.1.3 (1) above), is yet to be well described in the language. The function of awon (they), according to Bamgbose (1967:11), is pronominal (i.e. plural pronominal). His example, awon da? (where are they) does not indicate who awon stands for unless it is assumed to be retrievable in the speech situation. Awobuluyi (1978:11-12) describes it as a 'human noun' along with, for example, tisí^a (teacher), and mo (I). This study advances Ogunbowale's (1970:66) classification whereby 'iwònyen, àwòyèn, iwonni, or àwon-ni' are described as 'those.' Although the functions of Awon (those) are varied depending on the context in which it is used, because of its demonstrative potential it is generally translated 'those' in English. An example from Bamgbose (1967:16) may further clarify this position. Describing àwon as a 'neutral' form of 'third person plural pronoun,' he translates àwon tó mò as (i) 'those who know' - (reference to head) and (ii) 'those whom he knows' - (no reference to head). In textual environment, àwon (those) in both translations will be regarded in SFT as substitutive or elliptical. It substitutes for two or more people known to participants in the universe of discourse. Even though the focus of information shifts in (ii) to 'the person who knows them,' the demonstrative function of àwon (see section 3.1.4) in both cases is evident because the participants both share the knowledge of the particular referents to which it refers. In cohesive relation, àwon (those) may function structurally

as subject in elliptical clauses but when it premodifies a noun, it functions as a demonstrative.

Although each of eyin/e (you), nwon (they), awon (those) in Table 3.1.3 (1), and nyin/yin (you), e (s/he, it; him/her) has, grammatically, a plural meaning, each may have, sociologically, singular meaning whenever it is used for a single referent to show deference (Brown and Gilman 1968:260; Kempf 1985:223-224; Wardhaugh 1986:252-256; see also section 1.6 in chapter one,

3.1.4 - Demonstrative Reference

Demonstrative reference is the second type of reference. It is used by the speaker or writer to identify the direction of, and specify the referent whether human or non-human in the textual environment on a scale of proximity. Proximity is typically from the point of view of the speaker - 'nearness', or 'farness' in relation to other persons or objects. As discussed in chapter two (nominal group (2.1.2)), demonstratives function to identify the nearness, farness or neither the nearness or farness of the proximity between the speaker(s) and the addressee(s). Like the personals, demonstratives may be either exophoric (referring to an entity in the context of situation) or endophoric; and when endophoric function cohesively.

Demonstratives used either anaphorically or cataphorically have the potential to refer to part or a whole sentence:

Examples are as follows:

(3) ┌─── (naira mejo, mejila)
 Owó wa ni wònyí. Naira méjo fún búrédi; méjilá fún obè
 money our is these naira eight PREP. bread twelve PREP. sauce
 'These are our monies. Eight naira for bread; twelve for sauce'

(4) (column) (clause) ───┐
 Bí a se n se obè náà. Lehin iyen nkò?
 INT. we AUX. PROG. cook sauce d-d after that INT.
 'how/the way we prepare the sauce. What happens next?'

In example (3) above, wònyí (these), a plural implicit coding device, refers cataphorically only to the monetary part of the clause - naira méjo (eight naira), and naira méjilá (twelve naira), while iyen (that) in (4) is co-referential, anaphorically, with the preceding clause - Bí a se n se obè náà (the way the sauce is prepared).

It may also refer to extended text whose referent(s) may be persons, objects, circumstance or facts as in the following:

(5)

1. Adiitú fere mà iti isoro tan
 Adiitu AUX. ADV. NEG. AUX. ADV. say finish
 'Before Adiitu finished talking'
2. ti enia bi merinlelogun fi jade
 PREP. person like twenty-four AUX. ADV. out
 'about twenty-four people came out'
3. ti nwon mu u
 PREP. they take him
 'they seized him'
4. ti nwon ko owo rè mejeji sehin
 PREP. they gather hand his two-two PREP. back
 'they put his two hands behind him'
5. ti nwon dè e
 PREP. they tie him
 'and they tied him'
6. ti nwon fun u l'ókun dan-in-dan-in
 PREP. they tight him PREP. rope tightly
 'they tied him with the rope very tightly'

7. Lehin eyi, nwon so ogede pupo mo o l'órun
 after this they tie banana many PREP. him PREP. neck
 'after this they tied many bananas to his neck'

Eyi (this) in clause 7 above refers to 'events' or 'facts' concerning what the twenty-four people did to Aditu from clauses 3 - 6.

In a similar way to demonstratives, the definite determiner náà (the) makes definite the referent with which it forms a co-referential relation. As a referential device, it functions within one nominal group to identify a particular entity in another nominal group. The referential relation identified by the definite determiner between the elements which comprise these nominal groups is semantic because they share recognisable properties. Unlike English, the Yoruba language does not have the indefinite form. The nearest to a (indefinite article in English) is kan (one/certain) which is a contracted form of okan (Pry and Ogunbiyi 1950: 136). An example of náà (the) is given:

(6) Biola ní ewà púpù. Omidan /náà/ tún ga
 Biola has beauty much girl d-d AUX.ADV. tall
 'Biola is very beautiful. The girl is also tall'

Náà (the) in the second clause is cohesive referentially with Biola in the first clause because the element omidan (girl) shares some meaning relation with 'Biola.'

The following table contains basic demonstrative devices in the language:

Number	Nearness	Farness	Neutral
Singular	yì/èyì (this)	yen/iyen (that)	òhún (that) nàà (the)
Plural	iwònyí/wònyí (these)	iwònyen/wònyen (those)	àwon (those)

Table 3.1.4 - Basic Demonstratives in the Yoruba

In general each of these demonstratives (Table 3.1.4 above) functions to identify a particular 'Thing' by reference to some kind of proximity to the speaker which may also involve proximity to the addressee. In addition, the items in 'neutral' column require the explicit repetition of the Thing or its subset in order to refer to the specific reference. Nàà (the) functions in the Yoruba language in a similar way to English but it always postmodifies the Thing in Yoruba (see the section on nominal group in chapter two). Although Halliday and Hasan (1976:72) argue that the can never refer forward cohesively in English, Halliday's later analysis (1985:292) shows that it may cohere cataphorically.

3.1.5 - Comparative Reference

Comparative reference, as a kind of textual cohesion, sets up 'a frame of reference' (Halliday 1985a:294) in terms of 'likeness' and 'unlikeness' (Halliday and Hasan 1976:76-77). Unlike personals and demonstratives which set up a relation of co-reference, comparative reference sets up a relation of contrast. Like personals and demonstratives, it may be either anaphoric or cataphoric. This type of reference is

divided into two: general comparative reference and particular comparative reference. The former expresses likeness or otherwise between two things. The identity of its referent may be the same, similar or different but 'without respect to any particular property.' The latter concerns particular property in terms of quality or quantity.

Examples are as follows:

(7)
 Wo igi méji òkè yen. Wòó bí nwón se se gégé
 look tree two hill that look like they AUX. act perfectly
 'Look at the two trees over there. How perfectly they are.'

(8)
 Dipo àti Olu jé omo iyá kan. Sùgbón Dipo ga /ju/ Olu
 Dipo and Olu is child mother one. But Dipo tall more Olu
 'Dipo and Olu have the same mother. But Dipo is taller'

In (7) above, gégé (perfectly) is a general comparative device. The two trees appear perfect if compared with each other but not in any 'particular' way. Ju (more) in (8), on the other hand, is cohesive in a particular way; the height of Dipo and Olu is the focus of comparison.

Class	Function		
	Identity	Similarity	Difference
General	èyiini (that one)	dééde/géégé (perfectly)	òtò (alone)
Particular	tán/parí (worst) jùlo (best)	bákanná (similarly)	Ju (more)

Table 3.1.5 - Basic Comparative Devices in Yoruba

Following the above general introductory paragraphs on reference, I will describe the following types of co-

referential relations in the linguistic system of Yoruba. These cohesive relations emerge from the analysis of several texts which will be presented shortly.

3.1.6 - Types of Co-referential Devices in Yoruba

Seven types of co-referential devices are described. Each of these devices is referred to in SFT as implicit encoding device (Halliday and Hasan 1985:75) because its specific interpretation is dependent on what it is co-referential with in the text. The textual relation thus formed between these two or more elements enables it to function as a cohesive device. The types of these devices in Yoruba from my data are: 'single,' 'contracted,' 'compound,' 'inclusive,' 'partial,' 'dual' and 'cumulative.'

Through these devices, the textual relation also shows that cohesion interacts with register, or specifically, that referential cohesion predicts register. An example is the 'cumulative' type of co-referential device which is USED (sic.) cumulatively to depict referential cohesion in a series of items in scientific (including arithmetic) texts.

Another example is the 'partial' type which may appear to suggest that an implicit cohesive device is partial. I refer to it as 'partial' considering its explicit through the process of interpretation which reveals that the implicit cohesive device is seen as relevant to only a part of the referent (Halliday's idea of 'co-interpretation' in Halliday and Hasan 1976:314; Brown and Yule section 1.5 in chapter one).

I - Single

This is the single and most common type of co-referential device in the language. In its process, a referential item is co-referential with a Thing or Headword in a simple nominal group. Halliday and Hasan (1976:14) refer to its equivalent in English as 'the paradigm case of cohesion from a theoretical point of view' because it functions immediately between two sentences and this 'represents a minimal break in structural continuity.' It is also simpler in practice because it is co-referential to a single nominal group.

(9) /Ojo/ wá ilé wa lánà. (Ojo) " O jeun alé n' íbè
Ojo come house our yesterday he eat supper PREP. there
'Ojo came to our house yesterday. He ate supper there'

O (he) in the second sentence, as a cohesive device, is co-referential with Ojo in the first sentence.

II - Contracted

In some environments, the referential item is contracted or subsumes into another. Contracted types include negated (i.e. kò [NEG.+s/he,it]), verb-inclusive (i.e. l'ó [VB.+s/he/it]) and the conjunction (b'ó [CONJ.+ s/he,it]). Kí is a morphological variant of kò. Lí is also a variant of ló and also the euphonic form of the verb ní which means 'to have.' Bí (CONJ.[or]) is a contraction of 'abi' or 'tabi.' An example of the conjunctive type may be given because it is not prevalent in the data - sé ó n ta é ni à /b'ò/ n dùn é ? (is it pinching you or hurting you?) where b'ó is a combination of 'or' and 'it.'

This type of cohesive device depicts a characteristic feature of the language such that when a word beginning with a vowel is preceded by another word, particularly in speech, one of the two vowels in contact is either assimilated or elided (Bamgbose 1967: 50-53). It is significant, therefore, to distinguish two types of kò - one, which functions purely as a negating element, and second, as a cohesive device. It functions as a negator, for example, in Bàbá kò wà (father did/does NEG. come). In kò sàré (s/he/it did/does NEG. run), however, it is a combination of kò and the pronominal ò (s/he, it), or rather, ò is subsumed in kò. This may become vivid when ò sàré is seen as functioning to mean 'S/he/it runs/ran.'

The contracted symbol may or may not be indicated graphologically. It is not indicated, for example, as other tone marks, in the newspapers. The following example is, however, contracted:

(10) (Ojo) " ———
 Ojo wá lánà. Nse l'ò je óúnje ilé tán
 Ojo come yesterday indeed VB. +he eat food house finish
 'Ojo came yesterday. He indeed finished all the food in the house'

L'ò (VB. +he) in the second sentence, though contracted, still refers to 'Ojo.' The verbal element forming part of the contraction does not play any role in the co-referentiality. Even though negation may introduce a negated meaning into the clause, it is the pronominal aspect of it that is co-referential. Contracted cohesive device, more importantly, is always co-referential with a single referent functioning in a nominal group.

III - Compound

A compound cohesive device functions to emphasise a particular point of view in the clause. It consists of two cohesive devices which are simultaneously co-referential with a particular referent functioning, usually, in a nominal group with two items.

(11) (Ilé wònyí) " " " "
/Ilé wònyí/ tóbi púpò. Ita /àwon/ ilé /náà/ dára
house these big many outside those house d-d beautiful
'These houses are very big. The exterior of those very houses are beautiful'

In (11) above, both àwon (those) and náà (the) simultaneously emphasise the referent with which they are co-referential in the preceding clause. It functions in the very way that any two of these - 'the,' 'very,' 'particular' occur in an English sentence to specify certain referents or entities.

IV - Inclusive

This type occurs when a particular implicit referential device does not correspond grammatically with its referent. Even though the referent is usually singular and the corresponding referential device is plural, the usage is not ungrammatical. Rather, it is culturally meaningful. For example:

(12) (bàbá) " " " "
/Bàbá/ mi lo sí oko. Nwon kò ni pé dé
father my go PREP. farm they NEG. is delay come
'my father went to the farm. (he?) will come back soon'

Nwon (they?) in (12) above is a plural implicit cohesive device which grammatically is discordant with bàbá (father), as a singular referent. In the linguistic culture,

nevertheless, it is meaningful because it shows deference. It is an affront for a child, for example, to use a singular referential item for his or her parents or anyone markedly older in any linguistic communication (formal or informal). The implicit cohesive device is thus operating inclusive (taking another factor into account) because a particular culture-specific meaning is encoded (see Levinson's 'honorific concord' section 1.6).

V - Partial

By partial implicit cohesive device, it is meant that the referential item does not completely cohere with the referent. A kind of mediation must have occurred in the user's choice of making reference to just a part or an aspect of the referent. This categorisation draws attention to Brown and Yule's criticism of co-referentiality which I have attempted to respond to in chapter one (section 1.5.). It concerns the explicitness of the meaning relations which hold between items in a text and its expression. Partial cohesive device shows that it is not in all cases that the items forming a bond of co-referentiality are completely uniform - that is, forming an explicit bonding.

(13) Mo ra /àgbàdo/ orísi méjì. /Pupa yen/ ni ó dára jù
 I buy maize different two red that is it good more
 'I bought two types of maize. That red type is better'

The referent in the first clause is àgbàdo (maize). Although the maize consists of at least two types (red and another unspecified colour), the referential item yen (that) is co-referential ONLY (sic.) with the red subtype. There is a kind

of mediation between the referent and its referential device. The referential relation or meaning between the referent and its referential item is, therefore, evidently partial - yen (that) specifying the subset from the perspective of colour.

VI - Dual

A dual device is co-referential simultaneously with two referents. It is both anaphoric and cataphoric.

(14) X- Dárúko /omobirin/ tí ^(omobirin) ò dúró ^{«—|—»} yen. /0/ ga báyi ^(Radeyo)
 name girl that she stand that she tall this
 'Name that girl that is standing. She is tall like this'

(15) Y- /Radeyo/ ni
 Radeyo is
 'She is Radeyo'

In (14) above, ó (she) is anaphorically co-referential with omobirin (girl) in the first clause, and in the textual dialogic situation, it is co-referential, cataphorically, with Radeyo in clause 15. The first referent depicts sex - omobirin (girl); the second supplies her name. Even though a single cohesive device, it is co-referential simultaneously with two referents, each in a different nominal group.

VII - Cumulative

A cumulative cohesive device is used cumulatively and is co-referential with a list of referents. As a result, it is always plural in form. For example:

(16) Apapò ohun tí a rà ni wònyí. Owò /isu náírà méwà/,
 total thing that we buy is these money yam naira ten
 'The total of things we bought is this. Cost of yam
 (isu náírà méwà...)

/ata náirà méjì/; gbogbo rẹ̀ jẹ́ /náirà méjìlá/
pepper naira two all it is naira twelve
ten naira, pepper two naira; their total is twelve naira'

In (16) above, the plural cumulative device -wònyì (these) is co-referential with the foodstuffs and their prices. Although this example concerns the social activity of buying and selling, this type of cohesive device functions more in arithmetic and scientific texts. As a cumulative cohesive device, its referent often functions in complex nominal groups in phrases and clauses as in the above example -owó isu náirà méwà (cost of yam ten naira), ata náirà méjì (pepper two naira) and gbogbo rẹ̀ jẹ́ náirà méjìlá (their total is twelve naira). The first two contain four and three items in their nominal groups respectively, and the last a full clause consisting of two different nominal group.

3.1.7 - Notion of Referential Chains

The types of cohesive devices that I have described above are further exemplified in the following texts. The relevant nominal groups in the text will be identified using a slash on each side, and the phoric direction of the ties towards the referents will be shown.

More importantly, the formations of the cohesive chains will be described as they build up in each of the texts. Referential cohesive chains formed by cohesive devices, delineate the patterns of the sequential organisation of cohesive ties and generate cohesive forces in texts (a fuller account of cohesive chain is found in chapter five on

Cohesive Harmony). The organisation of these ties may also show differences in texts. The relative density of cohesive ties and their kinds across the different genres being used may be predictive of one type of reference or another. Two texts of each of seven genres are examined in order to be able to establish a fairly reliable finding. It seems essential, however, to take account of exophoric reference whenever it occurs if only to relate it to, and contrast it with the endophoric reference. That approach does not mean de-emphasising the main priority - its endophoric perspective, but because exophoric reference may also contribute to texture.

In examining the following texts from different genres, the following symbols are used in this section:

PER: Personal	CUL: Cumulative
DEM: Demonstrative	PAR: Partial
COMP: Comparative	DUA: Dual
EXT: Extended	INC: Inclusive
REF: Reference	CON: Contracted

```

“\ \ == anaphoric }
      }
      } endophoric
/ / == cataphoric }
i == exophoric }
i | == Firstly exophoric; but later cataphoric } In
      } texts
“| == Both anaphoric and cataphoric }
? == arguable/questionable
| == anaphoric }
      } In chains
| == cataphoric }
  
```

The Cohesive Devices (CD) in Text 3.1.8 are presented in Table 3.5 below: These are organised under the following six headings:

- (i) CLAUSE NUMBER (CN)
- (ii) NUMBER OF TIE(S) (NT)
- (iii) IMPLICIT ENCODING DEVICE (IED)
- (iv) TYPE OF REFERENCE and PHORIC DIRECTION (TR/PD)
- (v) DISTANCE (D)
- (vi) PRESUPPOSED ITEM(S) and LOCATION (PIL)

Clause rather than sentence division is used in this work.

Clause Number (CN) identifies the tie as organised in the Text.

Number of Tie(s) (NT) is the number of tie(s) which occur in a clause.

Implicit Encoding Device (IED) is the referential which is linked relationally with a referent - anaphorically or cataphorically.

Type of Reference (TR) means any of 'personal,' 'demonstrative' (and determiner), and 'comparative.'

The Phoric Direction (PD) will be always regarded as anaphoric unless otherwise identified (i.e. C is used to indicate cataphoric cohesive relation after the type of reference has been indicated; and where it is both, A/C will be used etc.).

Distance (D) relates to the relation between the referential item and the referent in terms of proximity. This is shown for each implicit cohesive device in a text (e.g. Table 3.1.7 (1) column 5). When it is contiguous - immediately following the referent in the next clause, it is indicated as 0. To indicate that the referent occurs earlier, it is marked 0+. When the distance between the two is mediated by relevant intervening clauses, it is marked M with the number of intervening clauses (i.e. M.2). When the mediated distance does not contain relevant clauses, it is marked N also with the number of intervening clauses indicated (i.e. N.4).

The Locative (L) position of the Presupposed Item (PI) is indicated by the addition of the clause number to the particular referent (Presupposed Item).

3.3 - Narrative Texts

This short text is taken from a popular story. It is a description of an aspect of farm life - the season when hedgehogs destroy the corn fields. Some farmers set traps to catch a few of these hedgehogs while the rest of them, on seeing some caught, look for other farms to destroy.

Text 3.1.0³

1. Nigbati o di oju ale
when it is eye night
'when it was late at night'
2. mo pada wa si abà wa
I back come PREP. hut our
'I came back to our hut'
3. mo lo si odo /egbon/ mi agba okunrin
I go PREP. place elder my older male
'I went to my elder brother's place'
4. ti o je omo iya baba mi
PERF who is child mother father my
'who is my father's brother (i.e. uncle)⁴

- (egbon. 3) “┘
5. mo wi fun \u\ pe
PER
I say PREP. him that
'I said to him that'
 6. mo nfe de /takute/
I PROG. want set trap
'I want to set a trap'

- “┘ (egbon. 3)
7. \ó\ si gbe okan fun mi
PER
he then carry one PREP. me
'he then gave one to me'

- “┘ (takute. 6)
8. mo gbe \e\ lo si inu oko wa
PER
I carry it go PREP. inside farm our
'I carried it into our farm'

9. ni inu (takute. 6) "┌
 agbado, mo de \e\ si
 PER
 in PREP. maize I set it PREP.
 'inside the maize-plot and I set it on'
10. oju ona /awon òyà/ ti nje agbado wa
 eye path those hedgehog that PROG. eat maize our
 'the track of those hedgehogs that eat our maize'
11. nigbati o di owuro ojo keji
 when it is morning day two
 'in the morning of the second day'
12. (takute. 6) "┌
 takute \na\ kò ré
 DEM
 trap d-d NEG. spring
 'the trap did not spring' (i.e. go off)
13. (awon oya. 10) "┌
 nitori biotilejepe \awon\ òyà wa pa agbado
 DEM
 even though those hedgehog come kill maize
 'even though those hedgehogs came to destroy the maize'
14. (awon oya. 10) "┌
 \nwon\ kò rin si /oju takute mi/
 PER
 they NEG. walk PREP. eye trap my
 'they did not come to where my trap was'
15. sugbon nigbati o di owuro ojo keta
 but when it is morning day three
 'but in the morning of the third day'
16. (takute. 6) "┌
 ti mo lo wo \o\
 PER
 that I go look it
 'that I went to look at it'
17. (takute. 6) "┌ (takute. 6) "┌
 mo ri \i\ pe \o\ ti ré
 PER PER
 I see it that it PERF. spring
 'I saw that it, that is the trap, has sprung'
18. (takute. 6) "┌
 \o\ ti mu oya ni apa
 PER
 it PERF. hold hedgehog PREP. arm
 'it has held a hedgehog by the arm'

«— (takute. 6)
 19. \o\ ti ge apa oya
 PER
 it PERF. cut arm hedgehog
 'it has cut the hedgehog's arm'

(oya. 10) «—
 20. eranko \na\ si ti gbe kukute iyoku lo
 DEM
 animal d-d (SEW) PERF. carry stump remain away
 'the animal has run away with only the stump of its arm'

The cohesive devices in Text 3.1.0. are thus organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
5	1	u (him)	P	M. 1	egbon mi (my elder). 3
7	1	o (he)	P	N. 3	egbon mi (my elder). 3
8	1	e (it)	P	M. 1	takute (trap). 6
9	1	e (it)	P	M. 2	takute (trap). 6
12	1	naa (the)	D	N. 6	takute naa (the trap). 6
13	1	awon (those)	D	N. 2	awon oya (those hedgehogs). 10
14	1	nwon (they)	P	N. 3	awon oya (those hedgehogs). 10
16	1	o (it)	P	N. 1+	takute mi (my trap). 14
17	2	i (it)	P	N. 2+	takute mi (my trap). 14
		o (it)	P	N. 2+	takute mi (my trap). 14
18	1	o (it)	P	N. 3+	takute mi (my trap). 14
19	1	o (it)	P	N. 4+	takute mi (my trap). 14
20	2	na (the)	D	0+	oya (hedgehog). 19

Table 3.1.7 (1) Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.0

The above Table 3.1.7 (1) shows the syntagmatic relation of Text 3.1.0. A detailed characterisation of each cohesive device is given from its source to the presupposed item. Takute (trap) which occurs eight times in the text, for example, is shown against the variants of personal tie.

A graphic display of the cohesive chains will show the paradigmatic relation in the text:

Table 3.1.7 (2) - Chain Relations in Text 3.1.0

The above chains are formed by referential devices which realise the relation of co-referentiality with their source elements (the base element of the chain). They also share the same situational referent with these source elements.

There are 3 chains in the text. The first one has egbon (elder (i. e. brother)) as its base element and consists of only personal cohesive ties. The second one has takute (trap) as base. With the exception of one definite referential tie in clause 12, it consists of personal ties all of which are

variants of ò (it).

The third has awon oya (those hedgehogs), a nominal group consisting of two elements as its source element and one of each demonstrative, personal and definite article ties. Unlike the source elements of the first two chains which are not made specific by a demonstrative item, and hence consist mainly of personal ties, the third chain has three types of referential ties.

The text is a first person narrative so there are repeated occurrences of first person pronoun mo (I) (which Awobuluyi calls polymorphic noun 1978:22^{ff})⁵ beginning from clause 2 to 8 and 16 to 17. Although these items are exophoric, it cannot be said that they are irrelevant in the text. They appear to provide some kind of cohesion and, obviously, some texture through repetition (Halliday and Hasan 1985:79).

Text 3.1.1⁶

This text is also taken from a popular fiction story book. It describes the punishment given to Adiitu, the main character, by twenty-four other people. Adiitu is beaten, and made to dance so as to ridicule him.

1. /Adiitú/ fere mà iti isoro tan
Adiitu AUX.ADV. NEG. AUX.ADV. say finish
'Before Adiitu finished talking'
2. ti /enia bi merinlelogun/ fi jade
PREP. person like twenty-four AUX.ADV. out
'about twenty-four people came out'
- (24 persons. 2) «— (Adiitu. 1) «—
3. ti \nwon\ mu \u\
PER PER
PREP. they take him
'they seized him'

(24 persons. 2) «— (Adiitu. 1) «—
 4. ti \nwon\ ko owo \rè\ mejeji sehin
 PER PER
 PREP. they gather hand his two-two PREP. back
 'they put his two hands behind him'

(24 persons. 2) «— (Adiitu. 1) «—
 5. ti \nwon\ dè \e\
 PER PER
 PREP. they tie him
 'and they tied him'

6. ti \nwon\ fun \u\ l'ókun dan-in-dan-in
 PER PER
 PREP. they tight him PREP. rope tightly
 'they tied him with the rope very tightly'

(clauses 3-6) «— (24 persons. 2) (Adiitu. 1) «—
 7. Lehin \eyi\, \nwon\ so ogede pupo mo \o\ l'órun
 DEM PER PER
 after this they tie banana many PREP. him PREP. neck
 'after this they tied many bananas to his neck'

(24 persons. 2) «— (Adiitu. 1) «—
 8. \nwon\ ti \i\ siwaju
 PER PER
 they push him PREP. forward
 'they pushed him forward'

«— (24 persons. 2)
 9. gbogbo \won\ kó pasan lowo
 PER
 all them carry whip PREP. hand
 'all of them held whips in their hands'

«— (24 persons. 2) «— (Adiitu. 1) «— (24 persons. 2)
 10. \nwon\ nna \a\ bi \nwon\ ti nlo
 PER PER PER
 they PROG. beat him as they (SEW) PROG. go
 'they were beating him as they went'

(24 persons. 2) «— (Adiitu. 1) «—
 11. Igbati o se, \nwon\ beresi /korin/ tele \e\
 PER PER PER
 after (SEW) happen they start sing follow him
 'After a time, they began to sing as they followed him'

(korin. 11) «—
 12. Enikan ni o nda orin \na\...⁷
 DEM
 person is who PROG. begin song d-d
 'One person began a particular song'

(24 persons. 2) «—
 13. Igbati o pe die ti \nwon\ ti nlo
 PER
 after (SEW) long little PREP. they PERF. PROG. go
 'after they had gone along for a while'

(24 persons. 2) (24 persons. 2)
 14. ni \nwon\ dede duro ti \nwon\ beresi patewo
 PER PER
 that they suddenly stop PREP. they start PREP. clap
 'they suddenly stopped and began to clap (i. e. hands)'

(24 persons. 2)
 15. ti \nwon\ ni ki Adiitú ma jo
 PER
 PREP. they say that Adiitu AUX. VB. dance
 'they said that Adiitu should start dancing'

(Adiitu. 1)
 16. kò fe lati jo rara
 CON
 NEG. +he want PREP. dance at all
 'he did not want to dance at all'

(24 persons. 2) (Adiitu. 1) (Adiitu. 1)
 17. sugbon nigbati \nwon\ kó pasan bo \o\
 PER PER
 but when they carry whip cover him
 'but when they started to beat him'

(Adiitu. 1)
 18. werewere l'o njo
 CON
 immediately is+he PROG. dance
 'he started dancing immediately'

(Adiitu. 1)
 19. ti \on\ ti omi ti o nsan
 PER
 PREP. he PREP. water that (SEW) PROG. flow
 'as tears began to flow'

20. bi àgbàrá ojo loju
 like torrent rain PREP. eye
 'like a torrent of rain on his face'

The cohesive devices in Text 3.1.1 are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
3	2	nwon (they)	P	0	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
		u (him)	P	M. 1	Adiitu. 1
4	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 2	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
		re (his)	P	M. 2	Adiitu. 1
5	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 3	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
		e (him)	P	M. 3	Adiitu. 1
6	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 4	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)

7	3	u (him)	P	M. 4	Adiitu. 1
		eyi (this)	D	M. 4	EXT. REF. (3 - 6)
		nwon (they)	P	M. 5	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
8	2	o (him)	P	M. 5	Adiitu. 1
		nwon (they)	P	M. 6	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
9	1	i (him)	P	M. 6	Adiitu. 1
		won (them)	P	M. 7	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
10	3	nwon (they)	P	M. 8	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
		a (him)	P	M. 8	Adiitu. 1
		nwon (they)	P	M. 8	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
11	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 9	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
		e (him)	P	M. 9	Adiitu. 1
12	1	na (the)	D	0	korin. 11 (sing)
13	1	nwon (they)	P	M. 10	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
14	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 11	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
		nwon (they)	P	M. 11	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
15	1	nwon (they)	P	M. 12	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
16	1	kò (NEG. +he)	CON	0+	Adiitu. 15
17	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 13	enia bi merinlelogun. 2 (twenty-four persons)
		o (him)	P	M. 1+	Adiitu. 15
18	1	l'o (is+he)	CON	M. 2+	Adiitu. 15
19	1	on (he)	P	M. 3+	Adiitu. 15

Table 3.1.7 (3) Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.1.

Clauses 16 and 18 in the above Table 3.1.7 (2) have contracted cohesive devices kò (NEG. +he) and l'o (VB. +he) respectively. These have personal co-referential meanings. L'o's (VB. + he) of verb to pronominal is different from the contracted of he's in English.

The figures show that the distance of the source referents to their implicit cohesive devices in clauses 13-17 appears large, but these do not hinder their cohesive force because there are identical intervening referents.

The following is the graphic display of the cohesive chains in Text 3.1.1:

Table 3.1.7 (4) - Chain Relations in Text 3.1.1

There are two chains (I & II) and two ties (III & IV) in Text 3.1.1. Since a tie is a single occurrence of cohesive

relation with the base element, a chain must consist of at least two ties.

The segments of the two chains seem to characterise or predict the nature of the text. To the source elements enia bi merinlelogun (about twenty-four persons) - (a phrasal nominal group) and Adiitu (a single nominal group) are attached a series of almost uniformly implicit cohesive devices. These implicit encoding devices are personal references - plural and singular respectively. Being a third person narration, unlike the first person technique in Text 3.1.0, the text does not have a single instance of first person pronoun but several instances of third person pronouns.

In chain II, the plural pronominal nwon (they) is used throughout the text except in clause 9 where its possessive variant won (them) is used. Chain I is, however, different in which a series of, and different singular pronominals are used to refer to the same referent. Except for rè (his), kò (NEG. +he), l'o (VB. +he) and on⁸ in clauses 4, 15, 18 and 19 respectively, all the other pronominals in the chain are morphophonologically conditioned. This means that the choice of each allomorph is phonologically conditioned.⁹ Two single ties occur: numbers III and IV.

Text 3.1.0 is a first person narrative. The narrator¹⁰ constantly refers to himself in relation to the other characters and materials in the text. That is the reason why, even though we have identified twenty clauses as in text

3.1.1, the number of the endophoric ties (all of which are anaphoric) are fourteen compared with twenty-nine in Text 3.1.1. Text 3.1.1 is a third person narrative. It appears more coherent topically because the ties are mainly co-referential with the two main referents in the text - Adiiitu and the twenty-four persons forming a front against Adiiitu. Halliday and Hasan's view (section 3.1.3 above) that the first and the second persons relate to speech roles thus become evident; that is, they merely define the speech roles of speaker and addressee rather than make reference to the text in which they function.

3.4 - Newspaper Texts

Text 3.1.2 ¹¹

The text is a newspaper report concerning a misunderstanding among the traditional rulers in Oyo State Council of Obas and Chiefs. The Governor of the State in an attempt to resolve the dispute disbands the Council. The tones are not indicated on the vowels in newspapers.

1. l'ehin awuyewuye ti ko l'afiwe
after secret talks that NEG. compare
'after a series of unprecedented complaints'
 2. ati wahala ija fun eto ara eni
and trouble fight PREP. right body self
'and trouble concerning citizens' rights'
 3. pelu iwa tenbelekun to fa oro kotu l'ese
with conduct rebellion that cause word court PREP. leg
'together with a rebellion that eventually ended in court'
 4. /Gomina Adetunji Olurin/ tu /Igbimo/
Governor Adetunji Olurin break council
'Governor Adetunji Olurin disbanded the council'
 5. /l'obaloba/ Ipinle Oyo ka ni /ijefa/
PREP. king king state Oyo scatter PREP. six days ago
'of the traditional rulers in Oyo State six days ago'
- (ijefa. 5) ← (Gomina. 4) ←
6. Ni ojo \naa\ gan an \lo\ si
DEM CON -PER
PREP. day d-d precisely (is + he) likewise
'on the day, precisely, he likewise'
- (igbimo l'obaloba. 4-5) ←
7. ti fi iwe atuka igbimo \naa\ s'owo
DEM
PERF. send book break up council d-d PREP. hand
'sent letters concerning the disbandment of the council'
- (l'obaloba. 7) ←
8. si okookan \awon\ oba alaye
DEM.
PREP. one-one those king owner-of-earth
'to each of His Highnesses;'

- (igbimo l'obaloba.7) «— (l'obaloba.8) «—
 9. to je omo igbimo \ohun\ ni aafin \won\ gbogbo
 DEM PER
 that is child council that PREP. palace them all
 'who is a member of that council, in their palaces'
- (Gomina.4) «— «—(Gomina.4)
 10. Gegebi alaye \re\, \o\ ni sise bee
 PER PER
 according explanation his, he say to do so
 'According to his explanation, his taking such a step'
11. di dandan l'atari /awuyewuye/ ati
 become necessary because complaints and
 'became necessary because of the complaints and'
12. rogbodyan enu loolo yi i
 trouble PREP. lately this
 'the troubles in the recent past'
- «— (awuyewuye.11, rogbodyan.12)
 13. /eyi i/ to mu ki wahala isakoso
 DEM
 that PERF. take (SEW) trouble governance
 'that has made the problem of governing'
- «—(l'obaloba.9)
 14. igbimo \naa\ di oro ile ejo giga
 DEM
 council d-d become word house court high
 'and the problem of the council, into a court issue'
15. Ogagun Olurin tun s'alaye pe
 military person Olurin AUX. ADV. explain that
 'Captain Olurin also explained that'
16. titi ti ijoba yoo fi se ikede
 until (SEW) government AUX. VB. make do announcement
 'until the government makes an announcement'
- (l'obaloba.14) «—
 17. lori i atunto igbimo \naa\
 DEM
 PREP. reconstitute council d-d
 'on the reconstituted council'
- «— (Gomina.14)
 18. \oun\ yoo maa fi ikunlukun pelu
 he AUX. VB₁ AUX. VB₂ use stomach-stomach PREP.
 'he would always consult with'
- «—(igbimo.17) «—(igbimo l'obaloba.17)
 19. okookan \awon\ omo igbimo \ohun\
 DEM DEM
 one-one those child council that
 'one or more of those members of that council'

20. l'ori iyowu to ba je mo adugbo \won\
 (l'obaloba. 19) ←
 PREP. whatever that PRE. VB relate PREP. area them
 'on whatever concerns their areas of jurisdiction'

The cohesive devices in Text 3.1.2 are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
6	2	naa (the)	D	0	ijefa .5 (six days ago)
7	1	lo (is+he) naa the)	CON D	M. 1 M. 1.5	Gomina Adetunji Olurin. 4 Igbimo l'obaloba. 4-5 (king's council)
8	1	awon (those)	D	0	igbimo naa. 7 (the council)
9	2	ohun (that) won (them)	D P	M. 1 0	igbimo naa. 7 (the council) awon oba alaye. 8 (His Highnesses)
10	2	re (his) o (he)	P P	M. 5 M. 5	Gomina Adetunji Olurin. 4 Gomina Adetunji Olurin. 4
13	1	eyi i (that)	D	0+	rogbodyan. 12 (trouble) awuyewuye. 11 (complaints)
14	1	naa (the)	D	M. 4+	igbimo ohun . 9 (that council)
17	1	naa (the)	D	M. 2+	igbimo naa. 14 (the council)
18	1	oun (he)	P	M. 2+	Ogagun Olurin. 14 (military/Olurin)
19	2	awon (those) ohun (that)	D D	N. 9 M. 1	igbimo naa. 17 (the council) igbimo naa. 17 (the council)
20	1	won (them)	P	0	igbimo ohun. 19 (that council)

Table 3.1.7 (5) - Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.2

Being a newspaper text, the contracted cohesive device lo (VB.+he) in clause 6 does not feature the contracted symbol. Significantly, from the newspaper style, it appears that this type of tie is gradually losing its normal contraction symbol - l'o (vb.+he) to become a full-fledged o (he) rather than feature as an inclusive word consisting of a verb and a pronominal.¹² Ohun (that) (which would be written as òhún [i.e. unmarked tones] were it not in a newspaper) occurs

twice in the text. Earlier in this chapter in Table 3.1.4. òhún (that) is categorised as a neutral demonstrative.¹³ This is because it also shares some characteristics with the determiner (Halliday and Hasan 1976:58). In clause 9, it occurs alone but in clause 19 it functions along with awon (those) to make up a four-element nominal group to form a compound cohesive device specifying omo igbimo (members of the council) [/awon/ omo igbimo /ohun/]. Ohun (that) in clause 19, postmodifies the compound head omo igbimo (member(s) of the council), and awon (those) premodifies it. Both the premodifier and the postmodifier are implicitly co-referential anaphorically, with igbimo naa (the council) in clause 17. Each compound cohesive occurs within a minimally possible distance from each other in terms of proximity to the Head that they modify. They not only modify the same Thing/Head, they also share the same referent. Being a compound cohesive device the meaning that they jointly express extends beyond what each of them may express - awon (those) identifies the referent in context proximally, while òhún (that) 'specifies' it.

Below is the graphic display of the cohesive chains Text 3.1.2:

Table 3.1.7 (6) - Cohesive Relations in Text 3.1.2

There are three chains (II - IV) in the text and two ties (I & V). The chains have gomina (governor), iqbimo (council) and l'obaloba (PREP.king king) as base elements. All the cohesive devices cohering with gomina (governor) are personal reference; those of iqbimo (council) are demonstratives and l'obaloba (PREP.king king) a mixture of personal and demonstrative reference.

It is significant perhaps to note that yi i (this)¹⁴ in clause 12 is structural (it merely modifies loolo (lately)), while eyi i (that) in clause 13 is cohesive with awuyewuye (complaints) in clause 11.

Text 3.1.3¹⁵

This text is from a different newspaper on the dispute among the traditional rulers in Oyo State. Like the last newspaper text, it does not have any tone placement.

1. /Igbimo//awon loba/ ati ijoye /Ipinle Oyo/
council those king king and chief state Oyo
'The Oyo State Council of Kings and Chiefs'

(Gomina. 3)

2. ni /wonti (?) /¹⁶ tuka lopin ose ti o koja
PER
ia they PERF. scatter vb. +end week PREP. it pass
'has been disbanded at the end of last week'

(ipinle Oyo) «—

3. Gomina Ipinle \naa\, Ogagun Adetunji Olurin
DEM
governor state d-d Captain Adetunji Olurin
'the governor of the State Captain Adetunji Olurin'

(lobaloba. 1) «—

4. ni o tu igbimo \naa\ ka¹⁷
DEM
PREP. who scatter council d-d about
'was the one who disbanded the council'

(tu-ka. 4) «—

5. Ituka \naa\ mu orisirisi /ariyanjiyan/
DEM
scattering d-d cause different dispute
'the disbandment brought the different disputes'

6. ti o ti nja ranyin nile lati
that it PERF. PROG. strive sometime ground since
'which have been going on for some time'

7. nkan bi i osu melokan seyin wa sopin
about like month few back come PREP. end
'a few months, to an end'

«—(ariyanjiyan. 5) «—(ariyanjiyan. 5)

8. \Awon\ ede-aiyede \naa\ ni eyiti o
DEM DEM
those misunderstanding d-d PREP which it
'those misunderstandings are the the ones which'

(igbimo. 4) «—

9. jemo ti alaga igbimo \naa\ laarin
DEM
concern PREP. chairman council d-d among
'concern the chairmanship of the council among'

«—(lobaloba. 1)

(lobaloba. 1) «—

10. \awon\ oba eyiti o si ti mu \awon\
DEM DEM
those king which it (SEW) PERF. cause those
'those kings and which has caused'

- (ipinle. 3) «—
11. oba ipinle \naa\ pin si wewe
DEM
king state d-d divide PREP. small
'divisions among the kings of the State'
- (awon oba. 10-11) «—
12. ti o tun mu \awon\ kan laarin
DEM
that it AUX. ADV. cause those one among
'which also caused a sub-group (i.e. a faction) among'
- «— (awon oba. 10-11) «— (ipinle Oyo. 11)
13. \awon\ oba ipinle \naa\ wo ara
DEM DEM
those king state d-d drag body
'those kings in the state to drag'
- «— (oba. 10-11)
14. \won\ lo sile ejo
PER
them go PREP. house case
'one another into court'
- (Gomina. 3 «— (igbimo. 9) «—
15. Leta ti \won\ fi tu igbimo \naa\ ka
PER DEM
letter that they use scatter council d-d about
'the letter for the disbandment of the council'
- (Adetunji Olurin. 3) «—
16. ni a gbo pe gomina funra \re\
PER
PREP. we hear that governor PREP. self him
'was, as we heard, the governor himself'
- i (lobaloba. 15) «—
17. fowosi ki won to ha fun \awon\
sign before they AUX. distribute PREP. those
'signed before being distributed to those'
- (igbimo llobaloba. 15) «—
18. omo egbe igbimo \naa\
child member council d-d
'members of the council'
19. gegebi Gboungboun ti gbo
as Gboungboun PERF. hear
'as reported by Gboungboun'

The cohesive devices in the above text are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
2	1	won (they) [from wonti]	P - C INC.	0	Ogagun Adetunji Olurin. 3 (Capt. Adetunji Olurin)

3	1	naa (the)	D	M.1 Ipinle Oyo.1 (Oyo State)
4	1	naa (the)	D	M.2 igbimo awon loba.1 (council of kings)
5	1	naa (the)	D	Ø tu-ka.4 (scatter)
8	2	awon (those)	D	M.2 ariyanjiyan.5 (dispute)
		naa (the)	D	M.2 ariyanjiyan.5 (dispute)
9	1	naa (the)	D	M.4 igbimo naa.4 (the council)
10	2	awon (those)	D	Ø igbimo naa.9 (the council)
		awon (those)	D	Ø igbimo naa.9 (the council)
11	1	naa (the)	D	N.7 ipinle naa.3 (the State)
12	1	awon (those)	D- PAR.	Ø awon oba.10-11(those kings)
13	2	awon (those)	D	M.1 awon oba.10-11 (those kings)
		naa (the)	D	M.1 ipinle naa.11 (the state)
14	1	won (them)	P	Ø awon oba.13 (those kings)
15	2	won (them)	P-INC.	N.11 Ogagun Adetunji Olurin.3 (Capt. Adetunji Olurin)
		naa (the)	D	N.5 igbimo naa.9(the council)
16	1	re (him)	P	N.12 Ogagun Adetunji Olurin.3 (Capt. Adetunji Olurin)
17	1	awon (those)	D	N.1 igbimo naa.15(the council)
18	1	naa (the)	D	N.8 igbimo naa.15(the council)

Table 3.1.7 (7) - Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.3.

Some significant features emerge from this second newspaper text. Wonti¹⁸ (they +ti(PERF.)) in line two is a cataphoric tie. It appears an exophoric referent until the reader moves ahead to lines 3-4 and realises that it is co-referential, cataphorically, with gomina (governor). Tuka (scatter) as a material process occurs in line 2 as one item but 'split' as tu-ka in line 4 and 15.

Two types of implicit cohesive devices which have already been illustrated above (section 3.1.6) may be exemplified from the text. These are the inclusive (INC.) and the partial (PAR.). Won(they?) of wonti (they + ti (PERF.)) in lines 2 and 15 both refer to gomina (governor) because of his position of authority. Won (they)¹⁹ in line 17 is exophoric. It is used for the person who distributes the letter to the kings but his referential identity does not

occur in the text.

Awon (those) in clause 12 premodifies an 'unusual'²⁰ Head - kan (awon kan (those ones)). Kan (one/ones/some out of many)²¹ though functions mainly as numerative is substitutive as well in this instance. As indicated in chapter two, a numerative may also function as the Head of a nominal group in Yoruba as it functions here. Awon (those) modifying kan (some out of many) is co-referential, anaphorically and partially with awon oba (those kings) in clauses 10-11. Through context awon (those) functions instantially as a partial cohesive device by modifying a sub-group of its referent. That is, as a result of its 'incomplete' meaning with its referent (some of the kings rather than all of them), it is categorised as forming a partial type of cohesive device.

o (it) functions structurally in the text but not cohesively. Such occurrences are in clauses 2, 4, 6, 10 and 12.

The following is a graphic display of the texts cohesive chains:

Table 3.1.7 (8) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.3

There are five chains in this newspaper text and just one tie (number III). Chain V is very short like a tie but has two cohesive devices in the same clause. Both newspaper texts²² have more demonstratives than the first two narrative texts which have far more personals and fewer demonstratives.

Focussing on the emerging types of co-referential ties in the language as the texts are being described, and the relative patterns/density of cohesive ties, the four texts above consisting of two genres (narrative and newspaper) may be compared as follows. The four texts have approximately the same length. Five types of co-referential ties emerge - single, contracted, compound, inclusive and partial. In terms of relative pattern/density of the types of reference in the narrative (i.e. personal, demonstrative, and comparative) - the first two texts, as expected, contain more personal ties (including the contracted forms) than the demonstrative (including the definite determiners). In Text

3.1.0, for instance, there 10 personal reference and 4 demonstratives. In Text 3.1.1, there are 25 personal reference and 2 demonstratives. The contrary is the case for the newspaper texts. In Text 3.1.2, there are 6 personal reference and 8 demonstratives. In Text 3.1.3, the difference is even greater - there are 4 personal reference and 15 demonstratives.

Unlike narrative, newspaper texts contain, generally, more demonstratives than personals. Reference is always made to things, places, time and events, in particular, newspaper reporting.

3.5 - Television Texts

Text 3.1.4²³

This is a television world news programme. It contains the highlights of the major events and the news item on the dispute among the traditional rulers in Oyo State.

1. E káále, /iròhìn/ káàkiri orígún méèrèrin ágbàyé
you evening news all-over corner four-four world
'good evening, this is the world news'
2. ni mo mú wá fún yín, Dokun Awolere ni oníròhìn
PREP.I bring come for you, Dokun Awolere is newscaster
'that comes to you; Dokun Awolere is your newscaster'
3. Sáájú e jé ká gbó \àwon\ tó se kókó làbè iròhìn \náà\
DEM DEM
(irohin.1) ← (irohin.1) ←
first you let us hear those that are salient under news d-d
'first of all, the following are the highlights of the news'
4. /Ijoba ipínle Oyo/ ti tú igblimò /àwon oba àti ijòye/ ká
govt. state Oyo PERF. untie council those king and chief
'the Oyo State govt. disbanded the council of kings & chiefs'

- (ipinle Ogun. 5) «—
5. Ewè ní ipinlè Ogun, ijoba ipinle \nàà\ ti se àgbénde
DEM
also in state Ogun govt. state d-d PERF. do raise
'Also in Ogun State, the government has passed'
6. àbádòfin kan làti se idásilè igbimò àjo ilé isé
PREP. law one to do establish council assembly house work
'into law the establishment of a council'
7. tí yíò máa rí sí gbìgbé àsà ibilè l'áruge
that AUX.VBS see PREP. support custom native promote
'that will promote the traditional customs'
8. Eka ilé isé /ijoba ibilè Somolu/ ní ipinlè Eko
branch house work govt. native Somolu PREP state Lagos
'the work Depart. of the Somolu Local Govt. in Lagos state'
9. ti ya owó tó tó igba ó lè ogbòn oké naira
PERF. set money up to 200 it excess 30,000 naira
'has set a sum of money up to six hundred thousand naira'
- (ijoba Somolu. 8) «—
10. sótò fún ipèsè idàgbàsókè àwon ekún igbèríko \rè\
PER
apart PREP. provision growth those district province its
'apart for the development of its districts'
11. Orílè-èdè /Brazil/ ni lròhin fi yé wa pé
country Brazil PREP. news make known us that
'The news that we gather from Brazil says that the nation'
- «— (Brazil. 11)
12. \o\ ti dāwó /sisan igbèsè owó/ tó je
PER
it PERF. stop PROG. pay debt money PREP. owe
'has stopped repaying its debt owed to'
- (sisan igbese owo. 13) «—
13. ilé ifowópamó àgbáyé dúró fún igbà dié \nàà\
DEM
house PROG. keep world stop PREP. time little d-d
'the world bank for some time'
- (awon oba. 4) «—
14. Ijoba ipinlè Oyo ló ti tú igbimò \àwon\ oba
DEM
govt. state Oyo it PERF. scatter council those king
'the govt. of Oyo state has disbanded the council of kings'
- (ijoye. 4) «—
15. àti ijòyè \rè\ ká báyi gégébi àlàyè òrò
PER
and chiefs its about now according explanation word
'and chiefs according to the statement by'

(ipinle Oyo. 14) «
 16. akòwé àgbà ijoba ipinlè \nàà\ /Ogbeni J. A. Adedeji/
 DEM.
 secretary senior govt. state d-d Mr. J. A. Adedeji
 'the chief secretary of the state govt. Mr. J. A. Adedeji'

(awon oba. 14) «
 17. Akókò tí igbimò \nàà\ kò fi ní jòkó mó báyi
 DEM
 time that council d-d NEG. AUX. VBS. sit again now
 'the period during which the council will not assemble'

18. ni ijoba ipinlè Oyo yíò ló láti fi yanjú isòro
 is govt. state Oyo AUX. VB. spend to use settle problem
 'will be used by the state govt. to settle the problem'

(ijoba Oyo. 18) « (Adedeji. 16) « (igbimo. 14)
 19. tó n dojú ko \ó\ \ó\ ní ohun kan \nàà\ ti
 PER PER DEM
 that PROG. face PREP. it he say thing one d-d that
 'facing it. He said that the only thing'

(tu igbimo. 14) «
 20. ijoba ipinlè Oyo lé se ni \yí\ lákokó yi
 DEM
 govt. state Oyo AUX. ADV. do is this time this
 'the government of Oyo State can do; at this time'

(igbimo oba. 14) «
 21. láti pèsè àlááfàa sàarin \àwon\ omo igbimò
 DEM
 PREP. provide peace between those child council
 'to bring peace to the members of the council'

(igbimo oba) «
 22. oba alayé \nàà\ Bákanná ni Ogbeni Adedeji
 DEM
 king highness d-d similarly is Mr. Adedeji
 'and the highnesses. Similarly, Mr Adedeji'

23. tún se àlàyé pe ojúse ijoba ipinlè Oyo ni
 also does explain that duty govt. state Oyo is
 'explained that it is the duty of the Oyo state government'

(igbimo oba. 21) «
 24. lati má se jékí èdè-aiyedè wo àárin \àwon\ oba
 DEM
 PREP. NEG. make permit misunderstanding enter mid those king
 'to prevent any misunderstanding among those'

(ipinle Oyo. 23) « (Adedeji. 21) «
 25. alayé ní ipinlè \nàà\ Paríparí òrò \re\
 DEM PER
 highnesses PREP. state d-d Conclusion word his
 'highnesses in the state. Concluding his statement'

26. Ogbeni Adedeji ni góminà ipinlè Oyo
Mr Adedeji say governor state Oyo
'Mr Adedeji said that the Oyo state governor'
27. Ogagun Adetunji Olurin ti ké sí gbogbo
military leader Adetunji Olurin PERF. call PREP. all
'Captain Adetunji Olurin has appealed to all'
28. èniyàn jàkànjàkàn tó wà ní'bí ipádé ipésé
people eminent that exist PREP. place meeting prepare
'the eminent persons who attended the meeting to foster'
29. àlàáfia ti ojó Abameta ojó keje osù ti ó kojá
peace PERF. day Saturday day seven month that. it pass
'peace last Saturday the seventh of last month'
30. ní ilú Ibadan lati máa lépa gbígbé /ibòwò/
PREP. town Ibadan PREP. AUX. VB pursue carry reverence
'in the city of Ibadan to aim at giving reverence'
- ← (oba alaye. 24-25)
31. fún \àwon\ oba alayé ní ipinlè Oyo l'áruge
DEM
PREP. those king highness PREP. state Oyo promote
'to those highnesses in Oyo state'
- ← (ibowo fun oba. 30-32)
32. \iyen\ ní gbogbo igbà
DEM
that PREP. all time
'that is, at all times'

The cohesive devices in the text are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
3	2	awon (those) naa (the)	D-PAR D	M. 1 M. 1	irohin. 1 (news) irohin. 1 (news)
5	1	naa (the)	D	O	ipinle Ogun. 5 (Ogun State)
9	1	ó (it)	P	O	owo. 9 (money)
10	1	rè (its)	P	M. 1	ijoba ibile Somolu. 8 (Somolu Local Govt.)
12	1	ó (it)	P	O	orile-ede Brazil. 11 (nation of Brazil)
13	1	naa (the)	D	O	sisan igbese owo. 12 (paying of debts)
14	1	awon (those)	D	M. 10	oba ati ijoye. 4 (king and chief)
15	1	re (its)	P	O	ijoba ipinle Oyo. 14 (Oyo State Govt.)
16	1	naa (the)	D	M. 1	ijoba ipinle Oyo. 14 (Oyo State Govt.)
17	1	naa (the)	D	M. 2	igbimo awon oba. 14 (kings' council)
19	3	ó (it)	P	O	ijoba ipinle Oyo. 18 (Oyo State Govt.)

		ó (he)	P	M. 2	Ogbeni J. A. Adedeji. 16
		naa (the)	D	N. 4	tu igbimo. 14 (disband council)
20	1	yi (this)	D	N. 5	tu igbimo. 14 (disband council)
21	1	awon(those)	D}	N. 6	igbimo awon oba. 14 (council of kings)
22	1	naa (the)	D}	N. 7	igbimo awon oba. 14 (council of kings)
24	1	awon (those)	D	M. 1	igbimo oba alaye. 21-22 (Highnesses Council)
25	2	naa (the)	D	M. 1	ipinle Oyo. 23 (Oyo State)
		rè (his)	P	M. 2	Ogbeni Adedeji. 22
31	1	awon (those)	D	N. 5	awon oba alaye. 24-25 (Highnesses)
32	1	iyen (that)	D	0	ibowo fun awon oba. 30-32 (respect for kings)

Table 3.1.7 (9) - Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.4

Text 3.1.4 above is a television 'world news' item on the Lagos television, Channel 8, commonly referred to as LTV 8. It contains, essentially, the same news item already investigated above from two different newspapers - Isokan and Gboungboun in Texts 3.1.2 and 3.1.3 respectively. As a result, the same subject-matter is being investigated, indirectly, in three texts from three different sources, and from two different media.

In television, unlike the newspaper, sound and sight have a more central role to play because they complement words, to a large extent, as main carriers of information. Both sound and sight form the two main sources of getting and maintaining the attention of the audience (Ellis 1985:153). Hence, the direct address form that is used to introduce this text which, unlike radio, presupposes the presence of an onlooking audience - E káalé (good evening). This introduction seems to serve two main functions: one, to signal the beginning of the news broadcast; and second, to

direct the attention of the viewers both to the programme and the newscaster.²⁴

A stylistic feature common to television and radio news broadcast is shown in the text by the newscaster's presentation of the highlights of the news first, as found in clauses 3-13 of the above text. These highlights consist of three news items from the states in the federation: Oyo, Ogun and Lagos; and the foreign news from Brazil.²⁵ Incidentally the main news item as found in Texts 3.1.2. and 3.1.3. is the first to be highlighted, and it forms the main text here. As highlights - unconnected pieces of information, clauses 1-13 contain fewer co-referential ties than, for example, clauses 14-25 which contain the main part of the news.

Awon (those) in clause 3 is the first cohesive device in the text. Rather than modifying an element of a nominal group, it modifies a phrase - to se koko (that are salient). Clauses and phrases may form part of the nominal group in the language (section 2.1.0. in chapter 2). Significantly, the second occurrence of the demonstrative yi (this) in clause 20 is structural while the first is cohesive.

Table 3.1.7 (10) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.4

Table 3.1.7 (10) above shows two interesting patterns. Ties I- V, being highlights of the news, form a very different pattern from the full news report as shown in chains VI-VIII. Being ties, the pattern of the highlights shows the referent and one corresponding referential item only, whereas chains VI-VIII, being the main part of one full item of the news,

form longer chains than the highlights. A single tie (IX), however, occurs at the end of the three chains.

The demonstrative cohesive tie awon (those) in clause 3, modifying the phrase to se koko (that are salient) forms, therefore, a partial co-referential tie with irohin (news) because ties II-V are 'the highlights' of the news, while 'the full news' is evidenced in chains VI-VIII.

The television text as a genre may be said to operate between written and spoken texts. Although this particular text is about fifty percent longer than those of the newspapers which report the same event, they all have, essentially, the same content. Newspapers are generally more economical in the use of words than television. One obvious feature of the television which does not appear in the newspaper²⁶ is that of highlighting the news. Highlighting, which is perhaps, a pragmatic device, increases the length of the text significantly. Like the newspaper, television texts have more demonstratives than the personals.

Text 3.1.5²⁷

This text is from a television quiz programme. Two couples who are participants in the competition sit on each side of the presenter before a large audience. The presenter calls on each couple to select a number in turn from the ones displayed on a board for everyone to see (both participants and the audience). The question is then read to them (and to the audience) and either of the couples may answer the question.

The first question, question 18 which begins from clause 6, is being read by the presenter of the quiz programme when she is interrupted by some members of the audience. She asks members of the audience to stop the noise in clause 9 and begins again to read the question starting from clause 10. She finishes in clause 15. For this analysis, clauses 6-8 will be regarded as discourse functional repair hence only clauses 10-15 will be used.

Presenter:

1. E sé é, tò, ó yá o²⁸
 you (all) thanks, alright it now (SEW)
 'thanks to you all, alright, it is time'

Participant:

2. ibéèrè /'eighteen'/²⁹
 question eighteen
 'the eighteenth question'

Presenter:

3. è è è, gèési èébo³⁰ l'e fò \hun\
 (eighteen. 2) ←
 eh! English English vb+you speak that DEM
 'Eh! that's said in English'

Participant:

4. ibéèrè méjidílógun
 question eighteen
 'the eighteenth question'

Presenter:

5. ikejidínlógún, E seun
 eighteenth, you thanks
 'the eighteenth, thank you'
6. láyé àtijó, kí ilò girisi³¹ tó gbòde kanken
 world past before use grease become all-over seriously
 'in the past, before the use of grease became the norm'
7. àwon iyá wa máa nre àwon ohun kan
 those mother our AUX.VB. PROG. soak those thing certain
 'our mothers used to soak certain things'

8. sínú àdín àgbon fún eni tó bá sèsè bimo
 PREP. palm kernel PREP. person that AUX. VB ADV. give birth
 'in the palm kernel for use by mothers who just gave birth'

(disturbing noise from members of the audience)

9. E yé pariwo
 You (all) stop make noise
 'You should stop the noise' (looking at the audience)

(The presenter repeats the question again)

10. ànísé làyé àtijó kí ilò girisi tó gbòde kankan
 again world past before use grease become everywhere
 'again before the use of grease became the norm'

í

í

11. /àwon iyá/ wa máa nre /àwon ohun kan/ sínú
 those mother our AUX. VB PROG. soak those thing certain PREP.
 'our mothers used to soak certain things in'

12. àdín àgbon fún eni tó bá sèsè bimo
 palm kernel PREP person that AUX. VB. ADV give birth
 'palm kernel oil for use by mothers who just gave birth'

(awon iya. 11) «—|—»

13. láti máa fi para. \Nwón\ sí tún fi
 PER

to AUX. VB use smear body they AUX. VB. ADV use
 'to lubricate their skins. They also used'

14. n para fún omo tuntun pàápàá
 PROG. smear body PREP. child new especially
 '(it) to lubricate (i.e. condition) the new babies' skins'

(awon ohun kan. 11) «—|—» (kanfo. 18) «—|—» (kanfo. 18)

15. E dárúko mérin nínú \àwon/ nkan \òhún/
 DEM DEM
 you name four PREP. those things that
 'you (participants) name four out of those very things'

(Quiet, then the presenter gives some leading sentences)

(awon nkan ohun. 15) «—|—» (kanfo. 18)

16. A nte sínú àdín sùgbón \ó/ là jé
 PER
 we PROG. lay PREP. oil CONJ. it AUX. VB. ADV. be
 'we put it in palm kernel oil; it may be'

(awon nkan ohun. 15) «—|—» (kanfo. 18)

17. dúdú pàápàá. A máa nre \é/
 PER
 black especially we AUX. VB. PROG. soak it
 'black indeed. We do soak it'

Participant: 1

18. /Kánfò/
(camphor)

Presenter:

« $\neg$ (kanfo. 18)
19. \ó\ di ení, óyá óyá óyá óyá
PER
it is one, quick, quick, quick, quick
'it's one, quick, quick, quick, quick'

Participant: 2

20. /Káfúrà/
spice (a kind of)

Presenter:

(kafura. 20) « $\neg$
21. Ehèén! hen! káfúrà, \ó\ wolè
PER
Ye...s ye...s káfúrà, it enter
'Yes! yes! spice it is correct'

Participant: 2

22. /Erù/
Erù (a kind of spice)

Presenter:

(eru. 22) « $\neg$
23. E sé é, \ó\ di méta, óyá, óyá, óyá
PER
you thanks it is three, quick quick quick
'thank you (2nd Part); it is now three, quick, quick, quick'

(Quiet - the presenter, once again, gives leading statements)

(eru. 22) « $\neg$ » (kanafuru. 26) (eru. 22) « $\neg$ » (kanafuru)
24. \l'awon/ ohun tó l'óórùn, tó l'óórùn \báyì/
DEM DEM
VB+those thing that VB+smell that VB+smell this
'things that smell, that smell like this'

« $\neg$ » (kanafuru. 26)
25. /ó/ kù kan
PER
it remain one
'it remains one' (i. e. we need one more)

Participant: 2

26. /Kánáfurù/
Kánáfurù (a kind of spice)

Presenter:

27. Kánáfurù, e bá mi fún \won\ l'atewo
 Kanafuru you help me give them VB. + clap
 'Kanafuru, give them a clap'

The cohesive devices in the above text are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
3	1	hun (that)	D	O	'eighteen'. 2
13	1	nwon (they)	P	M. 1	awon iya wa. 11 (our mothers)
15	2	awon (those)	D-A/C	M. 3/2	awon ohun kan. 11/ (those very things)
		ohun (that)	D-A/C	M. 3/2	kanfo. 18 (camphor) awon ohun kan. 11/ (those very things)
16	1	o (it)	P-A/C	O/M. 1	kanfo. 18 (camphor) awon nkan ohun. 15/ (those very things)
17	1	e (it)	P-A/C	M. 1	kanfo. 18 (camphor) awon nkan ohun. 18/ (those very things)
19	1	o (it)	P	O	kanfo. 18 (camphor)
21	1	o (it)	P	O	kanfo. 18 (camphor)
23	1	o (it)	P	O	kafura. 20 (spice)
24	2	l'awon (VB+those)	C-A/C	M. 1 (2)	eru. 22 (spice) kanafuru. 26 (spice)
		bayi (this)	D-A/C	M. 1 (2)	eru. 22 (spice) kanafuru. 26 (spice)
25	1	o (it)	P-C	O	kanafuru. 26 (spice)

Table 3.1.7 (11) - Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.5

The above text, being a quiz programme, presents a complex co-referential pattern. On Table 3.1.7.(11) above, A/C means that the cohesive devices so indicated are both simultaneously anaphoric and cataphoric. In clauses 15 and 24, this type of co-referentiality is motivated by compound cohesive devices. It operates differently, however, in clauses 16 and 17; it is motivated by single cohesive devices. Awon (those) and ohun (that/that very) both modify nkan (things). They both form a compound cohesive device with the same referent - awon ohun kan (those very things)³².

Given the nature of the environment in which the compound cohesive device functions, it performs a 'dual' function. It functions both anaphorically and cataphorically. It is co-referential, anaphorically, with awon ohun kan (those very [certain] things) in clause 11, and the extended reference which explains them in clauses 11-14. It forms a cataphoric co-referential device with kanfo (camphor) in line 18, in particular, and the other three types of 'things' in lines 20, 22, and 26. This type of pattern is formed by l'awon (VB.+those) and bayi (this/this way). The two pronominals o (it) and e (it) in clauses 16 and 17 occur in leading statements to enable the participants ³³ answer the question already asked in clause 15. ³⁴ These pronominals form, therefore, a 'dual' tie in the text or one part of two separate ties. They are co-referential, anaphorically, with awon nkan ohun (those very things) in clause 15 and kanfo (camphor), one of those things, in clause 18.

The following is a graphic display of the text's cohesive chains:

continued on next page

16.	ó (it)
	▪
	EXT. REF.
	▪
17.	e (it)
	▪
18.	kanfo (camphor)
	▪
19.	ó (it)
20.	kafura (spice)
	▪
21.	ó (it)
22.	eru
	▪
23.	ó (it)
24.	l'awon (vb+those)
	bayi (this)
	▪
25.	ó (it)
	▪ Kanafuru

Table 3.1.7 (12) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.5

Table 3.1.7 (12) above has two ties (I&II) and one complex chain (III); the latter containing the answers to the quiz. Hun (that) in clause 3 forms an anaphoric co-referential tie with 'eighteen' in clause 2. The presenter notices that the first participant code-mixes Yoruba with English in that clause, so she directs his attention to this error by the use of that cohesive demonstrative tie. Apart from hun (that) and ohun (that) which function like the definite determiner, no definite article in the text. Unlike the previous text (on

television) which does not have even one cataphoric tie, this text contains one 'pure' cataphoric tie and six 'dual' ones. I have remarked already that the narrative texts have more personals than newspaper texts. This distinction cannot be made with the two television texts because they belong to different sub-genres. The first is a news report, while the second is a quiz. The news text is closer to written genre, while the quiz text is spoken. No single structural or exophoric device is apparent in the quiz text.

3.6 - Radio Texts

Text 3.1.6 35

Unlike the previous texts which begin from the beginning, this text, apart from the first two lines, occurs in mid broadcast. It contains the last part, that is, the summary of the news items.

1. /Iròhin àpapò/ orilè-èdè wa /Naijèria/ l'ó ndé sí
news national nation our Nigeria is-it PROG.come PREP.
'the national news comes to'
2. etigbò yín láti ilé isé rédiò l'ipínlè Ogun l'Abeokuta
ear hear you PREP.house work radio VB+state Ogun at Abeokuta
'you (all) from the Ogun State radio at Abeokuta'
3. Lékàn sí, e tún gbó \àwon\ kókó
DEM
once more you AUX.VB.ADV. hear those salient
'once more listen to those salient'
4. inú iròhin \náà\ /Ijoba àpapò/ orilè-èdè
DEM
PREP. news d-d government national nation
'items of the news. The national government'
5. \yi\ so pé \òun\ ti múra tán láti ri
DEM PER
this say that it PERF.ready finish PREP. see
'said that it was ready to see'
6. dájú pé irú /àdéhùn-kádéhùn/ tó wùwù
sure that whatever agreement that whatever
'for sure that whatever agreement'
7. tí \òun\ yíò bá orilè-èdè kórilè-èdè
PER
that it AUX.VB. make nation any nation
'it might with whatever nation'
8. se ni àgbáyé kò ni jé èyítí yíò
make PREP.world NEG. is be which AUX.VB.
'make in the world will not be such that will'
9. (Naijèria. 1) \yi\ lára rará
DEM
kill nation this body at all
'suffer the nation at all'

10. Onírurú ilé-isé àwon omo ogun
 various house work those child battle
 'chief of general staff of the military'
- (Naijeria. 1) «—
 11. orilé-èdè \yì\, /Ogagun Sanni Abacha/ l'ó
 DEM
 nation this general Sanni Abacha is+he
 'in this country, General Sanni Abacha'
- (adehun-kadehun. 6) «— (Abacha. 11) «—
 12. so òrò idánilójú \yì\ l'Eko lánà nígbàtí \ó\
 DEM PER
 say word assurance this PREP. Lagos yesterday when he
 'said this re-assuring statement in Lagos yesterday when he'
13. sí ipàdé kan tí nwón nse ní pa
 open meeting one that they PROG.do PREP.
 'was declaring a meeting open on'
- (adehun-kadehun) «—
 14. àdéhùn ati àkosilé \àwon\ ètò àdéhùn
 DEM
 agreement and writing those plan agreement
 'the programme and writing of the plan for agreement'
- (orile-edè korile ede. 7) «—
 15. láàrín orilé-èdè wa ati \àwon\ orilé-èdè òkèèrè
 DEM
 between nation our and those nation distance
 'between our nation and those foreign nations'
- ì «— (Akinrinade. 22) ì
 16. /Nwon/ ti tóka si wí pé ònà ti nwón
 PER
 they PERF. point PREP. that way that they
 'they have pointed out that the way they'
17. fi nkó /awon ilé-isé olókò/ lórí
 use PROG. build those house work commerce PREP.
 'build those commercial houses'
18. 'lè-èdè wa lákòkò yì kò fi ònà
 nation our time this NEG. allow way
 'in our country at this time does not'
19. sílè fún idàgbàsókè ojó iwájú
 leave PREP. growth day future
 'provide for growth in the future'
- (ile-ise oloko. 17) «—
 20. Alákoso ètò idásilé \àwon\ ilé-isé olókò
 DEM
 President plan establish those house work commerce
 'the president in charge of those commercial houses'

21. owó fún ijoba àpapò orilè-èdè \yi\
trade PREP. government national nation this
'for this national government' (NaijERIA. 1)
22. Ogagun tó ti fèhinti /Alani Akinrinade/
military-leader who PERF. retire Alani Akinrinade
'the retired General Alani Akinrinade'
(ona ti... 16-19)
23. l'o tóka sí òrò \yi\ lánà ní ilú Ibadan
DEM
VB+he point PREP. word this yesterday PREP. town Ibadan
'made this statement yesterday at Ibadan'
24. tí'se olú ilú ipínlè Oyo nigbàtí \ó\ nsòrò
PER
PREP is chief town state Oyo when he PROG. say
'the capital of Oyo State when he was giving a speech' (Akinrinade. 22)
25. ní ibèrè ipàdé nlá kan fún àpapò
PREP. start meeting PROG. big one PREP. national
'at the beginning of a national conference'
- (NaijERIA. 1) «
26. orilè-èdè \yi\ nípa òrò \àwon\ onilé isé
DEM DEM
nation this PREP. word those owner house work
'in this country about the issue of commercial houses' (ile-ise oloko. 17)
27. olókòwò owó kéèkèké ati idàgbàsókè
trading money little and growth
'small business enterprises and the growth'
28. orilè-èdè wa Nigeria. /Idániléko/ olójó márùn
nation our Nigeria Induction day five
'of our nation, Nigeria. A five-day induction'
29. kan fún àwon tí yìò máa kó àwon òsìsè
one PREP. those that AUX. VBS teach those workers
'course for the teachers who would teach workers'
30. tí yìò máa sisé ní agbègbè igbèríko ní
that AUX. VBS PROG. work PREP. local areas PREP.
'that would be working in the remote areas in'
31. /ipínlè Imo/ tí bèrè ní Owerri lánà
state Imo PERF. start PREP. Owerri yesterday
'Imo State has begun in Owerri yesterday'
32. Awon /eni márùndínláádórin/ tí nwón sà jo
those person sixty-five that they gather together
'Those sixty-five participants that were invited'
33. láti agbègbè ijoba ipínlè mókàndínlógún tí
PREP. local government state nineteen that
'from the nineteen local government areas'

34. ó wà ní ipínlè \náà\ \l'ò\ n kópa ninú
 (Imo State. 31) « (eni marundinlaadorin. 32)
 DEM CON -PER
 it exist PREP. state d-d VB. he PROG participate PREP.
 'of the state are participating in'

35. idánilé kò \òhún\ Eyí l'òpin iròhin \náà\
 (idanileko. 28) « (irohin. 1) «
 DEM DEM
 induction that This VB. + end news d-d
 'that induction course. This is the end of the news'

36. tí ó ti ndé sí etígbò yín láti
 that it PERF. PROG. come PREP. ear you PREP.
 'that has been coming to you'

37. ilé-isé rédiò ipínlè Ogun l'Abeokuta
 house work radio state Ogun PREP. Abeokuta
 'the Ogun State radio at Abeokuta'

38. O dígbà
 it bye
 Goodbye

The cohesive devices in the above text are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
3	1	awon (they)	D-PAR	M. 1	irohin apapo. 1 (national news)
4	1	naa (the)	D	M. 2	irohin apapo. 1 (national news)
5	2	yi (this) oun (it)	D P	M. 3 O	NaijERIA. 1 (Nigeria) ijoba apapo. 4 (national govt.)
7	1	oun (it)	P	M. 2	ijoba apapo. 4 (national govt.)
9	1	yi (this)	D	N. 4	orile-ede yi. 4-5 (this nation)
11	1	yi (this)	D	N. 1	orile-ede yi. 9 (this nation)
12	2	yi (this)	D	N. 6	adehun-kadehun. 6-9 (whatever arrangement)
14	1	o (he) awon (those)	P D	O N. 7	Ogagun S. Abacha. 11 adehun-kadehun. 6 (whatever arrangement)
15	1	awon (those)	D	N. 7	orile-ede korile-ede. 7 (whatever nation)
16	1	nwon (they) [1]	P - C	N. 5	Ogagun A. Akinrinade. 22
20	1	awon (those)	D	M. 2	ile-ise oloko. 17 (commercial house)
21	1	yi (this)	D	M. 2	'le-ede wa. 18 (our nation)
23	1	yi (this)	D	M. 6	ona ti... 16-19 (path that...)
24	1	o (he)	P	M. 1	Ogagun A. Akinrinade. 22

26	2	yi (this)	D	N. 4	orile-ede yi. 21 (this nation)
		awon (those)	D	M. 5	ile-ise oloko. 20-22 (commercial houses)
34	2	naa (the)	D	N. 2	ipinle Imo State. 31 (Imo State)
		l'o (VB+he?)	C	M. 1	eni marundinlaadorin. 32 (sixty-five persons)
35	2	ohun (that)	D	N. 6	idanileko. 28 (induction)
		naa (the)	D	N. 33	irohin apapo. 1 (national news)

Table 3.1.7 (13) - Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.6

Awon (those) in clause 3, is a partial cohesive device because it modifies an adjectival phrase in the same clause - kókó inú iròhin náà (salient items of the news). Its meaning relation with the referent - iròhin (news) in clause 1 is therefore mediated because the adjectival phrase which it modifies does not completely share the meaning potential of the referent. This partial cohesive device is identical with the one in Text 3.1.3.

The meaning and function of the personal item nwon (they) in clause 16 may elude the listener until later in the news when he or she notices in clauses 22-23 that it is co-referential cataphorically with the Alani Akinrinade who made the statement. Its use, therefore, is inclusive - grammatically plural, but culturally it refers to a single person. The contracted tie l'o (vb+he) in clause 34, though singular rather than plural (i.e. l'awon (they)), is co-referential, anaphorically, with eni marundinlaadorin (sixty-five persons). Oun (it) as used in clauses 5 and 7 raises the status of the national government from inanimate to animate - a practice that also makes the usage inclusive.

Table 3.1.7 (14) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.6

The text being a summary of a radio news report, the pattern of its chains is fragmented in a similar way to the summary of the beginning of the television news report in Text 3.1.4.

Apart from chains I and II which are long but have few cohesive devices relative to their length, chains III, IV, VII and VIII are short. Numbers V, VI, IX and X-XII are ties.

There are six exophoric references (clauses 13, 16, 17, 29 [2] and 32) in the text. This may be attributed to the fact that it is the summary of a news report. Radio news texts, as well as television news texts, have generally more structural and exophoric references than newspaper texts perhaps because they are closer to spoken rather than written language.

Text 3.1.7 ³⁶

Text 3.1.7 is the last part of a very long radio discussion programme focussed on the general responsibilities of parents to their children particularly the school-age ones. The first clause is a statement of thanks from the presenter to the first participant for her contribution. Clauses 2-13 are the presenter's comments on the first participant's contribution. Clauses 14 to 29 are the second participant's contribution. Finally, clauses 30 to the end of the text consist of the presenter's comments as she ends the programme.

Presenter

1. E³⁷ seun iyáàfin Ogunsola. ³⁸ Eyin òbí òrò ni E gbó yen
 You thank madam Ogunsola You parents word is you hear that
 'thank you madam Ogunsola. You parents have just heard that'
2. Hen se bí ó nlo school³⁹, se bí tísà rí i se bí kinikan
 yes does he PROG. go school does teacher see him does what
 'Yes he does go to school, the teacher does see him or what'

3. Nwón ní èyítí èyin gan an tí e bá se lára /omo/
 they say what you especially that you AUX. VB. do body child
 'they 've just said that whatever you do to your children'

4. yen ní'lé \òhun\ \l'ó\ omo. 3)
 EXT. REF. DEM CON. máa gbé dé òdò olùkó
 that PREP. house that (is+he) AUX. VB. carry to place teacher
 'in the house that he would extend to the teacher'

5. torí igbàtí olùkó bá ní lágbájá jòkò nbè yèn ì
 because when teacher AUX. VB. say person sit place that
 'because when the teacher instructs him to sit there'

6. tó dè jé pé \kò\ 40 n /gbóran/ sí màmá \è\ l'ènu
 CON. PER
 such (SEW) is that NEG. +he PROG. hear to mother his mouth
 but since he does not obey his mother's instructions'

7. ní'lé. Báwo \l'ó\ se fé gbó t'olùkó?
 CON.
 PREP house. how (does+he) AUX. VBS. like hear PREP. teacher
 'at home; how will he listen to the teachers?'

8. \á\ fo dide ni \kò\ ní kò láti bú olùkó
 PER CON.
 he jump up is NEG+he (SEW) NEG. to abuse teacher
 'he would jump up and not hesitate to abuse the teacher'

9. Nwón ní owó àwa òbí ni gbogbo \è/ pò sí
 EXT. REF. PER
 they say hand we parents is all them many PREP.
 'they 've said that it is the parents who have much to do'

10. bí a se má kó àwon omo wa sí ònà ì
 (SEW) we do AUX. VB. train those child our PREP. way
 'how we would direct our children into the'

11. rere. ó kù sí owó wa iyá ati bàbá
 good it remains PREP. hand our mother and father
 'right path lies in our hands as mothers and fathers'

12. \áwon\ omo \nàá\ Ogbeni Okusanya
 DEM DEM
 those child d-d Mr Okusanya
 'What of those children themselves Mr Okusanya?'

13. e gbà \wón\ l'ámòrán ní sókí
 PER
 you 'give' them VB. +advice PREP. brief
 'do advise them briefly'

2nd Participant (in order of the programme)

14. Tò, èyin omo wa bí àwa /òbí/ bá ti nbá
 right! you child our as we parents AUX. VB. PERF. PROG. rebuke
 'Yes! as we parents rebuke you children'

15. yín wí bàbá ati iyá e máa gbó
 you rebuke father and mother you AUX. VB. listen
 'that is, the fathers and the mothers, you should listen'

(ko n gboran. 6) "┐
 16. nítorí àìgbóràn \yen\ pàápàá a máa bá
 DEM
 because disobedience that especially it always follow
 'because disobedience in particular always accompanies'

(elomiran. 17) "┐
 17. /elòmíràn/ dé' lé oko, \kò\ ní lè gbé ilé oko l' óhùn
 CON.
 person VB. +house husband NEG+he AUX. live house husband there
 'some to their husbands' homes and be unable to live there'

"┐ (elomiran. 17) (elomiran. 17) "┐
 18. nítorí \ko\ gbé' kò ilé. Ekó ilé tí \ò\ sì gbà yí
 CON. CON.
 PREP. NEG+he take lesson home. Lesson house NEG+she take this
 'because she is untrainable. This lack of home training'

"┐ (elomiran. 17) (eko. 18) "┐
 19. tí \ò\ sì rí lò l' óhùn nse ló máa má
 CON. CON.
 that NEG. + she AUX. see use there PROG. it AUX. VBS always
 'that she cannot use there will always'

"┐ (elomiran. 17)
 20. tí \í\ káàkiri. Ibí ò dára ibè ò suwòn
 PER
 push her everywhere. Here NEG. good there NEG. good
 'push her about. This place is not good; that is bad'

î î î
 21. ibè yen gbóná, ibí yì ga, ibí yì tutù
 place that hot here this high here this cold
 'that place is hot; this is high, it is cold here'

î (ibi yi. 20-21) "┐ "┐ (elomiran. 17)
 22. ibí yì loólè, \ohun\ \l'ó\ máa má bá káàkiri
 DEM. CON.
 here this deep, that vb+she always AUX. VBS. (SEW) about
 'This place is deep, that will be her complaints everywhere'

23. sùgbón tí gbogbo wa bá ti se' tí bèlèjè
 but if all us AUX. VB. PERF. VB. + ear open
 'but if all of us will open our eyes'

24. a bá ti gbó ti \áwon\ òbí wa ònà ni \nwón\
 DEM. PER
 we AUX. V. PERF. hear PERF. those parents our way is they
 'to listen to our parents. It is the right way they'

25. máa tó wa sí. Awa ò ti mú /ogbón kan/
 AUX. direct us to we NEG. PERF. bring wisdom one
 'would direct us. We are yet to bring any wisdom'

26. wá l'átòrun à f'èyítí a bá l'ódò \won\
 PER
 come PREP+heaven CONJ. which we meet PREP them
 'from heaven except the one we learnt from them'

« (ogbon. 25) « (awon obi. 24)

27. \òhun\ ni \nwon\ máa fi kó won⁴¹
 DEM PER
 that is they AUX. VB use train them
 'that they will use to train them'

28. E jé kí a má gbó èkó \áwon\ òbí wa
 DEM
 you let (SEW) us always hear lesson those parents our
 'let us always listen to our parents' instructions'

« (awon obi. 24)

29. \Nwon\ ò lè sì wá l'ónà
 PER
 they NEG AUX. VB. miss our PREP. way
 'they cannot mislead us'

Presenter

30. E seun /ogbeni Okusanya./ /Eyin omodé/
 you (sg.) thanks Mr Okusanya You (pl.) child
 'Thank you Mr Okusanya. You children'

31. sé e ti gbó /àmòrán/ tí \nwon\ fún yín?
 PER
 INT. you PERF hear advice that they give you
 'have you heard the advice given to you?'

32. /Eyin òbí/ pàápàá eyin ni a bá sòrò (jù)
 COM
 you parents especially you is we AUX. VB. speak more
 'You parents are being addressed more (i.e. than children)'

33. lóri ètò yì. kí e má gbàgbè gbogbo ohun
 PREP. programme this let you AUX. VB. forget all thing
 'on this programme. You must not forget all the things'

- (amoran. 31) «— (amoran. 31) «—
34. tí a so \yen\. Pípò inú \e\ ni e máa má rántí
 DEM PER
 that we speak that many that it is you AUX. VBS. remember
 'that we have said. You would remember many of it'
35. kí e fi sè wà hù. E máa dà òrò \àwon\
 (omode. 30) «— DEM
 let you use act act act. You AUX. VB. leave for word those
 'Show this in your behaviour. Do not leave those (matters)'
36. omo dá olùkó. Kí bàbá má da dá iyà
 child leave for teacher let father AUX. VB. leave for mother
 'children with teachers. The father not with the mother'
37. kí'yà pàápàá dé má da dá bàbá
 let mother especially also AUX. VB. leave for father
 'neither the mother for the father'
38. 'se bí ó se wù é .⁴² nwón ní \kó\ t'ónà
 í «— (se o se wu e. 38)
 CON.
 'do as it do like you' they say NEG+it PREP. right
 '"do as you like", we are often told, its not right'
39. fún òbí láti máa so fún omodé
 for parent PREP. AUX. VB. say PREP. child
 'for parents to always say to the children'
40. Pé eyiti a bá fi kó \won\ \òhun\ ni
 (omode. 39) «— «— (eyiti... 40)
 PER DEM
 that which we AUX. VB. use teach them that is
 'that whatever instruction we give to them that'
- «— (omode. 39)
41. \nwón\ máa fi s'àdùrà fún wa ni èyin òla
 PER
 they always use prayer PREP. us PREP. later tomorrow
 'they will cherish about us later in life'
42. 'Torinà èyin iyá ati bàbá títi di ojó méjo
 therefore you mother and father until (SEW) day eight
 'therefore mothers and fathers until next week'
43. l'órúko olújìròrò mi iyáàfin Olatunji
 V.+ name discussant DET. madam Olatunji
 'on behalf of my discussant(s) madam Olatunji'
44. E seun a dúpé⁴³ (she responds). Ogbeni Osisanya⁴⁴
 you(sg.) thanks we grateful Mr Osisanya
 'thank you, we are grateful. Mr Osisanya'
45. E kú ohùn (she responds). Iyáàfin Ogunsola
 You (SEW) voice Madam Ogunsola
 'Thanks for the talk. Madam Ogunsola'

46. èyin náà kú ò dide (she responds)
you d-d (SEW) (SEW) stand
'thank you for coming'
47. Sade Lediji l'ó n kí yín pé ó dàárò
Sade Lediji is+vb. PROG. greet you that it tomorrow
'It's Sade Lediji saying to you, good night'
48. ojú ò ni fèrakù o. ⁴⁵ T'óbá tún di ojó
eye NEG. AUX. VB. miss (SEW) PREP. when AUX. ADV. is day
'May we all meet again next week'
49. méjo l'ágbára Olórun, à á tún pàdé láyò
eight is+power God we AUX. VB ADV. meet PREP. happy
'in God's power; and meet happily'

The following are the cohesive devices in the above text:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
4	2	ohun (that)	D	0	eyiti e ba se. 3 (whatever you do)
		l'ó (VB+he)	CON	0	omo. 3 (child)
6	2	ko (NEG+he)	CON	M. 2	omo. 3 (child)
		e (his)	P	M. 2	omo. 3 (child)
7	1	l'ó (VB+he)	CON	M. 3	omo. 3 (child)
8	2	a (he)	P	M. 4	omo. 3 (child)
		ko (NEG+he)	CON	M. 4	omo. 3 (child)
9	1	e (them)	P-A/C	N. 6/0	eyiti e ba se. 3/ (whatever you do) bi a se ko. 10 (how we will)
12	2	awon (those)	D}	M. 1	awom omo wa. 10 (our children)
		naa (the)	D}	M. 1	awon omo wa. 10 (our children)
13	1	won (them)	P	0	awon omo wa. 12 (our children)
16	1	yen (that)	D	N. 9	ko n gboran. 6 (he is disobedient)
17	1	ko (NEG+he)	CON	0	elomiran. 17 (other person)
18	2	ko (NEG+he)	CON	0	elomiran. 17 (other person)
		ò (she)	P	0	elomiran. 17 (other person)
19	2	ò (she)	P	M. 1	elomiran. 17 (other person)
		l'ó (she)	CON	0	eko. 18 (lesson)
20	1	i (she)	P	M. 2	elomiran. 17 (other person)
22	2	ohun (that)	D	M. 1+	ibi yi o dara. 20-21 (this place isn't good)
		l'ó (she)	CON	M. 4	elomiran. 17 (other person)

24	2	awon (those)	D	N. 9	awa obi. 14 (we parents)
		nwon (they)	P	N. 9	awa obi. 14 (we parents)
26	1	won (them)	P	M. 1	awon obi. 24 (those parents)
27	2	ohun (that)	D	M. 1	ogbon. 25 (wisdom)
		nwon (they)	P	M. 2	awon obi. 24 (those parents)
28	1	awon (those)	D	M. 3	awon obi. 24 (those parents)
29	1	nwon (they)	P	M. 4	awon obi. 24 (those parents)
31	1	nwon (they)	P	0	Ogbeni Okusanya. 30
32	1	ju (more)	COMP.	M. 1/0	omode. 30 (child) / obi. 32 (parents)
34	2	yen (that)	D	M. 2	amoran (advice). 31
		e (it)	D	M. 2	amoran (advice). 31
35	1	awon (those)	D	N. 4	omode. 30 (child)
38	1	ko (NEG+it)	C	0	se bi o se wu e. 38 (do as you like)
40	2	won (them)	P	0	omode (child). 39
		ohun (that)	D	0	eyiti a ba fi ko won. 40 (whatever we teach them)
41	1	nwon (they)	P	M. 1	omode. 39 (child)

Table 3.1.7 (15) - Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.7

Being an education programme, the text is aimed at reaching parents and children. Its message is based on what may be described as generalised. Clauses like se bi o n lo school (he does go to the school)-(2), se bi tisa ri i (the teacher does see him)-(2), ibi o dara (this place is not good)-(20), ibe o suwon (its bad there)-(20), are generalised references because they do not refer directly to any particular child or place. The direct references are made directly to parents and children.

The text, being the last part of a discussion programme on the radio, consists of certain exophoric items which might have functioned cohesively in the full text. Such items are yen (that) in lines 1 and 4; o (s/he), i (him) and nwon

(they) in lines 2 and 4. Madam Ogunsola's contribution to the discussion had just concluded when the text begins. For the first yen (that) in line 1, there is no means of knowing from the text what the last discussant said to the parents. For the second yen (that) in line 4, there is no clue to knowing which child is being referred to. The o (he) and i (him), in lines 2-4, may refer to the child; and nwon (they) in line 3 may refer to Madam Ogunsola but their referents may be obtained in the part of the text not included in this one.

Ju (more) in clause 32, an adverb in the adjunctive position, belongs to a different class of reference - comparative reference. As earlier pointed out, from the theoretical point of view, a comparative tie either expresses a 'general' or a 'particular' type of comparison. The general type is expressed to show how one thing looks like, or does not look like the other. The particular type of comparative reference, on the other hand, expresses some particular property of the referent.

As used in the above clause, ju (more), as a referential item signals a comparison between the parents and their children concerning concerning the sharing of responsibility in the upbringing of the latter. The comparative tie shows that the the responsibility weighs more heavily on the parents rather than on the children whose sole responsibility is to pay attention. We have therefore in the text both the referents - the two groups of people being compared; and the particular property that the comparative tie signals that they do have. The property in question is quantitative rather than

qualitative. That is, the discussants have raised issues that concern the parents more than the children. As a kind of cohesive reference, ju (more) anaphorically brings into prominence all those points of view already expressed by the discussants.

Some of the co-referential devices refer to clausal and extended referents. Ohun (that) in clause 4 refers to eyiti e ba se lara omo yen n'ile (whatever you do to your children at home) in clause 3; e (them) in clause (9), which means what is done or can be done to the children, refers to long clausal referents both before and after its occurrence. Anaphorically, it refers to eyiti e ba se lara omo (whatever you do to your children) in clause 3, and cataphorically, bi a se ma ko awon omo si ona rere (how we would direct our children to the right path) in clause 10.

Os (she) in clauses 18 and 19 are interpreted as 'she' because of the particular meaning attributed to elomiran (person/other person) in clause 17, which contextually is 'one person who is unable to live in a husband's house.' It obviously is wives who may be associated with this kind of description, hence the interpretation that goes with it. Nwon (they) in clause 31, is different from all its other endophoric uses in the text. It is an inclusive use because it is co-referential anaphorically with Ogbeni Okusanya (Mr. Okusanya).

The following is the display of the above text's cohesive chains:

Table 3.1.7 (16) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.7

The text consists of 5 chains (I, II, IV, VII, and X) and 6 ties (III, V, VI, VIII, IX, and XI). Some general comparison is now necessary between the narrative and the mass media texts. The narrative texts have more personal co-referential ties and fewer demonstratives than newspapers, television and radio texts. The quiz and discussion mass media texts do not show any significant difference from the rest of the mass media texts as far as cohesive relation created by the ties is concerned. These have, however, more demonstrative reference than narrative texts. The cataphoric co-referential nwon (they) is used stylistically in the three sub-genres of the mass media reporting - the 'doer' or the 'performer' of the event is mentioned after the details of the events have been stated. Nwon (they) is also used culturally to refer to one person (instead of many) to show deference. There are, indeed, more exophoric reference in

television and in radio news items than in both narrative and newspaper texts. The mass media texts on quiz and discussion programmes will be compared with the next two texts, spoken forms, because they are closer to spoken than written language.

3.7 - Spoken Texts

Text 3.1.8⁴⁶

This is a casual conversation between Titi, a five-year old girl, and an adult. X stands for the adult participant, and Y for the little girl. (Titi's elder brother Seun is sent to go and buy a packet of biscuits for both of them)

1. X- Wá jòkó, Titi (a gesture accompanies the utterance)
come sit Titi
'come and sit down Titi'

2. Y- Hún ?
'What?'

3. X- Wá jòkó
come sit
'come and sit down'

4. Y- Emi náà maa jé biskit⁴⁷
I d-d AUX.VB. eat biscuit
'Me too will eat biscuit'

(Y nearly falls down from the concrete railing)

5. X- Má mà subú!
do NEG. fall
'do not fall down!'

6. Y- Emi náà maa je biskit
I d-d AUX.VB. eat biscuit
'Me too will eat biscuit'

7. X- Ta ló ra aso yi fún e? (pointing to her
INT.(is+he) buy cloth this PREP. you dress)
'who bought this attire for you?'

8. Y- Ehéen?
'What?'

9. X- Ta ló ra aso yi fún e? (a distant voice is
INT.(is+he) buy cloth this PREP. you heard and she
'who bought this attire for you?' looks at the
direction)

10. Y- móomì⁴⁸ mi
mummy DET.
'my mum (mother)'

11. X- mòómo e ló ra' so fún e (a distant voice
mum your (is+he) buy cloth PREP. you is again
'your mother bought this attire for you' heard)

12. Y- Hun
'Yes'

(silence)

13. X- /móomi/ e ló rà fún e
mum your (is+he) buy PREP. you
'Your mother bought this attire for you'

14. Y- hen
'Yes'

(moomi. 13) «

15. X- Igbàwo ni \nwón\ rà?
PER
when is they (sg.) buy
'when did she buy it?'

16. Y- igbà t'á n ló sí'bi kan, wò
when PREP. we PROG. go PREP. place one look
'when we were going somewhere, see'

17. - mòomo mi ó dè wá rà
mum my she then come buy
'my mother bought it then'

« (moomo. 17)

18. X- \Nwón\ rà
PER
they (sg.) buy
'she bought it'

19. Y- E wo bí báyi (she points to her knees)
you (sg.) look here this way/place
'You, look at this'

20. - tó máa n dùn mi, e wò
that always PROG. hurt me you (sg.) look
'and see, it hurts me, look'

« (to ma a n dun mi. 20)

21. X- \ó\ n dùn è
PER
it PROG. hurt you
'it hurts you'

22. Y- Hen
'Yes'

« (to ma a n dun mi. 20)

23. X- igbàwo \l'ó\ bèrè?
CON.
when (is+it) start
'when did it start?'

- «—(to maa n dun mi. 20)
24. Y- igbi \o\ n dùn mi ni mo subú, wò móomi
 PER
 when it PROG hurt me is I fall look mum
 'when it hurts me, then I fell down, look (mum)'
25. - mi dè wá fi àtikè⁴⁹ si, mo dè wá n ké
 DET then come put powder PREP. I then come PROG. cry
 'my mum then put powder into it and I started crying'
26. X- O wá n ké
 you come PROG. cry
 'you began to cry'
27. Y- Hen
 'Yes'
28. X- kí ló dé tó fi n ké?
 INT. (SEW) happens) that (SEW) PROG. cry
 'What happened that you have to cry?'
29. Y- igbò jé Seun l'ó wá gbé mi subú, wò (points)
 (SEW) (SEW) Seun (is+he) come carry me fall, look
 'when it was Seun who made me fall, look'
30. X- kí ló dé tó fi n ké
 INT. (SEW) happen that (SEW) PROG. cry
 'What happened that you have to cry?'
- «—(to maa n dun mi. 20) «—(to maa n dun mi. 20)
31. - sé \o\ n ta é ni à \b'o\ n dùn è?
 PER CON.
 INT. it PROG. pinch you is or (CONJ.+it) PROG. hurts you
 'is it pinching you or is it hurting you?'
- «—(to maa n dun mi. 20)
32. Y- \ó\ n ta mí
 PER
 it PROG. pinch me
 'it is pinching me'
- «—(to maa n dun mi. 20)
33. X- \ó\ n ta é
 PER
 it PROG. pinch you
 'it pinches you'
34. Y- Hen
 'Yes'
35. X- má ke mó o
 not cry again EMPH.
 'do not cry again.'
36. Y- Hùn ùn
 'Yes'

The cohesive devices in the Text are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
15	1	nwon (they)	P-INC	M.1	moomi.13 (mother)
18	1	nwon (they)	P-INC	0	moomo.17 (mother)
21	1	o (it)	P	0	to maa n dun mi.20 that hurt me)
23	1	l'o (VB+it)	C	M.2	to maa n dun mi.20 (that hurst me)
24	1	o (it)	P	M.3	to maa n dun mi.20 (that hurts me)
31	2	o (it)	P	M.10	to maa n dun mi.20 (that hurts me)
		b'o (Int.+it)	C	M.10	to maa n dun mi.20 (that hurts me)
32	1	o (it)	P	M.11	to maa n dun mi.20 (that hurts me)
33	1	o (it)	P	M.12	to maa n dun mi.20 (that hurts me)

Table 3.20 - Cohesive Devices in Text 3.1.8

This text reveals some variations that exist between adult-to-adult and adult-to-children talk - shorter sentences than normal adult speech (many of the clauses have one word), lack of subordinate clauses, far more repetitions and very simple grammatical relations. The child's frequent use of wo (look) in clauses 16, 20, 24 and 29, as an attention-getter-device is a phenomenon often described as 'the here-and-now semantics' characteristic of 'baby talk.' (Ferguson 1978: 205-274; Bohannon and Leubecker 1988: 89^{ff}). Her use of the 'intrusive pronominal' o (she) (clause 17) in which a subject of a simple sentence is pronominalised is also a feature of child talk. Both these features relate to the child's linguistic development and some general function for which the child is using language 'to mean' in specific situations (Halliday 1978: 45). It also shows the constraints on the adult interactant as he attempts to negotiate and facilitate the communication between both of them. Most of the

utterances have to be repeated because she is being distracted here and there.

The following is a graphic display of the text's cohesive chains:

Table 3.1.7 (18) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.8

The text has just two chains and no ties. Nwon (they) in clauses 15, and 18 is an inclusive co-referential device. The adult interactant uses it to show deference for the girl's mother [clause 13] with whom he is not familiar. The child's reference to her injured knee, which is exophoric but situationally represented in clause 19 by the use of bayi (this), opens up a series of cohesive ties in clauses 21, 23, 24, 31(2), 32, and 33. There is no means of interpreting these ties other than by giving recognition, instantially, to the exophoric referent bayi (this) in conjunction with to maa

n dun mi (that hurts me) in clause 20. The series of ties form the second and longer chains than the first inclusive and shorter chain.

Text 3.1.9⁵⁰

This text is a Yoruba language lesson taught to a third year (junior secondary) High School class in Lagos. The lesson concerns the writing of a composition. The topic is 'The Sauce I Like Best'. The entire text concerns, methodologically, how the pupils will sketch an outline for the essay before writing it.

Teacher

1. E káàrò o (to pupils)
You (all) morning EMPH.
'Good morning'

Pupils

2. E /káàro/ o (as they stand up)
You (all) morning EMPH.
'Good morning'

Teacher

3. ó yá, e jòkó. Nkan t'á má se
it ready you sit what that+we AUX. VB. do
'alright, sit down what we shall do'

(kaaro. 2) "—

4. láàro \yi\ ni àròko l'óri obè tí mo
DEM

morning this is composition PREP. sauce that I
'this morning is (discuss) a composition on 'the sauce I'

5. fèràn jùlo. Nisinyì kí a tó ko /àròko/
like best Now before we (SEW) write composition
'like best.' Now before we begin to write the composition'

6. sé e mò pé a kókó máa ko àwon
INT. you know that we first AUX. VB. write those
'do you know that we first of all need to sketch'

(aroko. 5) "—

7. /ilànà/ t'á má fi ko àròko \yen\
plan we AUX. VB. use write composition that
'a plan that we shall use to guide us in writing it'

8. Nisinyi mo fé kí e má so fún
 Now I want that you AUX.VB. say PREP.
 'Now I want you to start telling'
- « (ilana. 7) (aroko. 7) «
 9. mi \àwon\ ilàná ti a má fi ko \àwon\
 DEM DEM
 me those plan that we AUX.V. use write those
 'me the sub-topics with which to sketch out the plan of'
- (aroko. 7) «
 10. àròko \yen\ Akókó obè tí mo fèrán
 DEM
 composition that first sauce that I like
 'the composition. First, 'the sauce that I like'
11. jùlo l'a fé sòrò lé lóri o. Dayo⁵¹
 best (is+we) want speak PREP. head EMPH. Dayo
 'best' is what we want to discuss. Dayo'

Pupil₁

12. Orúko obè tí mo fèrán jùlo
 name sauce that I like best
 'The name of the sauce that I like best'

Teacher

13. Orúko /obè/ tí mo fèrán jùlo
 name sauce that I like best
 'the name of the sauce that I like best'
14. idí èkeji nkó? èkeji nkó o?
 reason second INT. second INT. EMPH.
 'what of the second reason? what of the second reason?'

Pupil₂

- (obe. 13) «
 15. idí tí o fi fèrán \rè\
 PER
 reason that you (SEW) like it
 'the reason why you like it'

Teacher

- (obe. 13) «
 16. idí tí o fi fèrán \rè\, heen, iketa
 PER
 reason that you (SEW) like it, yes third
 'the reason why you like it, yes, the third'

Pupil₃

- (obe. 13) «
 17. isé tí \ó\ nse ní ara
 PER
 work that it PROG. do PREP. body
 'its usefulness to our health'

Teacher

(obe. 13) «[┐]
18. isé tí \ó\ nse ní ara, ikerin
PER
work that it PROG. do PREP. body, fourth
'the usefulness to our health, the fourth'

Pupil 4

î
19. àwon ohun èlò tí a fi n sè \è\
PER
those thing uses that we use PROG. cook it
'the ingredients we use to cook it'

Teacher

î
20. àwon ohun èlò tí a fi n sè \è\
PER
those thing uses that we use PROG. cook it and fifth INT.
'the ingredients we use to cook it, and what of the fifth?'

Pupil 5

(obe. 13) «[┐]
21. Bí a se n sè \è\
PER
INT. we (SEW) PROG. cook it
'how (the way) we cook it'

Teacher

(obe. 13) «[┐] «[┐] (Bi a se... 22)
22. Bí a se n sè \è\
PER DEM
Léhìn \iyen/ nkó?
INT. we (SEW) PROG. cook it after that INT.
'how/the way we cook it . What happens next?'

(ikefa. 23) «[┐] ┐» (ohun... je e. 24)
23. /ikefà/. (silence) E so \ó/ o. Mo wá so fún yín
PER
sixth You speak it EMPH. I come speak PREP you
'the sixth. You say it. I can tell you.'

(obe. 13) «[┐]
24. nísinyì pé ohun tí a fi n je \é\
PER
now that thing that we use PROG. eat it. INT.
'what foods we use with the sauce. Isn't that it?'

(obe. 13) «[┐]
25. ohun tí a lè fi obè \yen\
DEM
je
thing that we AUX. VB. ADV. use sauce that eat
'what we can use with the sauce'

26. àbí bée kò?
INT. so NEG.
'isn't it so?'

All Pupils

27. Bèè ni!
so is
'Yes!'

Teacher

28. ó tún kù kan kan tó ye
it AUX. VB. ADV. remain one certain that fit
'it remains a certain one that is necessary'
29. kí e tún fi si o, ó kù o
(SEW) you AUX. VB. ADV. add PREP. EMPH. it remains EMPH.
'for you to mention in addition. It remains.'

Pupil₆

- (obe. 13) «
30. Bí \ó\ se máa n rí lí enu
PER
INT. it is AUX. VB. PROG. look PREP. mouth
'how/the way it tastes'

Teacher

- (obe. 13) «
31. kí l'ó fe se⁵² l'enu e?
PER
what (is+it) does do PREP. mouth your
'what would it do in your mouth?'

- (obe. 13) «
32. sé \ó\ má korò l'enu e ni (laughter) èhéen?
PER
INT. it AUX. VB. bitter PREP. mouth your is what
'is it going to be bitter in your mouth? What?'

Pupil₆

- « (obe. 13)
33. \ó\ lè má dùn
PER
it AUX. VB. ADV. NEG. sweet
'it may not be sweet'

Teacher

- « (obe. 13)
34. \á\ dùn kè. ó tún ku eyo kan o
PER
it sweet so it AUX. ADV. remain single one EMPH.
'it will be sweet. It still remains one'
35. eni tó bá lè ronú jinlè
person that AUX. VBS. think deep
'whoever can think hard about it'

36. «—(eni...jinle. 35) (eyo kan. 34) «—(ilu...je e. 37)
 \l'ó\ lè so eyo kan \yen/
 CON. DEM
 (is+he) AUX. ADV. speak single one that
 'can mention this last one'

Pupil 7

37. ilú tí a ti n je \é\
 town where we PERF. PROG. eat it
 'the town where it is eaten'

Teacher

38. E bá mi fún omo í yen l'átewó sé (clap)⁵³
 You help me give child that (is + clap) so
 'you (all) should clap for that child!'

39. Ha ha! ilú tí a ti n je \é\
 PER
 ha ha! town where we PERF. PROG. eat it town where
 'that's right! the town where it is eaten. The town'

40. nwón ti máa n je obè \yen\ jùlo, àbí?
 DEM
 they PERF. AUX. VB. PROG. eat sauce that best INT.
 'in which the particular sauce is widely eaten. Isn't it?'

41. ilú tí a ti n je obè \náà\ jùlo
 DEM
 town where we PERF. PROG. eat sauce (d-d) best
 'the town in which the sauce is widely eaten'

- «—(aroko lori obe. 4)
 42. sé \ó\ ti yé yín báyi nsinyi?
 PER
 INT. it PERF. clear your this now
 'do you all now understand?'

All Pupils

- «—(aroko lori obe. 4)
 43. \ó\ yé wa
 it clear us
 'we understand'

Teacher

44. sé ó ti yé yín báyi nsinyi?
 INT. it PERF. clear you this now
 'do you all now understand?'

All Pupils

45. ?
 ó yé wa
 it clear us
 'we understand'

The cohesive devices in the above text may be shown as below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
4	1	yi (this)	D	N. 1	kaaro. 2 (good morning)
7	1	yen (that)	D	M. 1	aroko. 5 (composition)
9	2	awon (those)	D	M. 1	awon ilana. 6-7 (those plans)
		awon (those)	D	M. 1	aroko yen. 7 (that composition)
10	1	iyen (that)	D	M. 2	aroko yen. 7 (that composition)
15	1	re (it)	P	M. 1	obe. 13 (sauce)
16	1	re (it)	P	M. 2	obe. 13 (sauce)
17	1	o (it)	P	M. 3	obe. 13 (sauce)
18	1	o (it)	P	M. 4	obe. 13 (sauce)
19	1	e (it)	P	M. 5	obe. 13 (sauce)
20	1	e (it)	P	M. 6	obe. 13 (sauce)
21	1	e (it)	P	M. 7	obe. 13 (sauce)
22	2	e (it)	P	M. 8	obe. 13 (sauce)
		iyen (that)	D	O. 1	Bi a se n se e. 22/ (how we cook it)
23	1	o (it)	P - A/C	O/O	ikefa. 23 (the sixth) / ohun ti a fi n je e. 24 (what we use it to eat)
24	1	e (it)	P	N. 10	obe. 13 (sauce)
25	1	yen (that)	D	N. 11	obe. 13 (sauce)
30	1	o (it)	P	N. 16	obe. 13 (sauce)
31	1	l'o (it)	CON	N. 17	obe. 13 (sauce)
32	1	o (it)	P	N. 18	obe. 13 (sauce)
33	1	o (it)	P	N. 19	obe. 13 (sauce)
34	1	a (it)	P	N. 20	obe. 13 (sauce)
36	2	l'o (he)	CON	0	eni le ronu jinle. 35 (whoever thinks deep)
		yen (that)	D - A/C	M. 1/0	eyo kan. 34 (just one) / (ilu ti a ti n je e) (the town ... eaten)
37	1	e (it)	P	N. 23	obe. 13 (sauce)
39	1	e (it)	P	N. 25	obe. 13 (sauce)
40	1	yen (that)	D	N. 26	obe. 13 (sauce)
41	1	naa (the)	D	0	obe yen. 40 (that soup)
42	1	o (it)	P	N. 28	aroko lori obe. 4 (composition on sauce)
43	1	o (it)	P	N. 29	aroko lori obe. 4 (composition on sauce)

Table 3.1.7 (19) - Cohesive Ties in Text 3.1.9

The text consists of several occurrences (six) of the

comparative reference julo (most/best) although some of them occur as a result of sheer repetitions and therefore not in the table. They function in the text as adjuncts (see lines 5, 11, 12, 13, 40 and 41). Neither the entire text nor the comparative reference depicts why one sauce is preferred to the other. Given that there are scores of different sauces⁵⁴ being prepared in many Yoruba homes, the name of any particular sauce is not given. I regard, therefore, this type of comparison as internal to the clause in which it occurs because there is no recognisable descriptive standard (i.e. in the text) by which its referential property of being the best is established. One of the questions one may ask is: first of all, 'what sauce?' But no specific name is given (first pupil [clause 12]). There is also no answer to the second question in comparison with what other sauce or sauces, and why is it or are they less preferable? Even though the sauce may be a referent, it is ambiguously so in this text in so far as its actual identity is never clarified by either the teacher or the pupils. The possibility of its being the 'best' is therefore internal to the clause although with a tacit mutual 'bestness' by the two groups of interactants - the teacher and her pupils.

Below is a graphic display of the text's cohesive chains:

7.	yen (that)	III ilana (plan)
9.	awon (those)	awon (those)
10.	yen (that)	
13.		IV obe (sauce)
15.		re (it)
16.		re (it)
17.		ó (it)
18.		ó (it)
19.		e (it)
20.		e (it)
21.		e (it)
22.		e (it) V Bi...nse (how cook it)
23.		iyen VI ikefa(sixth)
		ó (it)
24.		e (it) ohun ti a fi nje e (what we eat it with)
25.		yen (that)
30.		ó (it)
31.		l'ó (vb+it)
32.		ó (it)

CONT.

33.	II	IV ó (it)	
34.		à (it)	VIII eyo kan (one)
35.			VII eni to...jinle (who can think deep)
36.			l'o (vb+he) yen (that)

continued on next page

37.		e (it)	ilu...je e
			(the town...eat)
39.		e (it)	
40.		yen (that)	
41.		naa (the)	
42.	ó (it)		
43.	ó (it)		

Table 3.1.7 (20) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.8

Table 3.1.7 (20) above has four chains (II, IV, VI, and VIII) and four ties (I, III, V, and VII). The dual type of co-referential device functions twice in the text. ó (it), first of all, refers to the sixth point of the composition plan. It is co-referential, anaphorically, with ikefa (sixth) on the the same line. It is also co-referential, cataphorically, with the actual answer to the sixth point - ohun ti a fi n je e (what we use it [sauce] to eat) in clause 24. Yen (that) in line 36 modifying eyo kan ([single] one) is co-referential, anaphorically, with eyo kan (single one) in line 34. It is also co-referential, cataphorically, with its actual answer in clause 37 - ilu ti a ti n je e (the town where it [sauce] is eaten).

An examination of the two spoken texts reveals some underlying characteristics of the spoken language, particularly those ones which result from its dialogic nature. The most relevant one to this investigation is repetition. There are, in this instance, two types of repetitions. In Text 3.1.8, the adult participant uses repetition (features of repetition that may be more relevant

to the chapter on lexical cohesion) as a functional repair and any occurrence of cohesive device in it is discarded. But in Text 3.1.9, the repetition is cohesively and referentially functional because the teacher who repeats the correct answer given by any pupil uses it to a good effect. She uses it as a teaching strategy to enable the pupils to grasp the correct answer. The only exception to this pattern occurs in clauses 44 and 45 because they are used both by the teacher and the pupils as functional repairs.

Text 3.1.5, though a quiz programme on the television, shares many of the characteristics of a spoken text. Again, concerning cohesive devices, lines 10-12 are regarded as a functional repair and the ties in them are not functional. The use of first and second person speech roles makes texts highly exophoric - although the repetition of the forms throughout the texts contributes to the overall texture. Exophoric reference of this kind is typical of spoken, interactive registers/genre. One common but very important feature of these two spoken texts and the one on quiz programme (Text 3.1.5) concerning referential cohesion is that most of the cohesive devices are organised around the topic of the text. In Text 3.1.5, it is organised around the 'four things' which 'mothers used in those days'. In Text 3.1.8, it is either the child's mother or her injured knee. In Text 3.1.9, a series of personal reference are conspicuously linked with obe (sauce).

11. lolo iwo yio maa gbo iro ilu \yi\
 DEM
 quiet you AUX. VB. ADV. hear sound drum this
 'quiet you will be able to hear the sound of the drum'
12. ketekete bi o ti le je wi pe ona
 clearly as if it PERP. ADV. is that way
 'very clearly even though the place'
13. re jina si ibi ti \won\ gbe n lu ilu \náà\
 PER DEM
 your far PREP. place that they ?(SEW) PROG. beat drum d-d
 'you are is far away from where the drummers are'
14. ki ni o ro wipe o ran iro ilu \náà\
 DEM
 INT. do you think that it help sound drum d-d
 'what do you think helps the sound of the drum'
15. lowo lati wa lati ona to jin be ti
 hand that come from way that far like that
 'come from so distant a place such'
16. a si gbo \o\? Bi o ba se ise /yi/
 PER DEM
 we AUX. VB. hear it if you AUX. VB. do work this
 'that we hear it? if you will do this exercise'
17. iwo yio le dahun ibeere \wonyi\
 DEM. EXT. REF.
 you AUX. VB. ADV. answer questions these
 'you will be able to answer these questions'
18. /Ise akoko/⁵⁶ Oluko re yio wa /irin/ kan fun o
 work first teacher your AUX. VB. look spring one PREP. you
 'First exercise, your teacher will give you a coiled spring'
19. ki idi \eyi\ si inu igi kan ki \o\ ba le
 DEM PER
 put bottom this PREP/PREP tree one (SEW) it AUX. VBS.
 'insert its bottom into a block of wood so that it may'
20. duro daradara. Fi owo osi re mu opin \re\ dani
 PER
 stand very well Let hand left your hold end its handy
 'stand very well. Let your left hand hold its end'
21. Nisinsinyi fun die ninu awon elo irin \naa\
 DEM
 now press few PREP. those coiled spring d-d
 'Now press a few of its rings'

22. papo mo igi, ki o si fi \i\ sile lesekan náà
 together PREP. tree (SEW) you AUX. leave it down at once d-d
 'to the wood and let go suddenly'
 PER
23. ki ni o se akiyesi ? Ki ni o sele
 INT. do you (SEW) notice INT. do it happen
 'what do you notice? What happens?'
24. si owo re ti o fi mu opin irin \náà\ dani?
 to hand your that you use take end spring d-d handy
 'to your hand with which you held the end of the spring?'
 DEM
25. Ise ekeji: To kobo merin si ori tabili re,
 work second arrange coin four PREP. head table your
 'second exercise: arrange four coins on your table'
26. je ki \won\ fi ara kan ara \won\⁵⁷ daradara
 let (SEW) they(?) put body touch body them very well
 'and let them touch one another very well'
 PER PER
27. Fi omo ika re te kobo merin ti akoko
 use child finger your press coin four (SEW) first
 'use your little finger to press the four coins'
28. mo ori tabili, mu kobo karun miran
 to head table take coin fifth another
 'on the table, take the fifth coin'
- (kobo merin. 27) «—
 29. si iwaju \awon\ kobo akoko ti o to si
 PREP. front those coin first that you arrange PREP.
 'in front of those coins already arranged'
 DEM
- (kobo karun. 28) «— «—(awon kobo akoko. 29)
 30. ori tabili, je ki \o\ jinna si \won\ die
 head table let (SEW) it far PREP. them little
 'on the table, let it be further away from them a little'
 PER PER
- (ika re. 27) «— (kobo karun. 28) «— «—(akoko. 29)
 31. wa fi \awon\ ika otun re ta \a\ si \awon\
 then use those finger right your shoot it PREP. those
 'then use your right finger to shoot it at those'
 DEM PER DEM
- «—(awon kobo akoko. 29)
 32. kobo \náà\ Ki ni o sele si kobo
 coin d-d INT. do it happen PREP. coin
 'coins. What happens to the coin'
 DEM

33. ti o wa ni opin kobo ti o to si ori
that it exist PREP. end coin that you arrange PREP head
'at the end of the coins on the'
34. tabili? Idi re ti eleyi fi ri bee ?
table reason PREP. that this AUX. VB. be so
'table? Why did this happen?'

The cohesive devices in the above text are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
2	1	i (it)	P	O	abo. 1 (bowl)
4	1	naa (the)	D	M. 2	abo. 1 (bowl)
7	1	eyi (this)	D	M. 4	ju okuta kekere...odo. 1-4 (throw stone to brook)
11	1	yi (this)	D	M. 2	ilu. 8 (drum)
13	2	won (they)	P	M. 4	awon onilu. 8 (those drummers)
		naa (the)	D	M. 4	ilu. 8 (drum)
14	1	naa (the)	D	M. 5	ilu. 8 (drum)
16	2	o (it)	P	M. 1	iro ilu. 14 (the sound of drum)
		yi (this)	D - C	M. 1	ise akoko. 18 (first exercise)
17	1	wonyi (these)	D - C	M. 5	ki ni sele...dani. 23-24 (what happens...held)
				N. 16	ki ni o si...bee. 32-34 (what happens to...so)
19	2	eyi (this)	D	O	irin. 18 (coiled spring)
		O (it)	P	O	irin. 18 (coiled spring)
20	1	re (its)	P	M. 1	irin. 18 (coiled spring)
21	1	naa (the)	D	M. 2	irin. 18 (coiled spring)
22	1	i (it)	P	M. 3	irin. 18 (coiled spring)
24	1	naa (the)	D	M. 2	irin naa. 21 (the coiled spring)
26	2	won (they?)	P	O	kobo merin. 25 (four coins)
		won (them)	P	O	kobo merin. 25 (four coins)
29	1	awon (those)	D	M. 1	kobo merin. 27 (four coins)
30	2	O (it)	P	M. 1	kobo karun. 28 (fifth coins)
		won (them)	P	O	awon kobo akoko. 29 (those first coins)
31	3	awon (those)	D	N. 3	ika re. 27 (your fingers)
		a (it)	P	M. 2	kobo karun. 28 (the fifth coins)
		awon (those)	D}	M. 1	awon kobo akoko. 29 (those first coins)
			}		
32	1	naa (the)	D}	M. 2	awon kobo akoko. 29 (those first coins)

Table 3.1.7 (21) - Cohesive Ties in Text 3.1.10

Texts 3.1.10 and 3.1.11 are taken from the corpus of perhaps the only available scientific texts written in Yoruba in

Nigeria. Some of the characteristics of scientific texts are 'restricted grammar' and 'less ambiguity' (Sager 1982:9). Others are that they have 'elements and rules specific only to them' (Moskovich 1982:194), 'symbolic language' (Bellert and Weingartner 1982:226-227) and 'homogeneous subjects' (Moskovich op. cit. p.192). Symbolic language refers to the use of, for example, x and y to stand for certain meaningful elements.

Being an instructional guide to carrying out some scientific experiments on the physics of sound, the text's interpersonal effect is two-way structured between the teacher or the instructor and the pupils. The instructional direction is 'do this' in 'this way' and 'what is the result?'

Table 2.1.7 (22) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.10

Text 3.1.10 on Table 2.1.7 (22) contains 6 chains and 5 ties. These may be regarded as forming two distinct patterns; most of the ties forming the first pattern in clauses 1-16 and the chains (except one tie) in clauses 17-32. These two patterns of cohesive devices correspond to the introductory and the experimental parts although each of the experiments forms a distinct group as the chain formations have shown. Wonyi (these) in 17 may be described from three perspectives. Firstly, it may be seen as being co-referential, anaphorically, with the questions in clauses 3-4 and 14-16.

Secondly, it may be seen as being co-referential, cataphorically, with the questions in clauses 23-24 and 32-34. Thirdly, it may be seen as either cohering biphorically or even ambiguously by not indicating precisely to which sets of questions (before or after it) it refers.

Two reasons account for deciding for the second description. Clauses 1-17, first of all, are regarded as introductory to the two exercises hence the 'pseudo experiments' and the questions asked after them are designed to pose experimental, thought-provoking, problem-solving questions. Secondly, it is obvious considering the first reason, that the supervisory role of oluko (teacher) in the experiment as indicated in clause 18 points to a regulatory classroom scientific experiment rather than everyday observable phenomenon as the introductory paragraphs contain. Wonyi (these) is regarded, therefore, as co-referential, cataphorically, with questions in clauses 23-24 and 32-34. In the organisation of cohesive devices in scientific texts, wonyi (these) may be described as functioning cumulatively because it is always used to refer to a series of items concerning experiments and the series of exercises or steps that may be involved.

Generally, there are more demonstrative cohesive devices in the text than personal cohesive devices (14-11). Aiming at precision, the instructional mode of 'this' or 'that', and 'this way' and 'that way,' to effect the directions the experiment should go, evokes the choice of more demonstratives and determiners than personals. The prevalence of demonstrative and definite references in scientific texts

is regarded as typical. Unlike the previous texts, the use of the third person reference falls on inanimate (mostly materials) rather than animate subjects or objects. Apart from the personal reference won (they?) in 13 which is co-referential with animate referent - awon onilu (those drummers), all others cohere with materials for the experiment.

Text 3.1.11⁵⁸

Text 3.1.11. consists of four different simple mathematical data or sums. Each part is obviously demarcated from the other in terms of its inherent organisation, topics, and functions. Section 1 covers lines 1-8; two 9-16; three 17-22, and fourth 23 -28.

1. /Ade/ pinnu lati fi ese rin lati
Ade plan PREP. use leg walk PREP.
'Ade planned to walk from'
2. Eko lo si Abeokuta. Ojo marun \lo\
CON.
Lagos go PREP. Abeokuta day five (is+he)
'Lagos to Abeokuta. He spent five days'
- (Eko - Abeokuta. 2) «—┘
3. fi rin irin ajo \na\
DEM
use walk walk journey d-d PREP. day first
'to walk the distance. For the first day'
- «—┘ (Ade. 1) (Ade. 1) «—┘
4. \o\
rin opa 23,136; ni ojo keji \o\
rin
PER PER
he walk pole 23,136; PREP day two he walk
'he walked 23,136 poles; for the second day he walked'
- (Ade. 1) «—┘
5. opa 20,864, ni ojo keta \o\
rin 19,893,
PER
pole 20,864, PREP.day third he walk 19,893,
'20,864 poles. For the third day he walked 19,893.'

6. ojo kerin 20,106; \o\ si rin opa 1,242
 day fourth 20,106; he ADV. walk pole 1,242
 'the fourth 20,106; he also walked 1,242 poles'

7. ni ojo karun. Gbogbo opa
 PREP. day fifth all pole
 'on the fifth day. All the poles'

8. ti \o\ rin je d. Ki ni d?
 PER
 that he walk equals d what is d
 'that he walked equals d. What is d?'

9. Awon /ore marun/ kan lo si sobu
 those friend five certain go PREP. shop
 'Five friends went to the shop'

10. ti nwon ti nta (ore marun. 9) \oko/, enikookan \won\ si
 PER
 that they PERF. PROG. sell vehicle each-each them then
 'where vehicles are sold, each person'

11. ra okookan. Iye ti \nwon\ ra \awon\ oko
 PER DEM
 buy each-each cost PERF. they buy those vehicle
 'bought a vehicle. The prices for the vehicles'

12. \na\ /niwonyi/:ti eni kini naira 1963 ti eni
 DEM DEM
 d-d vb+these that person first naira 1963 that person
 'are these: for the first person 1963 naira, that of the'

13. keji naira 1734, ti eni keta naira 1613, ti eni kerin
 second naira 1734, that person third 1613, that person four
 'second 1734 naira, third, 1613 naira that of the fourth'

14. ti o ra aloku oko naira 947, ti eni karun naira 2,107
 that he buy old vehicle naira 947, that person fifth 2,107
 'who bought one second-hand for 947 naira; the fifth 2,107'

15. Owo ti \nwon\ san fun \awon\ oko
 PER DEM
 money that they pay PREP. those vehicle
 'the money that they paid for those vehicles'

16. maraarun je naira L. Ki ni L?
 five-five equal naira L. what is L
 'all the five equals L naira. What is L?'

- i
17. Ni oko awon Tomi /tanki/ omi nla nla
 in farm those Tomi tank water big big
 'In Tom's people's farm are very big water tanks'
18. merin lo wa nibe. Galonu omi ti \nwon\
 (tanki.17) «
 PER
 four that exist there gallon water that they
 'There are four. The gallons of water they'
19. gba /niwonyi/: tanki kini galonu 15,200
 DEM
 take vb+these tank first gallon 15,200
 'contain are these: the first tank 15,200 gallons.'
20. tanki keji galonu 22,147, galonu keta 10,100,
 tank second gallon 22,147, gallon third 10,100,
 'the second tank 22,147 gallons, the third 10,100 gallons'
21. galonu kerin 33,897. Omi ti mbe ninu
 gallon fourth 33,897 water that PROG. is PREP.
 'the fourth 33,897 gallons. The water in'
22. tanki mererin je galonu W. Ki ni W?
 tank all-four equal gallon W what is W
 'the four tanks are W gallons. What is W?'
23. Ijoba ibile kan na awon owo /wonyi/:
 i DEM
 government local one spend those money these
 'One local government spent the following money:'
24. lori ile iwe kiko, Naira 40,340; lori
 PREP. house book building naira 40,340 PREP.
 'on school building, 40,340 naira; on'
25. titun ona se Naira 17,146; lori ile
 make road repair naira 17,146, PREP. house
 'road repair 17,146 naira, on the'
26. iwosan Naira 15,000; lori omi ero
 healing naira 15,000, on water machinery
 'hospital 15,000 naira, on pipe-borne water'
27. Naira 18,136. Naira melo ni ijoba
 naira 18,136 naira many does government
 '18,136; How much naira did the government'
28. «(ijoba ibile.23) «(omi ero.26-24) «(omi ero.26
 ibile \na\ na fun \awon\ ise \wonyi?\ -24)
 local d-d spend PREP. those work these
 'of the local area spent for these works?'

The text's cohesive devices are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
2	1	lo (VB+he)	C	0	Ade. 1
3	1	na (the)	D	0	Eko lo si Abeokuta. 2 (Lagos to Abeokuta)
4	2	o (he)	P	M. 2	Ade. 1
		o (he)	P	M. 2	Ade. 1
5	1	o (he)	P	M. 3	Ade. 1
6	1	o (he)	P	M. 4	Ade. 1
8	1	o (he)	P	M. 6	Ade. 1
10	1	won (them)	P	0	ore marun. 9 (five friends)
11	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 1	ore marun. 9 (five friends)
		awon (those)	D	0	oko. 10 (vehicle)
12	2	na (the)	D	M. 1	oko. 10 (vehicle)
		niwonyi (vb+these)	D - C	0	1963. 12
				0	1734. 13
				0	1613. 13
				M. 1	947. 14
				M. 1	2,107. 14
15	2	nwon (they)	P	M. 5	ore marun. 9 (five friends)
		awon (those)	D	M. 3	oko. 11 (vehicle)
18	1	nwon (they)	P	0	tanki. 17 (tank)
19	1	niwonyi (VB+these)	D-C	0	15,200. 19
				0	22,147. 20
				0	10,100. 20
				M. 1	33,897. 21
				0	40,340. 24
23	1	wonyi (these)	D-C-	M. 1	17,146. 25
				M. 2	15,000. 26
				M. 3	18,136. 27
				M. 4	ijoba ibile. 23 (local government)
28	3	na (the)	D	M. 1	omi ero. 26 (pipe-borne water)
		awon (those)	D)		
		wonyi (these)	D)	M. 1+	ile iwosan. 25-26 (hospital)
				M. 2	titun ona se. 25 (road repair)
				M. 3	ile iwe kiko. 24 (building of schools)

Table 3.1.7 (23) - Cohesive Ties in Text 3.1.11

The above text 3.1.11, though a scientific text, is quite different from Text 3.1.10. The former describes a typical scientific experiment and this one consists of a number of mathematical problems. Mathematics, in spite of several

symbols, uses words (Rotman 1988: 6, 7).⁵⁹ Even though a specialised part of a natural language, a mathematics text must be linked referentially. Any scientific text has, therefore, referential properties which enable the other interactant(s) to understand the process of acting or responding to its content. Our focus of attention in this text is to examine those referential cues inherent in this mathematical text.

The following table sets out the text's cohesive chains:

continued on next page

CONT.			
VIII		IX	X
23. wonyi (these)	ijoba	ibile (local govt.)	clauses 24-26
■		■	■
40,000-18,136		na (the)	awon (those)
28.			wonyi(these)

Table 3.1.7 (24) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.11

The above Table 3.1.7 (24) contains 3 chains and 7 ties. Each of the mathematical problems is also distinctly organised in the table. The two scientific texts seem to have large numbers of ties because their events are fragmented in a similar way to the summary part of news items (television or radio). It contains also a number of cataphorically and cumulatively extended reference already introduced in Text 3.1.10. Niwonyi (vb+these) in 12 is used cataphorically to refer to the list of prices and their total price, mathematically and cumulatively represented by L. Niwonyi (vb+these) in 19 is also used in a similar way. It functions cataphorically to refer to the list of capacities of the four water-tanks and the cumulative number of gallons, W. Wonyi (these) in clause 23 is the third cumulatively cataphoric implicit cohesive device in the text. Like the last two sub-texts, it occurs in the text prior to a list of projects and expenses incurred. Wonyi (these) and awon (those) form a compound cohesive tie and cohere, anaphorically and inversely with the same list of expenses.

The demonstrative ties which direct the attention of the pupils 'this way' or 'that way', and the cumulative use of

wonyi (these) which is followed by a list of either numbers or materials mark the two scientific text significantly apart from other types of texts.

3.9 - Poetry Texts

Text 3.1.12. 60

This poem is meant mostly for children in Primary and High Schools. It is a didactic poem aimed at teaching these young people the importance of hard work.

1. Múra s'ísé, òré mi
haste PREP. work friend DET.
'work hard, my friend'
2. Isé l'a fi í di eni gíga
work (is+we) use (SEW) become person high
'It is through hard work that we become important persons'
3. Bí a kò rí eni f'èhin ti
if we NEG. see person PREP+back support
'if we have none to support us'
4. Bí òle l'à á rí
INT. lazy (is + we) look
'we look like a lazy person'
5. Bí a kò r'èni gbékèlé
if we NEG. (V.+person) rely upon
'if we have none to rely upon'
6. A tera mó 'sé eni
we persist PREP. work person
'we put our best to our work'
7. /iyá re/ lè lówó lówó
mother your ADV. PREP. (VB+money) PREP. hand
'your mother may have much money'
8. /Bàbá/ si lè l'ésin l'èékàn
father AUX. VB. ADVS. V+horse (VB+stable)
'your father may have horses in the stable'
9. Bí o bá gbójú le \won\
PER
if you AUX. VB. + eye PREP. them
'if you only rely on these'

10. O té tán ni mo so fún o
 you disgrace finish is I tell PREP. you
 'you will be a disgrace, I say to you'
11. /Ohun tí a kò jiyà fun/
 thing that we NEG. suffer PREP.
 'what we do not suffer for'
12. Sé kì (ohun... fun. 11)
 \í\ le t'ójó
 PER: EXT. REF.
 does NEG. it AUX. ADV PREP. day
 'does not last long'
13. /Ohun a bá f'ara sisé fun/
 thing we AUX. VB. +. body (VB. + work) PREP.
 'What we worked for ourselves'
14. " (ohun... fun. 13)
 \L' o\ npé l'ówó eni
 CON. EXT. REF.
 (VB. +it) PROG. last PREP. +hand person
 'lasts longer in one's hands'
15. Apá l'ará, ìgùnpá ni iyèkan
 hand (V. +body) elbow is relation
 'Our hands are our sources of strength'
16. Bí /ayé/⁶¹ nfé o lóni
 if world PROG. like you today
 'if the world likes you today'
17. Bí o bá l'ówó lówó
 if you AUX. VB. (VB. + money) (PREP. +hand)
 'if you have much money'
18. " (aye. 16)
 Ni \won\ máa fé o l'óla
 PER
 (SEW) they AUX. VB. like you (VB. tomorrow)
 'they will like you tomorrow'
19. Tàbí bi o wà ní ipò àtátà
 or if you exist PREP. position important
 'or if you are in an important position'
20. Ayé a yé o sí tètítèrín
 world AUX. VB. honour you PREP. laughter
 'People will honour you with smiles'
21. Jé kí o d'eni nráágo
 Let (SEW) you become-person PROG. suffer
 'The moment you start suffering'
22. Kí o rí b'áye ti í sí'mu sí o
 (SEW) you see like+world PERF. grimace PREP. you
 'the people start to frown at you'

23. /èkó/ si tún nso ni í d'ògà
Education AUX. VB. ADVS. PROG. make person become master
'Education also makes a person become a master'
24. Múra kí o kó \o\ dáradára
PER
haste (SEW) you learn it very well
'Be ready to learn very well'
25. Bí o sì rí òpò èniyàn
if you AUX. ADV. see many people
'if you come across many people'
26. Tí \won\ nfi èkó s'èrin rín
PER
that they PROG. make education VB. laugh laugh
'who make education a laughing-stock'
27. Sóra kí o má f'ara wé \won\
PER
becareful NEG. you AUX. VB. PREP. body compare them
'Be careful not to imitate them'
28. iyà mbò f'omo ti kò gbón
suffering PROG. come PREP. child that NEG. wise
'Suffering lies ahead for an unwise child'
29. Ekún mbe f'omo t'o nsa kiri
crying PROG. is PREP. child that. he PROG. run about
'crying lies ahead of a child who plays truant'
30. Má f'òwúró seré, òré mi
NEG. VB. morning waste friend DET.
'Do not waste your youth, my friend'
31. Múra s'ísé, ojó nlo!
haste PREP. work day PROG. go
'work hard, the day passes by'

The text's referential cohesive devices are organised below:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
9	1	won (them)	P	0	iya. 7 (mother), baba. 8 (father)
12	1	i (it)	P	0	ohun ti a ko jiya fun. 11 (what we do not suffer for)
14	1	l'o (VB+it)	C	0	ohun a ba f'ara sise fun. 13 (what we worked for ourselves)
18	1	won (they?)	P	M. 1	aye. 16 (world- [metaphor])
24	1	o (it)	P	0	eko. 23 (education)

26	1	won (they?)	P		
27	1	won (them)	P	0	eniyan. 25 (persons)
				M. 1	eniyan. 25 (persons)

Table 3.1.7 (25) : Cohesive Ties in Text 3.1.12

poetry, like scientific texts, is a different genre from the ordinary language either spoken or written. Yet it may be spoken and written. Poetry is often regarded as 'the most formalised manifestation of language' (Jakobson in Pomorska and Rudy [1985:39]). As a result, a poetry text like a scientific text is a specialised form of a natural language. Summing it up, Waugh (1985:144) remarks that 'poetry is the use of language par excellence.'

Some reasons may be given why a poetry text is very different from an ordinary language text. It offers many salient different features. A poem shows a compact, and most of the times complex, structural whole. Unlike the ordinary language, it is far less contextualised. That is, its verbal content is far more independent of context particularly as often shown by the relations of rhyme, alliteration, assonance and so on.

All this does not mean that a poem exists in a vacuum. It does contain evidence of a general history and cultural context - the semiotic environment in which it is written. Yoruba poetry, in particular, is mostly rendered orally. Oral poetry therefore depicts a great aspect of the people's day-to-day life (see Olatunji 1982:57) by direct and indirect references to people and events. Yoruba poetry is often classified into: epic and didactic (Ogunbowale 1970:150). Text 3.1.12 is exhortatively didactic. It is a poem well-

known to all primary school age children in Yoruba States in the country. By its constant recitation, it has become, particularly to the children, a carrier of some special kind of meaning to hard work.

The text's cohesive chains are organised below:

Table 3.1.7 (26) - Cohesive Chains in Text 3.1.12

Table 3.1.7 (26) above has five ties (I-V) and 1 chain (VI). The occurrence of more ties than chains is indicative of several topics which are briefly mentioned. Even though the base referential elements are varied (e.g. iya, baba [mother, father]; aye [world] - IV etc.), all the referential devices are personal.

Considering the specific sense in which reference is being investigated in this work, the poem is obviously cohesive in other respects. From the beginning to the end, it consists of words of exhortation addressed to an imaginary friend, also by an unknown addresser who, in this case, is the poet. One insight this perspective gives is the poet's moral (which is didactic) intention regarding the youths; the ones, in particular, who might want to rely on their parents' already accumulated riches or wealth rather than work hard themselves. The poet, therefore, sees the need to be impersonal. The use of the collective a (we) in clauses 2 - 5, and the two variant uses of the second person possessive pronoun re (yours), and the first person possessive pronoun mi (my) all depict this impersonal tone of the poet. All these, in some way or another, which is not strictly the concern of this work, also contribute to the overall understanding of the poem.

Text 3.1.13⁶²

This six-line poem is also a didactic one - albeit for the adult. It warns against the tempting pride mostly associated with rich people. It also reminds the reader or listener of the transient nature of riches. Though this is a universal sentiment, this particular poem is by far more meaningful in the Yoruba semiotic environment.

1. Eni t'o lówó k'o ma fi gbéraga
 person that+he VB. +money NEG. AUX. VB. use proud
 'whoever has money should not be proud'

2. Eni ti kò ní k'ó mú sùúrù
 person that NEG. has NEG. +he take patient
 'whoever does not should be patient'
 í
3. Awon òtòsi nde'eni nsùn té ⁶³
 those destitute PROG. become PROG. sleep cushion EMPH.
 'those very poor may become very rich' (live comfortably)
4. Aláso púpò nkù kan
 owner+cloth many PROG. remain one
 'those with many clothes (i.e. riches) may be left with one'
5. /Eye/ l'olá, /eye/ lo'lá⁶⁴
 bird VB. +riches bird VB. +riches
 'riches are like a bird' [refrain]
- (eye. 5) «—
6. Oluwa ma je \o\ fò kúrò n'ílé wa
 Lord NEG. allow it fly away PREP. house our
 'may the Lord not let it fly away from our home'

The following table shows the text's only referential cohesive device:

CN	NT	IED	TR/PD	D	PIL
6	1	o (it)	P	0	eye. 5 (bird (2))

Table 3.1.7.(27) - Cohesive Tie in Text 3.1.13.

The above poem has just one verse. Since it is, like the previous one, meant to be recited, its sound effect is all the more compelling. Also like Text 3.1.12, its didactic function is clear - a universal truth is expressed about the vicissitudes of the human life. K'o (NEG. +he) in clause 2 is structural.

Table 3.1.7 (28) - Cohesive Chain in Text 3.1.13

The poem has just one tie. The only cohesive device is the personal reference o (it) which is anaphoric to the two occurrences of eye (bird) in clause 5. The poem is, however, rich in other cohesive devices - repetition, collocation, opposition, antonym and several other devices particularly metaphors concerning 'riches', 'poverty', 'bird' and so on. All of these elements have relevance particularly in the culture of the users of the language.

3.10 -Conclusion

A few general comments on this chapter now may be made. In the language, any of the basic kinds of reference - personal, demonstrative, and comparative, particularly the first two, may be anaphoric or cataphoric or both. Cohesive comparative reference is very limited in the data and this may reflect generally on the language as a whole. There are, however, many non-cohesive general comparative references. Anaphoric devices are predominant in the texts and presumably, in the language. Cataphoric devices cluster in quiz and educational texts.

The prevalence of the anaphoric ties is understood because it is one of the main resources that any language possesses to link messages together in a text - the one that has been said with the one said NOW!

The narrative texts contain more personal reference than demonstrative. The mass media texts, on the other hand, contain more demonstrative reference than personals, or on

the other hand, may have a fair number of both forms of reference. Scientific texts, like mass media texts, use more of the demonstrative reference - particularly 'this', 'that', and most especially the cataphora wonyi (these) after which there is a list of items. Exophoric reference are far less in narrative texts than mass media texts. In mass media texts, apart from the normal use of nwon (they), three other special uses occur. It often appears in a text, at first, as an exophoric tie until later when its referent emerges and it becomes classifiable as cataphoric. It is thus a stylistic device used in the mass media. Secondly, its use may be co-referential not with a plural referent, but rather a single referent. When used this way, it is culture-specific. That is, it is used to show deference either to someone in a position of authority, or because of a significant difference in age. The third one is exophoric use whereby its referent is in the situation. In this circumstance, certain things are done or are expected to be done by a group of people whose identity is not regarded as important to the message.

Some differences between spoken and written texts emerge. Two of the four texts from the mass media - a quiz on television, and a discussion on radio, are, observably, closer to the spoken language than the two news texts. These are closer to spoken forms like the child-adult conversation and the classroom lesson texts in regard to their forms of co-referential ties. The two poems described are didactic and contain very few co-referential devices. Didactic poems often contain more impersonal or metaphorical reference

interpretable in the particular context of culture in which it is written. By being impersonal, the poet, stylistically, does not want to appear didactic. It is not unlikely that some traditional Yoruba epic poems, particularly ijala (hunters' chants) and oriki (cognomen chants) may have a tremendous amount of referential cohesive devices because most of these are composed to highlight the past deeds of heroic and historic characters.

Apart from the linkage property of co-referential devices as briefly observed above, they may be indicative of a particular genre. In science, for example, they are co-referential, more often than not with inanimate referents. Most importantly, the co-referential devices give shape to the organisation of the topics and themes in the text. That is, the organisation of these devices are patterned along the main ideas in the text.

Finally, an explanation may be given concerning the way the texts are described in this chapter. Going through each text clause by clause may appear tedious, but being the first attempt at the investigation of such a phenomenon in the language, this method of description seems to be the most practical in order to be able to give a fairly reliable description of the types of co-referential devices in the language, and some of the differences in the genres.

Notes

1. Reference, from an interdisciplinary perspective, cuts across several disciplines: namely, among several others, philosophy, logic, psychology, cognition, etc. Similarities are commonly defined and distinctions drawn between reference and sense (Lyons 1968:424-428, 1977a:174, 177-206); and denotation (Lyons 1969:293, 1977a:206-215, Palek 1977:360-366), inference (Grimes 1975:302-314, Schwarz 1979:15-172, Thrane 1980:7-8, Sanford 1985:183-204, Vonk 1985:205-218, Corsaro 1985:186-188); concreteness/abstraction (Grimes 1975:316-318; Lyons 1977a:191; Thrane 1980:7-12) ambiguity (Katz and Fodor 1963 in Nida 1975:87); predication (Lyons 1979:93); and logic (Lyons 1969:193, Palek 1977:360).
2. A language, generally, 'refers/designates/expresses' etc. (Palek 1977:359). In SFT terms, this type of referential function can be regarded as interpersonal reference. In some way, it is closely related to the usage 'terms of address' in other models of sociolinguistically-based descriptions (Lyons 1977a:197, Head 1978:151-211, Daramola 1983). Apart from these interpersonal references, there are other kinds of referring expressions like those often evoked by the deictics - nominals and pronominals which characteristically, are entity or proposition-referring expressions. Others are place-referring expressions particularly the demonstrative adverbs which do not function within the nominal group (Noun Phrase) Halliday and Hasan 1976:37; Lyons 1979)
3. Text 3.1.1. is from Ireke Onibudo by Fagunwa pp. 6-7, but copied here from Yoruba Orthography by Ayo Bamgbose, Ibadan University Press, p. 32.
4. We might have a line before this one having this translation - 'who is by the same mother as my father'.
5. The class of polymorphic nouns consists of six nouns. Most of them have three different forms functioning as subject, object and genitival qualifiers. These are also differentiated for persons: first, second and third.
6. Text 3.1.1. is from Adiitu Olodumare by D.O. Fagunwa, Nelson, 1961. Page 18.
7. The dotted line shows an omission between the two parts of the texts. This is the omitted part - 'Bi o ba ti le orin ti o wipe "Oju ole re", (Womu); "Aya ole re", (Womu); "ehin ole re", (Womu); "ati be be lo!". I have decided to omit this part for 'space management.' Being a song, it is related more to lexical rather than the kind of reference we are investigating.
8. In modern orthography, oun is used in place of on.

9. In non-technical language, the morphemes ending the verbs influence the form of the succeeding pronominal.
10. Further on 'narrator as participant' see, for example, Daramola (1984) 'A Stylistic Analysis of the Language of Achebe's Arrow of God'; Unpublished M.A. Dissertation, Postgraduate School, University of Lagos, Nigeria.
11. Text 3.1.2., like all the newspaper texts used in this and chapter 2, is a reporting text. Since a newspaper 'is always very eclectic' (Crystal 1969:173); so are Yoruba newspapers. We have therefore focussed mainly on reporting newspaper texts. This text is taken from Isokan, February 24 - March 2, 1987; (ed.) Moni Adewale, published by Ile Itewe Konkoodu ti Naijiria, Ikeja, Naijiria. The whole text is about three times as long as the one extracted, but the content of the part of the text presented for analysis gives a coherent understanding of the report.
12. Contrary to the orthographical style of lo (he) in the text, the newspaper still uses the contracted style as in clauses 1 (2), 3, 4, 7, 11, 15, and 20.
13. Ohun (that) also functions in the language as an adverb meaning 'beyond' or 'yonder' -having a locative meaning. Whenever it does, it is preceded by a preposition (e.g. si [into] or ni [at]).
14. In A Dictionary of the Yoruba Language (p.233), Yi, Eyi are marked as 'third pers. sing., demonstr. pron. 'this.' For eyi, Eyi are defined as 'pronominal adj. 'this'. There is therefore no clear difference between the words grammatically.
15. This text is taken from Gboundoun newspaper published by Sketch Press Ltd.'; (Ag.ed) - R. Ade Olajide. Published Wednesday February 25 - Tuesday March 3, 1987 p.1. It reports the same event as Isokan in Text 3.1.2.
16. Wonti appears a print error. It contains two words won (them) and ti (the perfective marker/that) that are not by any convention written together.
17. tu = ka is an example of serial verbs as briefly identified in Chapter 2.
18. It is the won of wonti that functions cohesively as o of l'o (vb+s/he) in the contracted cohesive device. Even then, it ought to have been written as nwon ti (they+PERF.) rather than the way it is written - (them+PERF.).
19. Nwon (they), is the subjective form of won (them) - the latter the objective form.
20. 'Unusual', in the sense that it introduces a new

phenomenon to the evolving types of co-referential devices.

21. see A Dictionary of the Yoruba Language, p. 136.
22. Both texts are extracted from longer stretches of text. Also see note 11 above.
23. Text 3.1.4 is recorded from television - LTV 8, Ikeja Lagos Weekend Television programme Irohin Agbaye, March 1, 1987.
24. The radio is obviously different from the television. In radio the effect of 'sight' is missing.
25. A corollary of highlighting is the method of summarising the main parts of the news at the end.
26. This feature also belongs to radio texts.
27. 'Adiitu' is a quiz programme on LTV 8. The word or title literally means 'a puzzle', or 'something packed that needs to be unpacked.'
28. The presenter thanks everyone - the participants and members of the audience and signals the beginning of the quiz.
29. The use of 'eighteen', an English word for its equivalent in Yoruba ikejidinloqun is an example of code-mixing between English and the other indigenous Nigerian languages. The quiz programme is expected to be completely produced in Yoruba, except when any question (very rare indeed) requires some translation between English and Yoruba or any other Nigerian languages.
30. 'Geesi' and 'eebo' are synonyms - both mean 'English' in the language. The combination of both in that clause show a feature of the spoken form of the language.
31. Girisi is a kind of melted animal fat or viscous lubricant used to lubricate (i.e. condition) the skin. It is the assimilated Yoruba form of the English word 'grease' (or some kind of pomade).
32. It should be noted awon ohun kan in clause 11, and awon nkan ohun both mean fairly closely 'those very things' in this context.
33. These surely are not 'functional repairs' as were clauses 6-8.
34. There was a significant pause after the question was asked.

35. This text is an extract from a radio news item from the Ogun State Broadcasting Corporation, Abeokuta. It was broadcast in February 1987.
36. Another text from the Ogun State Radio (see 35 above). This, however, is a discussion programme directed mainly to the parents of school-age children; and also to the children themselves.
37. By using E to address only Mrs Ogunsola, the presenter shows a deferential attitude.
38. From the text, Mrs Ogunsola is the first participant.
39. The speaker uses school instead of ile-iwe, which is its Yoruba equivalence. This is, again, an evidence of code-mixing by a bilingual individual.
40. Like the contracted cohesive device l'o; li (is) + o (he); ko inherently consists of ki (not) + o (he).
41. Won (them) in the clause seems to be a slip of the tongue in the speech of the discussant. Although it is not an ambiguous statement the meaning is distorted. The speaker's aim, apparently, is to address the children. So instead of won (them), wa (us) would have been appropriate. The whole distortion of meaning begins in the preceding two sentences where the discussant both includes and excludes himself from the group of the parents.
42. This is a common saying among the language users, particularly the elders.
43. As the presenter calls the name of each participant and thanks him/her, each of them either responds by saying 'thank you' or by, presumably, nodding the head.
44. This name Osisanya seems to refer to the same name Okusanya as the presenter earlier used in the text to address him.
45. The o is the expletive o. It is commonly used at the end of utterances by most Yoruba speakers as an emphatic particle.
46. This text is part of a larger Casual Conversation text between myself and a five year old girl at the balcony of a duplex at the University of Lagos, Nigeria, on my trip back home for data collection. It was in February 1987.
47. Biscuit also has its assimilated form in Yoruba.
48. Moomi is a corrupt form of mama (mother), and very close to the English form 'mummy'.

49. Atike may refer to talcum powder; a common household remedy used by parents for their children.
50. This is a Yoruba lesson text taught at Eletu-Odibo High School, Abule-Oja, Yaba, Lagos. January, 1987.
51. The teacher calls on Dayo among a few pupils who put up their hands to suggest points for the essay plan.
52. There seems to be an omission of ri (taste) in that sentence. It may read instead - 'ki l'o fe se ri l'enu e?' (How would it taste in your mouth?).
53. Clapping is a pedagogical device used to reinforce a good student's answer.
54. Examples of different sauces are obè ègúnsí (melon sauce), obè ata (stew sauce), obè ilá (okro sauce), obè àpòn (palaver sauce - see A Dictionary of the Yoruba Language, page 39, column 2) etc.
55. Texts 3.1.10. and 3.1.11. are from Workbooks: Iwe Akeko Sayensi 6 (Students' Science Textbook 6) pp. 11-12; and Matimatiki 4, Iwe Akeko (Mathematics Students' Book 4) pp. 59-60. These books were used for the integrated Primary School Curriculum Scheme in January 1970. It was a six-year project embarked upon by the Institute of Education University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo) under the directorship of Professor Babs Fafunwa. Yoruba, rather than English, was used as a medium of instruction throughout the six years. English was taught only as a subject. The hypothetical basis was that by the end of the programme, this group of children would have had a richer school experience by being taught in their first language. The hypothesis is considered to be proven correct (Fafunwa 1982). The text is divided into three parts: clauses 1-17 is the preamble; 18-24 is step 1, and 25 - 32, Step 2. Part 32-34 documents observations and results. Its title is Bawo ni iro se n lo lati ibikan de ekeji? (How does sound travel from one place to another?)
56. There ought to be a colon after akoko (first) as in ekeji (second) in clause 25. This is necessary to enable the reader to see clearly the ends and the beginnings of the exercises, and differentiate these from the instructions.
57. Another option for that clause will be - 'Jé ki wón fi ara kan ra dárádára.' This means this same thing but more economical.
58. This is an arithmetic text. The heading is Isiro (arithmetic). It is taken from Matimatiki 4 Iwe Akeko (Mathematics 4, Students' Book).
59. Rotman argues for these axes or aspects of discourse: referential, formal and psychological. Concerning

referential axis, he observes that 'any mathematical text is written in a mixture of words, phrases, and locutions drawn from recognisable natural language together with mathematical marks, signs, symbols, diagrams, and figures that (we suppose) are being used in some systematic and previously agreed way'; (see also Vine 1984:157-160).

60. This poem is titled: Isé ni òògùn isé (Work is the drug/panacea for poverty). It is taken from Akojopo Ewi Aladun by J. P. Odunjo; Longman Nigeria Ltd.; Page 3.
61. Aye (world) refers generally in the Yoruba cultural milieu, and particularly in this context, to all the people with whom one may come in contact, and specifically to those ones who will want to do evil to the other person. Literally, therefore, it means 'the world', but metaphorically, it has a meaning as in the old English phrase 'the world, the flesh and the devil.'
62. This poem is taken from the same book (see note 61) on page 21. The title is Orin Kilanko (What Song Do We Sing?).
63. Ite will, in most contexts, relate to the throne of a king - which in all cases throughout Yoruba land symbolises riches.
64. This is an idiomatic expression.

CHAPTER FOUR

LEXICAL COHESION

4.0 - Introduction

All types of cohesive relations, as earlier remarked in this work, presuppose some other elements in the co-text for their interpretation. Referential Cohesion functions, typically, within the items of the nominal group - 'the semantic representation of the participant' (Halliday 1985a:50) and is realised by grammatical cohesive ties. Grammatical ties establish the meaning relation which exists between these cohesive elements. The cohesive relation in reference is, therefore, realised through the grammar. Lexical cohesion is, however, realised through the vocabulary.

Lexical cohesion extends beyond the scope of the nominal group; it also covers the verbal as well as the adverbial groups. Generally, lexical items occupy any position in the grammatical structure, and lexical cohesion is realised by the occurrence of the same, similar or related lexical items in the text. Like referential cohesion, however, the 'two-ness' of lexical cohesion is evident because 'the very terms carry the implication of reciprocal elements since an element by itself, can neither be its own repetition nor can it be synonymous with itself' (Hasan 1984b:185).

Although some types of words (e.g. general noun) are said to have referents either when they presuppose other words in the text, or when accompanied by referential cohesive items; (Halliday and Hasan 1976:274-283; Lyons (1968:403-404);

Carter 1987:15-17) reference, it must be emphasised, is not directly relevant to lexical cohesion. Halliday and Hasan argue as follows:

"Properly speaking, reference is irrelevant to lexical cohesion. It is not by virtue of any referential relation that there is a cohesive force set up between two occurrences of a lexical item, rather, the cohesion exists as a direct relation between the forms themselves (and thus is more like substitution than reference)." (1976: 283, 284)

Halliday and Hasan, in common with other linguists (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 285-286, 290-292; Halliday et. al. 1964: 33 & 36; Lyons 1968: 68-70; Cummings and Simmons 1983: 178; Maley 1985b: 152-153), find it necessary to distinguish between a lexical item and a word. A word, for example, may be used in three ways or levels; firstly as an orthographic element, secondly as a grammatical entity and thirdly as a lexical item. A word identified at these three levels is thought to function in the same way, that is, one word may share part or all of these three levels at different times in different contexts. Yet some words can be classified as lexical items but not every lexical item can be classified as a word.

Halliday draws a clear distinction between a lexical item¹ and a word:

"...there is no one/one correspondence in exponence between the item which enters into lexical relations and any one of the grammatical units. It is for this reason that the term "lexical item" is used in preference to "word", "word" being reserved as the name for a grammatical unit, that unit whose exponents, more than those of any other unit, are lexical items." (1961: 273)

A lexical item is then, 'the smallest unit in the meaning system of a language that can be distinguished from other similar units'.² It may be a word, two words, or a phrase

and even an idiom. To exemplify this - tú (break/untie) and ká (around/about) which in its spoken or written form may consist of several words between them is a lexical item (e.g. 'olopa /tu/ awon onijo /ka/' ('the police disbanded the dancers')) . Furthermore, fi ikùn lu ikùn (use stomach beat stomach), consisting of four words - fi (use), ikùn (stomach), lu (beat), ikùn (stomach), is an idiom which means 'consult' or 'to consult' and is also a lexical item.³

How then does SFT view lexical cohesion? As the topic suggests, it basically concerns the investigation of the lexical items in either spoken or written texts. As a speaker or a writer uses language, his or her choice of lexical items is organised, most of the time unconsciously, through the selection of related items. These items are grouped into 'open set' and 'closed set' (Halliday et. al. 1964:22-24; Lyons 1968:436; Olusola 1982:158). An 'open-set' consists of a group of lexical items which have the same contextual range and function in the same situation types. This means that they have the same, similar or direct opposite meaning in a contextual range. These belong mostly to the classes of nouns and verbs in the language. A 'closed set,' on the other hand, is grammatical⁴; it consists of items of the structure such as personals, tense, gender markers, and negators.

Functioning between lexical and grammatical items is a class of general words or nouns (Halliday and Hasan 1976:274^{ff}). These words belong to groups of 'human noun' (e.g. 'people'), 'place noun' (e.g. 'place') and 'fact noun' (e.g. 'idea').

They are general in meaning because their interpretations usually depend on some other elements in the text (see Carter's (1988:9-10) description of 'core' words or vocabulary). Forming the superordinate members of lexical sets, these general words play important roles as part of verbal interaction particularly in the spoken language. One of these roles is the expressing of interpersonal meaning which may be attitudinal (e.g. idiot, dear). Most importantly, this group of words which correspond⁵ to the main group of lexical items have⁵ cohesive force in texts and are treated as instances of lexical cohesion (Halliday and Hasan (1976:280-281, 283).

Lexical items therefore are not bounded like grammatical items. Lexical items may be grouped into sets which form semantic relations with one another in the text. This lexico-semantic relation is potentially cohesive. Unlike reference whose cohesive relation is typically that of co-reference, that of lexical items is typically co-extension⁵ (Halliday and Hasan 1985:74 and 80; Hasan 1984b:185-187).

As the concept of choice is perhaps more explicit in the use of lexical items than say the phrase or the clause, lexical cohesion clearly relates to the two basic axes of paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations (Halliday 1959:10, 1976:75; Sinclair 1987:331; Hudson 1984:43; Lyons 1968:436, 1977:261 and 264).⁶ Syntagmatically, lexical items are related to 'structure' because they are organised in an ordered linear sequence (which he [Halliday] refers to as 'co-occurrence') and they are located within some

recognisable close distance (which he [Halliday] calls 'significant proximity'). Paradigmatic relation relates to the concept of 'system' in SFT. The open-endedness of lexical items which may result in the groupings of 'lexical set' is paradigmatic. The linear organisation of lexical items and the groupings of lexical sets are mutually defining as are 'structure' and 'system.'⁷

The mutual relationship between system and structure is rooted in the lexicogrammatical⁸ concept of SFT, the choice of words and the grammatical structures (Halliday 1976:75). Quoting Whorf, Hasan remarks:

"...we are all mistaken in our belief that any word has an 'exact meaning'... the reference of the words is at the mercy of the sentences and the grammatical patterns in which they occur." (1987:200)

Lexicogrammar⁹ may be explicated further by reference to context. Halliday asserts:

"In lexis, as in grammar, it is essential to distinguish between formal and contextual meaning. Once the formal description has identified the categories and the items, these can and must be treated contextually." (1961:276)

For what may be described as 'the complete meaning of a word,'¹⁰ its contextual environment becomes crucial. This means that any user of a language, though most of the time unconsciously, uses lexis linguistically and contextually. The context in which a lexical item functions delimits its particular meaning.

4.1 - Categories of Lexical Cohesion

For the general concept of lexical cohesion in English,

Halliday and Hasan (1976: 288, 1985: 82) suggest the following categories¹¹ which are most influential in achieving textual cohesion.¹²

4.1.0 - Reiteration

This is a type of lexical cohesion which concerns the repetition of a lexical item. It is the simplest or the most direct form of lexical cohesion. It may involve the repetition of the actual lexical item or its synonym. A synonym is the use of a lexical item which shares a meaning relation with a preceding lexical item (Halliday 1985a: 310, Manning 1989: 116). Synonyms may either be complete (absolute) that is, sharing all of the lexicogrammatical characteristics of the preceding lexical item, or in-complete (partial).¹³ Antonymy relates to the preceding lexical item by negation or by contrast in meaning. Halliday and Hasan (1985: 80) define this as 'the oppositeness of experiential meaning.' Some examples may be shown as follows:

(1) (i) Awon òyà tí wá inú oko àgbàdo wa
those hedgehogs PERF. come PREP. farm maize our
'those hedgehogs have come into our maize plot'

(ii) Ní \alé\ mo de \tākúté\ sí oko àgbàdo náà
PREP. night I set trap PREP. farm maize d-d
'at night, I set a trap in the maize plot'

(iii) Ni \òwúrò\ ojó kejì \ide\ náà kò re
PREP. morning day two trap d-d NEG. spring
'in the morning of the second day, the trap did not
spring (i.e. go off)

Agbàdo (maize) in (ii) above is a repetition of its form in (i). Ide (trap) in (iii) is synonymous with tākúté (trap) in (ii). Owúrò (morning) in (iii) is an antonym of alé (night) in (ii).

4.1.1 - Hyponymy

Hyponymy is a relation which holds between a lexical item and its sub-classes (Halliday and Hasan 1985:80). The basic lexical item is referred to as the superordinate item, and its sub-classes as hyponyms. It means that both hyponyms and superordinate items are within the same lexical set (lexical items which attract a paradigmatic grouping) but they differ in some characteristics. When 'animal' is superordinate, for example, 'cat' and 'dog' become its co-hyponyms. In example (2) below òyà -(i) (hedgehog) is a hyponym of eranko (animal) -(ii). The superordinate item has a more general characteristic of which the hyponym shares a specific aspect. The relations which exist between a superordinate lexical item and its co-hyponyms may be organised into a hyponymic hierarchy.

4.1.2 - Meronymy

Meronymy¹⁴ constructs a part-whole relation. The sub-parts of the item are referred to as co-meronyms. In English, 'man', for example, is a meronymic lexical item, and 'eyes', 'legs' etc. are co-meronyms naming the parts of the item 'man.' Another example is shown in the following text:

(2) (i) Tàkúte náà mú \òyà\ ó sì gé e lara
trap d-d hold hedgehog it AUX. cut it PREP. body
'the trap caught the hedgehog and cut its body'

(ii) \eranko\ náà gbé kùkùté \apá\ iyókù lo
animal d-d carry stump arm remain away
'the animal ran away with its arm's stump'

Apá (arm) -(ii) above is a meronymy of òyà (hedgehog) -(i).

4.1.3 - Collocation

Collocation¹⁵ refers to the linear relation or association of a small or large number of lexical items which occur within some recognisable proximity in a text. These items may or may not belong to the same classes but co-occur meaningfully. The tendency to co-occur, semantically, is what collocation is about. The patterns formed by these lexical items may be either purely lexical, grammatical or both, as these categories often overlap.¹⁶ Collocational relations, unlike those of synonymy, antonymy and hyponymy, do not depend mainly on the paradigmatic relation.¹⁷

When collocates are formed, the lexical items may be organised into lexical sets because of the meaning relations that they share. At many times, such collocates become indicative of a particular register or a variety of the language. In a particular context, this association or co-occurrence of lexical items forms a 'collocational range.' This means, in part, that the meaning of a lexical item in a context is strengthened by, or is dependent on, its nearby collocates. Halliday and Hasan (1976:286-287, 290) emphasise that such collocates exert cohesive force as long as they occur in adjacent sentences in the lexical environment. The lexical environment will be the extent of text which is relevant in the description of an item.¹⁸ The cohesive force that is exerted normally grows progressively weaker as the textual distance between the items increases. Considering that the data used for this study are not extremely long, Gutwinski's view is relevant:

"How far apart such clauses can be and still be said to display lexical cohesion is an empirical question. The reader's ability to remember a lexical item and to associate it with another occurrence of the same item later on in the text might provide a criterion for stating how distant clauses can be and still display lexical cohesion." (1976: 80)

Since none of the texts in my data is excessively long, the problem of distance between two lexical cohesive relation may not occur.

4.1.4 - Instantial

The textual environment defines the instancial category of lexical cohesion. This lexicogrammatical category creates a specific kind of unity in discourse by equivalence, naming and semblance. All the semantic relations of synonymy and the others, typically, express experiential meanings and the instancial category is textbound (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 289, 1985a: 81). By being textbound, is meant that an instancial lexical relation 'is an artefact of the text itself, and does not extend to the system' (Hasan 1984b: 201). An example is given below:

(3) Speaker A: ibeere 'eighteen'
 question eighteen
 'the eighteenth question'

Speaker B: é é é \gèési\ l'e fò hun
 eh English VB+you speak that
 'Eh! that's said in English'

Speaker A: ibéère méjidinlogún
 question eighteen
 'the eighteenth question'

= méjidinlógún

Through the linguistic phenomenon of code-switching, speaker A above, first of all, uses 'eighteen' (English) for its Yoruba equivalent - méjidinlógún (eighteen). Speaker B calls

A's attention to that error by using qèési (English) and èèbó (English) both of which relate to 'eighteen' by instantiation. I also regard méjídínlógun (eighteen) as used by speaker A after correcting the error as instantial. The difference between the two instantial uses is that the first is realised by 'naming' and the second by 'equivalence.' Semblance, as a sub-category of instantiation, is achieved when a lexical cohesive relation is established by two unrelated lexical items. Hasan (1984b: 202) gives the following examples in English - 'the deck was like a pool' and 'all my pleasures are like yesterdays'¹⁹ where 'deck' and 'pool,' 'pleasures' and 'yesterdays' are the main lexical items which may occur in a text.

4.2 - Some Factors of Occurrence of Lexical Items

Not all lexical items in a text whether 'general' or 'specific' can generate cohesion. The factor of frequency of occurrence of some lexical items plays a crucial role. Some lexical items which easily collocate with any other lexical items may or may not form lexical cohesion depending on the circumstance of occurrence. Halliday and Hasan (1976: 290) observe that 'in general the higher the frequency of a lexical item (its overall frequency in the system) the smaller the part it plays in lexical cohesion in texts.' Other items of lexis that have been classified as 'closed system' in the preceding chapter (e.g. those grammatical ones forming co-referential ties) are, except in rare cases, excluded in this consideration. In this chapter, a group of lexical items such as E (you) and ta (who) are described as

cohesive because of their repetitive relations even though each occurrence refers to a different thing. Yet others are prepositions and preverbs (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 290-291; Gutwinski 1976: 80-81).

The basis for the lexical cohesive relation set up by Halliday and Hasan as briefly described above is therefore that a lexical item is meaningful not merely because of its internal properties but because it may be repetitive, contrastive, differential or instancial with other lexical items in a particular text functioning in a particular linguistic and extralinguistic environment.

Hasan (1984b: 195, 202) often excludes collocation²⁰ from lexical cohesion because it proved problematic in two ways. Firstly, she believes that unless the details of the relations involved are unpacked in the Firthian sense, it is best to avoid it in research. Secondly, she realises that it proved difficult to operationalise the category sufficiently to ensure consistent analysis. In spite of Hasan's position regarding collocation, Halliday uses it although in a rather limited way (Halliday 1985a: 312-314). What seems practicable, particularly in the context of this study, is to restrict collocation to lexical items within the same general field of meaning when there is a high degree of predictability in the occurrence of the items. For example:

(4) (i) Funke àti Tosin wo inú /ilé/
Funke CONJ. Tosin enter PREP. house
'Funke and Tosin entered the house'

(ii) Nwón tún wo inú /ogbà/ èhìn ilé
they AUX. ADV. enter PREP. garden PREP. house
'they also entered the garden behind the house.'

The lexical items, ilé (house) in (i) and oqbà (garden) in (ii) collocate with each other not merely by functioning in the same general field of meaning but by a kind of proximity relation.

4.3 - Lexical Density

Lexical density is the means whereby the proportion of lexical items to the total number of words is measured in a text (Halliday 1985c: 64; Ure 1971: 445). It may be expressed as a percentage and calculated by the formula:²¹

$$\text{Lexical Density (L. D.)} = \frac{\text{number of lexical items (L. I.)} \times 100}{\text{total number of words (T. W.)}} \quad 1$$

A distinction is, however, made between lexical items and grammatical items (section 4.0 and 4.1.5). Grammatical words seems to occur in texts more than lexical items. Lexical items may be grouped into two; some have relatively high frequency of occurrence, and some low frequency. Those lexical items with low frequency of occurrence contribute a great deal to lexical density (Halliday 1985: 64-65). Lexical density is expressed, therefore, as the ratio of lexical and grammatical items.

Halliday (1985c: 65-66) suggests that the mean of lexical items per clause may be more revealing than the measurement in proportion to the total number of words. In my data, however, the spoken ones in particular, may even be more revealing if their lexical density is measured by finding the mean of their lexical items in proportion to their 'messages' rather than clause (the clause also a unit of message). A

message, in this regard, does not have the status of a clause. Rather, it consists of at least two lexical items which form a meaningful unit of information (i.e. 'a message content' - Richards et. al. 1985:176) For example:

- (5) (i) Aláso púpò nkù kan
 owner+cloth many PROG. remain one
 'one with many clothes may be left with one'
- (ii) Eye l'olá, eye l'olá
 bird VB+riches bird VB+riches
 'riches/wealth is like a bird' (refrain)

*homonym?
 of 'olá'riches'*

(i) above is a clause, but (ii) is not because its transitivity is implicit (i.e. elliptical) rather than explicit. Some examples may not have an implicit transitivity.

As well as the above two measurements, I measure in this study what I refer to as Lexical Cohesive Density (L.C.D.). Lexical cohesive density measures, in percentage, the proportion of lexical items in chains to the total number of lexical items in the text. It is, therefore, a second degree (lexical items being the first degree) of measurement to the total number of words comprising the text. This is expressed as follows:

$$\text{Lexical Cohesive Density} = \frac{\text{number of lexical cohesive items (L.C.I)} \times 100}{\text{total number of lexical items (L.I.)} \quad 1}$$

This measurement seems to quantify the percentage of the lexical items which actually help to determine the topic(s) in the text in proportion to the total number of lexical items. The figures of all these measurements for the entire texts analysed in this chapter will be collated at the end.

4.4 - Field and Register of Discourse

In the previous chapter on reference, referential cohesive devices and their organisation into chains become significant because they are indicative of the topic(s). This is so because the cohesive devices, through paradigmatic relation, establish identity of reference by pointing backward or forward mainly to participants, processes, and circumstances in the text.

Lexical cohesion involves both the paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations in the text and these are established through similarity or what in SFT is referred to as co-classification and co-extension (Halliday and Hasan 1985:82). Lexical items in cohesive function realise, therefore, the experiential meaning through the establishment of the field of discourse²² because the cohesive lexical chains track the participants, processes and circumstances as they sequentially establish the field of the register of a text. Through lexical cohesion, the inter-relatedness of cohesion and register - the functional varieties or types of language in use is established because it is both which effectively define a text²³ (chapter 1; 1.3.2). It is the interaction thus established by these participants and processes which forms the source of coherence in texts (chapter 5).

I will examine lexical cohesion in seven of the fourteen texts in which patterns of co-referential devices have already been examined in the previous chapter. The cohesive relations in the texts are shown, and lexical cohesive chains are drawn in order to see graphically the development of the

field of discourse. Finally, the lexical densities are calculated and are briefly discussed.

Key to some of the terms used in the analysis

<u>syn</u> : synonym	<u>exc</u> : exclusive	<u>seq</u> : sequential
<u>rep</u> : repetition	<u>mer</u> : meronymy	<u>equ</u> : equivalence
<u>ant</u> : antonymy	<u>co-mer</u> : co-meronymy	<u>set</u> : lexical set
<u>ins</u> : instantiation	<u>hyp</u> : hyponymy	<u>com</u> : complete
<u>inc</u> : inclusive	<u>sup</u> : superordinate	<u>num</u> : numerical
<u>col</u> : collocation	<u>met</u> : metaphorical	<u>nam</u> : naming

I set up the following categories in order to clarify further the lexical relations:

- Inclusive - a category of lexical items which has a specific or shared core meaning component along a unifying dimension
- exclusive - a group of two or more lexical items which appears to be synonymous but are hardly so
- complete - a group of two or more different lexical items which has exactly the same cohesive meaning
- sequential - a group of lexical items which, in cohesive relation, may be organised in certain logical order
- numerical - a category of lexical items which has numbering meaning in their cohesive relation
- metaphorical - any lexical item that has more than its literal meaning

4.5 - Text 4.1 Narrative Text (Text 3.1.0 in Chapter 3)

1. Nigbati o di oju ale
when it is eye night
'when it was late at night'
2. mo pada wa si abà wa
I back come PREP. hut our
'I came back to our hut'
3. mo \lo\ si odo egbon mi agba okunrin
ant: wa.2
I go PREP. place elder my older male
'I went to my elder brother's place'
4. ti ó je omo iya \baba\ mi
col: okunrin.3
PERF. who is child mother father my
'who is my father's brother (i.e. uncle)'
5. mo wi fun u pe
I say PREP. him that
'I said to him that'

6. mo nfe de \takute\
col: de. 6
I PROG. -want set trap
'I want to set a trap'
7. o si gbe okan fun mi
he then carry one PREP. me
'he then gave one to me'
8. mo \gbe\ e \lo\ si inu \oko\ wa
rep: 7 rep: 3 col: aba. 2
I carry it go PREP. PREP. farm our
'I carried it into our farm'
9. ni inu \agbado\, mo \de\ e si
col: oko. 8 rep: 6
in PREP. maize I set it PREP.
'inside the maize-plot and I set it on'
10. \oju\ ona awon òyà ti nje \agbado\ wa
rep: 1 rep: 9
eye path those hedgehog that PROG. eat maize our
'the track of those hedgehogs that eat our maize'
11. nigbati o di \owuro\ ojo keji
ant: ale. 1
when it is morning day two
'in the morning of the next day'
12. \takute\ na kò \ré\
rep: 6 col: takute. 6
trap d-d NEG. spring
'the trap did not spring (i. e. go off)'
13. nitori biotilejepe awon \oya\ \wa\ \pa\ \agbado\
rep. 10 rep: 2 col: nje. 10 rep: 10
even though those hedgehogs come kill maize
'even though those hedgehogs came to destroy the maize'
14. nwon ko rin si \oju\ \takute\ mi
rep: 10 rep: 12
they NEG. walk PREP. eye trap my
'they did not come to where my trap was'
15. sugbon nigbati o di \owuro\ \ojo keta\
rep. 11 col: ojo keji. 11
but when it is morning day three
'but in the morning of the third day'
16. ti mo \lo\ wo o
rep: 8
that I went look it
'that I went to look at it'
17. mo \ri\ i pe o ti \ré\
syn: wo. 16 rep: 12
I see it that it PERF. spring
'I saw that it has sprung'

18. o ti \mu\ \oya\ ni \apa\
 col: re. 17 rep: 13 mer: oya. 18
 it PERF. hold hedgehog PREP. arm
 'it has held hedgehog by the arm'
19. o ti \ge\ \apa\ \oya\
 col: mu. 18 mer: apa. 18 rep: 18
 it PERF. cut arm hedgehog
 'it has cut hedgehog's arm'
20. \eranko\ na si ti \gbe\ kukute iyoku lo
 sup: oya. 19 rep: 8
 animal d-d (SEW) PERF. carry stump remain away
 'the animal has run away with its arm's stump'

The following table shows the text's lexical relations:

Clause Number (CN), Number of Ties (NT), Lexical Items (LI),
Presupposed Items and Types of Cohesive Relations (PI & TCR)

CN	NT	LI	PI & TCR
3.	1	<u>lo</u>	[ant: <u>wa</u> (come). 2]
4.	1	<u>baba</u> (father) ²⁴	[col: <u>okunrin</u> (man). 3]
8.	3	<u>gbe</u> (give) <u>lo</u> (go) <u>oko</u> (farm)	[rep: 7] [rep: 3] [col: inc. <u>aba</u> (hut). 2]
9.	2	<u>aqbado</u> (maize) <u>de</u> (set)	[col: inc. <u>oko</u> (farm). 8; <u>aba</u> (hut). 2] [rep: 6]
10.	3	<u>aju</u> (eye) <u>oya</u> (hedgehog) <u>aqbado</u> (maize)	[rep: 1] [col: <u>aqbado</u> (maize). 9; <u>oko</u> (farm). 8 <u>takute</u> (trap). 6; <u>nje</u> (eating). 10] [rep: 9; col: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog). 10]
11.	1	<u>owuro</u> (morning)	[ant: <u>ale</u> (night). 1]
12.	2	<u>takute</u> (trap) <u>re</u> (spring)	[rep: 6; set: <u>re</u> (spring). 12; col: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog). 10; <u>aqbado</u> (maize). 10, 9; <u>oko</u> (farm). 8; <u>aba</u> (hut). 2] [col: <u>takute</u> (trap). 12]
13.	4	<u>wa</u> (come) <u>oya</u> (hedgehog) <u>pa</u> (kill) <u>aqbado</u> (maize)	[rep: 2] [rep: 10; col: <u>takute</u> (trap). 12, 6; <u>aqbado</u> (maize). 10, 9; <u>oko</u> (farm). 8] [col: ins. <u>nje</u> (eat(-ing)). 10] [rep: 10, 9; col: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog). 13, 10; <u>oko</u> (farm). 8; <u>aba</u> (hut). 2]

14.	2	<u>takute</u> (trap)	[rep: 12, 6; re (spring). 12; col: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog). 13, 10; <u>agbado</u> (maize). 13, 10, 9; <u>oko</u> (farm). 8; <u>aba</u> (hut). 2]
		<u>oju</u> (eye)	[rep: 10, 1]
15.	2	<u>owuro</u> (morning)	[rep: 11; ant: <u>ale</u> (night). 1]
		<u>ojo keta</u> (third day)	[col: <u>ojo keji</u> (second day). 11]
16.	1	<u>lo</u> (go)	[rep: 8, 3; col: <u>rin</u> (walk). 14]
17.	2	<u>ri</u> (see)	[col: seq. <u>wo</u> (look). 16]
		<u>re</u> (spring)	[rep: 12; col: <u>takute</u> (trap). 14, 12, 6; ant: <u>de</u> (set). 9, 6]
18.	3	<u>mu</u> (hold)	[syn: inc. /seq. <u>re</u> (spring). 17, 12; col: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog). 13, 10, <u>takute</u> (trap). 14, 12, 6]
		<u>oya</u> (hedgehog)	[rep: 13, 10; col: <u>mu</u> (hold). 18; <u>takute</u> (trap). 14, 12, 6; <u>agbado</u> (maize). 13, 10, 9; <u>oko</u> (farm). 8]
		<u>apa</u> (arm)	[mer: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog). 18, 13, 10]
19.	3	<u>ge</u> (cut)	[syn: inc. <u>re</u> (spring). 17, 12; seq: <u>mu</u> (hold). 18]
		<u>apa</u> (arm)	[rep: 18; mer: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog). 18, 13 & 10]
		<u>oya</u> (hedgehog)	[rep: 18, 13, 10; col: <u>mu</u> (hold). 18; <u>takute</u> (trap). 14, 12, 6; <u>agbado</u> (maize). 13, 10, 9; <u>oko</u> (farm). 8]
20.	2	<u>eranko</u> (animal)	[sup: <u>oya</u> (hedgehog) - hyp: 19, 18, 13, & 10]
		<u>gbe</u> (carry)	[rep: 8, 7]

Table 4.5 (1) - Lexical Cohesive Relations in Text 4.1

Apart from the identification of the lexical cohesive relations as in Table 4.5. above, a few comments on some lexical items become necessary because their roles may not be self-evident in the text.

Three lexical item oju ale (eye night [at night]). 1, oju ona (eye path [track, i.e hedgehogs]). 10, and oju takute (eye trap [a spot on the set trap]). 14 present an interesting collocation. The word oju (eye) in the three lexical items means various things other than its literal meaning.

The material process pa (kill).13 collocates, instantially, with another material process nje (eat [-ing]).10.²⁵ The narrator of the events in the text assumes that the readers understand, in the socio-cultural environment, that the hedgehogs go to the maize plot merely to 'eat,' while the farmer regards them as 'killing' his crop. Ojo keji (second day).11 and ojo keta (third day).15 collocate only in the narrative sequence of the events. This sequential unfolding of the events in the text becomes evident consequent upon the choice of lexical items used to describe the way the takute (trap) functions in the process of catching an hedgehog. These are re (spring).17, mu (hold).18 and ge (cut).19. That is, on the hedgehog's arrival on the spot of the trap, it 'springs', 'holds or catches' it and 'cuts' a part of its arm. What results from this is the meronymic description of apa (arm) to oya (hedgehog) in clauses 18-19, and eranko (animal).20 as superordinate to oya (hedgehog) its hyponymy.

Table 4.5 (1) above indicates that both takute (trap) in number 14 and oya (hedgehog) in number 19 form the longest cohesive relations in the text.

The following table shows the lexical chains in the text:

	I	II		
1.	ale	oju(eye)		
	(night)		III	IV
2.			wa	aba(hut)
			(come)	
				V
3.		lo		okunrin (man)
		(go)		
4.				baba(father)
				VI VII
6.				de takute(trap)
				(set) VIII
				continued on next page

7.					gbe(carry)	
8.		lo (go)	oko (farm)		gbe(carry)	
9.				de (set)	IX agbado(maize)	
10.		oju (eye)			X agbado oya (maize)('hog)	XI nje (eating)
11. owuro (morn.)						XII ojo keji (second day)
12.				takute (trap)		
				re (spring)		
13.		wa(come)			agbado oya (maize)	npa
14.		oju rin (eye)(walk)		takute (trap)	(hedgehog)	(kill)
15. owuro (morn.)						ojo keta (third day)
16		lo (go)				XIII wo (look)
						ri (see)
17.				re (spring)		
18.				mu (hold)	oya('hog)	
					apa(arm)	
19.				ge (cut)	apa(arm)	oya('hog)
20.					gbe(carry)	eranko(animal)

Table 4.5 (2) - Lexical Chains in Text 4.1

Some of the cohesive chains in Table 4.5 (2) above have more lexical items than others. Some chains consist of only process while some both processes and participants. Numbers VII and X are the longest of all the 13 chains. Chain VII consists of takute (trap) occurring thrice, re (spring) twice, and mu (hold/catch) and ge (cut) once each. Chain X consists of oya (hedgehog) occurring four times, apa (arm) twice, and eranko (animal) the superordinate lexical item (i.e. for oya [hedgehog]) once. Forming the two most

significant relations in numbers 14 and 18 in Table 4.5 (1), both takute (trap) and oya (hedgehog) appear to be the 'core' items for any description of the text's topic (e.g. 'the setting of a trap to catch hedgehogs in a maize farm'). With these two lexical items and several others, oko (farm), agbado (maize), in particular, show that the text's semantic variety concerns 'farming.'

The text's lexical densities are as follows:

(a) Lexical density:

(i) Total number of words = 126
 Lexical items = 65
 Percentage = 51.58

(ii) Lexical items = 65
 Number of messages = 21
 Mean = 3.09

(b) Lexical cohesive density:

Lexical cohesive items = 44
 Lexical items = 65
 Percentage = 67.69

% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	% Lexical Cohesive Density
51.58	3.09	67.69

Table 4.5 (3) - Lexical Densities in Text 4.1

4.6. - Text 4.2 Newspaper [Text 3.1.2 in Chapter 3]

1. l'ehin awuyewuye ti ko l'afiwe
after complaints that NEG. compare
'after series of unprecedented complaints'
2. ati \wahala\ ija fun eto ara eni
syn: inc. awuyewuye. 1
and trouble fight PREP. right body self
'and the trouble made to fight for one's rights'
3. pelu iwa \tenbelekun\ to fa oro kotu²⁶ l'ese
syn: inc. wahala. 2
with conduct rebellion that cause word court PREP+leg
'together with a rebellion that became a court issue'
4. Gomina Adetunji Olurin tu Igbimo
Governor Adetunji Olurin break council
'Governor Adetunji Olurin broke up the council'
5. l'obaloba Ipinle Oyo ka ni ijefa
PREP+king king state Oyo about PREP. six days ago
'of the traditional rulers in Oyo State six days ago'
6. Ni \ojo\ naa gan an lo si
syn: ijefa. 5
PREP. day d-d precisely is+he likewise
'on that day, precisely, he likewise'
7. ti fi iwe \atuka\ \igbimo\ naa s'owo
syn: tu-ka4-5 rep: 4
PERF. send book breaking council d-d PREP+hand
'had sent letters of the disbandment of the council'
8. si okookan awon \oba\ alaye
syn: l'obaloba. 5
PREP. each one those king owner-of-earth
'to each of the highnesses'
9. to je omo \igbimo\ ohun ni \aafin\ won gbogbo
rep: 4 col: oba. 8
that is child council that PREP. palace them all
'who is a member of that council in his palace'
10. Gegebi alaye re, o ni sise bee
according explanation his he say PROG. do that
'according to his explanation, he finds that step'
11. di dandan l'atari \awuyewuye\ ati
rep: 1
become necessary is+because complaints and
'has become necessary because of the complaints and'
12. \rogbodiyan\ enu \loolo\ yi i
syn: inc. wahala. 2 syn: inc. ijefa. 5
trouble PREP. lately this
'the troubles in the recent past'

13. eyi i to mu ki \wahala\ isakoso
 that PERF. take (SEW) trouble governance
 'that has led the problem of governance'
 rep: 2
14. \igbimo\ naa di \oro\ \ile ejo\ giga
 rep: 9 rep: 3 syn: com. kotu. 3
 council d-d become word house court high
 'that is, that of the council to a high court'
15. Ogagun \Olurin\ tun \s'alaye\ pe
 rep: 4 rep: 10
 military person Olurin AUX. ADV. VB+explain that
 'Captain Olurin also explained that'
16. titi ti \ijoba\ yoo fi se ikede
 col: isakoso
 until (SEW) government AUX. VB. make do announcement
 'until the government makes an announcement'
17. lori i \atunto\ \igbimo\ naa
 ant: atuka. 7 rep: 14
 PREP. reconstruct council d-d
 'on reconstructing the council'
18. oun yoo maa fi ikunlukun pelu
 he AUX. VB. 1 AUX. VB. 2 use stomach-stomach PREP.
 'he would always consult with'
19. \okookan\ awon \omo\ \igbimo\ ohun
 rep: 8 rep: 9 rep: 17
 each one those child council that
 'each of those members of that council'
20. l'ori iyowu to ba je mo adugbo won
 PREP. whatever that AUX. VB. relate PREP. area them
 'on whatever concerns their areas of jurisdiction'

The text's lexical cohesive relations are shown as follows:

CN NT LI

PI & TCR

2. 1 wahala (trouble) [syn: inc. awuyewuye (complaints). 1]
3. 1 tenbelekun (rebellion) [syn: inc. wahala (trouble). 2; awuyewuye (complaints). 1]
6. 1 ojo (day) [syn: ijefa (six days ago). 5]
7. 2 atuka (disbandment) [syn: tu-ka (break up). 4 & 5]
igbimo (council) [rep: 4]
8. 1 oba (king) [syn: l'obaloba (king king). 5]
9. 2 igbimo (council) [rep: 7, 4]
aafin (palace) [col: oba (king). 8; l'obaloba (king king). 5]

11. 1 awuyewuye(complaints)[rep: 1; syn: tenbelekun(rebellion)
3, wahala(trouble). 2]
12. 2 rogbodiyan(trouble)[syn: awuyewuye (complaints). 11, 1;
tenbelekun(rebellion). 3, wahala
lolo(recently) (trouble). 2]
(col: ojo(day). 6; ijefa(six days ago. 5)]
13. 1 wahala(trouble) [rep: 2; syn: rogbodiyan (trouble). 12,
awuyewuye (complaints). 11, 1; ten-
belekun (rebellion). 3]
14. 3 igbimo (council) [rep: 9, 7, & 4]
oro (word/issue) [rep: 3]
ile ejo (court) [syn: com: kotu (court). 3]
15. 2 Olurin (Olurin) [rep: 4]
s'alaye (explain) [syn: alaye (explanation). 10]
16. 1 ijoba(government) (col: isakoso (governance). 13]
17. 2 atunto(re-constitute)[ant: atuka(disbandment). 7; tu-ka
(break up). 4-5]
igbimo (council) [rep: 14, 9, 7 & 4]
19. 3 okookan (each one) [rep: 8]
omo (child/member) [rep: 9]
igbimo (council) [rep: 17, 14, 9, 7, & 4]

Table 4.6 (1) - Lexical Cohesive Relations in Text 4.2

The four lexical items rogbodiyan (trouble). 12, awuyewuye (complaints). 1 & 11, tenbelekun (rebellion). 3 and wahala (trouble). 2 & 13 are synonymous particularly in the context of this text. Tu (break/untie). 4 and ka (about/around). 5 both mean 'break up' or 'disband' in this text. It is a 'split' material process. From the lexical item Ile ejo giga (high court). 14, ile ejo (court) forms a complete synonym with kotu (court). 3 and both are co-hyponyms of their superordinate item ile ejo agba patapata (supreme court)²⁷ which is not available in the text. Ogagun²⁸ (military person/captain/general). 15 may be regarded as synonymous with gomina (governor). 4 in this text especially as they both are titles used for the same person. Ogagun is a military title, while gomina is a political (civil) title.

Numbers 13 and 19 (iii) form the longest sets of cohesive relations in the text. The lexical item igbimo (council) is reiterated several times in number 19 and the four synonymous lexical items rogbodyan (trouble).12, awuyewuye (complaints).1 & 11, tenbelekun (rebellion).3 and wahala (trouble).2, 13 in number 13.

The following table shows the text's lexical cohesive chains:

Table 4.6 (2). - Lexical Chains in Text 4.2

Table 4.6 (2) above, like numbers 13 and 19 in Table 4.6 (1), shows that each of chains I and VI has the largest lexical items. Chain I consists of the four synonymous lexical items already mentioned with awuyewuye (complaints).1,11 and wahala (trouble).2,13 occurring twice each, and chain VI has iqbimo (council) reiterated six times. Taking into consideration our general understanding of the text and these lexical patterns, it may be suggested that the topic of the text can be - 'a problem/disagreement among members of the council.'

Certain lexical items also reveal the text as having, not necessarily a newspaper genre, but a reporting characteristic. It is this feature that distinguishes it from, say for example, the narrative text already examined in 4.5. These lexical items may be divided into three parts. Firstly, verbal process such as s'alaye (explain).15, and nominal items such as alaye (explanation).10 and kede (announcement).16 are related to the field of newspaper reporting. Secondly, the events that are often reported concern ijoba (government).16 regarding isakoso (governance).13 in certain states (ipinle Oyo (Oyo State)).5 or iqbimo (council).4 in certain area (adugbo).20. Others may be events from the law courts (ile ejo).14. Thirdly, the nature of on-going activity is shown by the choice of the lexical items as ijefa (six days ago), and loolo (lately).12. The following are the lexical densities in the text:

(a) Lexical Density

(i)	Total number of words	=	122
	Lexical items	=	66
	Percentage	=	54.09

(ii) Lexical item
 Number of messages = 66
 Mean = 16
 = 4.12

(b) Lexical cohesive density

Lexical cohesive item = 34
 Lexical items = 66
 Percentage = 51.51

% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	% Lexical Cohesive Density
54.51	4.12	51.51

Table 4.6 (3) - Lexical Densities in Text 4.2

4.7 - Text 4.3 (Television) [Text 3.1.5 in Chapter 3]

Abbreviations of Lexical items in this text:

Pre: (Presenter)

Par.1 (1st Participant), Par.2 (2nd Participant)

Pre:

1. E sé é, tò, ó yá o
 you (all) thanks, alright it ready EMPH.
 'thanks to you all, alright, it's time'

Par:1

2. ibéèrè 'eighteen'
 question eighteen
 'the eighteenth question'

Pre:

3. é é é, gèésì èébò l'e fò hun
 eh! English English you speak that
 'Eh! that's said in English'

Par:1

4. \ibéèrè\ \méjìdìnlógún\
 rep:2 col:ins. 'eighteen'.2
 question eighteen
 'the eighteenth question'

Pre:

5. \ikejindinlogun\, E
syn: mejidinlogun. 4
eighteenth, you (Par.) thanks
'the eighteenth, thank you'
6. làyé àtijó, kí ilò girísi tó gbòde kankan
world past before use grease (SEW) all-over everywhere
'in the past, before the use of grease becomes the norm'
7. àwon iyá wa máa nre àwon ohun kan
those mother our AUX. VB. PROG. soak those thing one/certain
'our mothers do soak certain things'
8. sínú àdín àgbon fún eni tó bá sèsè bímó
PREP. oil kernel PREP. person (SEW) AUX. VB. ADV. give birth
'in the palm kernel for use by new mothers'
9. (noise) \E\ yé pariwo
rep: 1
You (all) stop make noise
'You should stop the noise'
10. ànísé làyé àtijó kí ilò girísi tó gbòde kankan
again world past before use grease (SEW) all-over everywhere
'again before the use of grease becomes the norm/in vogue'
11. awon iya wa maa nre awon ohun kan sinu
those mother our AUX. VB. PROG. soak those thing certain PREP.
'our mothers do soak certain things in'
12. àdín àgbon fún eni tó bá sèsè bímó
oil kernel PREP. person (SEW) AUX. VB. ADV. give birth
'palm kernel oil for use by new mothers'
13. láti máa fi para. Nwón sì tún \fi\
to AUX. VB. use smear body they (SEW) ADV. use
'to lubricate their skins. They also use'
14. n \para\ fún \omo\ tuntun pàápàá
rep: 13 col: bimo. 8
PROG. smear body PREP. child new especially
'(it) to lubricate the new babies' skins'
15. \E\ dárúko mérin nínú àwon \nkan\ òhún
rep: 5 syn: ohun. 7
you (Pars.) name four that those things that
'you (participants) name four of those things'
- (Quiet, the presenter gives some leading sentences)
16. A \nte\ sínú \àdín\ sùgbón ó lé jé
col: nre. 7
we PROG. lay PREP. oil but it AUX. BE
'we spread it in palm kernel oil; it may be'

17. dúdú \pàáapàá\ A máa nre é
rep. 14
black especially we AUX. VB. PROG. soak it
'very black. We do soak it'

Par. 1

18. \Kánfò\
col: nkan. 15
'camphor'

Pre.

19. o di eni, oya oya oya oya
it is one quick quick quick quick
'it's one, quick, quick, quick, quick'

Par. 2

20. \Káfúrà\
syn: kanfo. 18
'spice' (a kind of)

Pre.

21. Ehèén! hen! \káfúrà\ ó wolé
rep: 20
Yes! yes! kafura it enter
'Yes, yes, kafura it's correct!'

Par. 2

22. \Erù\
syn: kafura. 21
'Eru' (a kind of spice)

Pre.

23. \E\ \se\ e, o \di\ meta, \oya\, oya, oya
rep: 15 rep: 5 rep: 19 rep: 19
you(Par.) thanks it is three quick quick quick
'thank you; it is three, quick, quick, quick'

(Quiet - leading statements)

24. l'áwon ohun tó l'óórùn, tó l'óórùn báyi
VB+those thing that VB+smell that VB+smell like this
'those things that smell like this'

25. o ku kan
it remain one
'it remains one'

Par. 2

26. \Kánáfurú\
syn: eru. 22
'Kanafuru' (a kind of spice)

Pre.

27. \Kánáfurú\, \E\
rep: 26 rep: 9 bá mi fún won l'átewó
kanafuru you(all) help me give them VB+clap
'Kanafuru, do give them a clap!'

The following are the lexical relations in the text:

CN	NT	LI	PI & TCR
4.	2	<u>ibeere</u> (question) <u>mejidinlogun</u> (eighteen)	[rep: 2] [col: ins. equ.; ('eighteen'). 2]
5.	2	<u>ikejindinlogun</u> (the eighteenth) <u>seun</u> (thanks)	[rep: <u>mejidinlogun</u> (eighteen). 4, 'eighteen'(eighteen). 2] [syn: com. <u>se</u> (thanks). 1]
9.	1	<u>E</u> (you [all])	[rep: 1]
13.	1	<u>fi</u> (use)	[rep: 13; syn: ilo (use). 6]
14.	2	<u>para</u> (smear) <u>omo</u> (child)	[rep: 13] [syn: inc. <u>bimo</u> (give birth). 8]
15.	1	<u>nkan</u> (thing)	[syn: ohun (thing). 7]
16.	2	<u>nte</u> (laying) <u>adin</u> (oil)	[col: ins. equ. <u>nre</u> (soaking). 7] [rep: 8]
17.	2	<u>paapaa</u> (especially) <u>nre</u> (soaking)	[rep: 14] [rep: 7; col: ins. equ. <u>nte</u> (put). 16]
18.	1	<u>kanfo</u> (camphor)	[col: nkan (thing). 15; ohun (thing). 7]
20.	1	<u>kafura</u> (spice)	[syn: <u>kanfo</u> (camphor). 18; col: <u>nkan</u> (thing). 15; <u>ohun</u> (thing). 7]
21.	1	<u>kafura</u> (spice)	[rep: 20; syn: <u>kanfo</u> (camphor). 18; col: <u>nkan</u> (thing). 15; <u>ohun</u> (thing). 7]
22.	1	<u>eru</u> (spice)	[syn: <u>kafura</u> (spice). 21, 20; <u>kanfo</u> (camphor). 18; col: <u>nkan</u> (thing). 15; <u>ohun</u> (thing). 7]
23.	5	<u>E</u> (you[Par.]) <u>se</u> (thanks) <u>di</u> (is/become) <u>meta</u> (three) <u>oya</u> (quick x4)	[rep: 15] [syn: <u>seun</u> (thanks). 9; rep: 1] [rep: 19] [col: ins. nam. <u>eru</u> (spice). 22, <u>kafura</u> (spice). 20, <u>kanfo</u> (camphor). 19] [rep: 19, 1]
26.	1	<u>kanafuru</u> (spice)	[syn: <u>eru</u> . 22, <u>kafura</u> . 21, 20, <u>kanfo</u> (camphor). 18, <u>nkan</u> (thing). 15, <u>ohun</u> (thing). 7]

27. 2 kanafuru

[rep: 26; syn: eru (spice).22, kafura (spice).21,20; kanfo (spice).18; col: nkan (thing).15, ohun (thing).7]
[rep: 9,1]

E (you/all)

Table 4.7 (1) - Lexical Cohesive Relations in Text 4.3

In clause (9), the Presenter (Pre.) of the television quiz programme cautions the audience to stop the noise. I consider for analysis the lexical items in 6-8 and not 10-12 because the latter is a repetition of the former and, therefore, serves as a functional repair. E (you), is used in two ways by the presenter of the programme - one for all the people that are present in the studio, and the other for the participants in the quiz competition. Both uses are, nevertheless, grammatically plural (not as an inclusive lexical item)³⁰ Although these two groups are displayed in one chain in Table 4.7 (2) below, they are differentiated in Table 4.7 (1) above.

The following are the chains in the text.

Table 4.7 (2) - Lexical Cohesive Chains in Text 4.3

The lexical chains VII in Table 4.7(2), and number 15 of the cohesive relations in Table 4.7 (1) suggest the text's topic - 'the four items that question 'eighteen' seeks answers for.' These are the four things that 'mothers in the past soak in palm kernel oil for use by those who had new babies to lubricate their skins - \kanfo\, \kafura\, \eru\, and \kanafuru\. Ohun (thing).7 and nkan (thing).15 both collocate with these four 'things.'

Concerning the text's genre, the presenter's utterances show its dialogic nature. Lexical items showing appreciation as used by the presenter to either the participants or the audience abound in the text - E se e/seun (thank you (pl.)). 1, 5, and 23. The exclamatory remarks such as E e e

(eh).3 and Eheen! hen! (yes! yes!).21 further strengthens the text's dialogic nature. Whenever the answers to the questions are not readily given, the presenter hastens the participants up by the use of oya (quick) often in a repetitive form. All these and the presenter's response to answers by the use of substitutive lexical items as o di eni (that's/it's one).19, o wole (it's correct/accepted).21, o di meta (it's three).23, and o ku kan (it remains one).25 seem to reveal the text as a quiz because of its question and answer mode.

The text's lexical densities are as follows:

(a) Lexical Density

(i) Total number of words = 122
 Lexical items = 65
 Percentage = 53.27

(ii) Lexical items = 65
 Number of messages = 20
 Mean = 3.25

(b) Lexical Cohesive Density

Lexical cohesive item = 39
 Lexical items = 65
 Percentage = 60.00

% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	% Lexical Cohesive Density
53.27	3.25	60.00

Table 4.7 (3) - Lexical Densities in Text 4.3

4.8 - Text 4.4 (Radio Text) [Text 3.1.6 in Chapter 3]

1. Iròhìn àpapò orílẹ̀-èdè wa Naijèria l'ó ndé si
 news national nation our Nigeria is+it PROG.come to
 'the national news comes to'

2. etígbò yín láti ilé-isé rédiò l'ipínlè Ogun l'Abeokuta
 hearing you from house work radio vb.+state Ogun at-Abeokuta
 'you (all) from the Ogun State radio at Abeokuta'
3. Lékan sí, e tún \gbó\ àwon kókó
 syn: etigbo.2
 once more you ADV. hear those salient
 'once more, listen to those salient'
4. inú \iròhín\ náà. Ijoba \àpapò\ \orílè-èdè\
 rep:1 rep:1 rep:
 PREP. news d-d government national nation
 'items of the news. The national government'
5. yì so pé òun tí múra tán láti rí
 this say that it PERF. ready finish PREP. see
 'said that it was ready to see'
6. dájú pé irú àdéhùn-kádehùn tó wùwù
 sure that whatever agreement that whatever
 'for sure that whatever kind of agreement'
7. tí òun yíò bá \orílè-èdè\ \kórílè-èdè\
 rep;4 col: orile-ede
 that it AUX. VB. (SEW) nation any nation
 'it might have with any nation'
8. se ni \àgbáyé\ kò ni jé èyí tí yíò
 sup: orile-ede.7
 make in world NEG. is be that which AUX. VB.
 'make in the world will not be such that will'
9. pa \orílè-èdè\ yì lára rará
 rep:7
 kill nation this body at all
 'suffer the nation at all'
10. Onírurú ilé-isé àwon omo ogun
 various house work those child battle
 'the chief of staff of the military'
11. \orílè-èdè\ yì, Ogágun Sanni Abacha l'ó
 rep: 9 syn: ogun.10
 nation this general Sanni Abacha is+he
 'in this country, General Sanni Abacha'
12. \so\ òrò idánilójú yì l'Eko lánà nígbàtí ó
 rep:5
 say statement sure this PREP.+Lagos yesterday when he
 'said this re-assuring statement in Lagos yesterday when he'
13. sí ipàdé kan tí nwón nse ní pa
 open meeting one PERF. they PROG. about
 'was declaring a meeting open on'

14. \àdéhùn\ ati àkosílè àwon ètò \àdéhùn\
 syn: 6 rep: 6
 agreement and writing those plan agreement
 'the programme and writing of the plan for agreement'
15. láàrin \orílè-èdè\ wa ati àwon \orílè-èdè òkèèrè\
 rep: 11 syn: exc: orile-ede. 15
 between nation our and those nation distance
 'between our nation and those foreign nations'
16. Nwón ti tóka³¹ si wí pé ònà tí nwón
 they PERF. point PREP. that way that they
 'they have pointed out that the way they'
17. fi nkó àwon ilé-isé olókò lórí
 use PROG. build those house work commerce PREP.
 'build those commercial houses'
18. \lè-èdè\ wa lákòkò yì kò fi ònà
 rep: 15
 nation our time this NEG. allow way
 'in our country at this time does not'
19. sílè fún idàgbàsókè ojó iwájú
 leave PREP. growth day future
 'provide for growth in the future'
20. Alákoso ètò idásílè àwon \ilé-isé\ \olókò\
 rep: 17 rep: 16
 president plan establish those house work commerce
 'the president in charge of those commercial houses'
21. \owó\ fun \ijoba\ \àpapò\ \orílè-èdè\ yì
 syn: oloko. 20 rep: 4 rep: 4 rep: 18
 trade PREP. government national nation this
 'for this national government'
22. Ogágun tó ti fèhìntì Alani Akinrinade
 general who PERF. retire Alani Akinrinade
 'the retired General Alani Akinrinade'
23. l'ó \tóka\ sí òrò yì lánà ní ilú Ibadan
 rep: 16
 vb+he point PREP. statement this yesterday PREP. town Ibadan
 'made this statement yesterday at Ibadan'
24. tí 'se \olú ilú\ ipínlè Oyo nígbàtí ó \nsòrò\
 col: ibadan23 syn: oro. 23
 which is chief town state Oyo when he PROG. say
 'the capital of Oyo State when he was giving a speech'
25. ní ibèrè ipàdé nlá kan fún \àpapò\
 rep: 21
 PREP. beginning meeting PROG. big one PREP. national
 'at the beginning of a national conference'

26. \orílè-èdè\ yì nípa \òrò\ àwon \onílè isé\
 rep: 18 nation this about rep: 23 statement those owner house work
 'in this country about the issue of commercial houses'
27. \olókò\ \òwò\ kèèkèké ati \idàgbàsókè\
 rep: 20 rep: 21 commerce trade little and growth rep: 19
 'small business enterprises and the growth'
28. \orílè-èdè\ wa \Naijéria\ Idánilékò olójó márùn
 rep: 26 rep: 1 nation our Nigeria induction all-day five
 'of this nation, Nigeria. A five induction'
29. kan fún àwon tí yìò máa kó àwon òsísé
 one PREP. those that AUX. VBS. teach those worker
 'course for the teachers who would teach workers'
30. tí yìò máa \sísé\ ní agbègbè igbèríko ní
 syn: osise. 29 that AUX. VBS. PROG.+work PREP. area local PREP.
 'that would be working in the remote areas in'
31. ipínlè Imo State tí bèrè ní Owerri lánà
 state Imo State PERF. start PREP. Owerri yesterday
 'Imo State has begun in Owerri yesterday'
32. Awon eni márùndínláádórin tí nwón sà jo
 those person sixty-five that those gather together
 'Those sixty-five participants that were invited'
33. láti \agbègbè\ ijoba \ipínlè\ mókàndínlógún tí
 rep: 30 rep: 31 PREP. area government state nineteen that
 'from the nineteen local government areas'
34. ó wà ní \ipínlè\ náà l'ó n kópa nínú
 rep: 33 it exist PREP. state d-d (SEW) PROG. participate PREP.
 'of the state are participating in'
35. \idánilékò\ òhún. Eyì l'òpin \iròhìn\ náà
 rep: 28 rep: 4 induction that this VB+end news d-d
 'that induction course. This is the end of the news'
36. tí ó tí ndé sí \etigbo\ yín láti
 rep: 2 that it PERF. PROG. come PREP. hearing you PREP.
 'that has been coming to you from'
37. \ilé-isé\ \rédiò\ \ipínlè\ \Ogun\ \l' Abeokuta\
 rep: 2 rep: 2 rep: 2 rep: 2 rep: 2 house work radio state Ogun PREP.+Abeokuta
 'the Ogun State radio at Abeokuta'

38. ó digbà
it bye
'Goodbye'

The following are the Lexical Cohesive Relations in the text:

CN	NT	LI	PI & TCR
3.	1	<u>gbo</u> (hear)	[syn: <u>eti gbo</u> (hearing). 2]
4.	3	<u>irohin</u> (news) <u>apapo</u> (national) <u>orile-edede</u> (nation)	[rep: 1] [rep: 1] [rep: 1]
7	2	<u>orile-edede</u> (nation) <u>korile-edede</u> (any nation)	[rep: 4, 1] [syn: <u>orile-edede</u> (nation). 7, 4, 1]
8.	1	<u>aqbaye</u> (world)	[sup: <u>orile-edede</u> (nation). 7, 4, 1]
9.	1	<u>orile-edede</u> (nation)	[rep: 7, 4, 1; sup: <u>aqbaye</u> (world). 8]
11.	2	<u>orile-edede</u> (nation) <u>ogagun</u> (general)	[rep: 9, 7, 4, 1; sup: <u>aqbaye</u> (world). 8] [syn: <u>ogun</u> (battle). 10]
14.	1	<u>adehun</u> (agreement)	[rep: 14]
15.	2	<u>orile-edede</u> (nation) <u>orile-edede okeere</u> (foreign nation)	[rep: 11, 9, 7, 4, 1; sup: <u>aqbaye</u> (world). 8] [syn: exc. <u>orile-edede</u> (nation). 11, 9, 7, 4, 1; inc. <u>kori-</u> <u>le-edede</u> (any nation). 2]
18.	1	<u>'le-edede</u> (nation)	[rep: 15, 11, 9, 7, 4, 1; syn: inc. <u>ori-</u> <u>le-edede okeere</u> (foreign nation) . 15, <u>korile-edede</u> (any nation). 2; sup: <u>aqbaye</u> world). 8]
20.	2	<u>ile-ise</u> (work house) <u>oloko</u> (commerce)	[rep: 17] [rep: 17]
21.	4	<u>ijoba</u> (government) <u>apapo</u> (national) <u>orile-edede</u> (nation) <u>owo</u> (trade)	[rep: 4] [rep: 4] [rep: 18, 15, 11, 9, 7, 4, & 1; syn: inc. <u>orile-edede okeere</u> (foreign nation). 15, <u>korile-edede</u> (any na- tion. 2; sup: <u>aqbaye</u> (world). 8] [syn: <u>oloko</u> (commerce). 20]
23.	1	<u>toka</u> (point)	[rep: 16]
24.	2	<u>olu-ilu</u> (capital) <u>nsoro</u> (talking)	[syn: Ibadan. 23] [syn: <u>oro</u> (statement). 23]
25.	1	<u>apapo</u> (national)	[rep: 21]

26.	3	<u>orile-edede</u> (nation)	[rep: 21, 18, 15, 11, 9, 7, 4, &1; syn: inc. <u>orile-edede okeere</u> (foreign nation). 15; <u>korile-edede</u> (any nation). 2; sup: <u>aqbaye</u> (world). 8]
		<u>oro</u> (statement)	
		<u>ise</u> (work)	[rep: 23; syn: <u>nsoro</u> (talking). 24]
27.	3	<u>oloko</u> (commerce)	[syn: inc. <u>ile-ise</u> (work house). 20]
		<u>owo</u> (trade)	[rep: 20; syn: <u>owo</u> (trade). 21]
		<u>idaqbasoke</u> (growth)	[rep: 21; syn: <u>oloko</u> (commerce). 27, 20]
			[rep: 19]
28.	2	<u>orile-edede</u> (nation)	[rep: 26, 21, 18, 15, 11, 9, 7, 4&1; syn: <u>orile-edede okeere</u> foreign nation). 15; <u>korile-edede</u> (any nation). 2; sup: <u>aqbaye</u> (world). 8]
		<u>Naijeria</u> (Nigeria)	[rep: 1]
30.	1	<u>sise</u> (work)	[syn: <u>osise</u> (worker). 29]
33.	2	<u>aqbegbe</u> (area)	[rep: 30]
		<u>ipinle</u> (state)	[rep: 31]
34.	1	<u>ipinle</u> (state)	[rep: 33]
35.	2	<u>idanileko</u> (induction)	[rep: 28]
		<u>irohin</u> (news)	[rep: 4]
36.	1	<u>etiqbo</u> (hearing)	[rep: 2]
37.	5	<u>ile-ise</u> (work house)	[rep: 2]
		<u>redio</u> (radio)	[rep: 2]
		<u>ipinle</u> (State)	[rep: 2]
		<u>Ogun</u> (Ogun)	[rep: 2]
		<u>l' Abeokuta</u> (PREP+Abeokuta)	[rep: 2]

Table 4.8 (1) - Lexical Cohesive Relations in Text 4.4

As previously stated, Text 4.4. is culled from the end part of a long radio news text.³² It is the summary of the news items.³³ The text may be subdivided into several mini-texts which make up the summary.

Lines 1-4a ('a' equals about half of the line) introduce the beginning of the summary. The first mini-text then begins from line 4b. until line 15. The second begins in line 16 and it ends in line 28a. The third begins in line 28b and it ends in 35a. Lines 35b-38, like lines 1-4a, finally signal

the end of the news text. Each of the mini-texts, within the entire text, is a separate entity and the numbering is different (i.e. [i, ii], etc.). Certain lexical items, nevertheless, run through the entire text cohesively (irrespective of the sub-divisions).

As a result of the uniqueness of each of the mini-texts, the following lexical items cannot function cohesively with similar lexical items which occur inter-mini-textually. Ile-ise (work house).17, for example, concerns oloko (commerce), whereas its earlier occurrence in line 2 concerns, specially, redio (radio) at Abeokuta, Ogun State. Similarly, ipinle (state), in line 2, which forms a part of a series of epithets in a prepositional nominal group (plus circumstance) specifically refers to Ogun (Ogun) and ipinle (state) in lines 31, 33 and 34 refers to Imo (Imo). The lexical items occurring mini-textually have, therefore, different meanings. Ojo (day).19 in the second mini-text would have been cohesive through collocation with lana (yesterday).12 in the first mini-text but these refer to two different incidents. Other lexical items which only function within a particular mini-text rather than across these mini-texts are: ogagun (military-general) in lines 22 and 11; oro (word/statement).12,23; lana (yesterday).12,23; nsoro (talking).24, and oro (word/statement).12; ipade (meeting).25,13. Olojo (all-day).28b begins the third mini-text, hence does not cohere with ojo (day).19 in the mini-text. Osise (worker).29, in a similar way, does not cohere with ile-ise (work house).20.

The following are the lexical chains in the text:

	I	II	III	VI	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI
1.	iro- hin news	apa- po nati- onal	orile- ede nation	Naij- eria Nige- ria							
2.					eti- gbo hea- ring	ile- ise work house	re- dio ra- dio	ipi- nle sta- te	Ogl'	Abeokuta	
3.				gbo (hear)							
4.	iro- hin news	apa- po nati- onal	orile- ede nation								ijoba (govt.)
5.											(i) so(say)
6.											(ii) adehun-kadehun (whatever ag- reement)
7.			orile-ede (nation) korile-ede any nation								
8.			agbaye (world)								
9.			orile-ede								(iii)
10			(nation)								ogun (battle)
11			orile-ede (nation)								ogagun (general
12											so say
14											adehun (agreement) x2
15			orile-ede (nation) ede-okeere (f' nation)								(i)
16											to- ka (point)
17											ii iii 'ise' ko
18			'le-ede (nation)								work commerce
19											iv v ojo ida.. day growth

continued on next page

20									
21	apapo	orile-ede					'ise' ko		
	natio	- nation							
23	nal					ij-			
						oba			vi
24						to-		lana	Ibadan
						ka	owo		vii
25	apapo								ilu' so
	(national)								
26		orile-ede							
27		(nation)					'ise		oro
							olo	ko	ida. talk
							comm.	growth	
							owo		
28	orile-ede Nai-								(trade)
	(nation) jeria								
							(i) 34	(ii) 35	
29						'ojo	'eko	(induction	
						(day)	(iii)	osise(worker)	
30								(iv)	
								'se agbegbe	
31								work area (v)	
						lana		ipinle	
						('day)		(state)	
33									
								agbe ipinle	
								(area) state	
34									
35	irohin					idanileko		ipinle	(state)
	(news)					(induction)			
36		etigbo	ile-	re-	ipi-Og-	l'Abeokuta			
		(hearing)	ise	dio	nle un				
			(work-	ra-	state				
			house)	dio					

Table 4.8 (2) - Lexical Chains in Text 4.4

Some lexical items, nevertheless, cohere inter-minitextually. Table 4.4. (2) shows clearly that chains I-X run across the boundaries of the mini-texts. These are: irohin (news), apapo (national), orile-ede (nation), Naijeria (Nigeria), etigbo (hearing), ile-ise (work house), radio (radio), ipinle (state), Ogun (Ogun), and l'Abeokuta (at Abeokuta). Of all these, the chain consisting of orile-ede (nation) has more lexical items than any other chain. For

descriptive purposes, the lexical items which cut across the mini-texts are described as macro cohesive lexical items, and those that function within the mini-texts as micro cohesive lexical items: a macro cohesive relation as described in this work has a multi-feature; that is, it provides a vertical link through at least two parts of the entire text. These share, therefore, the same Generic Structure Potential (GSP) (a configuration of the optional and the obligatory elements of a text to context [Halliday and Hasan 1985:63-69]) and a micro cohesive relation has a uni-feature, occurring within a level of the mini-text alone (Biber 1985:337-339). That is, its GSP does not extend beyond the text.

Each of chain III on Table 4.8 (2) and line 28 on Table 4.8 (1) has the largest number of very similar cohesive relations with one macro cohesive lexical item predominant - orile-edo (country). It may be suggested from a general understanding of the text that its topic centres around Naijeria (Nigeria) and that its subject is 'national news.'

As for the text's genre, apart from the introductory and closing summaries, a few lexical choices reveal that it belongs to the media. The chains, generally, and those of the mini-texts in particular, indicate a news report as they seem to form a pattern whereby A participant either do B as process in C place as circumstance. Some of the participants are ijoba (government). 4, ogagun A or B (general A or B). 11, 22. Some of the processes are so (say). 5, 11, se (make). 8. Some of the circumstances are l'Abeokuta (at Abeokuta). 2 and lana (yesterday). 12.

The text's lexical densities are as follows:

(a) Lexical Density

(i) Total number of words = 257
 Lexical items = 144
 Percentage = 56.03

(ii) Lexical items = 144
 Number of messages = 30
 Mean = 4.80

(b) Lexical Cohesive Density

Lexical cohesive items = 73
 Lexical item = 144
 Percentage = 50.69

% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	% Lexical Cohesive Density
56.03	4.80	50.69

Table 4.8 (3) - Lexical Cohesive Densities in Text 4.4

4.9. - Text 4.5 (Spoken Text) (Text 3.1.8 in Chapter 3)

(Titi's elder brother Seun is sent to go and buy a packet of biscuits for both of them)

1. X- Wá jòkó, Titi (a gesture accompanies the utterance)
 come sit Titi
 'come and sit Titi'

2. Y- Hùn?
 'What?'

3. X- \Wá\ \jòkó\
 rep: 1 rep: 1
 come sit
 'come and sit'

4. Y- Emi náà máa je 'biskit'
 I d-d AUX. VB. eat biscuit
 'I too will eat biscuit'

(Y nearly falls down from the concrete railing on which both interlocutors sit)

5. X- Má mà subú!
 do NEG. fall
 'do not fall!'

6. Y- \Emi\ náà máa \je\ \'biskit'\
 I d-d AUX. VB. eat biscuit
 'I too will eat biscuit'

7. X- Ta ló ra aso yi fún e? (pointing to her
 who (is+he) buy cloth this PREP. you dress)
 'who bought this attire for you?'

8. Y- \Ehéen?\
 syn: hun. 2
 'what?'

9. X- \Ta\ ló \ra\ \aso\ yi fún e? (a distant voice
 rep: 7 rep: 7 rep: 7 can be heard)
 who (is+he) buy cloth this PREP. you
 'who bought this attire for you?'

10. Y- móomì mi
 mummy DET.
 'my mum' (mother)

11. X- \mòómo\ e ló \ra'so\ fún e
 syn: moomi. 10 rep: 9
 mum your (is+she) buy cloth PREP. you
 'your mother bought it (the attire) for you (a voice)'

12. Y- Hun
 'Yes'

(silence)

13. X- \móòmi\ e ló \rà\ fún e
 syn: 11 rep: 11
 mum your (is+she) buy PREP. you
 'your mother bought it (the attire) for you'
14. Y- \Hen\
 syn: com. hun. 12
 'Yes'
15. X- Igbàwo ni nwón \rà?\
 rep: 9
 when is they (sg.) buy
 'when did she buy it?'
16. Y- \ìgbà\ t'á n ló sí'bi kan wò
 when PREP. we PROG. go PREP. place one, look
 'when we were going to somewhere, see'
17. - \mòóomi\ mí ó dè wà \rà\
 rep: 13 rep: 15
 mum DET. she then come buy
 'my mother then bought it'
18. X- Nwón \rà\
 rep: 15
 they (sg.) buy
 'she bought it'
19. Y- E \wo\ bí báyi (she points to her knees)
 rep: 16
 you(sg.) look here this way (i. e. place/thing)
 'you look at this'
20. - tó máa n dún mi, e \wò\
 rep: 19
 that ADV. PROG. hurt me you (Sg.) look
 'and see; it hurts me always, look'
21. X- ó n \dùn\ è
 rep: 20
 it PROG. hurt you
 'it hurts you'
22. Y- \Hen\
 rep: 14
 'Yes'
23. X- Igbàwo l'ó bèrè?
 rep: 15
 when (is+it) start?
 'when did it start?'
24. Y- \ìgbì\ ó n \dùn\ mi ni \mo\ subú, \wò\ \móomi\
 rep: 23 rep: 20 syn: emi. 1 rep: 20 rep: 17
 when it PROG. hurt me is I fall look mum
 'when it hurts me, then I fell down, look (mum)'

25. - mi \dè wá\ fi àtikè si, \mo\ \dè wá\ n ké
 rep: 17 rep: 24 rep: 25
 DET. then come put powder PREP. I then come PROG. cry
 'my mum then put powder into it and I started crying'
26. X- O wá n ké
 rep: 25
 you come PROG. cry
 'you began to cry'
27. Y- \Hen\
 rep: 22
 'Yes'
28. X- kí ló dé tó fi n \ké?\
 rep: 26
 INT. (it+happen) that (SEW) PROG. cry
 'what happened such that you have to cry?'
29. Y- \ìgbò\ jé Seun l'ó wá gbé mi \subú\, \wò\ (points)
 rep: 24 rep: 24 rep: 24
 (SEW)(SEW) Seun (is+he) come carry me fall, look
 'when it was Seun who made me fall, look'
30. X- kí ló \dé\ tó fi n \ké?\
 rep: 28 rep: 26
 INT. (it+happen) that (SEW) PROG. cry
 'what happened that you have to cry?'
31. - sé ó n \ta\ é ni à b'ó n \dun\ è?
 syn: dun. 31 rep: 24
 INT. it PROG. sting you is or (INT+it) PROG. hurts you
 'it is stinging you or is it hurting you?'
32. Y- ó n \ta\ mí
 rep: 31
 it PROG. sting me
 'it is stinging me'
33. X- ó n \ta\ é!
 rep: 32
 it PROG. stings you
 'it is stinging you'
34. Y- \Hen\
 rep: 2
 'Yes'
35. X- má \ke\ mó o
 rep: 30
 NEG. cry again EMPH.
 'do not cry again'
36. Y- Hùn ùn
 rep: 27
 'Yes'

The following are the lexical relations in the text:

- CN NT LI PI & TCR
3. 2 wa (come) [rep: 1]
joko (sit) [rep: 1]
 6. 3 emi (I) [rep: 4]
je (eat) [rep: 4]
'biskit' (biscuit) [rep: 4]
 8. 1 Eheen (what) [syn: 2]
 9. 3 Ta (who) [rep: 7]
ra (buy) [rep: 7]
aso (cloth) [rep: 7]
 11. 3 moomo (mum) [syn: com: moomi (mum). 10]
ra' [of ra'so (buy) [rep: 9, & 7]
'so [of ra'so (cloth) [rep: 9, & 7]
 13. 2 moomi (mummy) [rep: 10; syn: com. moomo (mum). 11]
ra (buy) [rep: 11, 9, & 7]
 14. 1 hen (yes) [syn: com. Hun (yes). 12]
 15. 1 ra (buy) [rep: 13, 11, 9, & 7]
 16. 1 iqba (when) [syn: com. iqbawo (when). 15]
 17. 2 moomo (mum) [rep: 13, 10; syn: com. moomo (mum). 11]
ra (buy) [rep: 15, 13, 11, 9, & 7]
 18. 1 ra (buy) [rep: 17, 15, 13, 11, 9, & 7]
 19. 1 wo (look) [rep: 16]
 20. 1 wo (look) [rep: 19 & 16]
 22. 1 Hen (yes) [rep: 14; syn: com. Hun (yes). 12]
 23. 1 iqbawo (when) [rep: 15; syn: com. iqba (when). 16]
 24. 5 iqbi (when) [syn: com. iqbawo (when). 23]
dun (hurt) [rep: 21, 20]
mo (I) [syn: com. emi (I). 6, 4]
wo (look) [rep: 20, 19, & 16]
moomi (mum) [rep: 17, 13, & 10; syn: com. moomo (mum). 11]
 25. 2 de wa (then come) [rep: 17]
de wa (then come) [rep: 25]
 26. 2 wa (come) [rep: 25, 17; col: de (then). 25, 17]
mo (I) [rep: 24]
 27. 1 Hen (yes) [rep: 22, 14; syn: com. Hun (yes). 12]
 28. 1 ke (cry) [rep: 26, 25]

29.	3	<u>igbo</u> (when?) <u>subu</u> (fall) <u>wo</u> (look)	[syn: com. <u>igbo</u> (when). 24; <u>igbawo</u> (when). 23] [rep: 24] [rep: 24, 20, 19, 16]
30.	2	<u>de</u> (happen) <u>ke</u> (cry)	[rep: 28] [rep: 28, 26]
31.	2	<u>ta</u> (sting) <u>dun</u> (hurt)	[syn: <u>dun</u> (hurt). 24, 21, & 20] [rep: 24, 21, & 20; syn: inc. <u>ta</u> (sting). 31]
32.	1	<u>ta</u> (sting)	[rep: 31; syn: inc. <u>dun</u> (hurt). 31, 24, 21, 20]
33.	1	<u>ta</u> (sting)	[rep: 32, 31; syn: inc. <u>dun</u> (hurt). 31, 24,
34.	1	<u>Hen</u> (yes)	21, & 20] [rep: 27, 22, 14; syn: com. <u>Hun</u> (yes). 12]
35.	1	<u>ke</u> (cry)	[rep: 30, 28, 26]
36.	1	<u>Hun un</u> (yes)	[syn: com. <u>Hen</u> (yes). 34, 27, 22, 14; <u>Hun</u> (yes). 12]

Table 4.9 (1): Lexical Cohesive Relations in Text 4.5

This text, as previously stated, is a conversation between a five-year-old girl and myself in Lagos. In a similar way to the radio text just analysed above, it can be divided into two parts each of which then becomes a mini-text. Clauses 1-6 is the preamble to the conversation. Clause 7, which is begun by the adult interlocutor, begins the first mini-text. It ends in clause 18. In a turn-taking focusing style, the child begins the second mini-text in clause 19. This runs until the end of the text.

Being two mini-texts, a few lexical items which are repeated cannot cohere inter-mini-textually in the text. These are the micro-cohesive lexical items. Examples are -igbawo (when). 15, 23 ; igbi (when?). 16, 24, and subu (fall). 5 & 24. The first two, that is, igbawo(when). 15 and igba(when). 16 concern the topic of 'attire', whereas igbawo (when). 23 and igbi (when). 24 concern the child's 'injured knees'. By this classification, igbo (when). 29 coheres with both igbawo

(when). 23 and igbi (when). 24 but not igbawo (when). 15 and igba (when). 16. The 'falling' (subu). 5 does not bear any relation with the one in clause 24. Thus the subu (fall). 29 can only be a repetition of the one in clause 24 and not the one in 5. Moomo (mother), or its English language Yoruba assimilated form moomi in clauses 24, 17, 13, 11, & 10, is the only macro lexical item that runs through the entire text while its referent remains the same. Four others may be classified as macro lexical items because they relate specifically to the girl's linguistic development. These are organised in chains III, VIII, IX and X in Table 4.9 (2).

The material process ra (buy) in number 18, mental process wo (look) in number 19 (iii), behavioural process ta (sting/pinch) in number 33 and the minimal nominal item hùn ùn (yes) in number 36 on Table 4.9 (1) above have long lexical relations.

The following are the lexical cohesive chains in the text:

I	II				
1. wa	joko				
(come)	(sit)				
		III			
2.		Hun			
3. wa	joko	(what)			
(come)	(sit)		IV	V	VI
4.			Emi	je	'biskit'
			(I)	(eat)	(biscuit)
6.			Emi	je	'biskit'
			(I)	(eat)	(biscuit)
<hr/>					
			(i)	(ii)	(iii)
7.			ta	ra	aso
			(who)	(buy)	(cloth)
8.	Eheen				
9.	(what)		ta	ra	aso(cloth)
			(who)	buy)	VII
10.					moomi(mum)
continued on next page					

11.	ra	'so	moomo			
	(buy)	(cloth)	(mum)			
12.				VIII		
13.				Hun	(yes)	
14.	ra	(buy)	moomi			
			(mum)	Hen	(yes)	
15.	ra	(buy)		(iv)		
				igbawo	(when)	
16.						
				IX		
				igba	wo	(look)
17.	ra	(buy)	moomi	(when)		X
			(mum)			de
						wa
						(then come)
18.	ra	(buy)				
<hr/>						
19.					wo	
					(look)	
20.						(i)
						dun
						(hurt)
21.					wo	
					(look)	
22.				Hen	(yes)	
				(ii)		
23.				igbawo	(when)	
24.		(iii)				
	mo	subu	moomi	igbi	wo	dun
	(I)	(fall)	(mum)	(when)	look	(hurt)(iv)
25.	mo				de	ke
	(I)				wa	(cry)
					(then	
					come)	
					de	
					wa	
					(then	
					come)	
26.						ke
						(cry)
27.			Hen			
			(yes)			(v)
28.				igbi	wo	ke
				(when)	(look)	de
29.	subu					(cry)(happen
	(fall)					
30.						ke
						de
31.						(happen)
					ta	
					(sting)	
					dun	
					(hurt)	
32.					ta	
					(sting)	
					ta	
33.				Hen	(yes)	(sting)
34.						
35.				Hun	un	ke
				(yes)		(cry)
36.						

Table 4.9 (2). - Lexical Chains in Text 4.5

Chains III and VIII in Table 4.5.(2) may be described together because their lexical items are similar. In chain III, eheen (what).8 is a lexical variant but functionally and meaningfully a complete synonym of Hun (what).2. The girl requires, in the dialogic situation, repetitions of the declarative statement in clause 1, and the interrogative statement in clause 7. It is apparent that these are only required because the girl is not paying attention as she thinks of the biscuit that her elder brother is sent to buy (clauses 4 and 6). Chain VIII consists of variant of Hen (yes).2. The hun (yes).12 and hùn (what).2 are homographs. The difference in meaning is shown by the tonicity. Hùn (what).2 is said in low tone; and hun (yes).12 is said in mid tone. The variants of hun (yes).12 in the chain are Hen (yes) in 14 and 22, 27 and 34; and hùn ùn (yes).36 with an additional tonic syllable - /un/. The young girl's choice of these variants of 'yes' in the language shows the child's growing linguistic development.

Chains IX and X may also be grouped together because their lexical items function to illustrate, more than the ones described in the last paragraph, some aspects of a child's linguistic development. In chain IX, wo (look) occurs five times. Apart from its occurrences in clauses 19 and 29, other occurrences in clauses 16, 20 and 24 function beyond being merely attention-getting devices used to describe something in the immediate environment (Bohannon and Leubecker 1988:91). These function as 'expressing focussing device' (Baker and Greenfield 1988:89) used by children to emphasise 'a new aspect of situation' because they do not

actually point to a particular 'thing' or 'event' in the immediate or distant environment. Chain X consists of de (then) and wa (come to/then come). Both lexical items occur together once in clause 17 and twice in clause 25. The combination of the two lexical items is a feature of the Lagos dialect of the Yoruba language. In standard Yoruba language, each of the lexical items is sufficient to make the clause functional.³⁶ Another feature of this dialect in the text are igbi (when) and igbo (when).²⁹ Both are dialectal variation of the standard forms - igbati/nigbati/igbawo/nigbawo.

One feature of the text's lexical organisation, which Bamgbose (1982: 88-89) refers to, although with reference to Yoruba poetry, as 'full and partial lexico-structural repetitions' functions in the text.³⁷ For the full lexico-structural repetition, the structure and the entire lexical items of the clause (or line) are repeated. For the partial lexico-structural repetition, the structure of the clause is repeated but with one or more variations in its lexical items. Examples of the full lexico-structural repetitions are clauses 1 and 3, 4 and 6, 7 and 8; 28, and 30. The only example of the partial lexico-structural repetition are clauses 11 and 13 (an ellipsis - aso (cloth)).

In spoken utterances, however, the full lexico-structural repetitions are largely used to effect discursal repairs, and the partial lexico-structural repetitions are used as discursal variations largely to effect stylistic variations. By stylistic variation is meant that those clauses are varied

because new lexical items may be added, removed, abbreviated and contracted to bring about new information to the utterance. The full lexico-structural repetitions in this text do not seem to function as reparatory strategy, but rather as part of what Halliday (1975:80) describes as the 'mathetic function' of language whereby the adult interactant, in a child-adult dialogic situation, improves the dialogic development of the child. Clause 28 is repeated in 30, for example, because the adult interlocutor wants to probe further the actual reason for her crying - a choice between the 'fall' and the addition of 'powder' to the injured knee. The available options are made explicit in the clause which directly follows the question.

Like lines 18 and 23 on Table 4.5.(1), chains (ii) in clauses 7-18 and (i) in clauses 19-36 are suggestive of the text's topic(s). Material process ra (buy).15, which pertains to the girl's dress is repeated six times. Both dùn (hurt).20 and ta (pinch/sting).31 pertain, topically, to her falling (subú).24. These lexical items, which suggest two topics along with wo (look).16^{ff}, explain what Ninio (1988) observes in relation to adult-child speech:

"Adult speech to very young children is notoriously present-oriented; i.e. its topic is almost exclusively either a joint focus of perceptual attention shared by the child and the adult, or else it deals with the management and performance of on-going activities... Some of what passes for discussion of a focus of attention in analyses of adult-child discourse is actually a discussion of an event that had happened a very short while prior to the discussion, rather than concurrently with it." (pp. 35-36)

The reference made to the girl's dress by the adult interlocutor is strategic for 'a joint focus of perceptual

attention' for both of them. The second is a discussion of a recent event (DRE)³⁸ which Ninio (op.cit. p.36) observes is important for infants. Ta(sting) along with subu (fall). 29, 24, ke (cry). 35, 30, 28, and 26 and dun (hurt). 31, 24, 21 & 20, in the second mini-text may be organised sequentially. The topic of 'a young girl who falls down and injures her knees' is evident from this sequential pattern of these lexical processes if our understanding of the mini-text is brought to bear on them. That is, the girl 'falls' down, 'hurts' herself, feels the 'sting' and 'cries'.

Concerning the text's type, there is ample evidence to show that it is a conversation consisting of a child and an adult. The text is replete, among others, with repetitions which can only be understood in terms of child-adult speech. The child's discoursal attention-getting device 'wo (look) which does not particularly direct the adult interlocutor to any particular object in the environment, and use of variants of iqbati (when) and moomo (mother) shows, perhaps, the developmental stage of the girl's linguistic acquisition. It is a dialogue where the adult's turn-taking consists of picking up and repeating what the child has said (e.g. clauses 11 & 13). Topics are not well-developed as in adult speech so the adult participant in the discourse asks questions to keep the conversation going (e.g. clause 7, 15, 23 and 28. The lexical item moomo (mother), which is repeated four times (see line 24 of Table 4.5 (1), is usually used more by children to refer to their mothers.

The text's lexical densities are as follows:

(a) Lexical Density

- (i) Total number of words = 149
 Lexical items = 85
 Percentage = 57.04
- (ii) Lexical items = 85
 Number of messages = 29
 Mean = 2.93

(b) Lexical Cohesive Density

- Lexical cohesive items = 68
 Lexical items = 85
 Percentage = 80.00

% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	% Lexical Cohesive density
57.04	2.93	80.00

Table 4.5 (3) - Lexical Densities in Text 4.5

4.10 - Text 4.6 Scientific Text (Text 3.1.11 in Chapter 3)

1. Ade pinnu lati fi ese rin lati
 Ade plan to use leg walk PREP.
 'Ade planned to walk from'
2. Eko lo si Abeokuta. Ojo marun lo
 Lagos go PREP. Abeokuta day five (is+he)
 'Lagos to Abeokuta. He spent five days'
3. fi \rin\ \irin\ ajo na. Ni \ojo\ \kinni\
 rep:1 syn:rin.3 rep:2 col:marun.2
 use walk walking journey d-d PREP. day first
 'to walk the distance. For the first day'
4. o \rin\ opa 23,136; ni \ojo\ \keji\ o \rin\
 rep:3 rep:3 col:kinni.3 rep:4
 he walk pole 23,136; PREP day two he walk
 'he walked 23,136 poles; for the second day he walked'
5. \opa\ 20,864, ni \ojo\ \keta\ o \rin\ 19,893,
 rep:4 rep:4 col:keji.4 rep:4
 pole 20,864, PREP. day third he walk 19,893,
 '20,864 poles. For the third day he walked 19,893'

6. \ojo\ \kerin\ 20,106; o si \rin\ \opa\ 1,242
 rep:5 col:keta.5 rep:5 rep:5
 day fourth 20,106 he ADV. walk pole 1,242
 'the fourth 20,106; he also walked 1,242 poles'
7. ni \ojo\ \karun\ Gbogbo \opa\
 rep:6 col:kerin.6 rep:6
 PREP. day fifth. All pole
 'on the fifth day. All the poles'
8. ti o \rin\ je d. Ki ni \d\
 rep:6 rep:8
 that he walk equal d what is d
 'that he walked equals d. What is d?'
9. Awon ore marun kan lo si sobu
 those/some friend five certain go PREP. shop
 'Certain five friends went to the shop'
10. ti nwon ti nta oko, \enikookan\ won si
 col:ore marun.9
 that they PERF. PROG. sell vehicle each person them then
 'where vehicles are sold, each of them'
11. \ra\ \okookan\ \Iye\ ti nwon \ra\ awon \oko\
 ant:nta.10 col:oko.10 col:ra.11 rep:11 rep:10
 buy each-each cost PERF. they buy those vehicle
 'bought a vehicle. The prices for the vehicles'
12. na niwonyi: ti \eni kini\ \naira\ 1963, ti \eni
 col:marun.9 col:iye.11 col:
 d-d VB+these that person first naira 1963, that person
 are these: for the first person 1963 naira, that of the
13. keji\ \naira\ 1734, ti \eni keta\ \naira\ 1613, ti \eni kerin\
 kini.12 rep:12 col:12/13 rep:13 col:keta.13
 second naira1734 that person third naira1613 that personfour
 'second 1734 naira, third, 1613 naira, that of the fourth'
14. ti o \ra\ aloku \oko\ \naira\ 947, ti \eni karun\ \naira\ 2,107
 rep:11 rep:11 rep:13 col:eni kerin.13 rep:14
 that he buy old vehicle naira 947 that person fifth 2,107
 'who bought a second-hand for 947 naira; the fifth 2,107'
15. \Owo\ ti nwon \san\ fun awon \oko\
 syn:naira.14 col:owo.15 rep:14
 money that they pay PREP. those vehicle
 'the money that they paid for those vehicles'
16. \mararun\ \je\ L. Ki ni \L\
 col:karun.14 rep:8 rep:16
 five-five equals L. what is L
 '- all the five equals L naira. What is L?'
17. Ni oko awon Tomi tanki omi nla nla
 in farm those Tom tank water big big
 'In Tom's people's farm are very big water tanks'

18. merin lo wa nibe. Galonu \omi\ ti nwon
 four (SEW) exist there gallon water PERF. they
 '- there are four of such. The gallons of water they'
 rep: 17
19. gba niwonyi: \tanki\ \kini\ \galonu\ 15,200
 take VB+these tank first gallon 15,200
 'contain are these: the first tank 15,200 gallons'
 rep: 17 col: merin. 18 rep: 18
20. \tanki\ \keji\ \galonu\ 22,147, \galonu\ \keta\ 10,100,
 rep: 19 col: kini. 19 rep: 19 rep: 20 col: keji. 20
 tank second gallon 22,147, gallon third 10,100,
 'the second tank 22,147 gallons, the third 10,100,'
21. \galonu\ \kerin\ 33,897. \omi\ ti \mbe\ ninu
 rep: 20 col: keta. 20 rep: 18 syn: wa. 18
 gallon fourth 33,897 water that PROG. is PREP.
 'the fourth gallon, 33,897. The water in'
22. \tanki\ \mererin\ \je\ \galonu\ W. Ki ni \W\
 rep: 20 col: kerin. 21 rep: 16 rep: 21 rep: 22
 tank all-four equal gallon W what is W
 'the four tanks are W gallons. What is W?'
23. Ijoba ibile kan na awon owo wonyi:
 government native one spend those money these
 'One local government spent the following money:'
24. lori ile iwe kiko, \Naira\ 40,340; lori
 syn: owo. 23
 PREP. house book building naira 40,340 PREP.
 'on school building, 40,340 naira; on'
25. titun ona se \Naira\ 17,146; lori \ile\
 rep: 24 rep: 24
 repair road (SEW) naira 17,146 PREP. house
 'road repair 17,146 naira, on the '
26. iwosan \Naira\ 15,000; lori omi ero
 rep; 25
 health naira 15,000 PREP. water machinery
 'hospital 15,000 naira; on pipe-borne water'
27. \Naira\ 18,136. \Naira\ \melo\ ni \ijoba\
 rep: 26 rep: 27 col: naira. 27 rep: 23
 naira 18,136; naira many is government
 '18,136; How much naira did the government'
28. \ibile\ na \na\ fun awon ise wonyi?
 rep: 23 rep: 23
 native d-d spend PREP. those work these
 'of the local area spend for these works?'

The following are the lexical relations in the text:

CN NT LI

PI & TCR

3. 4 rin (walk) [rep: 1]
irin (walking) [syn: rin(walk). 1]
ojo (day) [rep: 2]
kinni (first) [col: num. marun (five). 2]
4. 4 rin (walk) [rep: 3, 1; syn: irin(walking). 3]
ojo (day) [rep: 3, 2]
keji (second) [col: num. kinni (first). 3; marun (five). 2]
rin (walk) [rep: 4(2), 3, 1; syn: irin (walking). 3]
5. 4 opa (pole) [rep: 4]
ojo (day) [rep: 4, 3, 2, 1]
keta (third) [col: num. keji(second). 4, kinni (first). 3,
marun (five). 2]
rin (walk) [rep: 4(x2), 3, 1; syn: irin (walking). 3]
6. 4 ojo (day) [rep: 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]
kerin (fourth) [col: num. keta (third). 5, keji (second). 4,
kinni (first). 3, marun (five). 2]
rin (walk) [rep: 5, 4, (2), 3 & 1; col: irin (walking). 3]
opa (pole) [rep: 5, 4]
7. 3 ojo [rep: 6, 5, 4, 2, 1]
karun (fifth) [col: num. kerin (fourth). 6, keta (third). 5,
keji (second). 4, kinni (first). 3, marun
(five). 2]
opa (pole) [rep: 6, 5, 4]
8. 2 rin (walk) [rep: 6, 5, 4(2), 3, & 1; syn: irin(walking). 3]
d (d) [rep: 8; syn: 1, 242(6)+20, 106(6)+19, 893(5)+
20, 864(5)+ 23, 136 (4); gbogbo opa
(all poles). 7]
10. 1 enikookan(each person) [col: ore marun(five friends). 9]
11. 5 ra (buy) [ant: nta (selling). 10]
okookan(each) [col: inc. nam. oko (vehicle). 10]
eye (cost) [col: ra (buy). 11, nta (selling). 10]
ra (buy) [rep: 11; ant: nta (selling). 10]
oko (vehicle) [rep: 10;]
12. 2 eni kinni (first person) [col: ore marun(five friends). 9]
naira Nigeria's currency) [col: ra (buy). 11 (2), eye
(cost). 11, nta (selling). 10,]
- 12/ 1 eni keji (second person) [col: num. eni kinni(first per-
13. son). 12; col: ore marun (five friends). 9]
13. 4 naira(Nigeria's -[rep: 12; col: ra (buy). 11(2), eye (cost)
currency) . 11, nta (selling). 10]
eni keta (third person) [col: num. eni keji (second per-
son) 12/13; eni kinni(first person). 12;
col: ore marun (five friends). 9]

- naira (Nigeria's -[rep: 13, 12; col: ra(buy). 11(2), ive currency) (cost). 11, nta(selling). 10)
- eni kerin (fourth person)[col: num. eni keta, (third person). 13, eni keji(second person). 12/13, eni kinni(first person). 12; col: ore marun (five friends). 9]
14. 5 ra (buy) [rep: 11 (2); ant: nta (selling). 10; col: ive (cost). 11,]
- oko (vehicle) [rep: 11, 10]
- naira(Nigeria's [rep: 13(2), 12; col: ra (buy). 11(2), ive currency) (cost). 11, nta (selling). 10)
- eni karun (fifth person)[col: num. eni kerin(fourth person). 13, eni keta(third person). 13, eni keji(second person). 12/13, eni kinni (first person). 12, col: ore marun (five friends). 9]
- naira (Nigeria's [rep: 14, 13(2), 12; col: ra(buy). 11 (2), currency) ive (cost). 11, nta(selling). 10]
15. 3 owo (money) [syn: naira (Nigeria's currency). 14 (2), 13 (2), 12, ive (cost). 11,]
- san (pay) [col: naira (Nigeria's currency). 14 (2), 13(2), 12, ive(cost). 11, nta(selling). 10]
- oko (vehicle) [rep: 14, 11, 10]
16. 3 mararun (all-five) [col: eni karun (fifth person.). 14]
- je (equals) [rep: 8]
- L (1) [rep: 16; syn: 1963 (12) + 1734 (13) + 1613 (13) + 9417 (14) 2, 107 (14)]
18. 1 omi (water) [rep: 17]
19. 3 tanki(tank) [rep: 17]
- kini(first) [col: num. merin (four). 18]
- galonu(gallon)[rep: 18]
20. 5 tanki (tank) [rep: 19, 18]
- keji (second) [col: num. kini (first). 19, merin(four). 18]
- galonu(gallon)[rep: 19, 18]
- galonu(gallon)[rep: 20, 19, 18]
- keta (third) [col: num. keji(second). 20, kini(first). 19, merin (four). 18]
21. 4 galonu(gallon)[rep: 20(2), 19, 18]
- kerin (fourth)[col: num. keta(third). 20, keji(second). 20, kini (first). 19, merin (four). 18]
- omi (water) [rep: 18, 17]
- mbe(is/exist) [syn: wa(exist). 18]
22. 5 tanki (tank) [rep: 20, 19, 18, 17]; col: galonu(gallon). 21, 20 (2), 19, 18; omi (water). 21, 18, 17,
- mererin(all [col: num. kerin(fourth). 21, keta(third). 20, four) keji (second). 20, kinni (first). 19; syn: merin (four). 18;]
- je (equals) [rep: 16, 8]
- galonu(gallon)[rep: 21, 20(2), 19, 18; tanki (tank). 20, 19, 18, 17]

- W (w)
- [syn: 15, 200(19) + 22, 147(20) + 10, 100(20)
+ 33, 897 (21); rep: 22]
24. 1 naira(currency)[syn: owo (money). 23]
25. 2 naira(currency)[rep: 24; syn: owo(money). 23]
ile (house) [rep: 24]
26. 1 naira(currency)[rep: 25, 24; syn: owo (money). 23]
27. 4 naira(currency)[rep: 26, 25, 24; syn: com. owo (money). 23;
naira(currency)[rep: 27, 26, 25, 24; syn: com. owo (money).
col: na (spend). 23]
melo(how much?)[col: naira (Nigeria's currency). 27a, 26,
23; col: na(spend). 23]
ijoba (government) [rep: 23] 25, 24; owo (money). 23]
28. 2 ibile (native) [rep: 23]
na (spend) [rep: 23]

Table 4.10 (1) - Lexical Cohesive Relations in Text 4.6

This scientific text, although specifically arithmetical, can be divided into four mini-texts. The first one begins from the first clause to line 8; the second, 9 to 16, the third, 17 to 22, and the fourth from 23 to the end. As a result of this division, and with specific reference to this text, all the lexical items are only cohesive within the mini-texts in which they function except je (equal) which runs through the first three mini-texts and is meaningful, generically, in the whole text.

Although each of the four mini-texts is about a different subject, all of them have figures and letters which are symbolic and representing certain things. These representations provide structural cohesion for the macro text as found in lines 8, 16, 22 and 27-28.

Table 4.10 (1) above shows that the material process rin (walk). 8 evolves with a larger collocation range, and is at

par with the symbolic d. Eni karun (fifth person). 14, also in the same Table, and naira (Nigeria's currency). 14 have five lexical items each in their relational patterns.

The following are the lexical chains in the text:

continued on next page

16.	mafarun (all-five)			san(pay)	je (equals)	(v) L L
17.	(i) tanki (tank)	(ii) omi(water)				
18.		omi (water)	(iii) merin (four)	(iv) wa (exist)	(v) galonu (gallon)	
19.	tanki(tank)		kini(first)		galonu(gallon)	
20.	tanki (tank)		keji(second) keta(third)		galonu(gallon) galonu(gallon)	
21.		omi (water)	kerin (fourth)	mbe (is)	galonu (gallon)	
22.	tanki (tank)		mererin (all-four)		galonu (gallon)	(vi) je w w
23.	(i) ijoba (government)	(ii) ibile (native)	(iii) na (spend)	(iv) owo (money)		(v) ile(house)
24.				naira (Nigeria's (currency)	ile(house)	
25.				naira (Nigeria's (currency)	ile(house)	
26.				naira (Nigeria's currency)		
27.	ijoba (government)			naira (Nigeria's currency)		
28.		ibile(native)	na(spend)	melo(how much)		

Table 4.10 - Lexical Chains in Text 4.6

Chains (i) in clauses 1-8, (i) in 9-16, (v) in 18-22 and (iv) in 23-28 form the core of the experiential meaning of the text. They represent the material process rin (walk) and the nominal groups ore marun (five friends).9, galonu (gallon).18, and owo (money).23 respectively. They also correspond to the lexical relations already established by rin (walk) in number (8.i), eni karun (fifth person) in (14.iv), galonu (gallon) in (22.iv) and naira (Nigeria's

currency) in (27.ii) respectively in Table 4.10 (1) and these realise the topics in the text.

What appears to be a common denominator in these mini-texts and which reveals its being a scientific text are the listings of numbers and figures for distance, money, and other materials. A set is created, therefore, for each of them by the repetition of such items as 1st, 2nd, and so on. Occurring with structural cohesive devices, these repetitions provide the text with its identity. By its arithmetical nature, the first three mini-texts end with a demand for what d, l, and w stand for. Ki ni (what(is)), and melo (how much) appear in the first three sub-texts. The nature of science is enquiry - hence ki ni (what (is)) means 'what is x ?' All these features reveal the text as belonging to an aspect of the scientific genre -arithmetic.

The text's lexical densities are as follows:

(a) Lexical Density

(i) Total number of words = 188
 Lexical items = 120
 Percentage = 63.82

(ii) Lexical items = 120
 Number of messages = 33
 Mean = 3.63

(b) Lexical Cohesive Density

Lexical cohesive items = 94
 Lexical items = 120
 Percentage = 78.33

% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	% Lexical Cohesive Density
63.82	3.63	78.33

Table 4.10 (3) Lexical Densities in Text 4.6

4.11 - Text 4.7 (Poetry) [Text 3.1.12 in Chapter 3]

1. Eni t'o lówó k'o ma fi gbéraga
 person PERF.+he VB+money NEG. AUX.VB. use proud
 'whoever has money should not be proud'
2. \Eni\ ti kò ní k'ó mú sùúrù
 rep:1
 person PERF. NEG. has should take patience
 'whoever does not have should be patient'
3. Awon \òtòsì\ \nd'eni\ \nsùn té\ o
 ant:lowo.1 rep:2 col:lowo.1
 those destitute become person PROG.sleep cushion EMPH.
 'the very poor may become the very rich'
4. \Aláso púpò\ nkù kan
 col:lowo.1
 owner+cloth many PROG.remain one
 'one with many clothes (i.e. riches) may be left with one'
5. \Eye\ \l'olá\, \eye\ \l'olá\
 syn:lowo.1 rep:5 rep:5
 bird (VB.+riches) bird (VB.+riches)
 'riches are like birds'(refrain)
6. Olúwa ma je ó \fò\ kúrò \n'ílé\ wa
 col:eye.5 col:sleep.3
 Lord NEG. allow it fly away PREP.house our
 'may the Lord not let it fly away from our home'

The following shows the Cohesive Relations in the text:

CN NT LI

PI & TCR

2. 1 Eni (person) [rep: 1]
3. 3 otosi(destitute) [ant: lowo (VB.+money).1.
nd'eni (become person)[syn:inc.eni(person).1]
sun te (cushion) [col: lowo (VB + money).1; ant: otosi
 (destitute).3]
4. 1 alaso pupo (owner of many clothes) [col: lowo (VB+riches).1; sun te
 (sleep in cushion).3; ant: otosi (destitute).3]
5. 3 l'ola (riches) [col: lowo (v + money).1; sun te (sleep
 cushion).3, alaso pupo (owner of many
 clothes).4; ant: otosi (destitute).3]
eye (bird) [rep:5]
l'ola(riches) [col: lowo (v+money).1; sun te (sleep
 cushion).3, alaso pupo (owner of many
 clothes).4; ant: otosi (destitute.3);
 rep:5]
6. 2 fo (fly) [col: eye (bird).5(2), met: l'ola

n'ile (PREP. house) (col: nsun te (sleep cushion). 3) (VB+riches). 5, (2))

Table 4.11 (1) - Lexical Cohesive Relations in Text 4.7

Number 5 (iii) in the above Table has the largest number of lexical relations which comprise both positive and negative aspects of riches from the Yoruba cultural perspective - 'having money,' 'sleeping on cushion,' and 'being destitute.'

The following are the cohesive chains in the text:

Table 4.11 - Lexical Chains in Text 4.7

Chain 2 in Table 4.11 (2) above, like number 5 (iii) in Table 4.11 (1), contains the largest number of relations. These lexical items express, within the poem's context, the instantial meaning, topically, of 'riches' and 'destitution.' Regarding its genre, two main characteristics of its lexical items reveal it as a poem.³⁹ The first is the use of contrasts - 'the rich' versus 'the destitute', and in a subtle way, 'the proud' and 'the patient'. The second, and

obviously the most important, is the use of metaphor - the association of 'flight' with 'riches'. 'Riches' and 'bird' in ordinary language are most unlikely to collocate. Yet the poet sees 'riches' as capable of 'flight' from some 'households' / persons that are lucky enough to have them.

The text's lexical densities are as follows:

(a) Lexical Density

(i) Total number of words	= 36
Lexical items	= 24
Percentage	= 66.66
(ii) Lexical items	= 24
Number of messages	= 7
Mean	= 3.42

(b) Lexical Cohesive Density

Lexical cohesive items	= 14
Lexical items	= 24
Percentage	= 58.33

% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	% Lexical Cohesive Density
66.66	3.42	58.33

Table 4.11 (3) - Lexical Densities in Text 4.7

4.12. - Conclusion

The way lexical items link messages in texts is different from that of referential ties. Referential cohesive devices attract, although not exclusively, the participants while lexical relations may comprise any group of lexical items.

In the above analysis, lexical cohesive relations are established only within the sub-parts of some of the texts while some cohesive relations run through the texts. Examples

are the radio, child-adult and scientific texts. This phenomenon seems to raise an interesting question concerning the establishment of the boundaries of texts and the determination of topic change. investigated. It may be described, meanwhile, as an embedded text in a meta-text which is both unique to itself as well as share some cohesive and structural relations with the meta-text. The proposed terms used to describe this phenomenon are 'macro' (ones which cut across mini-text boundaries) and 'micro' (functioning only within the mini-text).

The following table presents the figures for all the texts' lexical and cohesive densities:

No. of Text	Type of Text	% Lexical Density	Mean Lexical Density	Lexical Cohesive Density
4.1.	narrative	51.58	3.09	67.69
4.2.	newspaper	54.51	4.12	51.51
4.3.	television	53.27	3.25	60.00
4.4.	radio	56.03	4.80	50.69
4.5.	spoken	57.04	2.93	80.00
4.6	scientific	63.82	3.63	78.33
4.7.	poetry	66.66	3.42	58.33

Table 4.12 - Lexical and Cohesive Densities in the Texts

All the text's lexical and cohesive densities are collated in Table 4.12. Generally, from the above figures, it may be suggested that texts of natural language may have a lexical density of at least 40 percent and a mean of 2.00.

Some texts which have normal percentages of lexical density (i.e. 40% and over) as in the above Table, may have higher percentages of lexical cohesive density (i.e. Texts 4.1, 4.3, 4.5 and 4.6) while some may have lower percentage (i.e. Texts 4.2, 4.4 and 4.7).

Text 4.5, which is a spoken text has the lowest mean of 2.93 (a spoken text usually displays a much lower ratio of lexical items to total running words than a written text) even though its percentage of lexical density is high - 57.04., and its lexical cohesive density is also very high - 80.00. This may mean that the mean lexical density is more revealing as Halliday has suggested (1985:67).

Attempts have been made to suggest plausible topics, and identify the types of texts considering the meanings that the lexical items appear to express. All texts seem to consist of groups of lexical items which characterise their type. Two lines of evidence are used to support this - the chain patterns formed in each text, and the cumulative relations. By 'weaving' together the meanings expressed by the lexical items in the longest patterns of relations, topics are established and are sustained.

Notes

1. A lexical item is equated with a lexeme - its abstract unit (Richards et. al. 1985:163).
2. Richards et. al. , op. cit.
3. Halliday and Hasan (1976:291-292) observe that a lexical item may be 'less indeterminate,' in some instances than a word. They conclude, however, that the concept is very necessary for the understanding of text. (also Hasan 1984b:194).
4. Lyons (1968:436) finds this distinction of grammatical and lexical items the most satisfactory, and he gives credit to the linguists who proposed it including M. A. K. Halliday.
5. Although Halliday and Hasan (1976:284) find it difficult to be categorical regarding whether or not lexical cohesion has any relevance to co-reference, Hasan suggests here that some of the devices forming lexical relationships are capable of indicating the semantic bond of co-referentiality under specifiable condition.
6. It is assumed that Lamb's (1961) 'upward' and 'downward' signs may be equated to paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations respectively. Further distinctions may be made; to Sinclair (1966) lexis is syntagmatic and semantics paradigmatic. Hudson (1984) argues that lexical items may have paradigmatic relations irrespective of whether or not they occur in the sentence.
7. see Firth 1957:277; Mitchell 1971:48).
8. This combinatory power of grammar and semantics explains, in part, what Hasan (1987) describes as 'delicate grammar.'
9. It should be remembered that for Firth (1957:33) 'meaning' includes the function of the linguistic form. This he divides into 'minor' and 'major' functions. The minor is phonetic and the major equates to Halliday's lexicogrammar.
10. See Firth (1957:7); McIntosh (1966:194); Cummings and Simmons (1983:177)
11. The two taxonomies are not exactly the same. I have not copied them here because many questions may be asked. A few examples of their differences may be sufficient. Collocation which appears in the category set up in 1976 is not included in the 1985 category. The 1985 category includes instancial category but does not include hyponymy in its general types of co-classification or co-extension.
12. A similar category to Halliday and Hasan (1976) but which is by no means detailed is by Gutwinski (1976).

13. Lamb (1969:42) argues, however, that 'synonymy is always partial, never complete.'
14. This term is Hasan's creation (Halliday and Hasan 1985:81; Carter 1987:21).
15. The origin of this term can be traced to Firth (1957:194).
16. see Carter (1987:47-48).
17. Mitchell (1971:50-56) refers to collocation as particular members of generalised classes of association that have been labelled 'colligation.' He argues, more importantly, that collocations are to be studied within 'grammatical matrices' and colligation on the observation of collocational similarities or differences. Colligation, suggests, apparently, a stronger bonding between the lexical items than collocation.
18. see Sinclair(1966:412). He also rejects outright the view that the degree of proximity within the chosen boundaries of collocation should be considered of primary importance. He chooses a span of three lexical items before and after each node or the lexical item with which other collocates cohere.
19. These instantial meanings are exclusive to the particular texts in which they function.
20. She believes, however, in the 'intuitive reality' of the notion of collocation (Hasan 1984b:195).
21. see Richards et.al. (1985:163-164).
22. Philips (1985:31) refers to this as the 'aboutness' of the text.
23. see Fries (1983:134).
24. The lexical item, along with other lexical items in the clause, textually, explains the kinship relationship between the narrator and the person who gives him takute (trap). He is his uncle.
25. Both nje (eat[-ing]) and pa (kill) have, therefore, 'equivalent' type of instantial relations.
26. Kotu is an assimilated Yoruba word for court. Ile-ejo is its Yoruba equivalent.
27. Other courts like 'magistrate' and 'Court of Appeal' will be part of a large co-hyponyms.
28. 'Ogagun' in A Dictionary of the Yoruba Language is described as 'a captain in an army' (P.182). In practical terms, however, the title is generally used for all military officers whether in the army, navy or the air force. Although the Yoruba language has its own specific

titles for military officers, these do not exactly fit into the western style. So 'ogagun' neither indicates the differences among the armed forces nor the various ranks.

29. Mejidinlogun (eighteen) in clause 4 is cardinal, and ikejidinlogun (eighteen) is ordinal.
30. An inclusive E (you) though grammatically plural will refer, interpersonally, to a single person.
31. Other possible meanings of toka (point at/to) depending on the context are 'to observe', 'to explain' or 'to make reference to'. All three, in one way or another, may involve 'the act of saying' as it clearly does in this text.
32. This point is evident in lines 1-3 of the text particularly by considering the progressive material verbal item nde (coming) in clause 1, and conjunctive lexical item - lekan si (once more) in clause 3.
33. It is a characteristic of news texts, generally, to begin and end with summaries. 32. Olojo (day). 35b is part of the fourth mini-text.
34. Olojo (day). 35b is part of the four mini-text.
35. Idanileko (induction). 35b is part of the four mini-text.
36. Both the full and the partial lexico-structural repetitions are used in Yoruba poetry to achieve stylistic effects.
37. Bamgbose observes in this paper that the Yoruba poet deliberately juxtaposes lexical items in such a way 'as to force a comparison between them'. The writer as a linguist, in particular, demonstrates how such poems form 'semantic contrast or correspondence.'
38. Anat Ninio (1988: 35^{ff}) observes that 'Discussions of recent events (DRES) between mother-infant dyads' are important contexts for highlighting noteworthy events in the flow of experience for children.
39. For the characteristics and principles of Yoruba poetry, see Ogunbowale (1970: 147-180).

CHAPTER FIVE

COHESIVE HARMONY

5.0 -Introduction

Cohesion as described in the last two chapters is the existence of a non-structural semantic bond between at least two elements functioning in the textual environment. The descriptions of referential and lexical cohesion in the language show, among other things, that meaning does not reside solely in a single word, a phrase or a sentence. Rather, it also involves a complex inter-relatedness of semantic structures organised across a text.

How then does this description of referential and lexical cohesion relate to Cohesive Harmony?¹ I will begin to answer this question not by providing a definition of cohesive harmony straightaway, as this will be provided later in this chapter, but by drawing on its relationship to the analysis of texts. Cohesive harmony aims at showing, on the one hand, that cohesion is the basis for a text's coherence, and that 'variation in coherence,' on the other hand, 'is the function of variation in cohesive harmony of a text' (Halliday and Hasan 1985: 94).

Coherence is an important property of texts which enables a normal user of a language to comment whether or not a non-minimal text hangs together or coheres properly and, if necessary, which text is more coherent than another. A group of texts may then be grouped together on a cline of

coherence. Cohesion as a textual phenomenon provides one way of achieving coherence because texts vary in the extent to which they cohere, and cohesive harmony provides a way of establishing varying degrees of coherence (Hasan [1984b: 181 - 219]; Halliday and Hasan 1985: 89-94]). Like many other semantic phenomena in language, coherence is a representation of reality. It arises from 'the imposition of a grid upon sensory precepts; the categories of cohesion are the lexico-grammatical indication of the details of such a grid.' (Hasan 1984b: 210; Yang 1989: 256). A textual explanation for coherence may rest, therefore, on cohesive harmony.

For one thing, neither referential nor lexical cohesion as examined separately above (chapters three and four respectively) is sufficient to show a text's coherence. There are other kinds of cohesive ties which contribute to textual cohesion hence to coherence. Cohesive Harmony is the combination and the interaction of the cohesive chains formed by both referential and lexical cohesion because the elements which comprise them are able to function harmoniously with one another (Halliday and Hasan 1976: 292; 1985: 91-94; Hasan 1984b: 211-219; Halliday 1985a: 316). That is, the systemic function of cohesive harmony does not wholly reside in cohesive ties and their associated chains but in the potential inter-dependence of both of them. Thus, neither is seen in their textual formation just as grammatical nor lexical but as an integration of them. The resulting harmonious relationship then becomes a lexico-grammatical realisation of the semantic bonds which function in a text. It is the output of the two macrofunctions - the textual and

the experiential' (Halliday and Hasan 1985: 94).²

5.1 - Cohesive Harmony Hypothesis

The hypothesis³ establishing the relationship between cohesive harmony and coherence is stated as follows:

- (i) The lower the proportion of the Peripheral tokens to the Relevant ones, the more coherent the text is likely to be.
- (ii) The higher the proportion of the Central tokens to the non-central ones, the more coherent the text is likely to be. Any non-minimal text will be seen as coherent if its Central tokens form, at least, 50 per cent of the Total tokens. This percentage may be regarded as a measure of the text's cohesive harmony.
- (iii) The fewer the breaks or gaps in the picture of interaction, the more coherent the text. The larger the number of such gaps the less coherent the text would be.
- (iv) Gaps occur in non-interactive chains such that the patterns of interaction become separate. Several gaps in the interactive pattern show a feature of low coherence. Any two texts with the same measure of cohesive harmony can be measured further by considering the number of gaps in them. The one with a higher number of gaps is likely to be less coherent.

The core terms in the above hypothesis need to be explained.

Cohesive chains,⁴ (see also Chapter 3, section 3.1.7) as established in both referential and lexical cohesion in the last two chapters, form the systemic validity of cohesive relations.⁵ Identity chains (ICs), typically, are made up of items which are based on the semantic relation of co-referentiality. That is, they form a relation of identity with the same referent(s) - thing, event or circumstance in the text. These, therefore, are 'always textbound.' Lexical cohesive chains, which are referred to as Similarity Chains

(SCs), on the other hand, emerge from the semantic relation of either co-classification or co-extension (Hasan 1984b:205-206); Halliday and Hasan 1985:84-85). Similarity Chains (SCs) are based, typically, on the systemic realisation of the semantic fields of repetition, synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy and instantial relations (Hasan 1984b:202). Being that SCs may not refer to identical members of the same class of things, events, etc. but to their classes, they are not textbound.

A token is a lexical item. Both ICs and SCs are therefore made up of tokens. Five tokens are identified in the hypothesis - Total Tokens (TTs), Relevant Tokens (RTs), Central Tokens (CTs), Non-Central Tokens (NCTs) and Peripheral Tokens (PTs).

Total tokens refer to all the tokens in a text whether or not they have the potential to enter into cohesive chains. Relevant tokens refer to all the tokens which form either the Identity or the Similarity chains. Peripheral tokens do not participate in any kind of chain organisation. The Total tokens consist, therefore, of both the Relevant and the Peripheral tokens. The subset of Relevant tokens which actually interact in the text is the Central tokens. This group of tokens gives shape to the coherent development of the topic in the text (Hasan 1984:202, 216). The Non-central tokens are relevant tokens which do not participate in any interaction.

Interaction is effected when two or more members of a chain are in an identical functional relation to two or more

members of another chain. Even though cohesive chains help to build the foundation for coherence by grouping together the components of a message, the interactive relations brought about by certain sets of tokens is referred to as chain interaction (Halliday and Hasan 1985: 91).

Focal Chains are the groups of chains which interact more than other chains in a text.

Gaps are concerned with patterns of chain interaction. A set of interactive chains may form a continuous pattern which 'presents a unity' or the pattern so formed may consist of two or more groups thereby showing 'gaps.' A gap in an interactive pattern is usually associated with a feature of low coherence such that if two texts have the same measure of cohesive harmony, the one without a gap (or less number of gaps) may be regarded as more coherent (Hasan 1984b: 217-218).

In this analysis, I will exclude the other textual cohesive relations of substitution, ellipsis and conjunction.⁶ I will ignore also any extended collocation, instantial patterns, and all forms of structural relations (Hasan 1984b: 190, 202; Halliday and Hasan 1985: 85) - except where they are particularly germane to the analysis.

Two texts from different genres will be analysed for cohesive harmony in this chapter. These are Texts 5.2 and 5.3 below. Text 5.2 is a written narrative genre. Its referential cohesion is described in Chapter 3 (Text 3.1.0), and its lexical cohesion is described in Chapter 4 (Text 4.1). It is taken from a popular Yoruba fiction book. It describes an

aspect of farm life among the Yoruba - the destruction of maize plants by hedgehogs, particularly when they are just sprouting.

5.3 (Text 3.1.8 in Chapter 3; and Text 4.5 in Chapter 4), on the other hand, is a spoken genre. It is a casual conversation between a five-year-old girl and an adult. X stands for the adult interlocutor, and Y for the little girl.

The cohesive harmony of the two texts now will be described in the following pages. It is expected that the description will provide some insights into the nature of coherence and some differences between written and spoken texts.

5.2. - Written Text

The tokens comprising the ICs are in slashes while the ones comprising the SCs are put in brackets in the two texts.

Text 5.2 - Written Genre

1. Nigbati o di oju ale
when it is eye night
'when it was late at night'
2. mo pada wa si abà wa
I back come PREP. hut our
'I came back to our hut'
3. mo (lo) si odo egbon mi agba okunrin
ant: wa. 2
I go PREP. place elder DET. older male
'I went to my elder brother's place'
4. ti o je omo iya (baba) mi
col: okunrin. 3
PERF. who is child mother father DET.
'who is my father's brother (i.e. uncle)'
5. (egbon) "—
mo wi fun \u\ pe
I say PREP. him that
'I said to him that'

6. mo nfe de takute
 I PROG. want set trap
 'I want to set a trap'

« (egbon. 3)

7. \ó\ si (gbe) okan fun mi
 he then carry one PREP. me
 'he then gave one to me'

« (takute. 6)

8. mo (gbe) \e\ (lo) si inu (oko) wa
 rep: 7 rep: 3 col: aba. 2
 I carry it go (SEW) PREP. farm our
 'I carried it into our farm'

(takute. 6) «

9. ni inu agbado, mo (de) \e\ si
 rep: 6
 in PREP. maize I set it PREP.
 'inside the maize-plot and I set it on'

10. (oju) ona awon òyà ti nje (agbado) wa
 rep: 1 rep: 9
 eye path those hedgehog that eat maize our
 'the track of those hedgehogs that eat our maize'

11. nigbati o di (owuro) ojo keji
 ant: ale. 1
 when it is morning day two
 'in the morning of the next day'

(takute. 6) «

12. \ (takute) na\ kò ré
 rep: 6
 trap d-d NEG. spring
 'the trap did not spring' (i.e. go off)

(awon oya. 10) «

13. nitori biotilejepe \awon (oya)\ (wa) (pa) (agbado)
 rep: 10 rep: 2 col: nje. 10 rep: 10
 even though those hedgehogs come kill maize
 'even though those hedgehogs came to destroy the maize'

« (awon oya. 10)

14. \nwon\ kò (rin) si (oju) (takute) mi
 col: wa. 13 rep: 10 rep: 12
 they NEG. walk PREP. eye trap DET.
 'they did not come to where my trap was'

15. sugbon nigbati o di (owuro) (ojo keta)
 rep: 11 col: ojo keji. 11
 but when it is morning day three
 'but in the morning of the third day'

(takute. 14) «

16. ti mo (lo) wo \o\
 that I go look it
 rep: 8
 'that I went to look at it'

(takute. 12) «
 17. mo (ri) \i\ pe « (takute. 12)
 col: wo. 16 \o\ ti (ré)
 I see it that it PERF. spring rep: 12
 'I saw that it has sprung' (i.e. went off)

« (takute)
 18. \o\ ti (mu) (oya) ni (apa)
 col: takute. 14 rep: 14 mer: oya. 18
 it PERF. hold hedgehog PREP. arm
 'it has held hedgehog by the arm'

« (takute. 14)
 19. \o\ ti (ge) (apa) (oya)
 col: mu. 18 rep: 18 rep: 18
 it PERF. cut arm hedgehog
 'it has cut hedgehog's arm'

(oya. 19) «
 20. \ (eranko) na\ si ti (gbe) kukute iyoku lo
 sup: oya. 19 rep: 8
 animal d-d (SEW) PERF. carry stump remain away
 'the animal has run away with the stump of its arm'

On Table 5.2 (1) below is a lexical rendering of the text. Lexical rendering is a way of making clearer the underlying semantic relation of co-referentiality whereby certain relevant items are substituted for the text. (Halliday and Hasan 1985:87; Davies 1989:256). The underlined lexical items are the interpretation of the referential cohesive devices. For example, egbon (elder) in line (5) is the interpretation of the referential cohesive device u. The lexical items in broken slashes are either nouns modified by demonstratives or determiners. For example na (the) modifies takute (trap) in line 12.

1. oju (eye) ale (night)
2. wa (come) aba (hut)
3. lo (go) egbon (elder) okunrin (male)
4. baba (father)
5. egbon (elder)
6. de (set) takute (trap)
7. egbon (elder) gbe (carry)
8. gbe (carry) takute (trap) lo (go) oko (farm)
9. agbado (maize) de (set) takute (trap)
10. oju (eye) /oya/ (hedgehog) nje (eating) agbado (maize)

11. owuro (morning) ojo keji (second day)
12. |takute| (trap) re (spring)
13. |oya| (hedgehog) wa (come) pa (kill) agbado (maize)
14. oya (hedgehog) rin (walk) oju (eye) takute (trap)
15. owuro (morning) ojo keta (third day)
16. lo (go) wo (look) takute (trap)
17. ri (see) takute (trap) takute (trap) re (spring)
18. takute (trap) mu (hold) oya (hedgehog) apa (arm)
19. takute (trap) ge (cut) apa (arm) oya (hedgehog)
20. |eranko| (animal) gbe (carry)

Table 5.2 (1) Lexical Rendering in Text 5.2

The following Tables 5.2 (2 & 3) show the organisation of ICs and SCs in Texts 5.2. The bases for the organisation of these chains, more importantly, are the cohesive relations already identified in chapters three and four on referential and lexical cohesion respectively. The arrows between chains show evidence of potential chain connection.

continued on next page

19.
20.

19. o (it)

20. na (the)

Number of chains = 3
Tokens in ICs = 16

Table 5.2 (2) - Tokens in ICs in Text 5.2

Tokens in SCs in Text 5.2 are as follows:

<u>d</u>	<u>e</u>	<u>f</u>	<u>g</u>	<u>h</u>	<u>i</u>
1. ale (night)	1. oju (eye)	2. wa (come)	2. aba (hut)	3. okunrin (male)	6. de (set)
		3. lo (go)		4. baba (father)	9. de (set)
		8. lo (go)	8. oko (farm)		
	10. oju (eye)	13. wa (come)			
11. owuro (morning)	14. oju (eye)	14. rin (walk)			
15. owuro (morning)		16. lo (go)			
<u>j</u>	<u>k</u>	<u>l</u>	<u>m</u>	<u>n</u>	<u>o</u>
6. takute (trap)	7. gbe (carry)	9. agbado (maize)	10. oya (hedgehog)	10. nje (eating)	11. ojo keji (second day)
	8. gbe (carry)	10. agbado (maize)			
12. takute (trap) re					

continued on next page

(spring)		13. agbado (maize)	13. oya (hedge- hog)	13. pa (kill)	
14. takute (trap)		p			15. ojo keta (third day)
		16. wo (look)			
17. re (spring)		17. ri (see)			
18. mu (hold)			18. oya (hedge- hog) apa (arm)		
19. ge (cut)			19. apa (arm) oya ('hog)		
	20. gbe (carry)		20. era- nko (animal		

Number of chains = 13
Tokens in SCs = 44

Table 5.2 (3): Tokens in SCs in Text 5.2

The following are the Peripheral Tokens in Text 5.2:

2.	pada (back)
3.	odo (place) agba (older)
4.	omo (child) iya (mother)
5.	wi (say)
6.	nfe (PROG. want)
7.	okan (one) mi (me)
10.	ona (path)
13.	nitori (even/because) biotilejepe (though)
20.	kukute (stump) iyoku (remain) lo (away)

Number of PTs = 15

Table 5.2 (4) Peripheral Tokens in Text 5.2

For Text 5.2 above, the ICs are 16 (Table 5.2 [2]) and the SCs are 44 (Table 5.2 [3]). These two together (16+44 =60)

form the RTs because they participate in chain formation. The text's PTs is 15 (Table 5.2.(4)). The text's TTs, which is the sum of RTs + PTs is $(15+60) = 75$. This is shown on Table 5.2 (5) below:

Text	RTs	PTs	TTs
5.2.	60	15	75

Table 5.2 (5) - Total Tokens in Texts 5.2

5.3 - Spoken Text

Text 5.3 - Spoken Genre

(Titi's elder brother Seun is sent to go and buy a packet of biscuits for both of them).

1. X- Wá jòkó, Titi (a gesture accompanies the utterance)
come sit Titi
'come and sit down Titi'
 2. Y- Hún ?
'What?'
 3. X- (Wá) (jòkó)
rep:1 rep:1
come sit
'come and sit down'
 4. Y- Emi náà máa jé biskit
I d-d AUX. VB. eat biscuit
'me too will eat biscuit'
- (Y nearly falls down from the concrete railing)
5. X- Má mà subú!
do NEG. fall
'do not fall down'
 6. Y- (Emi) náà máa (je) (biskit)
rep:1 rep:1 rep:1
I d-d AUX. VB. eat biscuit
'me too will eat biscuit'

7. X- Ta ló ra aso yi fún e?
 who (is+he) buy cloth this PREP. you (pointing to her dress)
 'who bought this attire for you?'
8. Y- (Ehéen?)
 syn: Hun. 2
 'what?'
9. X- (Ta) ló (ra) (aso) yi fún e? (a distant voice
 rep: 7 rep: 7 rep: 7 (is heard and
 who(is+he) buy cloth this PREP. you (she looks at
 'who bought this attire for you?' (the direction
10. Y- móomi mi
 mummy DET.
 'my mum (mother)'
11. X- (mòómo) e ló (ra)('so) fún e (a distant voice
 rep: 10 rep: 9 rep: 9 (is, again,
 mum your (is+he) buy cloth PREP. you (heard
 'your mother bought this attire for you'
12. Y- Hun
 'yes'
- (silence)
13. X- (móomi) e ló (rà) fún e
 rep: 11 rep: 11
 mum your (is+he) buy PREP. you
 'your mum bought this attire for you'
14. Y- (Hen)
 rep: 12
 'yes'
- (moomi. 13) "┐
15. X- igbàwo ni \nwon\ (rà)?
 rep: 13
 when is they buy
 'when did she buy it?'
16. Y- (igbà) t'á n ló sí'bi kan wò
 syn: igbawo. 15
 when PREP. we PROG. go PREP. place one look
 'when we were going to somewhere, see'
17. - (mòómo) mi ó dè wá (rà)
 rep: 13 rep: 15
 mum DET. she then come buy
 'my mother then bought it'
- "┐ (mòómo. 17)
18. X- \nwon\ (rà)
 rep: 17
 they (sg.) buy
 'she bought it'

19. Y- E (wo) bí \báyi?\ (she points to her knees)
 rep: 16
 you (sg.) look here this way/place/at this
 'you, look at this' (that is, the knee)
20. - tó máa n (dùn) mi, e (wò)
 rep: 20
 that always PROG. hurt me you (sg.) look
 'and see, it hurts me, look'
- « (báyi*. 19)
 21. X- \ó\ n (dùn) è
 rep: 20
 it PROG. hurt you
 'it hurts you'
22. Y- (Hen)
 rep: 14
 'yes'
- « (báyi*. 19)
 23. X- igbàwo \l'ó\ bèrè?
 when (is+he) start
 'when did it start ?'
- « (báyi*. 19)
 24. Y- igbì \ó\ n (dùn) mi ni (mo) subú, wò (móomi)
 rep: 21 syn: emi. 6 rep: 17
 when it PROG. hurt me is I fall look mum
 'when it hurts me, then I fell down, look (mum)'
25. - mi (dè wá) fi àtikè si, (mo) (dè wá) n ké
 rep: 17 rep: 24 rep: 25
 DET. then come put powder PREP. I then come PROG. cry
 'my mum then put powder into it and I started crying'
26. X- o (wá) n (ké)
 syn: de wa. 25 rep: 25
 you come PROG. cry
 'you began to cry'
27. Y- (Hen)
 rep: 22
 'yes'
28. X- kí ló dé tó fi n (ké) ?
 rep: 26
 INT. (SEW) happen that (SEW) PROG. cry
 'what happened that you have to cry ?'
29. Y- (igbò) jé Seun l'ó wá gbé mi (subú), (wò) (points)
 rep: 24 rep: 24
 syn: igbì
 when is Seun (is+he) come carry me fall, look
 'when it was Seun who made me fall, look'

30. X- kí ló (dé) tó fi n (ké) ?
 rep: 28
 INT. (SEW) happen that (SEW) PROG. cry
 'what happened that you have to cry ?'

31. - sé \ó\ n (ta) é ni à \b'ò\ n (dùn) è?
 « (bayi*.19) (bayi*.19) »
 syn: dun. 24
 INT. it PROG. pinch you is or (INT.+it) PROG. hurts you
 'is it pinching you or is it hurting you ?'

32. Y- \ó\ n (ta) mí
 rep: 31
 it PROG. pinch me
 'it is pinching me'

33. X- \ó\ n (ta) é
 rep: 31
 it PROG. pinch you
 'it pinches you'

34. Y- (Hen)
 rep: 27
 'yes'

35. X- má (ke) mó o
 rep: 30
 NEG. cry again EMPH.
 'do not cry again'

36. Y- (Hùn ùn)
 syn: hen. 34
 'yes'

The source of bayi (this/this place), as starred in clause 21 above, is in clause 19. The child directs the attention of the adult interlocutor to look at a place which happens to be her knees; the knee which hurts her (clause 20). The object to which she directs attention, which in SFT is exophoric, is therefore retrievable in the context of situation. Although such an exophoric item may be difficult to interpret, it does not 'prevent the formation of cohesive ties'; and, indeed, it contributes to texture (Halliday and Hasan 1985:88). For the purpose of this analysis, I equate this referent to the girl's injured knee and bayi (this

place) is starred to represent this interpretation. Children's spoken texts, in particular, would contain several such indexical referents.

The following is a lexical rendering of the text:

1. wa (come) joko (sit)
2. hun (what)
3. wa (come) joko (sit)
4. emi (I) je (eat) biskit (biscuit)
6. emi (I) je (eat) biskit (biscuit)
7. ta (who) ra (buy) aso (cloth)
8. ehéen (what)
9. ta (who) ra (buy) aso (cloth)
10. móomi (mother)
11. mòómo (mother) ra (buy) 'so (cloth)
12. Hun (yes)
13. móomi (mother) ra (buy)
14. Hen (yes)
15. igbawo (when) moomi (mother) ra (buy)
16. igba (when) wo (look)
17. mòómo (mother) de wa (then come) ra (buy)
18. moomi (mother) ra (buy)
19. wo (look)
20. dun (hurt)
21. bayi* (this/place) dun (hurt)
22. Hen (yes)
23. igbawo (when) bayi* (this/place)
24. igbi (when) bayi* (this/place) dun (hurt) mo (I)
25. de wa (then come) mo (I) de wa (then come)
26. wa (come) ke (cry)
27. Hen (yes)
28. de (happen) ke (cry)
29. igbo (when) subu (fall) wo (look)
30. de (happen) ke (cry)
31. bayi* (this/place) ta (pinch) bayi* (this/place)
dun (hurt)
32. bayi* (this/place) ta (pinch)
33. bayi* (this/place) ta (picnh)
34. Hen (yes)
35. ke (cry)
36. Hun un (yes)

Table 5.3 (1) - Lexical Rendering in Text 5.3

There is no lexical item enclosed in broken slashes because neither a demonstrative nor a determiner is used in the text.

Below are the cohesive chain formations in the text:

Number of chains = 2
 Tokens in ICs = 11

Table 5.3 (2) - Tokens in ICs in Text 5.3

continued next page

m				(mum)	
12. hun (yes)	11. ra (buy)			11. moomo (mum)	11. aso (cloth)
14. Hen (yes)	13. ra (buy)	n		13. moomi (mum)	
	15. ra (buy)	15. igbawo (when)			o
		16. igba (when)			16. wo (look)
	17. ra (buy)	p		17. moomo (mum)	
	18. ra (buy)	17. de (then) wa(come)			
	q				19. wo (look)
	20. dun (hurt)				20. wo (look)
22. hen (yes)	21. dun (hurt)				
	24. dun (hurt)		24. mo (I)	24. moomi (mum)	24. wo (look)
				r	
		25. de (then) wa(come) [x2]	25. mo (I)	23. igbawo (when)	
			s	24. igbi (when)	
		26. wa (come)	24. subu (fall)		
		t			
		25. ke (cry)			

continued on next page

27. hen (yes)		26. ke (cry)			
		28. ke (cry)	29. subu (fall)	29. igbo (when)	29. wo (look)
					u
	31. ta (pinch) dun(hurt)	30. ke (cry)			28. de (happen)
	32. ta (pinch)				30. de (happen)
	33. ta (pinch)				
34. hen (yes)		35. ke (cry)			
36. Hun- un (yes)					

Number of chains = 19
Tokens in SCs = 68

Table 5.3 (3) - Tokens in SCs in Text 5.3

The following are the Peripheral Tokens in the text:

1. Titi (Titi)
16. lo (go) 'bi (place)
19. bayi* (this place)
23. bèrè (start)
25. àtikè (powder)
29. Seun (Seun) gbe (carry)
35. mó (again)

PTs = 9

Table 5.3 (4) - Peripheral Tokens in Text 5.3

For Text 5.3 above, the ICs are 11 (Table 5.3 (2)) and the SCs are 68 (Table 5.3 (3)). These two together (11+68 =79)

form the RTs because they participate⁷ in chain formation. The text's PTs is 9 (Table 5.3 (4)). The text's TTs, which is the sum of RTs + PTs is $(9+79) = 88$. This is shown together with the figures for Text 5.2 in Table 5.3 (5) below:

Text	RTs	PTs	TTs
5.2.	60	15	75
5.3.	79	9	88

Table 5.3(5) - Total Tokens in Texts 5.2 and 5.3

From Table 5.3 (5) above, the percentages of tokens in cohesive chains may be calculated for the two texts. For Text 5.2, it is 80.00 $(60 \times 100 \div 75)$, and Text 5.3, it is 89.77 $(79 \times 100 \div 88)$. Although each of the two texts is coherent⁸ for its purpose, the two percentages appear not significantly different as might be expected between a spoken and a written text (a written text is expected to have a higher percentage of cohesive tokens than a spoken text).⁹ The insignificant difference in the percentage may be attributed to the difference in the length of the two texts. Text 5.2 is organised into 20 lines and 5.3 into 36 although the latter consists of several one word lines.

The above finding is corroborated by the percentage of PTs to RTs of the two texts. The higher the number of PTs, the lower the percentage of PTs to TT. For Text 5.2 the Percentage of PTs to RTs is 25.00 $(15 \times 100 \div 60)$, and that 5.3 is 11.39 $(9 \times 100 \div 79)$. The high PTs for Text 5.2 reflects on the percentage of its RTs to TTs.

5.4 - Chain Interaction

Although the high percentage of tokens which participate in chain formation as seen in Texts 5.2 and 5.3 above may explain, in part, the basis for coherence, it is, however, not necessarily a proof of coherence. It is the textual formation of the ICs and the SCs¹⁰, which are constructed on semantic grounds, as well as the interaction which takes place among their members which provide cohesive harmony. Interaction takes place when two or more members of a chain stand in the same functional relation to at least two other members of another chain. The degree of such interaction among chains directly corresponds to the degree of coherence in a text. The higher the percentage of cohesive harmony in a text, the more coherent the text.

This type of interaction functions at two constituent levels - the group and the clause. At the group level, for example nominal group, the elements Thing or Head and Epithet may interact. At the clause level, elements from both the nominal and verbal groups may interact.¹¹

Below is an explanation of each type of relation involved (Hasan 1984b: 216; Halliday and Hasan 1985: 93):

Each block represents a chain or part of it. The broken lines enclose the tokens in interaction. Each block is connected to some other block by a double-tipped arrow. These arrows on top of which is a Roman numeral depict the operating functional relation. The following is a guide to the relations formed by the arrows and the numeral accompanying them:

- i. Actor-action/Medium-Process relation
- ii. Action-acted-upon/Process-Phenomenon relation
- iii. Actor-Location/Thing-Location relation
- iv. Attribute-attribuant/Epithet-Thing relation

An example of interaction at the group level which is taken from Text 5.2 is exemplified in Table 5.4 (1) below.

Table 5.4 (1) - Simple Interaction at Group Level

The above table illustrates a Thing-Epithet relation. Oya (hedgehog) is Thing and apa (arm) is Epithet.¹² Even if both tokens in either a or b are not of the same kind each token in b may modify each token in a.

An example at the level of the clause is also taken from Text 5.2 as shown in Table 5.4 (2) below:

Table 5.4 (2) - Intraclausal Interaction

Oya (hedgehog) in chain c above interacts with all of the tokens in d. It functions as Thing or 'actor', while any token forming part of chain d is a 'process'. Agbado (maize) in e is the 'thing' affected by the 'action' (i.e. pa

(destroy)) of the 'actor' oya (hedgehog). Intraclausally, therefore, the 'doer-doing, done-to' phenomenon which explains, in part, the grammar of the language as briefly explicated in Chapter Two on Structural Groups, forms the basis of the interaction being described in this chapter. This kind of interaction is 'staggered' (Hasan 1984b:213). By being 'staggered' is meant that the tokens involved in the interaction are not in very close proximity with one another in the text. 'Staggering', according to Hasan (op. cit. p.213) 'is a necessary attribute of multiple chain interaction when the grammatical function in question is group-internal, it is not confined solely to such interaction.'

Chain interaction, however, can be more elaborately described at a level other than that of group and clause. This elaborate chain interaction can be visually displayed if the text is not too long. Like the descriptions on referential and lexical cohesion, not all the Relevant tokens participate in chain interaction. Although cohesion forms the basis for the components of the message in the text, chain interaction visually highlights its continuities and the discontinuities (e.g. chain conjunction and chain disjunction (Hasan 1984b:198-199)) It represents the final picture of unity inherent in the messages as a whole. The textual phenomena of continuity and discontinuity in chain formation will be discussed in Table 5.4 (3) below:

Tables 5.4 (3) and (4) below display the chain interaction in Texts 5.2 and 5.3 respectively:

Table 5.4 (3) - Chain Interaction in Text 5.3

Block e may be used to illustrate continuity and discontinuity in chain formation. Oya (hedgehog) [10-14] as 'actor' interacts with the 'processes' [10-14] in block f. The interaction discontinues there but begins again in 18 where it forms a double chain of interaction with the tokens in blocks h and i. In chain conjunction, however, (no example is obtained in my data) two items merge with each other (e.g. 'boy' and 'girl' become 'they'). Disjunction begins when 'they' is separated somewhere along the chain interaction to become 'boy' and 'girl' or even when an additional item (e.g. 'daddy') is added to the 'conjunction' (Hasan 1984b: 197-199).

The following is the chain interaction in Text 5.3:

18. moomi
(mother)

18. ra
(buy)

f

g

f	g
21. bayi* (this)	21. dun (hurt)
24. bayi* (this)	24. dun (hurt)
31. bayi* (this)	31. ta (pinch)
bayi* (this)	dun (pinch)
32. bayi* (this)	32. ta (pinch)
33. bayi* (this)	33. ta (this)

Table 5.4 (4) - Chain Interaction in Text 5.3

Texts 5.2 and 5.3 as analysed above (Table 5.4 [3&4]) show that chains have the potential of participating in multiple interaction. A glance at the analysis also shows that not all the tokens are involved in chain interaction. Those tokens involved in chain interaction are the CTs and those not involved are the NCTs. Examples of NCTs in Text 5.2 are ale (night), owuro (morning), egbon (elder), aju (eye), okunrin and aba (hut). Examples in Text 5.3. are joko (sit), subu (fall), ke (cry) de (happen) and wo (look).

The two texts may be compared at this stage of the analysis. Text 5.2 is a written (narrative) genre, and is divided into 20 lines. Text 5.3 is a spoken (child-adult conversation) genre, and is divided into 35 lines several of which are one-word utterances. In terms of their cohesion, Text 5.3 (TTs = 88) appears to be more cohesive than Text 5.2 (TTs = 75)

although a mention has already been made of the greater length of the former. Text 5.2 (Table 5.4 (3)) shows a more complex chain interaction than Text 5.3 (Table 5.4 (4)). Furthermore, the percentage of its CTs to TTs, as shown below, shows that it is more coherent than Text 5.3.

Texts	TTs	RTs	PTs	CTs	CTs as % of TTs	Ratio CTs to PTs
5.2.	75	60	15	34	45.33	2.26
5.3.	88	79	9	30	34.09	3.33

Table 5.4. (5) - Percentage of CTs to TTs

The percentage of CTs to TTs in both Texts (Table 5.4 (5)) is less than 50% as the cohesive harmony hypothesis suggests (section 5.1 above). The ratio of CTs to PTs which may also be significant is higher in Text 5.3 than in Text 5.2 because the latter's PTs is higher than the former. Perhaps 50% is too high a grid because both texts are obviously coherent. If bayi* (this place), which is apparently exophoric, is not analysed as orókún (knee) the entire text will have displayed, perhaps, an unconvincing lack of coherence because the text is obviously functional and coherent as a casual conversation between a child and an adult. It is significant, however, that Text 5.2, which is the written text, has a higher percentage of CTs to TTs despite the extended length of Text 5.3 which is the spoken text and its larger number of cohesive tokens. This result seems to justify the fact that the written text are generally more coherent than the spoken text.

5.5 - Conclusion

The above description of textual coherence, though very brief indeed, is a necessary part of the understanding of the linguistic concept of cohesion from the point of view of SFT. It puts in perspective the relationship between cohesion and coherence; the former forming the foundation on which the edifice of the latter is built.¹³ It also shows that the mere identification of both referential and lexical relations is very useful but clearly insufficient without a mapping of the two phenomena harmoniously. Through chain interaction, the two-ness which forms the basis for cohesion clearly depicts the semantic bond which exists among parts of the messages in the text.

Even though Text 5.2, a written genre, is shown by the percentage of CT to TT to be more coherent than Text 5.3, a spoken genre, it does not mean that the written language is more complex than the spoken language. The spoken language is capable of the degree of complexity of the written language. The written language, for example, may be complex and dense lexically because of the details that have to be included so that the readers may understand it, whereas the spoken language is usually dynamic and intricate.¹⁴ The two genres are, therefore, alternative realisations of the meaning potential of language.

The fact that Text 5.2 is more coherent than Text 5.3 may be explained in terms of the type of the register of the latter - it is a casual conversation between a five-year-old child and an adult. Even though the child uses relatively

long structures in clauses 16-17, 19-20 and 24-25, her level of conversation is commensurate with her age - simple sentences, child-like repetitions and lack of clear focus and concentration on either of the two topics which emerge from the text.¹⁵ The spoken text consists of many lexical items which do not participate in chain interaction. These lexical items contribute to the its low coherence. If it had been an adult-adult conversation,¹⁶ it would have been more coherent. Text 5.2, on the other hand, is written by a mature adult and writer, with the kind of complexity not obtainable in the kind of spoken text of Text 5.2.

Cohesive harmony is, on the whole, a very useful index of coherence. It is, nevertheless, more restricted to bringing into prominence the network of scattered messages in the text. There are usually several tokens not directly involved in the measurement - Peripheral and those not forming a part of the Central tokens. The ratio between the CTs and PTs, as shown in Table 5.4 (5), is, however, significant because it seems to show that Text 5.3 is, nevertheless, coherent. Cohesive harmony also brings into focus the referential cohesive devices as most of them appear to interact more than the lexical items. Finally, as Hasan (1984b:219) asserts, much work still needs to be done to extend the scope of cohesive harmony to the study of interpersonal and logical relations.

Notes

1. The development of the concept of Cohesive Harmony may be solely attributed to Hasan, except that she herself admits borrowing largely, though with divergencies, from Halliday's earlier works (Hasan 1984b: 214).
2. Halliday and Hasan (op. cit. p.94) observe that the concept of cohesive harmony can be further refined by bringing in the logical and the interpersonal functions into the picture.
3. see Hasan 1984b: 218; Halliday and Hasan 1985: 93-94. Also this hypothesis has been variously applied partly or wholly by some linguists to investigate language disorders in people and in teaching - (Pappas [1984]; Bingham [1986]; Yang [1989] and Davies [1989] etc.).
4. In SFT's technical term, cohesive chain is formed by a set of items each of which is related to the others by the semantic relation of co-reference, co-classification, and/or co-extension (Halliday and Hasan 1985: 84).
5. They do establish substitution, ellipsis and conjunction cohesion as well.
6. These three other types of cohesion - substitution, ellipsis and conjunction are, indeed, outside the scope of this work.
7. Hasan (1984: 210) used 'subsumed' instead.
8. There seems to be no need to test the coherency of the two texts by the listening judgements of native speakers as was done in an earlier analysis (Halliday and Hasan 1985; Hasan 1984b). One of the three texts used by Halliday and Hasan was obviously incoherent. 5.1 and 5.2 in this work are coherent.
9. Even though both written and spoken forms of any language are different, they can be alternative ways of expressing the meaning potential of the language. Halliday (1985b: 93) observes that 'there is a sense in which speech and writing create different realities. Writing creates a world of things; talking (i.e. speech) creates a world of happening.'
10. The integration becomes a lexicogrammatical unit.
11. Hasan (1984b: 213) describes these interactions as 'intragroup' and 'intraclausal' respectively.
12. In the description of nominal group, apa (arm) is an Epithet to oya (hedgehog). But in lexical relation, it is meronymic.

13. Hasan (op. cit. p. 218) compares the two to Saussurean's concept of paradigm and syntagm respectively.
14. 'Grammatical intricacy takes the place of lexical density' (Halliday 1985b: 87).
15. Evidence of these claims abound in the text. Few examples are: (1) several uses of Hun (yes) and Hen (what) makes the adult interlocutor to, apparently to his annoyance, repeat several of his utterances.
16. Spoken texts from formal meetings are also most likely to be more coherent than this one.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

6.0 - Introduction

In this chapter, the relevance and the limitations of this study are briefly described. Its relevance concerns, basically, its contribution to the understanding of the Yoruba language and its application in further researches. Its limitations, as perhaps in any other study, may include my lack of a 'complete' knowledge of the language even as a native speaker and, indeed, the linguistic theory.¹

6.1 - The Relevance of the Study

Like proponents of other linguistic theories, systemic linguists have paid more attention to the description of the English language than any other language. This study is a contribution to the study of a language other than English from the perspective of SFT.² It demonstrates the applicability of SFT to Yoruba because some of its categories have been found useful in the analysis of the cohesive patterns of the language. These categories, through the analysis, provide some insights into the nature and structure of the language. The importance of this study may be understood considering the fact that most of the previous grammatical descriptions of the Yoruba language do not have any sound theoretical basis.

Rather than examine ad hoc sentences, copious natural texts in different genres have been examined because one of the main strengths of SFT is to examine natural texts in use. These numerous, diversified and fairly lengthy texts give a wide coverage of most of the systemic possibilities in the language and substantially reduce the field of subjective judgements. The study also provides, as far as the descriptions in each section are concerned, the relevant basis for comparing different genres. Realities which form part of the day-to-day use of the language become evident in most of the texts. Some of these include explanations of certain cultural implications, features of code-mixing, particularly in spoken texts, and of English language lexical items which are already assimilated into the system of the language.

In specific terms, a more detailed description of the nominal group than the narrower descriptions by Bamgbose and Awobuluyi has been provided. It is argued that rather than a nominal group which has other elements modifying the Head only to its right, a series of modifiers may also precede the Head.³ As appropriate, SFT's terminologies have been adopted to describe, for example, the elements which precede the Thing. In experiential terms, those elements which precede the Thing are referred to as pre-qualifiers and those which follow it are post-qualifiers. In interpersonal terms, these are referred to as pre-modifiers and post-modifiers respectively. The structure of the Yoruba nominal group like English is built upon the nucleus of the Head - but unlike

English has extended pre- and post-modifiers and double deictics.

Having pointed out that co-referentiality forms the basis of referential cohesion, seven types of co-referential devices are identified in the language. These are single, contracted, compound, inclusive, partial, dual and cumulative devices. These co-referential devices variously form meaningful textual relations with their referents.

Some texts' lexical cohesive relations are established only within their sub-parts, while some run through the entire text. This phenomenon, which means that the text is both unique to itself as well as shares some cohesive and structural relations with the whole text, is described as an embedded text in a meta-text or simply as micro and macro cohesive relations. Lexical density is measured both by finding its percentage and mean. A measurement of lexical cohesive density supplements these two measurements.

The concept of cohesion in SFT may be understood better by the application of the concept of cohesive harmony because the latter is a very useful index of coherence. Through chain interaction, the dynamic organisation of certain tokens which form the core of messages (i.e. topics) and the coherence of a text is realised and measured. This is used to show which is more coherent between two texts - spoken and written.

6.2 - The Study's Limitations

describing a language using a theory that has been used extensively to describe another language can be a very difficult task. Basic difficulties often arise particularly in the areas of meaning. The cultures on which the languages are based and their terminologies may be blurred in certain areas. Being aware of these differences between English and Yoruba, efforts are made throughout this study to describe Yoruba in its own terms.

Three main difficulties can be mentioned concerning its data. Firstly, despite the fact that the translations of the texts are two-layered - literal and equivalent, no claim can be made to their being completely in one-to-one correspondence in terms of their meanings mainly because the two languages have different world-views. Their clausal organisations on different lines may run into one another such that the equivalent translations have to flow according to their meaning rather than their linear organisations. The focus of attention, throughout the analysis, is on the Yoruba text rather than either the literal or equivalent English translations. Secondly, the general use of tone marks on the vowels is varied. The variation ranges from well-marked to zero-marked texts. Spoken texts - formal (classroom lesson) and informal (child-adult conversation), radio and television texts are well-marked because it is my responsibility to mark them. Written texts - narrative, scientific and poetry texts, in most cases, are poorly marked; at times, the marks are completely omitted. All these are represented in this

who?

study as they are found in their sources. The newspaper texts, unfortunately, do not have tone marks on the vowels at all. This deliberate omission may not pose any problems to most literate native speakers of the language, although it will definitely affect their pace of reading. Non-literate native speakers, on the other hand, and those who use it as a second language will find such texts very difficult to understand. Thirdly, although the examples given are numerous and comprise different discourse genres, they have by no means exhausted all the linguistic possibilities even in the particular areas investigated. In many cases, ad hoc examples have had to be provided in clause form to clarify certain vital points.

6.3 - Implications for Further Research

SFT's description of cohesion for the English language is basically organised into five parts. Referential and lexical cohesion are two of the parts. Others are substitution, ellipsis and conjunction. These features may also occur in the Yoruba language, although their forms of occurrence, which are yet to be described using this theoretical framework, may be different. One of the strengths of this study as remarked is its broad-based data. For lack of space and time, the data used are controlled (i.e. culled out from longer texts). Far more examples of diversified data still need to be used to further elucidate referential and lexical cohesion in the language.

The concept of cohesive harmony also may be used to measure various linguistic tasks (social and clinical) such as the language development of children, second language learning, reading and comprehension, language disorders (i.e. aphasia) and several other linguistic problems.⁴

Although the use of a large body of natural texts as my main data, instead of relying solely on ad hoc clauses and short texts, has been very beneficial because many issues, which may not have occurred, did in fact occur, naturally. This points, however, to certain areas in which further work could be done.

Some of these areas concern the nature and status of text (e.g. defining and classifying embedded text in a meta-text), ambiguity (e.g. children's casual conversation and the sequence of messages)⁵ and grammar (e.g. (i) the elements comprising a group; (ii) the measurement of lexical density (e.g. by word, or clause or message)).

6.4 - Conclusion

Systemic Functional Theory (SFT) has been used, in this study, to describe both referential and lexical cohesion in Yoruba using texts of different genres.⁶ There seem^s to be no doubt that the theory is as applicable to Yoruba as it is to English, even though the two languages belong to language families that are far apart. Chapters on theoretical foundation, structural groups and cohesive harmony have provided very useful support in achieving this goal.

In this final chapter, the importance and the limitations of the research have been summarised, and areas of further research, and further applications of the concept of cohesion, have been foreshadowed.

Notes

1. This, indeed, is my first attempt at studying my language and the linguistic theory in any great depth.
2. Some aspects of Chinese, Arabic, Beja and Tagalog have been studied using the theory (Butler 1985b:191-192).
3. This feature of the nominal group is evident in the newspaper texts.
4. Elizabeth Armstrong, in an unpublished M.A.(Hons) thesis submitted to Macquarie University, Australia, in 1988, used the concept to measure the degree of aphasia in children with disability.
5. The casual conversation between the child and me (Text 3.1.8. [24]) shows that some topical elements may not be coherent in children's talk. The clause is repeated for ease of reference:

igbi ó n dùn mí ni mo subú
when it PROG. hurt me VB. I fall
'when it hurts me I fell down'

The order in which she organises the events in the above clause is incoherent because the event of 'falling' would normally precede the event of sustaining an injury. For this child, this sequential order of events is not the likelihood.

6. These are narrative, newspaper, radio, television, casual conversation, classroom, scientific and poetry texts.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abimbola, Wande (1982), 'Notes on the Collection, Transcription, Translation and Analysis of Yoruba Oral Literature' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Abiri, J. O. O. (1981), Learning and Teaching Yoruba in Post-Primary Institutions, Macmillan (Nig.) Publishers Ltd.
- Adenaike, Felix A. (1987), (ed.), Iroyin Yoruba, African Newspapers of Nigeria Ltd. Ibadan, Wednesday, January 28 - Tuesday, February 3.
- Adenaike, Felix A. (1987), (ed.), Iroyin Yoruba, African Newspapers of Nigeria Ltd. Ibadan, Wednesday, February 25 - Tuesday, March 3.
- Adeniran, Adekunle (1978), 'The Standard Language Question in Language Planning: A Preliminary Appraisal of Developments in Yoruba' in (ed.) R. N. Egudu, Nigerian Journal of the Humanities, A Publication of the Faculty of Arts, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria.
- Adetugbo, Abiodun (1973), 'The Yoruba Language in Yoruba History' in (ed.) S. O. Biobaku, Sources of Yoruba History, Oxford University Press.
- Adetugbo, Abiodun (1979), 'Nigerian English and Communicative Competence' in (ed.) Ebo Ubahakwe, Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria, Selections from the Proceedings of the Ninth Annual Conference of the Nigerian English Studies Association, African Universities Press, Ibadan.
- Adetugbo, Abiodun (1982), 'Towards a Yoruba Dialectology' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Adewale, Moni (1987), (ed.), Isokan, Ile Itewe Konkoodu ti Naijiria (Concord Press of Nigeria), Ikeja, February 10 - February 16.
- Adewole, Lawrence O. (1989), 'Sequence and Co-occurrence of Yoruba Auxiliary Verbs' in (ed.) William Cowan, Canadian Journal of Linguistics, Carleton. Bitnet, 34(1):1-17, March.
- Afolayan, Adebisi (1982), 'Yoruba Language and Literature' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.

- Allan, Keith (1986), Linguistic Meaning, Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Allerton, D. J. (1979), Essentials of Grammatical Theory, Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Alo, Moses A. (1989), 'A Prototype Approach to the Analysis of Meanings of Kinship Terms in Non-native English' in (ed.) C. C. Peng, Language Sciences, A World Journal of the Sciences of Language, Volume 11, Number 2, Pergamon Press, Oxford.
- Austin, J. L. (1962), How to Do Things with Words, The William James Lecture delivered at Harvard University in 1955, (ed.) J. O. Urmson and Marina Sbisa, Oxford University Press.
- Awobuluyi, Oladele (1978), Essentials of Yoruba Grammar, Oxford University Press.
- Awobuluyi, Oladele (1982), 'The Yoruba Verb Phrase' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Awoniyi, Adedeji (1981), 'Yoruba Teaching in Nigerian Schools: 1960-1980' in (ed.) Ayo Banjo et. al. West African Studies in Modern Language Teaching and Research, The National Language Centre, Federal Ministry of Education, Lagos.
- Badejo, Rotimi B (1986), 'A Case for Suprasegmented Tone in Yoruba: The Melodic Tone' in Working Papers in Linguistics, Linguistics Section, Department of Russian and Language Studies, University of Melbourne, Volume 12.
- Baker, C Mark (1989), 'Object Sharing and Projection in Serial Verb Constructions' in (ed.) Samuel Jay Keyser, Linguistic Inquiry, Volume 20, Number 4.
- Baker, D Nancy and Greenfield, M. Patricia (1988) 'The Development of New and Old Information in Young Children's Early Language' in (ed.) Fred C. C. Peng, Language Sciences, A World Journal of the Sciences of Language, Volume 10, Number 1.
- Bamgbose, Ayo (1966), A Grammar of Yoruba, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bamgbose, Ayo (1967), A Short Yoruba Grammar, Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) Ltd.
- Bamgbose, Ayo (1976), Yoruba Orthography, Ibadan University Press.

- Bamgbose, Ayo (1982), 'Lexical Matching in Yoruba Poetry' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Bamgbose, Ayo (ed.) (1984), Yoruba Metalanguage, A Glossary of English-Yoruba Technical Terms in Language, Literature, and Methodology, Nigeria Educational Research Council, Lagos.
- Bamgbose, Ayo (1986), Yoruba: A Language in Transition, J.F. Odunjo Memorial Lectures Series, Number 1, (ed.) Olatunde O. Olatunji, Moluko and Co., Ibadan.
- Banjo, Ayo (1983), Grammars and Grammarians, An Inaugural Lecture delivered at the University of Ibadan, 22nd December 1981, Ibadan University Press.
- Barnouw, Erik (1956), Mass Communication, Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York.
- Bascom, William (1969), The Yoruba of Southern Nigeria, Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Bassnett-Mcquire, Susan (1980), Translation Studies, Methuen.
- Bellert, Irena and Weingartner, Paul (1982), 'On different characteristics of scientific texts as compared with everyday language texts' in (eds.) Richard Kittredge and John Lehrberger, Sublanguage, Studies of Language in Restricted Semantic Domains, Walter De Gruyter.
- Berger, Peter and Luckmann, Thomas (1966), The Social Construction of Reality, A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge, Penguin Books.
- Berry, Margaret (1975), An Introduction to Systemic Linguistics, 1. Structures and Systems, St Martin's Press, New York.
- Berry, Margaret (1977), An Introduction to Systemic Linguistics, 2. Levels and Links, B.T. Batsford Ltd., London.
- Berry, Margaret (1981), 'Systemic Linguistics and discourse analysis: a multi-layered approach to exchange structure' in (eds.) Malcolm Coulthard and Martin Montgomery, Studies in Discourse Analysis, Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Biber, Douglas (1985), 'Investigating macroscopic textual variation through multifeature/multidimensional analyses' in (ed.) Wolfgang Klein, Linguistics 23, Mouton Publishers.

- Bingham, Adelaide Bates (1986), 'Readers' and Listeners' Use of Cohesive Ties in Processing Relational Meanings' in (ed.) Fred C.C. Peng, Language Sciences, Volume 8, Number 8, April.
- Bohannon, Neil John and Leubecker, Warren Amye (1988), 'Recent Developments in Speech to Children: We've Come a Long Way, Baby-Talk' in (ed.) Fred C.C. Peng, Language Sciences, Volume 10, Number 1.
- Brown, Gillian and Yule, George (1983), Discourse Analysis, Cambridge University Press.
- Brown, R, and Gilman A (1960), 'The Pronouns of Power and Solidarity' in (ed.) Pier Paolo Giglioli Language and Social Context, Selected Readings, Penguin Books.
— also appeared in (1968), (ed.) J. Fishman, Readings in the Sociology of Language, The Hague, Mouton.
- Burges, Anthony (1964), Language Made Plain, Foutana Paperbacks.
- Butler, Christopher S (1985a), 'The Applicability of Systemic Theories' in (ed.) Howard Nicholas, Australian Review of Applied Linguistics, Volume 8, Number 1, June.
- Butler, Christopher S (1985b), Systemic Linguistics Theory and Applications, Batsford Academic and Educational, London.
- Butler, Christopher S (1985c), 'Discourse Systems and Structures and their Place within an Overall Systemic Model' in (eds.) James D. Benson and William S. Greaves, Systemic Perspectives on Discourse, Volume 1, Alex Publishing Corporation.
- Butler, Christopher S (1988), 'Pragmatics and Systemic Linguistics' in (ed.) Jacob L. Mey, Journal of Pragmatics, An Interdisciplinary Bi-monthly Journal of Language Studies, Volume 12, No.1, February.
- Butt, David et. al. (1989), Living with English, A Macquarie University Linguistics Study, Book One, Literacy Technologies Pty. Ltd.
- Buyssens, Eric (1988), 'Reference and communication' in (ed.) Thomas A. Sebeok, Semiotica, Journal of the International Association for Semiotic Studies, Volume 70-3/4, Mouton De Gruyter.
- Buysechaert, Joost (1987) 'The Position of English Adverbials' in (eds.) Bertil Malmberg/Lund and Gerhard Nickel/Stuttgert, IRAL, International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching, XXV/2, May.

- Candlin, C. N. (1983), 'Discoursal Patterning and the Equalizing of Interpretive Opportunity' in (ed.) Larry Smith, Readings in English as An International Language, Pergamon Institute of English.
- Carter, Ronald (1987), Vocabulary, Applied Linguistic Perspectives, Allen & Unwin, London.
- Carter, Ronald (1988), 'Front pages: Lexis, style and newspaper reports' in (ed.) Mohsen Ghadessy, Registers of Written English, Situational Factors and Linguistic Features, Pinter Publishers.
- Catford, J. C. (1965), A Linguistic Theory of Translation, An Essay in Applied Linguistics, Oxford University Press.
- Colby, Benjamin N. (1987), 'Coherence in language and culture' in (eds.) Ross Steele and Terry Threadgold, Language Topics, Essays in honour of Michael Halliday, Volume 11, John Benjamins Publishing Co. Ltd.
- Comrie, Bernard (1987), The World's Major Languages, Crown Helm, London and Sydney.
- Corsaro, William A (1985), 'Sociological Approaches to Discourse Analysis, Volume 1, Disciplines of Discourse.
- Craig, C. and Hale, K. (1988), 'Verb Sequencing Constructions in Macro-Chibchan,' a paper presented at 2nd Niger-Congo Syntax and Semantics Workshop, MIT, Cambridge, Massachusetts, April.
- Crick, Malcolm (1976), Explorations in Language and Meaning, Towards a Semantic Anthropology, Malaby Press, London.
- Crystal, David and Davy, Derek (1969), Investigating English Style, Longman Group, Limited.
- Cummings Michael, and Simmons, Robert (1983), The Language of Literature, A Stylistic introduction to the study of literature, Pergamon Press.
- Dadzie, A. B. K. (1985), 'The Nature of Question: A Consideration of Polar and Open-ended Questions in English, Fante and Yoruba,' in (ed.) D. O. Olagoke, Lagos Review of English Studies, A Journal of Language and Literary Studies, The Department of English, University of Lagos, Volumes VI/VII.
- Daramola, Adeyemi (1983), 'A Sociolinguistic Description of Terms of Address and Greetings in Nigerian English,' Unpublished B. A. (Hons.) Dissertation, University of Lagos.

- Daramola, Adeyemi (1984), 'A Stylistic Analysis of the Language of Achebe's Arrow of God,' Unpublished M. A. Dissertation, Postgraduate School, University of Lagos.
- Daramola, Adeyemi (1988), 'Paradigmatic and Syntagmatic Models of Teaching English as a Second Language,' A paper presented at the Thirteenth Congress of the Applied Linguistics Association of Australia (A. L. A. A), Tasmanian State Institute of Technology, Launceston, Australia, 26th August.
- Daramola, Adeyemi (1990), 'My Friend, where is Anini? - Decoding the meaning of utterances, A Systemic Linguistic Analysis,' manuscript.
- Darbyshire, A. E. (1971), A Grammar of Style, Andre Deutsch Limited.
- Davies, Martin (1989), 'Prosodic and Non-Prosodic Cohesion in Speech and Writing' in (ed.) Ruth M. Brend, Word, Journal of the International Linguistic Association, New York, Volume 40, Numbers 1-2, April-August.
- Debyasuvann, M. L. Boonlua (1981), 'Will EIL Succeed Where ESL and EFL Fail?' in (ed.) Larry E. Smith, English for Cross-Cultural Communication, The Macmillan Press Ltd.
- Dijk, Teun A. van (1977), Text and Context, Explorations in the Semantics of Discourse, Longman.
- Dixon, Robert M. W. (1985), What is Language?, A New Approach to Linguistic Description, Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd.
- Ellis, Jeffrey (1966), 'On Contextual Meaning' in (eds.) C. E. Bazell et. al. In Memory of J. R. Firth, Longman.
- Ellis, John (1985), 'Broadcast TV as sound and image' in (eds.) John Corner and Jeremy Hawthorn, Communication Studies, an introductory reader, Edward Arnold.
- Pafunwa, A. Babs (1982), 'Yoruba in Education: An Integrated Primary School Curriculum Scheme in Nigeria: A Six Year Project' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Fagunwa, D. O. (1961), Adiutu Olodumare, Thomas Nelson and Sons Limited.
- Fawcett, Robin P. (1984a), 'Language as a Resource' in (ed.) Mark Garner, Australian Review of Applied Linguistics, A Publication of the Applied Linguistics Association of Australia, Volume 7, Number 1, June.

- Fawcett, Robin P. (1984b), 'System networks, Code and Knowledge of the Universe' in (ed.) Robin P. Fawcett et al., The Semiotics of Culture and Language, Volume 2, Frances Pinter Publishers.
- Fawcett, Robin P. (1987), 'The semantics of clause and verb for relational processes in English' in (eds.) M. A. K. Halliday & Robin P. Fawcett, New Developments in Systemic Linguistics, Volume 1, Theory and Description, Frances Pinter (Publishers).
- Ferrara, Alessandro (1985), 'Pragmatics' in (ed.) Teun A. van Dijk, Handbook of Discourse Analysis, Volume 2, Dimensions of Discourse, Academic Press.
- Ferguson, Charles A. (1978), 'Talking to Children: A Search for Universals' in (ed.) Joseph H. Greenberg, Universals of Human Language, Volume 1, Method and Theory, Stanford University Press, Stanford, California.
- Firth, J. R. (1957a), 'General Linguistics and Descriptive Grammar' in Papers in Linguistics, Transactions of the Philological Society, 1951, 1934-1951, Oxford University Press.
- Firth, J. R. (1957b), 'The Technique of Semantics' in Papers in Linguistics, Transactions of the Philological Society, 1935, 1934-1951, Oxford University Press.
- Firth, John Rupert (1973), 'Personality and Language in Society' in (eds.) J. P. B. Allen and S. Pit Corder, Readings for Applied Linguistics, Volume 1, Oxford University Press, London.
- Foley, W. and M. Olso (1985), 'Clausehood and Verb Serialization' in (eds.) J. Nicholas and A. Woodbury, Grammar Inside and Outside the Clause, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Fowler, Roger (1977), 'Cohesive, Progressive, and Localizing Aspects of Text Structure,' in (eds.) Teun A. van Dijk and Janos S. Petofi, Grammar and Description, Studies in Text Theory and Text Analysis, Walter de Gruyter.
- Fries, Peter H. (1983), 'On the Status of Theme in English: Arguments from Discourses' in (eds.) Janos S. Petofi and Emel Sozer, Micro and Macro Connexity of Texts, Helmut Buske Verlag Hamburg.
- Fries, Peter H. (1985), 'How Does a Story Mean What it Does? A Practical Answer' in (eds.) James D. Benson & William S. Greaves, Systemic Perspectives on Discourse, Volume XV in the Series Advances in Discourse Processes, Ablex Publishing Corporation, Norwood, N. J.

- Fry, E., and Ogunbiyi, T. A. J. (1950), A Dictionary of the Yoruba Language, Ibadan University Press.
- Gandour, Jackson T. (1978), 'The Perception of Tone' in (ed.) Victoria Fromkin, Tone, A Linguistics Survey, Academic Press.
- Givon, Talmy (1978), 'Definiteness and Referentiality' in (ed.) Joseph H. Greenberg, Universals of Human Language, Volume 4, Syntax, Stanford University Press, Stanford, California.
- Greenberg, Joseph H. (1957), Essays in Linguistics, The University of Chicago Press.
- Greenberg, Joseph H. (1966), The Languages of Africa, Indiana University Press.
- Greenberg, Joseph H. (1971), Language, Culture and Communication, Essays by Joseph H. Greenberg, Stanford University Press.
- Greenberg, Joseph H. (1974), Language Typology, A Historical and Analytical Overview, Mouton.
- Gregory, Michael (1967), 'Aspects of Varieties differentiation,' Journal of Linguistics, Published for the Linguistics Association of Great Britain, Volume 3, Number 2, Cambridge University Press.
- Gregory, Michael (1987), 'Knowledge in discourse analysis and catalysis: a functional approach to gnostology,' A plenary paper presented at the 14th International Systemic Workshop (ISW), University of Sydney, August 24-28 (on tape).
- Grimes, Joseph E. (1975), The Thread of Discourse, Mouton and Co. B. V. Publishers, The Hague.
- Guenther, F. and Guenther-Reutter, M. (1978), Meaning and Translation, Philosophical and Linguistic Approaches, Duckworth.
- Gumperz, John J. et.al. (1985), 'Cohesion in Spoken and Written Discourse: Ethnic Style and Translation to Literacy' in (ed.) Deborah Tannen, Coherence in Spoken and Written Discourse, Volume xii in Series Advances in Discourse Processes, Series Editor Roy O. Freedle, Ablex Publishing Corporation.
- Gutwinski, W. (1976), Cohesion in Literary Texts, The Hague, Mouton.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1959), The Language of the Chinese 'Secret History of the Monquls', Oxford: Blackwell.

- Halliday, M. A. K. (1961), 'Categories of the Theory of Grammar' in (eds.) Andre Martinet et.al., Word, The Journal of the Linguistic Circle of New York, Volume 17, No. 3.
- Halliday, M. A. K., McIntosh, Angus, Strevens, Peter (1964), The Linguistic Sciences and Language Teaching, Longman.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1968), 'Notes on transitivity and theme in English,' in (ed.) John Lyons, Journal of Linguistics, Volume 4, Number 1, April, Cambridge University Press.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1970), 'Language Structure and Language Function' in (ed.) John Lyons, New Horizons in Linguistics, Penguin.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1973), Explorations in the Functions of Language, Edward Arnold.
- Halliday M. A. K. (1975), Learning How to Mean, Explorations in the Development of Language, Edward Arnold.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1976), Halliday: System and Function in Language, (ed.) G. Kress, Oxford University Press.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1977a), 'Text as Semantic Choice in Social Contexts' in (eds.) Teun A. van Dijk and Janos S. Petofi, Grammars and Description, Studies in Text Theory and Text Analysis, Walter De Gruyter.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1977b), Aims and Perspectives in Linguistics (ed.) D. E. Ingram, A Publication of the Applied Linguistics Association of Australia, Occasional Papers Number 1.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1978), Language as social semiotic, The social interpretation of language and meaning, Edward Arnold.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1981), 'Linguistic function and literary style: an inquiry into the language of William Golding's 'The Inheritors'' in (ed.) Donald C. Freeman, Essays in Modern Stylistics, Methuen, London.
- Halliday, M. A. K. and Martin, J. R. (1981), Readings in Systemic Linguistics, Batsford Academic and Educational Ltd.
- Halliday, M. A. K. and Hasan, Ruqaiya (1976), Cohesion in English, Longman.
- Halliday, M. A. K. and Hasan, Ruqaiya (1985), Language, context and text: Aspects of language in a social semiotic perspective, Deakin University Press.

- Halliday, M. A. K. (1985a), 'Dimensions of Discourse Analysis: Grammar,' in (ed.) Teun A. van Dijk, Handbook of Discourse Analysis, Vol. 2, Dimensions of Discourse, Academic Press.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1985b), Spoken and written language, Deakin University
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1985c), Introduction to Functional Grammar, Edward Arnold.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1987), 'Systemic linguistics: directions for development' A plenary paper presented at the 14th International Systemic Workshop (ISW), University of Sydney, August 24-28 (on tape).
- Hammond, Jennifer (1987), 'An Overview of the Genre-Based Approach to the Teaching of Writing in Australia' in (ed.) Tim McNamara, Australian Review of Applied Linguistics, Volume 10, Number 2.
- Hartmann, Paul and Husband, Charles (1972), 'The Mass Media and Racial Conflict' in (ed.) Dennis McQuail, Sociology of Mass Communications, Penguin Books.
- Hasan, Ruqaiya (1978), 'Text in the Systemic-Functional Mode' in (ed.) Wolfgang U. Dressler, Current Trends in Textlinguistics, Walter de Gruyter.
- Hasan, Ruqaiya (1984a) 'What kind of Resource is Language?' in (ed.) Mark Garner, Australian Review of Applied Linguistics, Volume 7, Number 1, June.
- Hasan, Ruqaiya 'Coherence and Cohesive Harmony' (1984b) in (ed.) James Flood, Understanding Reading Comprehension, International Reading Association, Newark Delaware.
- Hasan, Ruqaiya (1984c), 'Ways of Saying: ways of meaning' in (ed.) Robin P. Fawcett et.al., The Semiotics of Culture and Language, Volume 1, Frances Pinter.
- Hasan, Ruqaiya (1985a), Linguistics Language and Verbal Art, Deakin University Press.
- Hasan, Ruqaiya (1985b), 'Lending and Borrowing: From Grammar to Lexis' in (ed.) J. E. Clark The Cultivated Australian, Festschrift in Honour of Arthur Delbridge, Helmut Buske Verlag Hamburg.
- Hasan, Ruqaiya (1987), 'The Grammarian's dream: lexis as most delicate grammar' in (eds.) M. A. K. Halliday and Robin P. Fawcett New Developments in Systemic Linguistics, Volume 1, Frances Pinter (Publishers).

- Head, Brian F. (1978), 'Respect Degrees in Pronominal Reference' in (ed.) Thomas T. Ballmer Linguistic Dynamics, Discourses, Procedures and Evolution, Walter de Gruyter.
- Henderson, J. A. Eugenie (1987), 'J. R. Firth in retrospect: a view from the eighties' in (eds.) Ross Steele and Terry Threadgold Language Topics, Essays in honour of Michael Halliday, Vol. 1, John Benjamins Publishing Co.
- Hrebicek, Ludek (1985), 'Text as a Unit and Co-references' in (ed.) Thomas T. Ballmer Linguistic Dynamics, Discourses, Procedures, & Evolution, Walter de Gruyter.
- Huddleston, Rodney (1988), 'Constituency, multi-functionality and grammaticalization in Halliday's Functional Grammar' in (ed.) Nigel Vincent Journal of Linguistics, Vol. 24, No. 1, Cambridge University Press.
- Hudson, Richard A (1976), Arguments for a non-transformational grammar, Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Hudson, Richard (1981), 'Some issues on which linguists can agree?', Journal of Linguistics, Volume 17, Cambridge University Press.
- Hudson, Richard (1984), Word Grammar, Basil Blackwell Ltd.
- Hudson, Richard (1986), 'Systemic grammar' in (ed.) Wolfgang Klein Linguistics, an interdisciplinary journal of the language sciences, Volume 24-4 (284), Mouton de Gruyter.
- Hudson, Richard A. (1987), 'Grammar, society and the pronoun' in (eds.) Ross Steele and Terry Threadgold, Language Topics, Volume 2, John Benjamins Publishing Co.
- Ibikunle, Supo and Owolabi, Olu (1972), Iwe Ijinle Yoruba, Apa Keta, Oxford University Press.
- Idowu, Bolaji (1962), Olodumare: God in Yoruba Belief, Longman.
- Ingram, David (1978), 'Typology and Universals of Personnel Pronouns' in (ed.) Joseph H. Greenberg, Universals of Human Language, Volume 3, Stanford University Press.
- Jakobson, Roman (1973), Main Trends in the Sciences of Language, Harper and Row Publishers.
- Jakobson, Roman (1985), 'Sign and System of Language: A Reassessment of Saussure's Doctrine' in (eds.) Krystna Pomorska and Stephen Rudy Verbal Art, Verbal Sign, Verbal Time, The University of Minnesota Press.

- Joia, de Alex et.al. (1980), Terms in Systemic Linguistics, A Guide to Halliday, Batsford Academic and Educational Ltd.
- Katner, Kenneth (1975), The Languages of the World, Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Keenan, E. (1978), 'Some Logical Problems in Translation' in (ed.) Meaning and Translation, Philosophical and Linguistic Approaches, Duckworth.
- Kempf, Renate (1985), 'Pronouns and terms of address in Neues Deutschland' in (ed.), Dell Hymes, Language in Society, Volume 14, Number 2, June.
- Kittredge, Richard (1982), 'Variation and Homogeneity of Sublanguages' in (eds.) Richard Kittredge and John Lehrberger, Sublanguage, Studies of Language in Restricted Semantic Domains, Walter De Gruyter.
- Lamb M. Sydney (1969), 'Lexicology and Semantics' in (ed.) Archibald A. Hill Linguistics Today, Basic Books, Inc.
- Lamb. M. Sydney (1984), 'Semiotics of language and culture: a relational approach' in (eds.) Robin P. Fawcett, The Semiotics of Culture and Language, Volume 2. Frances Pinter (Publishers).
- Langendoen, D. Terence (1969), The London School of Linguistics, A Study of the Linguistic Theories of B. Malinowski and J. R. Firth, The M. I. T. Press Cambridge.
- Larson, Mildred L. (1984), Meaning-Based Translation, A Guide to Cross-Language Equivalence, University Press of America.
- Lemke, J. L. (1985), 'Ideology, Intertextuality and the Notion of Register' in (eds.) James D. Benson and William Greaves Systemic Perspective on Discourse, Volume 1, Ablex Publishing Corporation, Norwood, N. J.
- Lyons, John (1969), Introduction to Theoretical Linguistics, Cambridge University Press.
- Lyons, John (1969), 'Firth's Theory of "Meaning"' in (eds.) C. E. Bazell, J. C. Catford, M. A. K. Halliday and R. H. Robins In Memory of J. R. Firth, Longman.
- Lyons, John (1977a), Semantics, Volume 1, Cambridge University Press.
- Lyons, John (1977b), Semantics, Volume 2, Cambridge University Press.

- Lyons, John (1979), 'Deixis and Anaphora' in (ed.) Terry Myers, The Development of Conversation and Discourse, Edinburgh University Press.
- Maley, Yon (1985a), 'Judicial Discourse: The Case of the Legal Judgement' in (ed.) J.E. Clark, The Cultivated Australian, Festschrift in Honour of Arthur Delbridge, Helmut Buske Verlag Hamburg.
- Maley, Yon (1985b), 'The Semantic Field of Homicide' in (ed.) James D. Benson & William S. Greaves, Systemic Perspective on Discourse, Volume 2, Ablex Publishing Corporation.
- Manning, Alan D. (1989), 'The invariant code-significance of lexical item,' in (ed.) Thomas A. Sebeok Semiotica, Volume 73-1/2, Mouton de Gruyter, Berlin.
- Martin, J. R. (1985), 'Process and Text: Two Aspects of Human Semiosis' in (ed.) James D. Benson & William S. Greaves, Systemic Perspective on Discourse, Volume 1, Ablex Publishing Corporation.
- Martin, James R. (1987), 'The meaning of features in Systemic Linguistics' in (eds.) M.A.K. Halliday and Robin P. Fawcett New Developments in Systemic Linguistics, Volume 1, Frances Pinter (Publishers).
- Matthiessen, Christian [Reviewer] (1989), Introduction to functional grammar, M.A.K. Halliday (1985), London and Baltimore; Edward Arnold in (ed.) Sarah Grey Thomson, Language, Volume 65, Number 4, December.
- McIntosh, Angus (1966), 'Patterns and ranges' in (eds.) Angus McIntosh and M.A.K. Halliday, Patterns of Language, Longman.
- McQuail, Dennis et. al. (1972), 'The Television Audience: A Revised Perspective' in (ed.) Dennis McQuail, Sociology of Mass Communication, Penguin Books.
- Mitchell, T.F. (1971), 'Linguistic 'Going on': Collocations and other Lexical Matters arising on the Syntagmatic Record' in (eds.) I.M. Campbell and T.F. Mitchell, Archivum Linguisticum, Volume 11, The Scholar Press, Menston.
- Morley, G.D. (1985), An Introduction to Systemic Grammar, Macmillan.
- Morley, G.D. (1986), 'A Review of An Introduction to functional grammar' in (eds.) J.G. Kooji et. al. Lingua, Volume 69, Numbers 1/2 June.

- Moskovich, W. (1982), 'What is a sublanguage? The Notion of sublanguage in modern Soviet linguistics' in (eds.) Richard Kittredge and John Lehrberger, Sublanguage, Walter de Gruyter.
- Nasr, T. Raja (1986), The Essentials of Linguistic Science, Longman.
- Newmark, Peter (1981), Approaches to Translation, Pergamon Press.
- Nida, Eugene A. and Taber, Charles R. (1969) The Theory and Practice of Translation, E.J. Brill, Leiden, Netherlands.
- Nida, Eugene A. (1975), Language Structure and Translation, Stanford University Press, Stanford, California.
- Ninio, Anat (1988), 'The Roots of Narrative: Discussing Recent Events with Very Young Children' in (ed.) Fred C. C. Peng, Language Sciences, Volume 10, Number 1.
- Noth, Winfried (1978), 'The Semiotic Framework of textlinguistics' in (ed.) Wolfgang U. Dressler, Current Trends in Textlinguistics, Walter de Gruyter.
- Obanya, P. A. I. (1979), 'Nigerian Teachers' View on the Functions of English as a Language of Verbal Interaction in the Upper Primary School' in (ed.) Ebo Ubahakwe, Varieties and Functions of English in Nigeria, African Universities Press, Ibadan.
- Odunjo, J. F. (1961), Akojopo Ewi Aladun, Longman (Nig.) Ltd.
- Odunuga, Segun (1982), 'Tense and Aspect in Yoruba' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Ogunbowale, P. O. (1966), Asa Ibile Yoruba, Oxford University Press.
- Ogunbowale, P. O. (1970), The Essentials of Yoruba Language, Hodder and Stoughton Ltd.
- Oke, D. Ola (1982), 'On the Use of Verbal Group Negators in Yoruba' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Olagoke, D. O. (1979a), 'The Mother-tongue and ESL in Nigerian Education' in (ed.) Ebo Ubahakwe, The Teaching of English Studies: Readings for Colleges and Universities, Ibadan University Press.

- Olagoke, D. O. (1979b), 'The Mobility of English Adverbials' in (ed.) Ebo Ubahakwe, The Teaching of English Studies: Reading for Colleges and Universities, Ibadan University Press.
- Olatunji, Olatunde (1982), 'Classification of Yoruba Oral Poetry' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Ologunde, Agboola (1982), 'The Yoruba Language in Education' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- O'Toole, Michael (1988), 'Semiotic Systems in Painting and Poetry' in (eds.) C.M. Falchikov, and R. Russell Pike, A Festschrift for Dennis Ward.
- O'Toole, Michael (1989), 'A Systemic-Functional Semiotic of Art' in (eds.) Peter Fries and Michael Gregory, Discourse in Society: Functional Perspectives, Ablex Publications Ltd.
- Olusola, Ajolore (1982), 'Lexical Borrowing in Yoruba' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Palek, Bohumil (1977), 'Reference and Text' in (eds.) Teun A van Dijk and Janos S. Petofi, Grammars and Descriptions, Walter De Gruyter.
- Palmer, F.R. (1976), Semantics, Cambridge University Press.
- Pappas, Christine C. (1985), 'The Cohesive Harmony and Cohesive Density of Children's Oral and Written Stories' in (eds.) James D. Benson and William S. Greaves, Systemic Perspectives on Discourse, Volume 2, Ablex Publishing Corporation, Norwood, New Jersey.
- Petofi, J.S. (1977) 'A Formal Semiotic Text Theory as an Integrated Theory of Natural Language (Methodological Remarks), in (ed.) W.U. Dressler, Current Trends in Textlinguistics, Walter De Gruyter.
- Phillips, Martin (1985), Aspects of Text Structure, Elsevier Science Publishers B.V.
- Pike, Kenneth (1948), Tone Languages, The University of Michigan Press.
- Pike, Kenneth L. and Pike, Evelyn G. (1977), Grammatical Analysis, Summer Institute of Linguistics.
- Platts, Mark de Bretton (1979), Ways of Meaning, Routledge and Kegan Paul.

- pulleyblank, Douglas (1987a), 'Niger-Kordofanian Languages' in (ed.) Bernard Comrie, The World's Major Languages, Croom Helm Ltd.
- pulleyblank, Douglas (1987b), 'Yoruba,' in (ed.) Bernard Comrie, The World's Major Languages, Croom Helm Ltd.
- Quirk, Randolph et. al. (1972), A Grammar of Contemporary English, Longman Group Ltd.
- Richards, Jack et. al. (1985), Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistics, Longman.
- Ridler, Vivian (1933), The Oxford English Dictionary, Oxford University Press.
- Rotman, Brian (1988), 'Toward a semiotics of mathematics' in (ed.) Thomas A. Sebeok, Semiotica, Journal for Semiotic Studies, Volume 72-1/2, Mouton De Gruyter.
- Rowlands, E. C. (1970), 'Ideophones in Yoruba' in (ed.) Guy Atkins, African Language Studies, Collected papers in Oriental and African Studies in Honour of Malcolm Guthrie, University of London, Volume XI.
- Ruhlen, Merritt (1975), A Guide to the Languages of the World, Stanford University.
- Sager, Naomi (1982), 'Syntactic formatting of science information' (eds.) Richard Kittredge and John Lehrberger, Sublanguage, Walter de Gruyter.
- Salami, Adebisi (1982) 'Vowel and Consonant Harmony, and Restriction in Assimilated Loan Words in Yoruba' in (ed.) Adebisi Afolayan, Yoruba Language and Literature, University of Ife Press.
- Sampson, Geoffrey (1980), Schools of Linguistics, Hutchinson.
- Sanford, Anthony J. (1985), 'Aspects of Pronoun Interpretation: Evaluation of Search Formulations of Inference' in (eds.) Gert Rickheit and Hans Strohner, Inferences in Text processing, Elsevier Publishers.
- Saussure, F. de (1973), 'Language: A well-defined Object' in (eds.) J. P. B. Allen and S. Pit Corder, Readings in Applied Linguistics, Vol. 1, Oxford University Press.
- Schwarz, David S. (1979), Naming and Referring, The Semantics and Pragmatics of Singular Terms, Walter De Gruyter.
- Shaw, Thurstan (1978), Nigeria: Its Archaeology and Early History, Thames and Hudson Ltd., London.

- Simpson, Ekundayo (1981), 'Objective criteria for evaluating a translation' in (eds.) Ayo Banjo et.al. West African Studies in Modern Language Teaching and Research, The Caxton Press.
- Sinclair, McH. John (1966), 'Beginning the Study of Lexis' in (eds.) C. E. Bazell et.al., In Memory of Firth, Longman.
- Sinclair, McH. John (1987), 'Collocation: a progress report,' in (eds.) Ross Steele & Terry Threadgold, Language Topics, Volume 2, John Benjamins Publishing Co.
- Singler, John Victor (1988), 'The Story of O' in (eds.) John W. M. Verhaar and Werner Abraham, Studies in Language, Volume 12, Number 1, John Benjamins Publication Co.
- Smith, Larry (1983), 'Some Distinctive Features of EIL vs. ESOL in English Language Education' in (ed.) Larry E. Smith, Readings in English as an International Language, Pergamon Institute of English.
- Talbot, P. Amaury (1969), The Peoples of Southern Nigeria, Frank Cass and Company Limited.
- Tannen, Deborah (1984), Coherence in Spoken and Written Discourse, Series on Advances in Discourse Processes, (ed.) Roy O. Freedle, Ablex Publishing Corporation.
- Thrane, Torben (1980), Referential-Semantic Analysis, Cambridge University Press.
- Tosi, Arturo (1984), Immigration and Bilingual Education, Pergamon Press.
- Turner, Geoffrey J. (1987), 'Sociosemantic networks and discourse structure' in (eds.) M. A. K. Halliday and Robin P. Fawcett, New Developments in Systemic Linguistics, Volume 1: Theory and Description, Frances Pinter (Publishers).
- Tymoczko, T. (1978), 'Translation and Meaning' in (ed.) Meaning and Translation, Philosophical and Linguistic Approaches, Duckworth.
- Udo, Reuben K. (1970), Geographical Regions of Nigeria, Heinemann Educational Books Limited.
- Ure Jean N. (1969), 'Practical Registers' in (ed.) W. R. Lee English Language Teaching, English as a Foreign or Second Language, Volume XXIII, Number 3, Oxford University Press.

- Ure, Jean (1971), 'Lexical density and register differentiation' in (eds.) G. E. Parren and J. L. M. Trim, Applications of Linguistics, Selected papers of the Second International Congress of Applied Linguistics, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Velley, La (1974), 'An Experimental Study of Yoruba Tone' in (ed.) R. Carl, U. C. L. A. Working Papers in Phonetics. 27, University of California, Los Angeles, September.
- Vine, Elaine (1984), 'When Does More Mean Less? A Study of Language Use in Arithmetic Problems' in (ed.) Mark Garner, Australian Review of Applied Linguistics, A Publication of the Applied Linguistic Association of Australia, Volume 7, Number 1, June.
- Vonk, Wietske (1985), 'The immediacy of Inferences in the Understanding of Pronouns' in (eds.) Gert Rickheit and Hans Strohner, Inferences in Text Processing, Elsevier Science Publishers, B. V.
- Wardhaugh, Ronald (1986), An Introduction to Sociolinguistics, Basil Blackwell Ltd.
- Waugh, Linda R. (1985), 'The Poetic Function and the Nature of Language' in (eds.) Krystyna Pomorka and Stephen Rudy, Verbal Art, Verbal Sign and Verbal Time, The University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis.
- Welmers, E. Wm. (1973), African Language Structures, University of California Press Ltd.
- Widdowson, Henry (1979), 'Rules and Procedures in Discourse Analysis' in (ed.) Terry Myers, The Development of Conversation and Discourse, Edinburgh University Press.
- Wilss, Wolfram (1982), The Sciences of Translation, Problems and Methods, Gunter Narr Verlag Tubingen.
- Yang, Agnes Weiyun (1989), 'Cohesive Chains and Writing Quality' in (ed.) Ruth Brend, Word, Journal of the International Linguistic Association, New York, Volume 40, Numbers 1-2, April-August.